

STRUCTURE, KINEMATICS, AND
CHEMICAL ABUNDANCES OF THE
INNER AND OUTER HALO
POPULATIONS

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*To the strength, the tenacity, the endurance and the passion that supported me during
this travel.*

May the immense power of Nature provide vision to those who do not see

Disclaimer

I hereby declare that the work in this thesis is that of the candidate alone, except where indicated below.

All thesis chapters and appendices are a representation of papers already published, submitted or in preparation. Accordingly, a list of authors is given at the beginning of each chapter. That said, I hereby wish to acknowledge the more significant contributions made by some co-authors.

Chapter 2: T.C. Beers has provided the data for the analysis (SDSS-DR5) and contributed some text. M. Chiba has evaluated the global density distributions reported in Figure 2.5. Y.S. Lee has contributed to the development and testing of the SSPP (SEGUE Stellar Parameter Pipeline).

Chapter 3: T.C. Beers has provided the data for the analysis (SDSS-DR7 calibration stars), and contributed to improve the text. He also has suggested some useful statistical tools (Sect. 3.5.2; PAM-CLARA). M. Chiba has provided valuable suggestions on the derivation of the velocity ellipsoids for the inner- and outer-halo components, during a visit to Japan in 2008. K. Freeman has provided valuable suggestions on the derivation of the scale height and scale length for the thick disk and metal weak thick disk, as well as for the evaluation of the tilt of the velocity ellipsoids. Z. Ivezić has performed some useful cross-checks on the kinematics derived for the inner and outer halos.

Chapter 4: T. Sivarani has estimated the carbon abundances for the SDSS-DR7 calibration stars. J. Norris has performed a cross-check of the carbon abundance estimation. J. Bovy has provided useful suggestions for the implementation of the Extreme Deconvolution technique.

Appendix A: T.C. Beers is the senior author, but I have contributed text as well. I have performed the comparisons between different samples examined in this rebuttal paper, computed the kinematic and orbital parameters, and performed the maximum likelihood analysis of all the samples under consideration.

Appendix B: Wako Aoki is the senior author. In this paper I have performed the kinematic analysis of the star discussed.

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Abstract

The halo of the Milky Way provides unique elemental abundance and kinematic information on the first objects to form in the Universe, which can be used to tightly constrain models of galaxy formation and evolution. This thesis presents a wide-ranging analysis of the global structure of the Galactic stellar halo system, comprising the inner and outer halos, through inference of its density profile(s) and determination of the kinematic and orbital parameters of its constituent stars (e.g., mean rotational velocity, velocity ellipsoids, eccentricities). This study also addresses the possible chemical distinction between the two halo components in terms of the frequency of the carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars among their membership.

In an initial study, the full space motion and orbital parameters for a large number (over 20000) of "calibration stars" from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) are combined with estimates of their chemical compositions (metallicity; $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$). Although there are many possible (and more complex) alternative models that might be considered, multiple lines of evidence derived from these data clearly confirm that the halo can be resolved into (at least) two primary populations, the inner halo and the outer halo, with very different observed properties. The inner-halo component of the Milky Way dominates the population of halo stars found at distances up to 10-15 kpc from the Galactic Centre, while the outer-halo component dominates in the regions beyond 15-20 kpc. It has been shown that stars in the inner-halo population are non-spherically distributed about the centre of the Galaxy, with an inferred axial ratio on the order of ~ 0.6 . Inner-halo stars possess generally high orbital eccentricities, and exhibit a modest prograde rotation (between 0 and 50 km s^{-1}) around the centre of the Galaxy (Galactocentric rotational velocity; V_ϕ). The metallicity distribution function (MDF) for stars in the inner halo peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$, with tails extending to higher and lower metallicities. The outer halo, by contrast, comprises stars that exhibit a much more spherical spatial distribution, with an axial ratio ~ 0.9 to 1.0. Outer-halo stars cover a wide range of orbital eccentricities, including many with lower eccentricity orbits than found for most stars associated with the inner halo, and exhibit a clear retrograde net rotation (between -40 and -70 km s^{-1}). The MDF of the outer halo peaks at lower metallicity than that of the inner halo, around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$, and includes a larger fraction of low-metallicity stars than does the MDF of the inner-halo population.

Next, a more detailed analysis of the structure and kinematics of the recognized stellar components of the Milky Way has been carried out with a more extensive sample of 32360 calibration stars from the SDSS and its first extension, (SDSS-II), which included the sub-survey SEGUE: Sloan Extension for Galactic Understanding and Exploration. Full space motions for a sub-sample of 16920 stars, exploring a local volume within 4 kpc of the Sun, are used to derive velocity ellipsoids for the inner- and outer-halo components of the Galaxy, as well as for the canonical thick-disk and proposed metal-weak thick-disk (MWTD) populations. This new sample of calibration stars represents an increase of 60% relative to the numbers used in the previous analysis. The question of whether the data require the presence of at least a two-component halo, in

order to account for the rotational behavior of likely halo stars in the local volume, and whether more than two components are needed, has been examined. In addition, the fractions of each component required to understand the nature of the observed kinematic behavior of the stellar populations of the Galaxy, as a function of distance from the plane, were evaluated. The full set of calibration stars (including those outside the local volume) is used to test for the expected changes in the observed stellar metallicity distribution function with distance above the Galactic plane *in-situ*, due to the changing contributions from the underlying stellar populations.

It has been found that: (a) A single-population halo is incompatible with the observed kinematics of local stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, while a dual (inner/outer) halo model is necessary to describe the observations. (b) The net rotation of the outer halo is slightly more retrograde than previously reported, $\langle V_\phi \rangle = -80 \pm 13 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (c) The net rotation of the inner halo is consistent with zero (at the two-sigma level), $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 7 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The slopes of the inferred power-law spatial-density profiles for the inner- and outer-halo populations are -3.17 ± 0.20 and -1.79 ± 0.29 , respectively. (d) The derived velocity ellipsoids, $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z})$, for the two halo components are as follows: Inner Halo = $(150 \pm 2, 95 \pm 2, 85 \pm 1) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and Outer Halo = $(159 \pm 4, 165 \pm 9, 116 \pm 3) \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (e) The "as observed" metallicity distribution function of stars in our sample exhibits clear changes with distance from the Galactic plane, exhibiting the anticipated shift from dominance by thick-disk and MWTD populations, with peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.6$ and -1.3 , respectively, to dominance by the inner-halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$) and outer-halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$) populations. (f) The tilt angle, α , between the long axis of the Schwarzschild velocity ellipsoid and the sun-center line is, in Galactocentric cylindrical coordinates, for stars of relatively high metallicity ($-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$), $\alpha = 7^\circ.1 \pm 1^\circ.5$ for $1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$, and $\alpha = 5^\circ.2 \pm 1^\circ.2$ for $2 < |Z| < 4 \text{ kpc}$, consistent with one another. For stars of intermediate metallicity ($-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.8$), the tilt is $\alpha = 10^\circ.3 \pm 0^\circ.4$ close to the plane, and $\alpha = 15^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.3$ farther from the plane, which differ significantly from one another. For stars of lower metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$), the tilt is $\alpha = 8^\circ.6 \pm 0^\circ.5$ close to the plane, and $\alpha = 13^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.4$ farther from the plane, again significantly different.

The question of whether the proposed MWTD is kinematically and chemically distinct from the canonical thick disk has also been addressed. It has been found that the Galactocentric rotational velocity inferred for the metal-weak thick disk, as well as its mean metallicity, appear quite similar to the values derived previously for the Monoceros stream, suggesting a possible association between these structures. Scale lengths and scale heights for the disk system components are determined. It has been found that: (g) The net rotation of the canonical thick-disk population, for stars close to the plane, is $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (h) The asymmetric drift of the thick disk varies with distance from the plane, as shown by previous work, $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -36 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$. A MWTD, kinematically independent of the canonical thick disk (with net rotation $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 100\text{-}150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), is required to account for the rotational properties of low-metallicity stars close to the Galactic plane. (i) The metallicity range for stars that are likely members of the MWTD is $-1.8 [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] -0.8$, possibly up to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.7$. (f) The derived velocity ellipsoids, $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z})$, for the thick disk

components are as follows – Thick Disk = $(53 \pm 2, 51 \pm 1, 35 \pm 1)$ km s⁻¹, MWTD = $(59 \pm 3, 40 \pm 3, 44 \pm 3)$ km s⁻¹. (g) The kinematically derived scale length and scale height for the thick disk are $h_R = 2.20 \pm 0.35$ kpc and $h_Z = 0.51 \pm 0.04$ kpc, respectively. (h) The radial scale length for the MWTD is on the order of $h_R \sim 2$ kpc, while the scale height is 1.36 ± 0.13 kpc.

Finally, the CEMP stars in the inner- and outer-halo components of the Milky Way are explored, based on accurate determinations of the carbon-to-iron abundance ratios and kinematic quantities for over 30000 calibration stars from the SDSS and its first extension, (SDSS-II). The carbon abundance estimates are based on fits to the CH G-band at 4305 Å; the kinematic and orbital parameters have been evaluated for a subsample of the calibration stars (with distances $d < 10$ kpc from the Sun), employing previously developed methods. It was found that 1%, 6%, and 18% of stars in the metallicity intervals $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.5$, $-2.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.5$, respectively, exhibit carbon-to-iron abundance ratios ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$, or “carbonicity”) in excess of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] = +0.7$, the adopted definition for CEMP stars. The carbonicity distribution function (CarDF) as a function of distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$, has been examined, and was demonstrated that its nature changes dramatically with increasing distance. For $|Z| < 5$ kpc, relatively few CEMP stars are identified (over all metallicities). For distances $|Z| > 5$ kpc, the CarDF exhibits a strong tail towards high values, up to $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > +3.0$. For low-metallicity stars located above $|Z| = 5$ kpc a significant increase in the fraction of CEMP stars with declining metallicity has been confirmed. In the low-metallicity regime, for both $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.4$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$, it has been found a clear increase in the CEMP star fraction with $|Z|$, approaching $\sim 15\%$ in the most distant bins. We have sought to understand whether these behaviors are metallicity driven, due to differences in the mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ of the inner- and outer-halo components, or population driven, due to differences in the fractions of CEMP stars associated with each population at a given metallicity. To accomplish this, we have obtained a statistical separation of the inner- and outer-halo components in velocity space using the Extreme Deconvolution technique, which provides membership probabilities for each star. At low metallicity ($-2.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$), where the dominant component is the outer halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{peak,out}} = -2.2$), there is evidence for a significant contrast in the CEMP star fraction between the inner- and outer-halo components, such that $F_{\text{CEMP,out}} \sim 2 \times F_{\text{CEMP,in}}$. This may continue to even lower metallicities, but the sample is too small to be certain.

All the above results are considered in the context of the formation of the halo system of the Milky Way, and the nature of the likely progenitors of the inner- and outer-halo populations.

1

Introduction

The field of cosmology is quickly converging to a “Standard Model” whereby the fundamental parameters of the Universe are reasonably well constrained. While there do remain fundamental questions, such as the nature of dark matter and dark energy, much of the effort is now shifting to understanding the details of how and when galaxies formed and how they evolved. This field of research has been coined Galactic Archaeology (Bland-Hawthorn & Freeman 2000), in which the numerous details (kinematics, dynamics, and elemental abundances) of various stellar components in the Milky Way (and eventually, other Local Group galaxies) are examined and used to constrain their past history. This approach is particularly suitable for our own galaxy. Indeed, the Milky Way is a unique laboratory, as it is the one large galaxy where it is possible to analyze the full space motions and chemical compositions of its stellar populations based on individual stars, and to use this information to disentangle its structural properties in great detail. Knowledge of the full six-dimensional location and velocity phase space, and the chemical properties of stellar populations in the Galaxy, provides invaluable information, not only on its recognized structures (and sub-structures, such as tidal streams), but by extension, on the nature of its formation and evolution. Low-mass stars live for the age of the Universe, and therefore retain significant "memory" of the initial conditions in which they formed, such as chemical abundances and orbital angular momentum (often a nearly conserved quantity). By analyzing the motions and chemical compositions of these ancient stars, one can attempt to identify the environment in which they formed, and trace the assembly mechanisms of the Galaxy and its Local Group neighbours.

1.1 The Galactic Stellar Halo

The stellar halo is the component that contains the most metal-poor stars in the Galaxy as well as many of the oldest ones. Low-mass stars retain in their atmospheres a record of the chemical elements of the environment in which they were born, over the long history of the Galaxy. Metal-poor stars are thus the scribes of the fossil record. More-

over, the time required for stars to exchange their energies and momenta is very long compared with the age of the Galaxy (Eggen, Lynden-Bell & Sandage 1962). Therefore, knowledge of the present energy and momenta of individual stars also provides a record of the initial dynamic conditions under which they were formed. By combining the chemical compositions and motions of halo stars, it is possible to trace back the evolutionary history of the Galaxy.

A basic tenet of Λ CDM cosmology is that structure forms in a hierarchical manner, with small scales going non-linear and collapsing to form DM clumps, under their self gravity at early epochs, with the subsequent merging of these small systems into larger ones. Owing to the strong gravitational attraction of dark matter, gas particles also assemble into each of the clumps. The first systems to form stars are probably similar in mass to the (surviving) satellite galaxies of the Milky Way, leading to the prediction (Johnston et al. 1996) that the stellar halo of the Milky Way is created by the merging of such systems (indeed, this suggestion pre-dates Λ CDM; see Searle & Zinn 1978, who advocated that the outer halo formed in this manner). The properties of the stellar populations in the satellite galaxies (age distributions, kinematics, elemental abundances, etc.) and in the stellar halo can be used to constrain the defining properties of the systems that could have merged to form the halo, and when they were assimilated (Helmi et al. 2006; Johnston et al. 2008). Signatures in elemental abundance and age space persist over a Hubble time, and kinematic phase-space signatures persist for many dynamical times. Recent mergers should also be traceable by overdensities in coordinate space.

While the stellar halo is only a small fraction of the baryonic mass of the Milky Way, it provides a clean test of the Λ CDM paradigm on small scales. It now seems clear that a significant proportion of the stellar halo could indeed have been built from the accretion and disruption of smaller systems, predominantly during the early formation epoch of the Galaxy. The stellar populations of the field halo therefore provide a unique window into the nature of the Galactic building blocks. It is only in the stellar halo that we can find a relatively clean sample of stars that were formed in these progenitor systems, uncontaminated by subsequent star formation.

1.2 Structure and Kinematics

The structure of the stellar halo is quite complex, and is strongly linked to how the Galaxy was formed (Freeman & Bland-Hawthorn 2002). In the canonical model of Milky Way formation (Eggen, Lynden-Bell, & Sandage 1962; ELS), the Galaxy began with a rapid ($\sim 10^8$ yr) radial collapse of the initial protogalactic cloud, followed by an equally rapid settling of gas into a rotating disk. This model readily explained the general structure and kinematics of field stars, and, in this context, the distribution of halo stars was expected to be a smooth function of position. However, starting with the pioneering work of Searle & Zinn (1978; SZ), evidence has been increasing that supports a more complex picture of Galactic halo structure and its formation. SZ noted a number of difficulties in reconciling several observed properties of the halo globular

cluster system with predictions of the ELS model, and suggested that in its earliest epochs the halo component of the Galaxy may have experienced prolonged, chaotic accretion of subgalactic fragments.

In the last decade, the detection of extended stellar components around external galaxies, such as M31 (Ferguson et al. 2002; Irwin et al. 2005; Ibata et al. 2007) and other nearby galaxies (Mouhcine et al. 2005a,b; de Jong et al. 2007; Ibata et al. 2009) has inspired efforts to model stellar halos in the context of Λ CDM cosmogony. Several theoretical studies suggest that the main properties of stellar halos can be explained entirely by the accretion and disruption of satellites (Bullock & Johnston 2005; Font et al. 2006a,b,c; De Lucia & Helmi 2008; Font et al. 2008; Johnston et al. 2008; Cooper et al. 2010). However, even though a large fraction of the stellar halos of normal disk galaxies may be explained by the accretion scenario, some properties of the stellar halo of the Milky Way, and other nearby galaxies, cannot be reproduced in the context of accretion-only models. Among these are the origin of large scale metallicity gradients in stellar halos. An underlying metallicity gradient in the halo of the Milky Way was suggested by the net difference in the mean metallicity between the inner and the outer halo, noted already in ELS (1962). Models that form halos by non-dissipative accretion and mergers are not able to produce significant metallicity gradients (Font et al. 2006a; De Lucia & Helmi 2008; Cooper et al. 2010). The presence of a metallicity gradient is a consequence of dissipative collapse/mergers. Therefore, on the theoretical side, the stellar halos of galaxies may have a *dual nature*: while the outer halo formed primarily by accretion/mergers, a significant fraction of the inner halo may have formed through dissipational collapse involving *in situ* star formation.

From the observational point of view, in the last two decades studies of halo field stars have provided increasing evidence that supports the accretion scenario. Examples are the possible age spread among halo subdwarfs (Schuster & Nissen 1989; Carney et al. 1996), a gradient in the inferred ages of field horizontal-branch (FHB) stars and RR Lyrae variables (Preston, Shectman, & Beers 1991; Lee & Carney 1999), possible kinematic substructure in the halo (Doinidis & Beers 1989; Majewski, Munn, & Hawley 1994; 1996), changes in the kinematics of the field populations as one moves from the inner to the outer halo (Majewski 1992; Carney et al. 1996; Sommer-Larsen et al. 1997). In the last decade, with the advent of large-scale sky surveys such as the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al. 2000), the Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS; Skrutskie et al. 2006), and the QUEST survey (Vivas et al. 2001), the picture of the stellar halo has increased in complexity with the discovery of numerous substructures. Examples include the Sagittarius Dwarf tidal stream in the halo (Ibata et al. 1994; Ivezić et al. 2000; Vivas et al. 2001; Majewski et al. 2003) and the Monoceros stream in the region closer to the Galactic plane (Newberg et al. 2002; Rocha-Pinto et al. 2003). More recently, the presence of additional clumps and overdensities strewn throughout the halo have been clearly established (Bell et al. 2008; Juric et al. 2008; de Jong et al. 2010).

In terms of global properties, the density profile of the stellar halo has been described by a power-law, of the form $\rho \sim r^n$, where r is the Galactocentric radius and n is negative, due to the finite extent and mass of the Galaxy. Sommer-Larsen & Zhen

(1990) argued that there is clear indication that the halo, at any given radius, consists of *both* a main, nearly spherical component and an *overlapping*, highly flattened component. This property has been extensively explored in Chiba & Beers (2000). They found that for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$, the density distribution in the outer part of the halo, $r \sim 20$ kpc, is quite round, with an axial ratio of $q \sim 0.9$, while at $r < 15$ kpc, the axial ratio decreases to $q \sim 0.65$. In terms of the halo's kinematics, Chiba & Beers reported a radially elongated velocity ellipsoid, $(\sigma_U, \sigma_V, \sigma_W) = (141 \pm 11, 106 \pm 9, 94 \pm 8)$ km s⁻¹, with a small prograde rotation.

In the past few decades a number of studies provided evidence that the halo of the Milky Way may not comprise a single population, primarily from the analysis of spatial profiles (or inferred spatial profiles) of halo objects (Carney 1984, Hartwick 1987; Allen et al. 1991; Zinn 1993; Preston et al. 1991; Kinman et al. 1994). A recent example of such an analysis is the observation of two different spatial density profiles for the distinct Oosterhoof classes of RR Lyrae variable stars in the halo (Miceli et al. 2008). In addition, tentative claims for a net retrograde motion of halo objects by previous authors supports the existence of a likely dual-component halo (Norris & Ryan, 1989; Majewski 1992; Carney et al. 1996; Wilhelm 1996; Kinman et al. 2007; Lee et al. 2007).

1.3 Chemical Abundances

Metal-poor stars are fundamental for constraining and understanding the formation history of the Galaxy, as well as the physics of the high-redshift Universe (re-ionization, initial mass function, etc.). The general approach is to obtain such information through study of the detailed elemental abundances of metal-deficient stars, because many of these objects have formed from primordial gas clouds during the early chemo-dynamical evolution of the Galaxy (Beers & Christlieb 2005 and references therein). The extremely metal-poor stars ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$) that are currently being observed are candidate low-mass stars among those formed in this early stage of the Galaxy. Chemical abundance studies for such metal-poor stars provide useful constraints on the pertinent nucleosynthesis processes and the chemo-dynamical evolution of the early Galaxy (Zhao & Magain 1990, 1991; McWilliam et al. 1995; Ryan et al. 1996; McWilliam 1998; Carretta et al. 2002; Cayrel et al. 2004; Barklem et al. 2005; Cohen et al. 2008; Lai et al. 2008).

In the last decade, significant efforts have been made to better characterize the metallicity distribution function (MDF) of the halo, particularly at the very metal-poor end. The HK survey of Beers and collaborators and the Hamburg/ESO (HES) survey of Christlieb and colleagues have yielded a dramatic increase in the number of very metal-poor stars known (Beers & Christlieb 2005). High-resolution spectroscopic studies of stars identified in the HES have established the existence of ultra ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -4$) and hyper ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -5$) stars in the halo (Christlieb et al. 2002, Frebel et al. 2005; Norris et al. 2007), all of which are carbon rich. No completely metal-free stars (Population III) have been found thus far. These results can be used to place strong constraints

on the initial mass function (IMF). For example, Salvadori et al. (2007) found, using semi-analytic models of Galaxy formation, that the lack of metal-free stars constrains the critical metallicity for low-mass stars formation to be $Z_{cr} > 0$ (Schneider et al. 2002), or the masses of the first stars to be $M_{PopIII} > 0.9M_{\odot}$.

More information about the chemical history of the Galactic halo can be obtained from detailed studies of elemental abundance patterns. This is because the various chemical elements are synthesized by different processes in stars of different masses, and on different timescales (McWilliam et al. 1997). For example, the α -elements (O, Mg, Si, Ca, and Ti) are produced during explosions of massive stars (Type II supernovae), only a few million years after their formation. Iron-peak elements are produced both by Type Ia (and to some extent) Type II supernovae. Type Ia supernovae are the result of a thermonuclear explosion induced by the transfer of mass onto the surface of a white dwarf (WD) by a binary companion star (single-degenerate), or a result of WD–WD (double-degenerate) collisions¹. This implies that such explosions take place typically on a longer timescale, of the order of 0.1 to few Gyr (Matteucci & Recchi 2001). Heavier elements beyond the iron-peak are created by neutron captures, through the slow (s) and rapid (r) processes. The majority of halo stars are α -enhanced (Wheeler et al. 1989; Nissen et al. 1994; Carretta et al. 2000), where typically $[\alpha/Fe] \sim +0.3$ to $+0.4$.

The observational evidence that the Galactic halo may not comprise a single population, in terms of spatial density profiles and kinematics, can be strengthened by the presence of distinct chemical signatures associated with the inner- and outer-halo populations. For example, studies of the $[Mg/Fe]$ abundance ratios of stars thought to be associated with the inner halo appear different (generally 0.1 dex higher) than those associated with the outer halo (Roederer 2009). This same study also demonstrated that stars associated with the inner halo exhibit considerably lower star-to-star abundance scatter for both the iron-peak element ratio $[Ni/Fe]$ and the neutron-capture element ratio $[Ba/Fe]$ than found for stars of the outer halo.

Another possible chemical signature is the carbon-to-iron ratio, $[C/Fe]$. Carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars were originally defined as the subset of very metal-poor stars ($[Fe/H] \leq -2$) that exhibit elevated carbon relative to iron, $[C/Fe] > +1$ (Beers & Christlieb 2005). It has been recognized, primarily from spectroscopic follow-up of metal-poor candidates selected from objective-prism surveys (e.g., Beers et al. 1985, 1992; Christlieb 2003), that roughly 20% of stars with $[Fe/H] < -2$ exhibit enhancement of $[C/Fe]$ up to several orders of magnitude relative to the solar ratio (Lucatello et al. 2006). The fraction of CEMP stars rises to 30% for $[Fe/H] < -3$, 40% for $[Fe/H] < -3.5$, and 100% for $[Fe/H] < -4$ (Beers & Christlieb 2005; Frebel et al. 2005; Norris et al. 2007); definitive explanations for the origin of this increase have not been previously offered – we describe one possibility later in this thesis. Regardless of the ultimate reason, these results indicate that significant amounts of carbon (relative to iron) were produced in the early stages of chemical evolution in the Universe.

There exist a number of sub-classes of CEMP stars, some of which have been asso-

¹The progenitors of SN Ia are still a matter of debate

ciated with proposed progenitor objects. CEMP-s stars (those with s-process element enhancement), for example, are the most commonly observed type to date. High-resolution spectroscopic studies have revealed that around 80% of CEMP stars exhibit s-process-element enhancement (Aoki et al. 2007). The favored mechanism invoked to account for these stars is mass transfer of carbon-enhanced material from the envelope of an asymptotic giant-branch (AGB) star to its binary companion; it is this surviving binary companion that is now observed as a CEMP-s star (e.g., Herwig 2005; Sneden et al. 2008). The class of CEMP-no stars (which exhibit no strong neutron-capture-element enhancements) are particularly prevalent among the most metal-poor stars. Possible progenitors for this class include massive, rapidly rotating, mega metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -6$) stars, which models suggest have greatly enhanced abundances of CNO due to distinctive internal burning and mixing episodes, followed by strong mass loss (Hirschi et al. 2006; Meynet et al. 2006, 2010). Another mechanism is pollution of the interstellar medium by so-called faint supernovae associated with the first generations of stars, which experience extensive mixing and fallback during their explosions (Umeda & Nomoto 2003, 2005; Tominaga et al. 2007).

1.4 Aim of This Study

The aim of this study is to better understand the global structure of the Galactic stellar halo system, through inference of its density profile(s) and determination of the kinematic and orbital parameters of its constituent stars (e.g., mean rotational velocity, velocity ellipsoids, eccentricities). I address the possible presence of a second stellar halo component, explore its properties, and identify differences between them and those of the canonical single-halo interpretation.

The full space motion and orbital parameters of a large number of calibration stars from the SDSS are combined with chemical compositions (metallicity; $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$). Moreover, the thick disk and MWTD are investigated in terms of kinematics, orbital properties, and chemical composition. Finally, the frequency and distribution of the CEMP stars in the Galactic halo system are explored. The data employed are SDSS DR5 (Data Release 5; Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2007), and data from its first extension, (SDSS-II), which included the sub-survey SEGUE: Sloan Extension for Galactic Understanding and Exploration (SDSS DR7 & SEGUE; Abazajian et al. 2009; Yanny et al. 2009).

1.5 Outline of the Papers to be Presented

This thesis comprises a series of papers (published or submitted) that describe the discovery of the second stellar halo component of the Milky Way (the outer halo), and characterize the kinematic and chemical properties of the inner- and outer-halo populations, as well as of the thick disk and MWTD. Each paper is presented as a stand-alone chapter.

Chapter 2 describes the discovery of the dichotomy of the halo of the Milky Way, based on calibration stars from SDSS DR5. This important discovery was built on existing clues that such a dichotomy was present. The kinematics, orbital parameters, and chemical composition of the inner and outer halo are derived and compared. The discovery reported in this paper is a fundamental breakthrough in the understanding of the formation of the Galactic halo and its subsequent evolution.

Chapter 3 reports an extended analysis of the properties of the two halo components, based on calibration stars from SDSS DR7, and addresses the question of how many components are necessary to explain the kinematic properties of the metal-poor stars in the local volume. The velocity ellipsoids for the inner- and outer-halo components, as well as for the thick disk and MWTD, are evaluated. Also, the power-law density profiles of the inner and outer halo and the tilt of their velocity ellipsoids are determined. Finally, the as-observed MDF of the calibration-star sample, as a function of the distance from the Galactic plane ($|Z|$), is derived.

Chapter 4 explores the CEMP stars in the inner- and outer-halo components. The analysis is based on accurate determination of carbon-to-iron abundance ratio ($[C/Fe]$, or carbonicity) and kinematic quantities for SDSS DR7 calibration stars. The carbon abundance estimates are based on fits of the CH G-band at 4300 Å. The kinematic and orbital parameters have been evaluated for an Extended Sample ($d < 10$ kpc) of stars by employing the methodologies described in Chapter 3. The Extreme Deconvolution technique is applied to the extended sample to separate the two components in velocity space, and provides membership probabilities for each star (Bovy, Hogg, & Roweis 2009). The as-observed carbonicity distribution function (CarDF), as a function of the distance above or below the Galactic plane, and the global fraction of CEMP stars as a function of metallicity ($[Fe/H]$), are explored. Finally, I consider the contrast in the CEMP stellar fraction between the inner- and outer-halo components based on stars with $[Fe/H] < -1.5$ and $Z_{max} > 5$ kpc.

Chapter 5 reports a brief synopsis of the main thesis results, and addresses the issue of the determination of accurate distances in Galactic studies. In the concluding remarks section, the inner and outer halo are considered in the context of Galaxy formation, together with a summary of the theoretical models that reproduce the dual halo properties, such as the density mass profile and the shift in metallicity going from the inner- to the outer-halo component, in the context of the Λ CDM model. Also, a possible dichotomy in the halos of other galaxies is examined. In addition, the thick-disk component is examined from theoretical modeling, and the properties of the MWTD are summarized. Finally, recent studies on the possible chemical distinction between inner and outer halos, and a subsection related to future work are provided.

Appendix A demonstrates that recent criticisms raised concerning the original identification of a retrograde signature for the outer halo are incorrect. New derivations of the rotational behavior of the calibration-star samples (including a subset with revised distances), show that the retrograde signature and the high velocity dispersion of the outer-halo population remains, with values similar to those derived in Chapter 2 and 3. Moreover, an additional test of the presence of the retrograde signature is provided, based exclusively on observed proper motions among the low-metallicity stars.

Appendix B describes the discovery of a cool metal-poor, main-sequence star exhibiting large excesses of r-process elements. This star is one of two newly discovered cool subdwarfs (effective temperatures of 5000 K) with extremely low metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$) identified from follow-up high-resolution spectroscopy of metal-poor candidates from the SDSS. The star has $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.4$ and $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] = +1.9$, and exhibits a scaled solar r-process abundance pattern of heavy neutron-capture elements. This is the first example of an extremely metal-poor main-sequence star showing large excesses of r-process elements. The kinematic parameters are consistent with membership in the outer halo.

1.6 Presentation and Style

Chapter 2 has been written as an article for publication in the journal *Nature*, while Chapters 3 and 4 were written for publication in the *Astrophysical Journal*. In accordance with journal style, each contains an Abstract, Introduction, Conclusion and Bibliography of its own. The article in *Nature* was written with less technical language, following the journal's policy (terminology, style, etc.). It also contains extended supplementary material which was published on-line. Appendix A and B were written for publication in the *Astrophysical Journal*.

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2

Two Stellar Components in the Milky Way Halo

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Abstract

The halo of the Milky Way provides unique elemental abundance and kinematic information on the first objects to form in the Universe, which can be used to tightly constrain models of galaxy formation and evolution. Although the halo was once considered a single component, evidence for its dichotomy has slowly emerged in recent years from inspection of small samples of halo objects. Here we show that the halo is indeed clearly divisible into two broadly overlapping structural components – an inner and an outer halo – that exhibit different spatial density profiles, stellar orbits and stellar metallicities (abundances of elements heavier than helium). The inner halo has a modest net prograde rotation, whereas the outer halo exhibits a net retrograde rotation and a peak metallicity one-third that of the inner halo. These properties indicate that the individual halo components probably formed in fundamentally different ways, through successive dissipational (inner) and dissipationless (outer) mergers and tidal disruption of proto-Galactic clumps.

2.1 Introduction

Astronomers have long sought to constrain models for the formation and evolution of the Milky Way (our Galaxy) on the basis of observations of the stellar and globular cluster populations that it contains. These populations are traditionally defined as samples of objects that exhibit common spatial distributions, kinematics and metallicities (the age of a population, when available, is also sometimes used). Metallicity is taken by astronomers to represent the abundances of the elements heavier than helium, which are only created by nucleosynthesis in stars - either internally via nuclear burning in their cores or externally during explosive nucleosynthesis at the end of their lives. The earliest generations of stars have the lowest metallicities, because the gas from which they formed had not been enriched in heavy elements created by previous stars and distributed throughout the primordial interstellar medium by stellar winds and supernovae.

Previous work has provided evidence that the halo of the Milky Way may not comprise a single population, primarily from analysis of the spatial profiles (or inferred spatial profiles) of halo objects (Hartwick 1987; Zinn 1993; Preston et al. 1991; Kinman et al. 1994). A recent example of such an analysis is the observation of two different spatial density profiles for distinct classes of RR Lyrae variable stars in the halo (Miceli et al. 2007). In addition, tentative claims for a net retrograde motion of halo objects by previous authors supports the existence of a likely dual-component halo (Majewski 1992; Carney et al. 1996; Wilhelm 1996; Kinman et al. 2007; Lee et al. 2007). The central difficulty in establishing with confidence whether or not a dichotomy of the halo populations exists is that the past samples of tracer objects have been quite small, and usually suitable only for consideration of a limited number of the expected signatures of its presence. In the present work, we examine this question in detail using a large, homogeneously selected and analysed sample of over 20,000 stars, originally obtained as calibration data during the course of Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al. 2000). Although there are many possible alternative (and more complex) models that might be considered, multiple lines of evidence derived from these data clearly confirm that the halo can be resolved into (at least) two primary populations, the inner and the outer halo, with very different observed properties.

We find that the inner-halo component of the Milky Way dominates the population of halo stars found at distances up to 10-15 kpc from the Galactic Centre (including the Solar neighbourhood). An outer-halo component dominates in the regions beyond 15-20 kpc. We show the inner halo to be a population of stars that are non-spherically distributed about the centre of the Galaxy, with an inferred axial ratio on the order of ~ 0.6 . Inner-halo stars possess generally high orbital eccentricities, and exhibit a modest prograde rotation (between 0 and 50 km s⁻¹) around the centre of the Galaxy (see Table 2.2). The distribution of metallicities for stars in the inner halo peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$, with tails extending to higher and lower metallicities. (Here, metallicity is defined as

$$[A/B] = \log_{10}(N_A/N_B)_* - \log_{10}(N_A/N_B)_\odot \quad (2.1)$$

where N_A and N_B represent the number density of atoms of elements A and B, and the subscript \odot indicates solar values.) The outer halo, by contrast, comprises stars that exhibit a much more spherical spatial distribution, with an axial ratio ~ 0.9 to 1.0 . Outer-halo stars cover a wide range of orbital eccentricities, including many with lower eccentricity orbits than found for most stars associated with the inner halo, and exhibit a clear retrograde net rotation (between -40 and -70 km s^{-1}) about the centre of the Galaxy. The metallicity distribution function (MDF) of the outer halo peaks at lower metallicity than that of the inner halo, around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$, and includes a larger fraction of low-metallicity stars than does the MDF of the inner-halo population.

2.2 Evidence for the dichotomy of the halo

The spectroscopy, photometry, and astrometry for our large sample of stars were obtained from observations carried out with the Apache Point 2.5-m SDSS telescope; these data are publicly available as Data Release 5. Details concerning the selection of the stars and the measurement of their stellar parameters (temperature, surface gravity, and metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$), as well as the methods used to obtain their estimated distances, proper motions and derived kinematics, can be found in the Supplementary Information.

Our 20,236 program stars explore distances up to 20 kpc from the Sun, but we can only obtain useful estimates of the full space motions (as described in the Supplementary Information) for the subset of 10,123 stars in a local volume (up to 4 kpc from the Sun; Fig. 2.1). The restriction of the sample to the region of the solar neighbourhood is also made so that the assumptions going into the kinematic calculations are best satisfied. Figure 2.2 shows the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for different cuts in the V velocity, which is the orbital component that measures the motion of a star (with respect to the Local Standard of Rest) in the rotation direction of the Galaxy. The transition in the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ that is expected as one sweeps from stars with thick-disk-like motions to stars with halo-like motions is clear. However, with the large sample of stars in our sample, it is possible to investigate the change in the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for stars that are increasingly more retrograde, as well as for those that are both highly retrograde and have orbits taking them to high Z_{max} (the maximum distance above the Galactic plane reached by a star during the course of its orbit about the Galactic Centre - the Supplementary Information describes the methods used to derive this fundamental parameter). This figure shows that stars with the most retrograde orbits, and those that reach large distances in their orbits above the Galactic plane, exhibit distributions of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ that peak at metallicities between -2.0 and -2.2 , which we associate with the outer-halo population. The inner-halo population dominates the samples of stars with peak metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1.6$.

Astronomers have long debated whether there might exist a change in the rotational properties of the halo of the Milky Way as a function of distance from the Galactic Centre, based on much smaller samples of globular clusters (Zinn 1993; Lee et al. 2007) and stars (Majewski 1992; Carney et al. 1996; Wilhelm 1996; Sandage & Fouts

1987; Ryan & Norris 1991) than we consider here. The stellar samples were obtained with selection criteria (for example, on the basis of high proper motions for halo stars in the solar neighbourhood – Carney et al. 1996; Sandage & Fouts 1987; Ryan & Norris 1991, or from in situ, apparent-magnitude limited surveys – Majewski 1992; Kinman et al. 2007; Chiba & Beers 2000) that we suggest favoured membership in one or the other of the now-clearly-revealed halo components. A detailed summary of the kinematics of our programme stars is presented in the Supplementary Information, where we also establish consistency between properties obtained through techniques based on full space motions and those based on radial velocities alone, which argues against the existence of any large systematic errors in the proper motions. Table 2.1 summarizes the past and present determinations of $\langle V_\phi \rangle$, the mean rotational velocity with respect to the Galactic Centre, where claims for a retrograde halo have been made. Previous samples that have addressed this question were based on either much smaller total numbers of objects (with the limitation that they could not well sample both the inner- and outer-halo populations), did not have proper motions available (or only highly uncertain ones), or were otherwise restricted due to the selection criteria employed (that is, they were kinematically biased – Carney 1999, or had limited sky coverage, rendering them sensitive to the effects of individual star streams – Majewski et al. 1994). The local sample of SDSS calibration stars we have assembled does not suffer from any of these limitations. The retrograde signatures for stars we associate with the outer-halo population are robust and highly statistically significant (except for the smallest subsample).

Figure 2.1 The spatial distribution of the stars analyzed in the present sample. The distribution of the full sample of 20,236 unique SDSS (Data Release 5 – Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2007) spectrophotometric and telluric calibration stars in the Z-R plane is shown, where Z is the derived distance from the Galactic plane in the vertical direction and R is the derived distance from the centre of the Galaxy projected onto this plane. The dashed blue line represents the Galactic plane, while the filled orange dot is the position of the Sun, at $Z = 0$ kpc and $R = 8.5$ kpc. The 'wedge shape' of the selection area is the result of limits of the SDSS footprint in Galactic latitude. The red points indicate the 10,123 stars that satisfy our criteria for a local sample of stars, having $7 \text{ kpc} < R < 10 \text{ kpc}$, with distance estimates from the Sun $d < 4 \text{ kpc}$, and with viable measurements of stellar parameters and proper motions.

Figure 2.2 See next page for caption.

Figure 2.2 The distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for various cuts in the V velocity, the component of orbital motion measured with respect to the Local Standard of Rest. The Local Standard of Rest is a frame in which the mean space motions of the stars in the Solar neighbourhood average to zero. A blue dashed line at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$ is added for reference in all three columns. In the left-hand column, the full data set is considered. The stars with modestly negative V velocities in the upper three panels are dominated by stars from the thick-disk (and metal-weak thick-disk) populations, with a peak metallicity around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -0.7$. A transition to dominance by inner- and outer-halo population stars becomes evident for $V < 90 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; in the bottom panel of this column, the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ appears similar to what in the past was considered ‘the halo’, but we argue results from a superposition of contributions from both inner- and outer-halo populations. In the middle column, the large numbers of stars with $V < 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ are broken into smaller ranges in V velocity. As V becomes increasingly retrograde ($V < -220 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), the metallicity distribution shifts to include ever larger numbers of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, and relatively fewer stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1.6$. The same V velocity cuts are applied in the right-hand column, but only for stars with $Z_{\text{max}} > 5 \text{ kpc}$, in order to decrease the contribution from inner-halo population stars. Although fewer stars are included, the increasing dominance of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ is even more apparent. We associate the stars with the most extreme retrograde orbits (and those that reach far above the Galactic plane in their orbits) with the outer-halo population.

Table 2.1. Studies claiming a retrograde outer halo

Sample and Selection Criteria	N	Additional Restrictions	$\langle V_\phi \rangle$ (km s^{-1})	Method	Source
Globular clusters (non kinematic)	19	Young Halo	-64 ± 74	F&W	Ref. 2
Globular clusters (non kinematic)	20	Young Halo	-42 ± 80	F&W	Ref. 10
RR Lyraes (non kinematic)	26	$ Z < 8$ kpc	-95 ± 29	FSM	Ref. 9
Field subdwarfs (kinematic)	30	$Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc	-45 ± 22	FSM	Ref. 7
		Bias Corrected	$+24 \pm 13$		Ref. 16
Field horizontal-branch stars (non kinematic)	90	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.6$ $ Z > 4$ kpc	-93 ± 36	F&W	Ref. 8
Field subdwarfs (kinematic)	101	$V < -100$ km s^{-1} $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$	-32 ± 10	FSM	Ref. 13
Field F,G,K dwarfs (non kinematic)	250	$ Z > 5$ kpc	-55 ± 16	FSM	Ref. 6
Field F,G turnoff (non kinematic)		$Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc		FSM	This work
	2.228	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$	-11 ± 2		...
	200	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.2$	-41 ± 11		...
		$Z_{\text{max}} > 10$ kpc			
	771	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$	-38 ± 5		...
	94	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.2$	-71 ± 17		...
					...
		$Z_{\text{max}} > 15$ kpc			
	371	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$	-56 ± 8		...
	54	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.2$	-71 ± 25		...

Note. — Ref. 2: Zinn 1993 – Ref. 10: Lee et al. 2007 – Ref. 9: Kinman et al. 2007
 Ref. 7: Carney et al. 1996 – Ref. 16: Carney 1999 – Ref. 8: Wilhelm et al. 1996 – Ref. 13:
 Sandage & Fouts – Ref. 6: Majewski 1992. See next page for table caption.

Table 2.1 Previous and current determinations of the mean rotational velocity, V_ϕ and the error in the mean (σ/\sqrt{N} , where σ is the standard deviation and N is the number of stars) for samples in which a counter-rotating halo has been claimed, ordered by sample size. The samples listed in the first column are classified as to whether they were chosen on the basis of high proper motions (kinematic) or not (non-kinematic). Restrictions placed on each sample by the authors are listed in the third column (see original papers for details). The method of analysis used for each determination is listed: F & W, estimate based on the technique of Frenk & White (Frenk & White 1980), which considers distances and radial velocities alone, under the assumption of a cylindrically symmetric Galaxy; FSM, estimate based on consideration of the full space motions, which requires the use of proper motions, as well as distances and radial velocities. The samples analyzed with the F & W approach are either not statistically different from zero (refs 2, 10), or are only marginally so (ref. 8). Previous samples based on analysis of the full space motions vary from statistically insignificant (ref. 7), to just over 3 significance (refs. 6, 9, 13), due to the small numbers of stars considered. Note that after application of (uncertain) corrections for kinematic bias (ref. 16), the retrograde result reported in ref. 7 disappears entirely. One can assume that a similar outcome might apply to the ref. 13 determination. The samples of ref. 6 and ref. 9 are both selected over a restricted region of sky (towards the North Galactic Pole) and are therefore subject to possible contamination by individual stellar streams. All but two subsamples of the SDSS calibration star sample have retrograde signals that are significant at more than the 4 level. The subsample at $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1$ is likely to include significant contamination from inner-halo stars.

However, even our precise present determination of the net retrograde rotation of the outer halo, based on our local sample, is probably influenced by some degree of overlap between outer-halo stars with those from the inner-halo population. The distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for stars on increasingly retrograde orbits about the Galactic Centre for subsamples that reach different distances from the Galactic plane (Z_{max}) is shown in Figure 2.3. The MDFs of the stars with Z_{max} close to the Galactic plane are very different from those whose orbits reach farther from the plane. The distribution of metallicity clearly shifts to lower abundances as more severe cuts on V_{ϕ} or Z_{max} are applied, as supported by rigorous statistical tests. We conclude that the halo of the Galaxy comprises stars with intrinsically different distributions of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$; the observed changes in the MDF of halo stars with V_{ϕ} and Z_{max} would not be expected if the halo is considered as a single entity. The Supplementary Information presents additional observed differences in the energetics, the distribution of orbital eccentricities, and changes in the nature of stellar orbits for our programme stars that are also inconsistent with a single halo population.

In order to provide confirmation of the shift in the MDF inferred from our analysis of a local sample of stars, we also examine an auxiliary sample of stars that are presently located much farther from the Galactic Centre. This sample comprises 1235 blue horizontal-branch stars selected from the SDSS (Sirko et al. 2004). The stars cover a wide range of distances, from 5 kpc to over 80 kpc from the centre of the Galaxy. Statistical tests strongly reject the hypothesis that the stars at large distances from the Galactic centre could be drawn from the same parent population as those at distances close to the Galactic Centre (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.3 See next page for caption.

Figure 2.3 The distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for the stars in our sample on highly retrograde orbits. Stars from the disk populations, which possess prograde orbits, cannot be present in this plot. The panels show various cuts in V_ϕ , the rotational velocity with respect to the Galactic Centre in a cylindrical coordinate system, and for different ranges of Z_{max} (in kpc). A blue dashed line at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$ is added for reference. The left-hand column applies for stars with $V_\phi < -100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; the clearly skewed distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ exhibits an increased contribution from lower metallicity stars as one progresses from the low ($Z_{\text{max}} < 5 \text{ kpc}$) to the high ($Z_{\text{max}} > 15 \text{ kpc}$) subsamples. Simultaneously, the predominance of stars from the inner-halo population, with peak metallicity at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1.6$, decreases in relative strength, and shifts to lower $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Similar behaviors are seen in the middle and right-hand columns, which correspond to cuts on $V_\phi < -150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and -200 km s^{-1} , respectively. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of the null hypothesis that the MDFs of stars shown in the lower panels for the individual cuts on V_ϕ could be drawn from the MDFs of the same parent population as those shown in the upper panels, against an alternative that the stars are drawn from more metal-poor parent MDFs, is rejected at high levels of statistical significance. For $V_\phi < -100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, one-sided probabilities less than 0.0001 are obtained for the cuts on $Z_{\text{max}} > 5, 10,$ and 15 kpc , respectively. For $V_\phi < -150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, one-sided probabilities of 0.0004, 0.0001, and 0.0003 are obtained, for $Z_{\text{max}} > 5, 10,$ and 15 kpc , respectively. For $V_\phi < -200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, one-sided probabilities of 0.014, 0.010, and 0.033 are obtained, for $Z_{\text{max}} > 5, 10,$ and 15 kpc , respectively.

Figure 2.4 A sample of blue horizontal-branch stars exploring much larger distances from the Galactic Centre than the SDSS calibration stars. The distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ is shown for various cuts on the distance from the Galactic Centre, r , in kpc. The nature of the MDF appears to shift from the upper two panels, which exhibit the character of a mixture of inner- and outer-halo populations, over to a unimodal distribution in the third panel, centred on $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -2.0$. The most distant blue horizontal-branch (BHB) stars in the lowest panel also exhibit the appearance of a mixture of the two populations, possibly due to the inclusion of inner-halo stars on highly eccentric orbits that take them far from the Galactic Centre. The peak around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.0$ seen in several of the panels is an artefact arising from the limit of the metallicity grid that is used for abundance determinations of the BHB stars. A Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test of the null hypothesis that the MDFs of stars shown in the lower panels for the individual cuts on Galactocentric distance r could be drawn from the same parent population as the stars shown in the first panel, against an alternative that the stars are drawn from more metal-poor parent MDFs, is rejected at high levels of statistical significance (one-sided probabilities of 0.0262, 0.0005, and 0.0243, respectively, for the three higher cuts on Galactocentric distance). The fraction of stars with metallicities $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ (primarily outer-halo stars) grows from 31% for stars with $5 < r < 10$ kpc to 46% for stars at larger Galactocentric distances.

It has been shown, on the basis of Jeans' theorem (Binney & May 1986; Sommer-Larsen & Zhen 1990), that the global structure of the stellar halo can be recovered from local kinematic information, as long as one has a sufficiently large number of stars observed in the solar neighbourhood that explore the full phase-space distribution of the pertinent stellar populations. We note that the actual halo systems of the Galaxy are unlikely to be in well-mixed equilibrium states. However, the relaxation process is very slow compared to the orbital periods of typical stars, so the Jeans' theorem and the approach based on it remain at least approximately valid. The result of this exercise for our large sample of SDSS calibration stars, over narrow cuts in metallicity, is shown in Figure 2.5. The observed changes in the inferred spatial density profiles suggest that a flattened inner-halo population dominates locally for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, whereas the outer-halo population has a nearly spherical distribution, and dominates at distances beyond $r \approx 15\text{-}20$ kpc (where r represents the distance from the Galactic Centre), as well as locally for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. Variations in the halo spatial profile with distance have been recognized by a number of previous authors (Hartwick 1987; Zinn 1993; Preston 1991; Kinman 1994; Chiba & Beers 2000; Sommer-Larsen & Zhen 1990), based on samples of stars that are one to two orders of magnitude smaller than our present data set.

Figure 2.5 Equidensity contours of the reconstructed global density distributions for stars in our sample with various metallicities. The global density distributions are constructed from the sum of the probability density of an orbit at each location in the Z-R plane, with a weighting factor being inversely proportional to the corresponding density at the currently observed position of the star. High-density regions are indicated by redder colours, while low-density regions are indicated by bluer colours (a linear density scale is employed). Within each metallicity cut the apparent flattening of the inner regions slowly goes over to a more spherical shape with increasing distance. As one progresses from the more metal-rich ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1.0$) to the most metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.2$) subsets of these data, the overall nature of the equidensity contours also changes from highly flattened (axial ratios of ~ 0.6), to more spherical (axial ratio of ~ 0.9). This suggests that the inner- and outer-halo components are broadly overlapping in space and in metallicity – the inner-halo population is characterized as a flattened density distribution that dominates locally for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2$, whereas the outer-halo population is nearly spherical, and dominates at larger distances and locally for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2$.

2.3 Implications of the dichotomy of the halo

An early model for the formation of the Galaxy, based on the rapid (a few hundred million years) monolithic collapse of a gaseous proto-Galaxy (Eggen, Lynden-Bell & Sandage 1962), has yielded to the more recent idea that the halo of the Galaxy was assembled, over the span of several billion years, from smaller proto-Galactic clumps (Searle & Zinn 1978). This hierarchical assembly model has received close attention in recent years, in part because it fits well with the prevailing theory for the formation and evolution of structure in the Universe, based on the early collapse of ‘mini-haloes’ of cold dark matter (CDM) (White & Rees 1978; Moore et al. 2006). Modern numerical simulations for the assembly of large spirals based on CDM cosmogonies predict that the stars in the haloes of galaxies like the Milky Way might be comprised of the shredded stellar debris of numerous dwarf-like galaxies that have been torn apart by tidal interactions with their parent galaxy (Moore, et al. 2006; Bullock & Johnston, 2005; Abadi et al. 2006; Brook et al. 2007). Recent quantitative analysis of the amount of structure visible in the halo of the Galaxy from SDSS (Fukigita et al. 1996; Gunn et al. 1998; Pier et al. 2003; Gunn et al. 2006) imaging provides compelling additional evidence (Bell et al. 2007). Others have argued that some combination of a monolithic collapse and a hierarchical assembly model may be necessary to fully explain the observed data (Zinn 1993; Chiba & Beers 2000; Majewski 1993). Within the context of the CDM model, the formation of the inner halo may be understood in the following manner. Low-mass sub-Galactic fragments are formed at an early stage. These fragments rapidly merge into several (in many simulations, two – Abadi et al. 2006; Bekki & Chiba 2001) more-massive clumps, which themselves eventually dissipatively merge (due to the presence of gas that has yet to form stars). The essentially radial merger of the few resulting massive clumps gives rise to the dominance of the high-eccentricity orbits for stars that we assign here to membership in the inner halo. Star formation within these massive clumps (both pre- and post-merger) would drive the mean metallicity to higher abundances. This is followed by a stage of adiabatic compression (flattening) of the inner halo component owing to the growth of a massive disk, along with the continued accretion of gas onto the Galaxy (Bekki & Chiba 2001; Chiba & Beers 2001). The fact that the outer-halo component of the Milky Way exhibits a net retrograde rotation (and a different distribution of overall orbital properties), as found here, clearly indicates that the formation of the outer halo is distinct from that of both the inner-halo and disk components. We suggest, as others have before, that the outer-halo component formed, not through a dissipative, angular-momentum-conserving contraction, but rather through dissipationless chaotic

merging of smaller subsystems within a pre-existing dark-matter halo. These subsystems would be expected to be of much lower mass, and subject to tidal disruption in the outer part of a dark-matter halo, before they fall farther into the inner part. As candidate (surviving) counterparts for such subsystems, one might consider the low-luminosity dwarf spheroidal galaxies surrounding the Galaxy, in particular the most extreme cases recently identified from the SDSS (Belokurov et al. 2006; Belokurov et al. 2007). Subsystems of lower mass, and by inference, even lower metallicity, may indeed be destroyed so effectively that none (or very few) have survived to the present day. If so, the outer-halo population may be assembled from relatively more metal-poor stars, following the luminosity-metallicity relationship for Local Group dwarf galaxies (Dekel et al. 2003). The net retrograde rotation of the outer halo may be understood in the context of the higher efficiency of phase mixing for the orbits of stars that are stripped from subsystems on prograde, rather than retrograde orbits (Quinn & Goodman 1986; Norris & Ryan 1989). The clear difference in the MDFs of the two halo populations we identify also suggests that the lowest metallicity stars in the Galaxy may be associated with the outer halo, which can be exploited for future directed searches. It is noteworthy that the hyper metal-poor stars HE 0107-5240 (Christlieb et al., 2002) and HE 1327-2326 (Frebel et al. 2005), both of which have $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -5.0$, as well as the recently discovered ultra metal-poor star HE 0557-4840 (Norris et al. 2007), with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -4.8$, are either located greater than 10 kpc away (HE 0107-5240, HE 0557-4840) or have space motions that carry them far out into the Galaxy (HE 1327-2326; A. Frebel, personal communication). In addition, efforts to determine the primordial lithium abundance from observations of the most metal-poor stars (Bonifacio et al. 2007) may have inadvertently mixed samples from the inner- and outer-halo populations; such stars could have formed and evolved in rather different astrophysical environments. The inner/outer halo dichotomy may also have an impact of the expected numbers of carbon-enhanced metal-poor stars as a function of declining metallicity (Lucatello et al. 2006), and as a function of distance from the Galactic plane (Frebel et al. 2006; Tumlinson 2007). Much remains to be learned as the database of low-metallicity stars, in particular those that are found in distant in situ samples, or from those nearby stars with available proper motions that indicate membership of the outer-halo population. We look forward to the next dramatic increase in the numbers of very metal-poor stars that will come from the ongoing stellar samples from SDSS, in particular from SEGUE, the Sloan Extension for Galactic Understanding and Exploration.

2.4 Supplementary Information

2.4.1 Selection of the SDSS Calibration Stars

During the course of the original SDSS it was necessary to obtain medium-resolution ($R = \Delta\lambda/\lambda = 2000$) spectroscopy of a small number (16) of calibration stars per spectroscopic plug-plate (when fully populated with fibres, one plug-plate obtains 640 spectra simultaneously), chosen for two primary reasons. The first set of these objects, the spectrophotometric calibration stars, are stars that are selected to approximately remove the distortions of the observed flux of stars and galaxies arising from the wavelength response of the ARC 2.5m telescope and the SDSS spectrographs, as well as the distortions imposed on the observed spectra by the Earth's atmosphere. For this purpose, there is an advantage in choosing stars that satisfy three conditions: (1) their spectra are relatively clean of absorption lines arising from metallic species in the stars, (2) they are sufficiently bright, so that high signal-to-noise ($S/N > 20/1$) spectra can be obtained, and (3) they exhibit spectra that can be reasonably well-modelled by synthetic spectra on a known flux scale for a known class of stars, in this case, stars close to the halo main-sequence turnoff with metallicities near $[Fe/H] = -2.0$. These goals lead to a selection of stars with apparent magnitudes in the range $15.5 < g_0 < 17.0$, and satisfying the colour ranges $0.6 < (u-g)_0 < 1.2$; $0 < (g-r)_0 < 0.6$. The subscript 0 in the magnitudes and colours indicates that they are corrected for the effects of interstellar absorption and reddening, following standard procedures (Schlegel et al. 1998). The colour range is intentionally kept rather large, so that possible spectrophotometric calibration stars may be found even in cases where the density of stars is low, such as at the Galactic poles. Within these constraints, efforts are made to select stars that are as blue as possible, as these are the most likely to be consistent with $[Fe/H] = -2.0$. The second set of calibration stars, the telluric calibration stars, are used in order to calibrate and remove from SDSS spectra the presence of night sky emission and absorption features. The telluric calibration stars cover the same colour ranges as the spectrophotometric calibration stars, but at fainter apparent magnitudes, in the range $17.0 < g_0 < 18.5$. The requirement for favouring the bluer stars is also relaxed.

Figure 2.6 The U, V, and W components of the space motions of stars in our sample as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. A blue dashed line at 0 km s^{-1} has been added in each panel for reference. In the metallicity range $-1.2 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.3$, all three panels exhibit a low velocity dispersion population of stars with mean values of the velocity components near 0 km s^{-1} , and dispersion in velocities of around $40\text{--}50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. These are the stars of the thick-disk and metal-weak thick-disk populations. The metal-weak thick-disk population likely contains stars with metallicities as least as low as $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$ (Chiba & Beers 2000), but in much lower relative proportion compared to the more metal-rich stars. At metallicities below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.2$, the large velocity dispersions (on the order of 100 to 150 km s^{-1}) observed in each component are associated with the broadly overlapping inner- and outer-halo populations of stars.

Table 2.2. Full space motions for stars in the local volume

Sample	[Fe/H] Range	N	$\langle U \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\langle V \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\langle W \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	σ_U (km s ⁻¹)	σ_V (km s ⁻¹)	σ_W (km s ⁻¹)	$\langle V_\phi \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)
All Stars	-0.4 to -0.8	1853	-24 ± 1	-52 ± 1	-2 ± 1	58 ± 1	60 ± 1	40 ± 1	170 ± 1
	-0.8 to -1.0	1616	-23 ± 2	-78 ± 2	-3 ± 1	81 ± 1	77 ± 1	54 ± 1	143 ± 2
	-1.0 to -1.4	2496	-19 ± 3	-153 ± 2	-2 ± 1	132 ± 2	102 ± 1	73 ± 1	68 ± 2
	-1.4 to -1.8	2491	-14 ± 3	-199 ± 2	0 ± 2	152 ± 2	107 ± 2	81 ± 1	22 ± 2
	-1.8 to -2.2	1260	-21 ± 4	-224 ± 3	1 ± 3	158 ± 3	119 ± 2	103 ± 2	-2 ± 3
	< -2.2	349	-25 ± 9	-241 ± 8	8 ± 6	169 ± 6	159 ± 6	120 ± 5	-19 ± 8
Z < 1 kpc	-0.4 to -0.8	117	-4 ± 4	-14 ± 3	8 ± 3	46 ± 3	35 ± 2	32 ± 2	206 ± 3
	-0.8 to -1.0	108	-1 ± 7	-48 ± 7	-4 ± 4	70 ± 5	70 ± 5	44 ± 3	172 ± 7
1 < Z < 2 kpc	-1.0 to -1.4	1173	-10 ± 4	-136 ± 3	-5 ± 2	123 ± 3	99 ± 2	63 ± 1	85 ± 3
	-1.4 to -1.8	1211	-8 ± 4	-193 ± 3	-5 ± 2	144 ± 3	106 ± 2	79 ± 1	28 ± 3
	-1.8 to -2.2	502	-14 ± 7	-216 ± 5	-2 ± 5	147 ± 5	114 ± 4	95 ± 2	5 ± 5
	< -2.2	115	1 ± 14	-232 ± 14	11 ± 10	153 ± 10	147 ± 10	124 ± 5	-13 ± 14
2 < Z < 3 kpc	-1.0 to -1.4	971	-32 ± 4	-170 ± 3	-1 ± 3	139 ± 3	103 ± 2	78 ± 2	51 ± 3
	-1.8 to -2.2	561	-31 ± 7	-226 ± 5	2 ± 4	166 ± 5	117 ± 4	99 ± 3	-4 ± 5
	< -2.2	182	-36 ± 14	-236 ± 12	12 ± 9	187 ± 10	159 ± 8	120 ± 6	-12 ± 11
3 < Z < 4 kpc	-1.00 to -1.40	217	-34 ± 10	-191 ± 7	5 ± 6	154 ± 7	104 ± 5	82 ± 4	28 ± 7
	-1.4 to -1.8	208	-45 ± 11	-218 ± 8	4 ± 7	159 ± 8	121 ± 6	95 ± 5	2 ± 8
	-1.8 to -2.2	141	-9 ± 15	-254 ± 12	8 ± 10	177 ± 11	138 ± 8	122 ± 7	-34 ± 12
	< -2.2	43	-60 ± 18	-285 ± 28	-9 ± 21	121 ± 13	184 ± 20	139 ± 15	-63 ± 28

Note. — Table 2.2 Kinematic quantities for stars in the local volume based on full space motions. The estimates of $\langle U, V, W \rangle$ and $\sigma_{(U, V, W)}$ are derived making use of the combination of measured proper motions and radial velocities, as well as estimated distances. The errors listed are the error in the mean (σ/\sqrt{N}). For stars with $|Z| < 1$ kpc one can clearly recognize thick-disk-like rotation and velocity dispersions, while at higher $|Z|$ the rotation and dispersions result from the overlap of the inner- and outer-halo populations.

Table 2.3. A Frenk & White Analysis of Rotational Velocities

Sample	[Fe/H] Range	N	$\langle V_\phi \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	V_{rot} (km s ⁻¹)
All Stars	-0.40 to -0.80	1853	170 ± 1	156 ± 3
	-0.80 to -1.00	1616	143 ± 2	131 ± 3
	-1.00 to -1.40	2496	68 ± 2	57 ± 4
	-1.40 to -1.80	2491	22 ± 2	412 ± 6
	-1.80 to -2.20	1260	-2 ± 3	156 ± 3
	< -2.20	349	-19 ± 8	-10 ± 13
Z < 1 kpc	-0.40 to -0.80	117	206 ± 3	192 ± 7
	-0.80 to -1.00	108	172 ± 7	154 ± 12
1 < Z < 2 kpc	-1.00 to -1.40	1173	85 ± 3	73 ± 5
	-1.40 to -1.80	1211	28 ± 3	12 ± 6
	-1.80 to -2.20	501	5 ± 5	12 ± 9
	< -2.20	115	-13 ± 14	-12 ± 20
2 < Z < 3 kpc	-1.00 to -1.40	971	51 ± 3	37 ± 7
	-1.40 to -1.80	944	17 ± 3	8 ± 7
	-1.80 to -2.20	561	-4 ± 5	16 ± 10
	< -2.20	182	-12 ± 11	0 ± 18
3 < Z < 4 kpc	-1.00 to -1.40	217	28 ± 7	22 ± 17
	-1.40 to -1.80	208	2 ± 8	-1 ± 22
	-1.80 to -2.20	141	-34 ± 12	-17 ± 28
	< -2.20	43	-63 ± 28	-106 ± 56

Note. — Table 2.3 See next page for comments.

Note Table 2.3 Rotation estimates for stars in the local volume. The Frenk & White analysis employed for the calculation of the net rotation, V_{rot} , makes use of the measured radial velocities and distance estimates, so is not subject to possible systematic and random errors arising from use of the measured proper motions. An axi-symmetric Galaxy is also assumed. For comparison, the value of $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ from Table 2.2, based on analysis of the full space motions, is listed for the same subsamples of stars. The errors listed are the error in the mean (σ/\sqrt{N}). Note that the estimates of net rotation are, in most cases, commensurate within the quoted errors.

The S/N of the resulting spectra is lower than for the spectrophotometric stars owing to their fainter apparent magnitudes. Generally, the achieved range is $20/1 < S/N < 30/1$ for these stars. The full sample comprises 20,236 unique stars with acceptable derived atmospheric parameters. Although there is clearly a bias towards the identification of metal-poor stars arising from the colour selections (in particular for the spectrophotometric calibration stars), it should be kept in mind that it is not possible to discriminate the lowest metallicity stars, e.g., those with $[Fe/H] < -2.5$, from those with $[Fe/H] \sim -2.0$, since the effect of declining metallicity on broadband stellar colours is minimal in this regime. Hence, we expect that the distribution of metallicities for the calibration stars should reflect the true shape of the low-metallicity tail of the MDF for stars outside the disk populations. The same does not apply for stars with $[Fe/H] > -2.0$; the observed distributions of metallicity for such stars will mis-represent the true MDFs at these abundances. It is important to note that no bias on the kinematics, e.g., by making use of measured proper motions (the angular displacement of a given star over time, in the direction perpendicular to the line of sight), is introduced in the selection of the calibration objects. This choice enables our kinematic studies, without the need to apply explicit corrections or modeling of any selection bias for the motions of the stars in the sample. Once estimates of the atmospheric parameters for each of the calibration stars are obtained (as described below), one can use the derived surface gravity of each star to infer whether it is a likely dwarf, subgiant, or giant. Photometric estimates of the distance to each star (accurate to $\sim 10\text{--}20\%$) are then obtained by comparison of its observed apparent magnitude (corrected for interstellar absorption) with its expected absolute magnitude based on calibrated open cluster and globular cluster sequences (Beers et al. 2000).

2.4.2 Stellar Atmospheric Parameter Analysis

The SEGUE Stellar Parameter Pipeline (SSPP) (Beers et al. 2006; Lee et al. 2006; Allende Prieto et al. 2007; Lee et al. 2007a; Lee et al. 2007b) processes the wavelength- and flux-calibrated spectra generated by the standard SDSS spectroscopic reduction pipeline (Stoughton et al. 2002), obtains equivalent widths and/or line indices for about 80 atomic or molecular absorption lines, and estimates the effective temperature, T_{eff} , surface gravity, $\log(g)$, and $[Fe/H]$ for a given star through the application of a number of approaches. The current techniques employed by the SSPP include chi-square minimization with respect to synthetic spectral templates (Allende Prieto et al. 2006; Lee et al. 2006; Lee et al. 2007a), neural network analysis (Re Fiorentin et al. 2007), auto-correlation analysis (Beers et al. 1999), and a variety of line-index

calculations based on previous calibrations with respect to known standard stars. The SSPP employs five primary methods for the estimation of T_{eff} , eight for the estimation of $\log(g)$, and nine for the estimation of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The use of multiple methods allows for empirical determinations of the internal errors for each parameter, based on the range of reported values from each method – typical internal errors for stars in the temperature range that applies to the calibration stars are ($T_{\text{eff}} \sim 100 \text{ K}$ to 125 K , $\log(g) \sim 0.25$ dex, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim 0.20$ dex). Over the past two years, large-aperture telescopes have been used to obtain high-resolution spectroscopy for over 150 of the brighter ($14 < g_0 < 16.0$) SDSS stars. Analysis of these data indicates that the external errors on the determinations of atmospheric parameters generated by the SSPP are in fact of similar magnitude (Sivarani et al. 2006; Allende Prieto et al. 2007; Lee et al. 2007a; Lee et al. 2007b).

2.4.3 Derivation of Kinematic Parameters

In order to obtain the best available estimates of the kinematics and orbital parameters for the stars in our sample as a function $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, we consider only those stars satisfying several cuts: (1) a selection in the effective temperature range $5000 \text{ K} < T_{\text{eff}} < 6800 \text{ K}$, over which the SSPP is expected to provide the highest accuracy in both the atmospheric parameters and chemical compositions, reducing the number of stars to 19,592, (2) a selection of the stars in the sample with distances $d < 4 \text{ kpc}$ from the Sun, in order to restrict the kinematical and orbital analyses to a local volume (where the assumptions going into their calculation are best satisfied), reducing the number of stars to 14,175. This selection also mitigates against the increase in the errors in the derived transverse velocities, which scale with distance¹ from the Sun (e.g., for a typical star in our sample, at $d = 1 \text{ kpc}$, errors of 3.5 mas/yr in proper motions and 15% in distance result in errors in the derived transverse velocities of 22 km s^{-1} ; these rise to 37 km s^{-1} and 46 km s^{-1} for stars at $d = 2 \text{ kpc}$ and 4 kpc , respectively) and (3) a selection on R , the present Galactocentric distance of a star projected onto the Galactic plane, to be in the range $7 < R < 10 \text{ kpc}$. After these restrictions are applied, the number of stars in the remaining sample is 10,123. Radial velocities for stars in our sample are derived from matches to an external library of high-resolution spectral templates with accurately known velocities (Prugniel & Soubiran 2001), degraded in resolution to that of the SDSS spectra. The typical accuracies of the resulting radial velocities are on the

¹Note that the transverse velocity uncertainty depends as well on the proper motion uncertainty. When the propagation of both uncertainties (distance and proper motion) is applied, the net effect is that the transverse velocity scales more slowly with distance.

order of 3–20 km s⁻¹, depending on the S/N of the spectra, with zero-point errors no more than 3 km s⁻¹, based on a comparison of the subset of stars in our sample with radial velocities obtained from the high-resolution spectra taken for testing and validation of the SSPP (Allende Prieto et al. 2007). The proper motions (taken from the re-calibrated USNO-B catalogue, with typical accuracy around 3–4 mas yr⁻¹ – Munn et al. 2004), in combination with the distance estimates and radial velocities, provide the information required to calculate the full space motions. The components of the space motions are represented as the (U,V,W) velocities of the stars with respect to the Local Standard of Rest (LSR; defined as a frame in which the mean space motions of the stars in the Solar neighbourhood average to zero). The velocity component U is taken to be positive in the direction toward the Galactic anti-centre, the V component is positive in the direction toward Galactic rotation, and the W component is positive toward the north Galactic pole. Corrections for the motion of the Sun with respect to the LSR are applied during the course of the calculation of the full space motions; here we adopt the values (U_⊙ , V_⊙ , W_⊙) = (–9, 12, 7) km s⁻¹ (Mihalas & Binney 1981). For our analysis it is also convenient to obtain the rotational component of a star’s motion about the Galactic centre in a cylindrical frame; this is denoted as V_φ, and is calculated assuming that the LSR is on a circular orbit with a value of 220 km s⁻¹ (Kerr & Lynden-Bell 1986). The value of the Solar distance is assumed to be R (8.5 kpc). The orbital parameters of the stars, such as the perigalactic distance (the closest approach of a stellar orbit to the Galactic centre, r_{peri}), the apogalactic distance (the farthest extent of a stellar orbit from the Galactic centre, r_{apo}), the orbital eccentricity, and Z_{max} (the maximum distance of stellar orbits above or below the Galactic plane) are derived by adopting an analytic Stäckel-type gravitational potential (which consists of a flattened, oblate disk and a nearly spherical massive halo) and integrating their orbital paths based on the starting point obtained from the observations (Chiba & Beers 2000).

2.4.4 Kinematics of the SDSS Calibration Stars

Figure 2.6 shows the three velocity components (U,V,W) as a function of the derived metallicity, [Fe/H]. One can clearly distinguish the presence of the low velocity dispersion thick-disk and metal-weak thick-disk populations (Chiba & Beers 2000), as well as a second group of stars that exhibits a broad dispersion in both their velocity components and metallicities; these stars comprise the overlapping inner- and outer-halo populations. Table 2.2 summarizes the derived kinematics of our sample as a whole, as well as for different cuts in the present distance of stars above or below the Galactic

plane. The errors on the derived $\langle U, V, W \rangle$ and on their dispersions, $\sigma(U, V, W)$, are the most precise estimates obtained to date, owing to the very large numbers of stars in our sample. Table 2.3 provides an alternative set of estimated net rotation for the subsamples considered in Table 2.2. These estimates are derived on the basis of radial velocities and distances alone (and through adoption of an axi-symmetric model for the distribution of stars in the Galaxy – Frenk & White 1980), so that errors in the measured proper motions cannot propagate into the inferred values of rotation (the net rotation about the Galactic centre obtained from such an analysis is conventionally referred to as V_{rot}). As is clear from inspection of this table (Figure 2.7 provides a graphical representation of these results), the values of rotation obtained from the analysis of the full space motions are generally in good agreement with the reported V_{rot} , although the derived errors in V_{rot} become quite large when the number of stars is small. This provides a demonstration that any systematic errors in the derived proper motions used in our analysis must be rather small, and furthermore, that they do not scale with distance.

Figure 2.7 Comparison of the derived net rotational velocities of our sample stars with respect to the Galactocentric rest frame, V_ϕ , using two alternative methods. The black dots (and lines) correspond to the net rotations listed in Table 2.3 obtained with the Frenk & White analysis (F & W), which only considers the distances and radial velocities. The red dots (and lines) correspond to the net rotations obtained when proper motions are employed, along with distances and radial velocities, to estimate full space motions (FSM). It is clear that the methods return equivalent estimates of net rotation when large numbers of stars are involved (upper left-hand panel). The remaining panels, which are for cuts on increasing distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$, indicate that the agreement remains acceptable, in particular at higher metallicities. Note, however, that the errors obtained from the Frenk & White analysis become quite large at lower metallicities, due to the smaller numbers of stars in the calculation.

Toomre (as attributed by Sandage & Fouts 1987) introduced a convenient method for visualizing the distribution of orbital energies for stars observed in the local neighbourhood, by plotting the parameter $[U^2 + W^2]^{1/2}$ as a function of the V velocity component. Sets of Toomre diagrams for the stars in our sample are shown in Figure 2.8, for various cuts on Z_{\max} and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The different cuts on these quantities demonstrates that there exists an imbalance in the distribution of orbital energies for stars with $Z_{\max} < 5$ kpc, and for stars in the intermediate interval $5 \text{ kpc} < Z_{\max} < 10$ kpc, in the sense that the stars on prograde orbits populate lower-energy orbits than do the stars with retrograde orbits. Only when one considers the lower panels of Figure 2.8, which correspond to stars with $Z_{\max} > 10$ kpc, does it appear that there the distribution of orbital energies between the prograde and retrograde stars is roughly similar at all metallicities. This behaviour is a result of the highly overlapped inner- and outer-halo populations in the Solar neighbourhood.

The use of metallicity and kinematics to constrain models of the formation of the Galaxy began over four decades ago (Eggen, Lynden-Bell & Sandage 1962; ELS). The relatively clear correlation between $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ and eccentricity in Figure 4 of ELS (1962) was interpreted as providing strong evidence for a rapid, monolithic collapse of the Galaxy, with stars forming on a similar timescale as that of the collapse, on the order of no more than 1 Gyr. In this model, the motions of lower metallicity stars reflected earlier gas dynamical evolution of the proto-Galactic cloud, inside of which star formation, and thus chemical evolution, proceeded progressively. The adoption of orbital eccentricity as a dynamical indicator for stars is advantageous, as this is nearly an adiabatic invariant under a slow change of a gravitational potential (ELS). It has since been shown that the appearance of the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ vs. eccentricity diagram was strongly influenced by the kinematic selection criteria used by these authors. The equivalent diagram for a larger non-kinematically selected sample of stars (see Figure 6a of Chiba & Beers, 2000) clearly demonstrated that stars are found in the Galaxy over the entire range of observed $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ and orbital eccentricity (Chiba & Beers 2000). Figure 2.9 shows this diagram for the sample of SDSS calibration stars considered herein; the number of stars shown represents an order of magnitude increase in sample size as compared to all previous samples. Although one can clearly discern concentrations of stars with higher metallicity and lower eccentricity, as well as stars with lower metallicity and higher eccentricity, there exist many stars for which these two quantities appear uncorrelated. A monolithic collapse model would not predict such behaviour. We now consider how the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ changes for stars as a function of their orbital eccentricities.

Figure 2.8 See next page for caption.

Figure 2.8 Toomre energy diagrams for various cuts of our sample on Z_{\max} , the maximum distance above or below the Galactic plane that a star reaches during the course of its orbit about the Galactic centre, and on metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The blue dashed line indicates the division between retrograde (RET) and prograde (PRO) orbits with respect to the Galactic centre (assuming the LSR rotates at 220 km s^{-1}). The red dotted lines indicate total space velocities of the orbits, in the frame with respect to the Galactic centre; between 100 km s^{-1} (inner-most) and 500 km s^{-1} (outer-most). In the upper row, energy diagrams for stars exploring all ranges of Z_{\max} and various cuts in metallicity are shown – the left-most panel shows stars of all metallicities, the middle and right panels are for stars with intermediate ($-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$) metallicities, and very low metallicities, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, respectively. Inspection of this row shows the decreasing importance of stars on disk-like orbits (the highly prograde stars near 0 km s^{-1}) with declining $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Although a number of metal-weak thick-disk stars remain in the middle panel of this row, the majority of stars are associated with a prograde rotation inner-halo population. In the right-hand panel of this row the metallicity selection has effectively eliminated any metal-weak thick-disk stars, and one can appreciate that the stars with retrograde orbits explore to much larger energies than the prograde stars. The orbits of the retrograde stars are also more uniformly distributed in energy than those of the prograde stars, which concentrate in the region of this diagram corresponding to lower orbital energies. The middle panels show the same cuts on metallicity but for intermediate cuts on Z_{\max} . Even though the total numbers of stars is lower, the contrast between the higher orbital energies of the stars on retrograde orbits with the lower orbital energy stars on prograde orbits remains clear. Stars in these intervals of Z_{\max} are contributed from both the inner- and outer-halo populations, and exhibit different distributions in energy depending on $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The lower panels show the same cuts on metallicity but for stars reaching $Z_{\max} > 10 \text{ kpc}$, which are dominated by stars from the outer-halo population. The relative contributions of stars on various energy orbits is now much more evenly distributed between retrograde and prograde orbits, independent of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The V velocities of the retrograde orbits explore to much lower V than the prograde orbits explore to higher V .

Figure 2.9 The relationship between $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ and orbital eccentricity for the sample of 10,123 SDSS calibration stars considered in the present analysis. At the bottom left of the panel, one can clearly distinguish the presence of moderate metallicity ($-1.3 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.3$, with a mode $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.8$), low-eccentricity (0 to 0.4) stars of the thick-disk and metal-weak thick-disk populations. (Note that the thick disk of the Galaxy actually contains much larger numbers of stars near $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.6$ than shown here; such metal-rich stars are heavily censored by the selection process used in the assembly of the calibration star sample). At the right of the panel, one can also discern the presence of low-metallicity ($-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, with a mode $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.5$), high-eccentricity (0.6 to 1.0) stars which we associate with the inner-halo population; additional members of the inner-halo population extend over all eccentricities and metallicities. The outer-halo population exhibits a relatively uniform distribution of orbital eccentricities over the full range from 0.0 to 1.0, and is dominated by lower metallicity stars (-1.5 to -3.5 , with a mode $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.0$) as a result it is not easily separated from the other populations shown in this diagram.

The left column of Figure 2.10 applies for stars at all Z_{\max} , while the right column applies for stars with $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc. Very different behaviours in the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ are found when comparing the left-hand and right-hand columns in various ranges of orbital eccentricity. The change in the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ in the left-hand column could be fully explained by considering the transition from stars with disk-like metallicities (and low-eccentricity orbits) to those with a single-component halo distribution of metallicities and high-eccentricity orbits. However, the right-hand column, which applies to stars with $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc, exhibits a behaviour that has not been seen previously. The upper panel of this column shows a clear bimodal distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, due to the presence of outer-halo stars with low-eccentricity orbits. The middle panels exhibit a broad distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, which we interpret as an overlap of contributions from the inner- and outer-halo populations, and the lower panels show the dominance of the contribution from inner-halo stars. This would not be expected if the halo were a single stellar population. Our analysis also indicates that the inner- and outer-halo populations exhibit different orbital characteristics. Figure 2.11 shows the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for stars as a function of the derived r_{peri} and r_{apo} distances for various cuts in the value of V_{ϕ} . It is clear that the majority of inner-halo stellar orbits penetrate close to the Galactic centre (within about 3 kpc), while the outer-halo stellar orbits (those stars on highly retrograde orbits) rarely penetrate this close. The majority of inner-halo stars also exhibit orbits that reach no farther than about 15-20 kpc from the Galactic centre, whereas the outer-halo stars cover the range in apogalactic distance between 10 and 80 kpc fairly uniformly. It should be kept in mind that in order to appear in our sample, stars must be on orbits that pass through the Solar neighbourhood. Thus, there exists the possibility that some degree of ‘Keplerian censorship’ applies (as pointed out by an anonymous referee). The full extent of this orbital censorship, and its influence on the appearance of Figure 2.11, requires additional modeling. Regardless of the degree of orbital censorship that might exist, the shift in the mean metallicity from the higher metallicity inner-halo to the lower metallicity outer-halo population is clear.

Figure 2.10 Distribution of $[Fe/H]$ for various cuts in the orbital eccentricities of stars for two cuts in Z_{\max} . A blue dashed line at $[Fe/H] = -2.0$ is shown for reference in both columns. In the left-hand column, all distances from the Galactic plane are considered. At low eccentricity, one clearly sees the presence of thick-disk and metal-weak thick-disk stars. As eccentricity increases, the influence of the disk-like stars decreases, and eventually, at high eccentricity, one recovers a metallicity distribution similar to the ‘canonical halo’; these stars are dominated by the contribution of the inner-halo population. In the right-hand column, only those stars with $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc are shown, which effectively eliminates any stars from the disk-like populations. The behaviour at low eccentricity is clearly very different, as one sees a bimodal distribution in the upper panel, transitioning to a distribution with peak $[Fe/H] \sim -1.5$ at high eccentricity, but with long tails extending to lower metallicity. At intermediate eccentricities, the distribution of $[Fe/H]$ exhibits characteristics of a mixture of populations with different metallicity distributions.

Figure 2.11 See next page for caption.

Figure 2.11 The nature of the derived orbits for our sample in different velocity regimes. The panels indicate metallicity as a function of the extrema of the orbits for the stars in our sample, as a function of cuts in V , from modestly prograde to highly retrograde. A blue dashed line at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$ is shown for reference in both columns. These diagrams illustrate the change in the nature of the orbits of the stars in the inner- and outer-halo populations over increasingly retrograde cuts in V . The left-hand column is the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ vs. r_{peri} (the distance of closest approach to the Galactic centre for a given orbit); the right-hand column is the corresponding distribution for r_{apo} (the farthest distance from the Galactic centre reached for a given orbit). The upper panels of the left-hand column illustrate the dominance of inner-halo stars, which penetrate to the region near the Galactic centre (owing to their primarily high-eccentricity orbits). In this column, as one progresses to more retrograde orbits, the fraction of stars that penetrate to the Galactic centre decreases precipitously, as does the numbers of stars with metallicity near $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.5$. With only handful of exceptions, the most highly retrograde stars (which are dominated by the outer-halo population) exhibit $r_{\text{peri}} > 6$ kpc. The upper panels of the right-hand column show that the large fraction of inner-halo stars do not possess orbits that take them beyond roughly 15-20 kpc. This trend becomes more evident as the rotation velocity trends to ever more negative retrograde values. The mean metallicity of the stars on highly retrograde orbits that reach large r_{apo} is clearly lower than that of the inner halo stars that reach such large distances (again, presumably due to their highly eccentric orbits) seen in the upper panels.

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3

Structure and Kinematics of the Stellar Halos and Thick Disks of the Milky Way Based on Calibration Stars from SDSS DR7

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Abstract

The structure and kinematics of the recognized stellar components of the Milky Way are explored, based on well-determined atmospheric parameters and kinematic quantities for 32360 “calibration stars” from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) and its first extension, (SDSS-II), which included the sub-survey SEGUE: Sloan Extension for Galactic Understanding and Exploration. Full space motions for a sub-sample of 16920 stars, exploring a local volume within 4 kpc of the Sun, are used to derive velocity ellipsoids for the inner- and outer-halo components of the Galaxy, as well as for the canonical thick-disk and proposed metal-weak thick-disk populations. This new sample of calibration stars represents an increase of 60% relative to the numbers used in a previous analysis. We first examine the question of whether the data require the presence of at least a two-component halo in order to account for the rotational behavior of likely halo stars in the local volume, and whether more than two components are needed. We also address the question of whether the proposed metal-weak thick

disk is kinematically and chemically distinct from the canonical thick disk, and point out that the Galactocentric rotational velocity inferred for the metal-weak thick disk, as well as its mean metallicity, appear quite similar to the values derived previously for the Monoceros stream, suggesting a possible association between these structures. In addition, we consider the fractions of each component required to understand the nature of the observed kinematic behavior of the stellar populations of the Galaxy as a function of distance from the plane. Scale lengths and scale heights for the thick-disk and metal-weak thick-disk components are determined. Spatial density profiles for the inner- and outer-halo populations are inferred from a Jeans Theorem analysis. The full set of calibration stars (including those outside the local volume) is used to test for the expected changes in the observed stellar metallicity distribution function with distance above the Galactic plane *in-situ*, due to the changing contributions from the underlying stellar populations. The above issues are considered, in concert with theoretical and observational constraints from other Milky-Way-like galaxies, in light of modern cold dark matter galaxy formation models.

3.1 Introduction

The Milky Way is a unique laboratory, as it is the one large galaxy where it is possible to analyze the full space motions and chemical compositions of its stellar populations based on individual stars, and to use this information to disentangle its structural properties in great detail. Knowledge of the full six-dimensional location and velocity phase space and the chemical properties of stellar populations in the Galaxy provides invaluable information, not only on its recognized structures (and sub-structures, such as tidal streams), but by extension, on the nature of its formation and evolution. These concepts are well-understood, and have been widely used in previous studies, from the seminal work of Eggen, Lynden-Bell, & Sandage (1962) and Searle & Zinn (1978), to more recent research based on much larger samples of tracer objects (e.g., globular clusters: Zinn 1993; field stars: Hartwick 1987; Sandage & Fouts 1987; Sommer-Larsen & Zhen 1990; Allen, Schuster, & Poveda 1991; Ryan & Norris 1991; Kinman et al. 1994; Norris 1994; Carney et al. 1996; Chiba & Beers 2000; Ivezić et al. 2008; Xue et al. 2008; Morrison et al. 2009), all working toward drawing a much more detailed picture of our host galaxy.

The primary recognized stellar populations in the solar neighborhood are the thin disk (sometimes separated into the old and young thin disks), the thick disk, and the halo; the properties of these components have been reasonably well-determined by numerous previous authors. However, some issues remain unresolved. Examples include the origin of the thick disk, and the lower metallicity limit of its member stars. While many authors argue that the thick disk is likely to have formed in response to ancient accretion events (e.g., Quinn & Goodman 1986, Freeman 1987; Abadi et al. 2003, and references therein), recent suggestions have been made that some properties of the thick disk could be understood as the result of the radial migration of stars within the disk itself (e.g., Schoenrich & Binney 2009). Furthermore, despite numerous efforts, the issue of whether or not the so-called metal-weak thick disk (MWTD; see Chiba & Beers 2000, and references therein) is a distinct structure from the canonical thick disk has yet to be settled. Details concerning the origin of the Galactic halo are of particular interest for understanding the formation and evolution of our Galaxy. Indeed, the halo contains most of the metal-poor stars of the Milky Way, objects that encode the nature of the first stars to form in the Universe, which can be used to constrain models of large galaxy formation and evolution in general.

The Galactic halo has long been considered a single component. However, evidence has accumulated over the past few decades that it may be more complex (Carney 1984; Hartwick 1987; Allen et al. 1991; Preston, Shectman, & Beers 1991; Majew-

ski 1992; Zinn 1993; Kinman et al. 1994; Norris 1994; Carney et al. 1996; Chiba & Beers 2000; Kinman et al. 2007; Lee, Gim, & Casetti-Dinescu 2007; Miceli et al. 2008). Recently, based on an analysis of a large sample of calibration stars from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) DR5 (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2007), Carollo et al. (2007) argued for the existence of *at least* a two-component halo. In their view the Galactic halo comprises two broadly overlapping structural components, an inner and an outer halo. These components exhibit different spatial density profiles, stellar orbits, and stellar metallicities. It was found that the inner-halo component dominates the population of halo stars found at distances up to 10-15 kpc from the Galactic center, while the outer-halo component dominates in the region beyond 15-20 kpc. The inner halo was shown to comprise a population of stars exhibiting a flattened spatial density distribution, with an inferred axial ratio on the order of ~ 0.6 . According to Carollo et al. (2007), inner-halo stars possess generally high orbital eccentricities, and exhibit a small (or zero) net prograde rotation around the center of the Galaxy. The metallicity distribution function (MDF) of the inner halo peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$, with tails extending to higher and lower metallicities. By comparison, the outer halo comprises stars that exhibit a more spherical spatial density distribution, with an axial ratio ~ 0.9 . Outer-halo stars possess a wide range of orbital eccentricities, exhibit a clear retrograde net rotation, and are drawn from an MDF that peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$, a factor of four lower than that of the inner-halo population.

In this paper we present further details on the structural and kinematic parameters for the inner and outer halos, as well as for the thick disk and MWTD, based on analysis of a large sample of calibration stars from SDSS DR7 (Abazajian et al. 2009). The DR7 sample includes stars obtained during the Sloan Extension for Galactic Understanding and Exploration (SEGUE; see Yanny et al. 2009), one of three sub-surveys obtained during the first extension of SDSS, known as SDSS-II.

This paper is outlined as follows. For the convenience of the reader the basic assumptions of our analytic approach and our main results are briefly summarized in Section 3.2. Section 3.3 describes the calibration stars from SDSS DR7, the methodology used to derive their stellar atmospheric parameter estimates (T_{eff} , $\log g$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$), and the criteria used to identify a local sample for our kinematic analysis. The techniques used to derive estimates of the kinematic and orbital parameters for stars in our sample are described in Section 3.4. This section also provides a comparison of the changes in the sampling of the spatial distribution and in the derived local kinematic properties for the calibration-star samples due to the expansion from DR5 to DR7. Section 3.5 considers the optimal variables for extracting knowledge of the primary stellar-population components revealed in the solar neighborhood, and addresses the

question of whether a dual-halo population is in fact required to understand the observed local kinematics of the halo. This section also describes the general properties of the maximum likelihood technique we employ, and its application for de-coupling the thick-disk, inner-, and outer-halo components. In this section we also evaluate the fractions of each component as a function of distance from the Galactic plane inferred from the present data, consider whether the MWTD might be an independent component from the thick disk, and derive the rotational lag and dispersion of the MWTD, as well as the range of metallicities covered by the MWTD. Derived velocity ellipsoids for the thick-disk, MWTD, and the halo components are reported in Section 3.6. In Section 3.7 the scale length and scale height of the thick disk are derived; the MWTD scale length is also constrained. Section 3.8 derives the inferred spatial density profiles for the two halo components, based on a Jeans Equation analysis. In Section 3.9 we consider the observed tilts of the velocity ellipsoids as a function of vertical distance and metallicity. The *in-situ* “as-observed” MDF, based on cuts in distance from the Galactic plane for the full sample of calibration stars, is described in Section 3.10. Section 3.11 presents a summary and discussion of our results.

3.2 Basic Assumptions and Brief Synopsis of Main Results

In order to carry out our analysis we make the central assumption that the Galaxy comprises a number of principal stellar components that are well-described by Gaussian kinematic distribution functions and individual metallicity distribution functions of (for now) unknown shape. We then model these components using Maximum Likelihood techniques, and compare these models with the observed properties of the SDSS DR7 calibration stars. We make the additional assumption that the number of stellar components should be taken as the minimum necessary to adequately describe the observations, and no additional components are added to the models if they do not result in statistically significant improvements in the ability of our models to fit the data.

With the above set of assumptions, we find: (a) A single-population halo is incompatible with the observed kinematics of local stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, while a dual (inner/outer) halo model is necessary to describe the observations. (b) The net rotation of the outer halo is slightly more retrograde than previously reported, $\langle V_\phi \rangle = -80 \pm 13 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (c) The net rotation of the inner halo is consistent with zero (at the two-sigma level), $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 7 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (d) There exists a gradient in the mean rotational velocity of likely inner-halo stars, $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -28 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$, for stars located within

2 kpc of the Galactic plane. (e) The dispersions in the rotational-velocity component for both the inner- and outer-halo populations increase with distance from the plane. This may apply to the MWTD as well. (f) The net rotation of the canonical thick-disk population, for stars close to the plane, is $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (g) The asymmetric drift of the thick disk varies with distance from the plane, as shown by previous work, $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -36 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$. (h) The thick-disk and MWTD systems only contribute to our sample within 5 kpc of the plane, the inner-halo population dominates between 5 and 10 kpc, and the outer-halo population dominates beyond 20 kpc. The inversion point in the dominance of the inner/outer halo is located in the distance range 15-20 kpc. (i) A MWTD, kinematically independent of the canonical thick disk (with net rotation $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 100\text{-}150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), is required to account for the rotational properties of low-metallicity stars close to the Galactic plane. (j) The metallicity range for stars that are likely members of the MWTD is $-1.8 \text{ [Fe/H]} - 0.8$, possibly up to $\text{[Fe/H]} \sim -0.7$. (k) The derived velocity ellipsoids, $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z})$, for the four components we have considered are as follows – Thick Disk = $(53 \pm 2, 51 \pm 1, 35 \pm 1) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, MWTD = $(59 \pm 3, 40 \pm 3, 44 \pm 3) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, Inner Halo = $(150 \pm 2, 95 \pm 2, 85 \pm 1) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, Outer Halo = $(159 \pm 4, 165 \pm 9, 116 \pm 3) \text{ km s}^{-1}$. (l) The kinematically derived scale length and scale height for the thick disk are $h_R = 2.20 \pm 0.35 \text{ kpc}$ and $h_Z = 0.51 \pm 0.04 \text{ kpc}$, respectively. The radial scale length for the MWTD is on the order of $h_R \sim 2 \text{ kpc}$, while the scale height is $1.36 \pm 0.13 \text{ kpc}$. (m) The slopes of the inferred power-law spatial-density profiles for the inner- and outer-halo populations are -3.17 ± 0.20 and -1.79 ± 0.29 , respectively. (n) The tilt angle, α , between the long axis of the Schwarzschild velocity ellipsoid and the Sun-center line is, in Galactocentric cylindrical coordinates, for stars of relatively high metallicity ($-0.8 < \text{[Fe/H]} < -0.6$), $\alpha = 7^\circ.1 \pm 1^\circ.5$ for $1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$, and $\alpha = 5^\circ.2 \pm 1^\circ.2$ for $2 < |Z| < 4 \text{ kpc}$, consistent with one another. For stars of intermediate metallicity ($-1.5 < \text{[Fe/H]} < -0.8$), the tilt is $\alpha = 10^\circ.3 \pm 0^\circ.4$ close to the plane, and $\alpha = 15^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.3$ farther from the plane, which differ significantly from one another. For stars of lower metallicity ($\text{[Fe/H]} < -1.5$), the tilt is $\alpha = 8^\circ.6 \pm 0^\circ.5$ close to the plane, and $\alpha = 13^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.4$ farther from the plane, again significantly different. (o) The “as-observed” metallicity distribution function of stars in our sample exhibits clear changes with distance from the Galactic plane, exhibiting the anticipated shift from dominance by thick-disk and MWTD populations, with peaks at $\text{[Fe/H]} = -0.6$ and -1.3 , respectively, to dominance by the inner-halo ($\text{[Fe/H]} = -1.6$) and outer-halo ($\text{[Fe/H]} = -2.2$) populations.

3.3 The SDSS Calibration-Star Sample

3.3.1 SDSS and SEGUE Data

SDSS-I was an imaging and spectroscopic survey that began routine operations in April 2000, and continued through June 2005. The SDSS and its extensions used a dedicated 2.5m telescope (Gunn et al. 2006) located at the Apache Point Observatory in New Mexico. The telescope is equipped with an imaging camera and a pair of spectrographs, each of which are capable of simultaneously collecting 320 medium-resolution ($R \sim 2000$) spectra over its seven square degree field of view, so that on the order of 600 individual target spectra and roughly 40 calibration-star and sky spectra are obtained on a given spectroscopic “plug-plate” (York et al. 2000).

The SEGUE sub-survey, carried out as part of SDSS-II, ran from July 2005 to July 2008. SEGUE obtained some 240000 medium-resolution spectra of stars in the Galaxy, selected to explore the nature of stellar populations from 0.5 kpc to 100 kpc (Yanny et al. 2009). In the present paper we make use of the spectroscopy and photometry obtained by SDSS/SEGUE for the small number (16) of calibration stars obtained for each spectroscopic plug-plate, chosen for two primary reasons. The first set of these objects, the spectrophotometric calibration stars, are stars that are selected to approximately remove the distortions of the observed flux of stars and galaxies arising from the wavelength response of the Astrophysical Research Consortium (ARC) 2.5m telescope and the SDSS spectrographs, as well as the distortions imposed on the observed spectra by the Earth’s atmosphere. The spectrophotometric calibration stars cover the apparent magnitude range $15.5 < g_0 < 17.0$, and satisfy the color ranges $0.6 < (u-g)_0 < 1.2$; $0.0 < (g-r)_0 < 0.6$.¹ The second set of stars, the telluric calibration stars, is used to calibrate and remove night-sky emission and absorption features from SDSS spectra. The telluric calibration stars cover the same color ranges as the spectrophotometric calibration stars, but at fainter apparent magnitudes, in the range $17.0 < g_0 < 18.5$.

The SEGUE Stellar Parameter Pipeline (SSPP) processes the wavelength- and flux-calibrated spectra generated by the standard SDSS spectroscopic reduction pipeline, obtains equivalent widths and/or line indices for about 80 atomic or molecular absorption lines, and estimates the effective temperature, T_{eff} , surface gravity, $\log g$, and metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, for a given star through the application of a number of approaches.

¹The subscript 0 in the magnitudes and colors indicates that they are corrected for the effects of interstellar absorption and reddening, following standard procedures, based on the dust map of Schlegel, Finkbeiner, & Davis (1998).

A given method is usually optimal over specific ranges of color and signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio. The SSPP employs 8 primary methods for the estimation of T_{eff} , 10 for the estimation of $\log g$, and 12 for the estimation of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. The final estimates of the atmospheric parameters are obtained by robust averages of the methods that are expected to perform well for the color and S/N of the spectrum obtained for each star. The use of multiple methods allows for empirical determinations of the internal errors for each parameter, based on the range of reported values from each method – typical internal errors for stars in the temperature range that applies to the calibration stars are $\sigma_{T_{\text{eff}}} \sim 100 \text{ K}$ to $\sim 125 \text{ K}$, $\sigma_{\log g} \sim 0.25 \text{ dex}$, and $\sigma_{[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]} \sim 0.20 \text{ dex}$. The external errors in these determinations are of similar size. See Lee et al. (2008a,b) and Allende Prieto et al. (2008) for more details.

Over the past several years, large-aperture telescopes have been used to obtain high-resolution spectroscopy for over 300 of the brighter ($14.0 < g_0 < 17.0$) SDSS stars (see Allende Prieto et al. 2008; W. Aoki et al., in preparation; D. Lai et al., in preparation). W. Aoki et al. (in preparation) and D. Lai et al. (in preparation) suggest that the current SSPP is actually somewhat conservative in the assignment of metallicities for stars of the lowest $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, in the sense that high-resolution estimates of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ are on the order of 0.2-0.3 dex lower than those reported by the SSPP. For the purpose of our present analysis, we have used these preliminary results to apply a quadratic correction to the SSPP-derived metallicities, of the form:

$$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C = -0.186 + 0.765 * [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A - 0.068 * [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A^2 \quad (3.1)$$

where $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A$ is the adopted metallicity from the SSPP, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C$ is the corrected metallicity. This polynomial has little effect on stars with metallicity greater than about $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.5$, but lowers the estimated metallicities for stars below this abundance by 0.1 to 0.2 dex.

Once estimates of the atmospheric parameters for each of the calibration stars are obtained, one can use the derived surface gravity of each star to infer whether it is a likely dwarf, main-sequence turnoff star, subgiant, or giant. Photometric estimates of the distance to each star (accurate to an estimated 10%-20%) are then obtained by comparison of its observed apparent magnitude (corrected for interstellar absorption) with its expected absolute magnitude based on calibrated open-cluster and globular-cluster sequences, using the techniques described by Beers et al. (2000). See the discussion by Ivezić et al. (2008) for a comparison between the Beers et al. (2000) distances with those obtained by use of cluster fiducials in the native SDSS *ugriz* system.

Radial velocities for stars in our sample are derived from matches to an external li-

brary of high-resolution spectral templates with accurately known velocities, degraded in resolution to match the SDSS spectra (see Yanny et al. 2009). The typical precision of the resulting radial velocities is on the order of $5\text{-}20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (depending on the S/N of the spectra), based on multiple repeat observations of individual objects with different plug-plates. Zero-point errors are negligible (after correction for a global offset of 7.3 km s^{-1} of unknown origin), and exhibit a dispersion of no more than 2 km s^{-1} , based on a comparison of the subset of stars in our sample with radial velocities obtained from the high-resolution spectra taken for testing and validation of the SSPP (Allende Prieto et al. 2008; Yanny et al 2009).

The full sample considered in the present paper consists of 32360 unique stars with acceptable derived atmospheric parameters. This represents a 60% increase with respect to the starting sample of 20236 calibration stars considered by Carollo et al. (2007). Although there is clearly a bias towards the identification of metal-poor stars arising from the color selections (in particular for the spectrophotometric calibration stars), it should be kept in mind that it is not possible to discriminate the lowest metallicity stars (e.g., those with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.5$) from those with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.0$, since the effect of declining metallicity on broadband stellar colors is minimal in this regime (see Ivezić et al. 2008). Hence, we expect that the distribution of metallicities for the calibration stars should reflect the true shape of the low-metallicity tail of the MDF for stars outside the disk populations. The same does not apply for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$; the observed distributions of metallicity mis-represents the true MDFs at these abundances. It is important to note that no selection on the kinematics, e.g., by making use of measured proper motions, is made in the choice of the calibration objects. This enables our kinematic studies to be carried out without the need to apply explicit corrections or modeling of any selection bias for the motions of the stars in the sample.

3.3.2 Selection of Local Sample of Stars

We begin with a total sample of 32360 unique calibration stars with available spectroscopy and average $S/N \geq 10/1$ over the spectral range 3800 \AA to 8000 \AA . We then consider all stars with effective temperatures in the range $4500 \text{ K} \leq T_{\text{eff}} \leq 7000 \text{ K}$, over which the SSPP is expected to provide the highest accuracy for the derived atmospheric parameters. This reduces the sample to 32329 stars. In addition to this restriction, stars in our primary sample for kinematic analysis must satisfy the following criteria:

- Stars must have derived distances $d < 4 \text{ kpc}$ from the Sun, in order to restrict the kinematic and orbital analyses to a local volume (where the assumptions going into their calculation are best satisfied). This selection also mitigates against

the increase in the errors in the derived transverse velocities, which scale with distance from the Sun (e.g., for a typical star in our sample, at $d = 1$ kpc, errors of 3.5 mas/yr in proper motions and 15% in distance result in errors in the derived transverse velocities of 22 km s^{-1} ; these rise to 37 km s^{-1} and 46 km s^{-1} for stars at $d = 2$ kpc and 4 kpc, respectively). This cut reduces the numbers of stars to 24824.

- Stars must have a measured radial velocity, accurate to better than 20 km s^{-1} (which eliminates only a handful of stars from consideration), as well as an “acceptable” proper motion available (which means that the star satisfies additional criteria designed to eliminate spurious reported motions; see Munn et al. 2004). Note that all proper motions have been corrected for the systematic error described by Munn et al. (2008).² After these cuts are applied, the total numbers of stars remaining is 23643.
- Stars must have a present Galactocentric distance, projected onto the plane, in the range $7 < R < 10$ kpc. This restriction also serves to improve the applicability of the simple models for the adopted form of the Galactic potential we apply during the kinematic analysis. This cut reduces the numbers of stars in our local sample to 16920.

Figure 3.1 compares the (projected) spatial distributions of the SDSS/SEGUE calibration stars used by Carollo et al. (2007), based on DR5 (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2007), with that of our present analysis, based on DR7 (Abazajian et al. 2009). In addition to the overall increase in the numbers of stars, one can also notice the impact of the SEGUE fields, which included substantial numbers of stars at lower Galactic latitudes. The upper panel of Figure 3.2 shows the “as-observed” MDF for the DR7 calibration stars in the full sample (black histogram), as well as for stars selected for the local sample, as described above. The MDFs of the two samples are clearly very similar, and comprise stars with metallicities that sample all of the primary stellar components of the Galaxy. The lower panel of Figure 3.2 shows the distribution of derived surface gravity, $\log g$, versus effective temperature, T_{eff} , obtained by the SSPP. Stars in the full sample are indicated by black dots, while those in the local sample are represented by red dots. Note that the full sample contains substantial numbers of objects

²We call attention to the extensive testing of the SDSS-recalibrated proper-motion errors carried out by Bond et al. (2009). By comparison with the derived (non-)motions of distant quasars, they demonstrated that systematic errors on proper motions are no more than 1 milli-arcsecond per year (with an rms of 0.6 milli-arcseconds per year).

with gravities consistent with main-sequence turnoff stars, subgiants, and giants, while the local sample primarily comprises main-sequence turnoff stars and dwarfs. We emphasize that both of the panels in Figure 3.2 are influenced by the selection functions used for targeting of the calibration stars, and should not be taken as representative of the distribution of either $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ or $\log g$ in the explored volume.

Figure 3.1 Spatial distribution in the Z-R plane of the 20236 SDSS DR5 (upper panel), and 32360 SDSS/SEGUE DR7 (lower panel) calibration stars. The black points represent the full sample, while the red points indicate the stars that satisfy our criteria for a local sample. The dashed blue line represents the Galactic plane, and the filled orange dot is the position of the Sun (at $Z = 0$ kpc; $R = 8.5$ kpc). In both panels, the wedge shape of the selection area is the result of the limits of the SDSS footprint in Galactic latitude. The overall increase in the numbers of calibration stars between DR5 and DR7 is clear, in particular for regions closer to the Galactic plane, due to the lower Galactic-latitude fields explored by SEGUE.

Figure 3.2 Upper panel: Metallicity Distribution Function (MDF), *as-observed*, for the full sample of calibration stars (black histogram), and for the stars satisfying our criteria for the local sample (red histogram). Lower panel: Distribution of surface gravity, $\log g$, versus effective temperature, T_{eff} , for the full sample (black dots) and local sample (red dots). Note that the full sample contains substantial numbers of main-sequence turnoff stars, subgiants, and giants, while the local sample primarily comprises main-sequence turnoff stars and dwarfs.

3.4 Derivation of Full Space Motions and Orbital Parameters

Proper motions, used in combination with distance estimates and radial velocities, provide the information required to calculate the full space motions (the components of which are referred to as U,V,W) of our program stars with respect to the Local Standard of Rest (LSR; defined as a frame in which the mean space motions of the stars in the solar neighborhood average to zero)³. Corrections for the motion of the Sun with respect to the LSR are applied during the course of the calculation of the full space motions; here we adopt the values (U,V,W) = (-9,12,7) km s⁻¹ (Mihalas & Binney 1981). For the purpose of analysis it is also convenient to obtain the rotational component of a star's motion about the Galactic center in a cylindrical frame; this is denoted as V_ϕ , and is calculated assuming that the LSR is on a circular orbit with a value of 220 km s⁻¹ (Kerr & Lynden-Bell 1986). It is worth noting that our assumed values of R (8.5 kpc) and the circular velocity of the LSR are both consistent with two recent independent determinations of these quantities by Ghez et al. (2008) and Koposov, Rix, & Hogg (2009).

The orbital parameters of the stars, such as the perigalactic distance (the closest approach of an orbit to the Galactic center), r_{peri} , and the apogalactic distance (the farthest extent of an orbit from the Galactic center), r_{apo} , of each stellar orbit, the orbital eccentricity, e , defined as $e = (r_{apo} - r_{peri}) / (r_{apo} + r_{peri})$, as well as Z_{max} (the maximum distance of a stellar orbit above or below the Galactic plane), are derived by adopting an analytic Stäckel-type gravitational potential (which consists of a flattened, oblate disk, and a nearly spherical massive dark-matter halo; see the description given by Chiba & Beers 2000, Appendix A) and integrating their orbital paths based on the starting point obtained from the observations.

We have considered the possible systematic uncertainty in Z_{max} when one adopts a different gravitational potential, such as the model originally constructed by Dejonghe & de Zeeuw (1988), and later elaborated upon by Batsleer & Dejonghe (1994) and Chiba & Beers (2001), which takes a Kuzmin-Kutuzov potential for both a highly flattened disk and a nearly spherical halo. Experiments with our data indicate that, with the adoption of this alternative potential, the systematic change in this orbital parameter is on the order of 10% for $Z_{max} < 50$ kpc. A larger systematic applies when $Z_{max} >$

³The velocity component U is taken to be positive in the direction toward the Galactic anticenter, the V component is positive in the direction of Galactic rotation, and the W component is positive toward the North Galactic Pole.

50 kpc, where this parameter is more sensitive to the potential. However, the range of Z_{max} explored in this paper is always below 50 kpc, even though a handful of stars have larger values. Errors on the derived orbital parameters due to the observational errors have been estimated through a Monte Carlo simulation (100 realizations for each star). Although the sizes of these errors depend on sample selection, for the Stäckel potential used in Chiba & Beers (2000), together with constraints $Z_{max} < 50$ kpc and $R_{apo} < 50$ kpc (apogalactic distance projected onto the Galactic plane), the estimated one-sigma errors are $\sigma_{r_{peri}} = 1.1$ kpc, $\sigma_{r_{apo}} = 2.2$ kpc, $\sigma_{ecc} = 0.12$, and $\sigma_{Z_{max}} = 1.3$ kpc. The errors in these parameters show little dependence on Z_{max} over the range we consider in this analysis.

Figure 3.3 shows the derived U,V,W velocity components, as a function of metallicity, for both the DR5 and DR7 calibration-star samples. A comparison of the eccentricity versus [Fe/H] diagrams from DR5 and DR7 is shown in Figure 3.4. As can be appreciated from inspection of these figures, the increased sample of stars in DR7, as well as refinements in the estimates of metallicities made recently in the SSPP, have better delineated stars in the three primary stellar populations represented in the local volume – the thin disk, the thick disk, and the halo. It should be kept in mind that the numbers of stars shown in Figures 3.3 and 3.4 *do not reflect the actual relative proportions* of these populations in our sample volume, due to the selection criteria used and the bright limit of $g \sim 14.5$ imposed by the SDSS imaging.

Figure 3.3 Distribution of the velocity components (U,V,W) versus $[Fe/H]$ for the SDSS DR5 (left-hand panels) and the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 (right-hand panels) calibration stars. In both sets of panels only the local sample has been considered, comprising totals of 10120 and 16920 stars, respectively. The red dashed line is the adopted LSR for stars in the solar neighborhood. Note how the primary components of the stellar populations represented in the local volume, the thin disk, the thick disk, and the halo, are more clearly discerned in the DR7 sample. This is primarily due to refinements in the stellar parameter estimates obtained by the SSPP.

Figure 3.5 shows the distribution of derived orbital eccentricities for stars covering different regions of metallicity, chosen to isolate the contributions of the various stellar components we describe in more detail below, for two different intervals on distance $|Z|$ from the Galactic plane. In the upper panels, for stars with $-1.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$, the dominance of the canonical thick disk is clear in both distance intervals. In the second row of panels, for stars in the metallicity region $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, the feature extending to $e \sim 0.5$ indicates the likely presence of a MWTD population close to the Galactic plane. Farther from the Galactic plane the observed distribution of eccentricity appears more consistent with inner-halo stars, with some residual contribution from the MWTD. The eccentricity distribution for the metal-poor halo stars with $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, shown in the third row of panels, is close to the linear distribution $f(e) \propto e$ for both intervals on distance from the plane. This form of $f(e)$ is expected for a well-mixed steady-state system of test particles for which the distribution function is a function of the energy only, moving in the potential of a strongly centrally concentrated density distribution (see Binney & Tremaine, 2008, p. 387). We see below, however, that the distribution function for the metal-poor halo stars cannot simply depend on energy only, because the three components of their velocity dispersion are significantly different. In the lower row of panels, for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, the distribution of orbital eccentricities appears strikingly different than in the third row of panels. As discussed below, we expect that this distribution reflects the contribution from an outer-halo population with a less prominent fraction of stars on highly eccentric orbits, superposed on the inner-halo population that dominates the third row of panels.

Figure 3.4 [Fe/H] versus orbital eccentricity for the SDSS DR5 (upper panel) and the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 (lower panel) calibration stars in the local volume. Note the far greater numbers of stars from DR7, as compared to DR5, in addition to the more densely populated disk-like regions for the DR7 data, due to the addition of the SEGUE fields.

Figure 3.5 Distribution of the derived orbital eccentricity for sub-samples of stars selected in different metallicity ranges, for two different intervals on vertical distance $|Z|$, close to ($1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc; left-hand column of panels) the Galactic plane, and farther from ($2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc; right-hand column of panels) the Galactic plane.

3.5 Extracting the Major Stellar-Population Components in the Solar Neighborhood

3.5.1 Basic Parameters

Carollo et al. (2007) explored how to combine the derived kinematic parameters and metallicity estimates for the calibration stars in DR5 to reveal the presence of the primary stellar populations of the Galactic halo. With the much larger sample of calibration stars available from SDSS/SEGUE DR7, we now refine our investigation in order to disentangle the main components in the solar neighborhood and extract their spatial and kinematic parameters. Although the Galactic disk system comprises both a thin disk and a thick disk (and likely MWTD), the thin disk is not well-represented in our present sample due to the color and apparent magnitude selection criteria used for the SDSS calibration stars. Thus, the main populations we expect to contribute to our sample of local stars are the thick disk (and possibly a MWTD), as well as the inner and outer halos.

Given the strong overlap in the spatial and metallicity distributions of the components we consider, it is necessary to define a suitable set of parameters to best identify the presence of each population. Based on our tests of alternatives, the best parameters for this purpose are the distance from the Galactic plane, the rotational velocity of a star in a cylindrical frame with respect to the Galactic center, and the stellar metallicity. As shown in Figure 3.1, the local sample within 4 kpc of the Sun well-covers the region where the thick-disk (and MWTD) components are expected to be prominently represented. Thus, for exploration of these components we employ $|Z|$, the present distance of a star above or below the Galactic plane. In contrast, for exploration of the halo components we use Z_{max} , which depends on the adopted gravitational potential, as an indicator of their vertical extension. The choice of Z_{max} for the Galactic halo is necessary because of the much larger spatial extent of its two primary components, relative to that of the thick-disk components. Below we consider possible correlations of Z_{max} with other kinematic or spatial parameters used in this analysis.

Velocity ellipsoids are evaluated in a Galactocentric cylindrical reference frame, (R, ϕ, Z) , where R is the distance of the star from the Galactic center, projected onto the Galactic plane. The angular coordinate ϕ is taken to be positive in the direction of Galactic rotation, and Z is the height above or below the Galactic plane. In this system, the mean velocities and their dispersions are denoted by $(\langle V_R \rangle, \sigma_{V_R})$, $(\langle V_\phi \rangle, \sigma_{V_\phi})$, and $(\langle V_Z \rangle, \sigma_{V_Z})$. It is also explicitly assumed, for the present analysis, that the

velocity ellipsoids of the disk and halo systems are aligned on the coordinate axes. We explicitly test this assumption in Section 3.9 below.

The first step is to understand the *global behavior* of the derived kinematic parameters as a function of metallicity and $|Z|$ or Z_{max} . Figure 3.6 shows the derived velocity distributions for V_R , V_ϕ , and V_Z for different metallicity ranges. As expected, the rotational velocity exhibits rather different behavior as the range in $[Fe/H]$ changes. In the two upper panels of this figure the thick disk is dominant ($V_\phi \sim 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), while in the lower panels, as metallicity decreases, the halo becomes more clearly present ($V_\phi \sim 0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). The long tail of the rotational velocity distribution towards retrograde velocities seen in the lower panels arises from stars that likely belong to the outer-halo population. In contrast to this behavior, the distributions of V_R and V_Z remain almost symmetric over all ranges of metallicity, and the mean velocities are always close to zero, as expected. Notice that the dispersions of V_R and V_Z increase as $[Fe/H]$ decreases, reflecting the dominance of the halo components at lower metallicity. This figure suggests that, among these parameters, V_ϕ most clearly distinguishes the influence of the different stellar populations in the Galaxy represented in our local sample.

Figure 3.6 Distribution of the derived velocity components in a cylindrical Galactocentric frame, (V_R, V_ϕ, V_Z) , for different ranges of $[Fe/H]$. The blue dashed line is a reference line at zero for each component.

It is important to check for possible correlations that might exist between Z_{max} and (V_R, V_ϕ, V_Z) before their use in the kinematic analysis of the inner- and outer-halo populations. Figure 3.7 shows the cylindrical velocity components, as a function of Z_{max} , for the stars in our local sample. The upper panel indicates a correlation between V_R and Z_{max} , in particular for extreme values of V_R . An even stronger correlation is seen in the lower panel of the figure, which represents the vertical velocity component, V_Z . These correlations arise because large values of V_R and V_Z correspond to large orbital energy in the meridional plane, (R,Z) , and thus also to large values of Z_{max} . By contrast, the rotational velocity V_ϕ (middle panel) does not exhibit a strong correlation with Z_{max} , other than that expected from the presence of the thick-disk population at high positive rotation velocity and the halo at lower rotational velocity. Note, in the middle panel, the clear excess of stars with retrograde motions for $Z_{max} > 15$ kpc, which we associate with the outer-halo component, as discussed below. We conclude that the Galactocentric rotational velocity, V_ϕ , and the vertical distance, Z_{max} (or $|Z|$), when combined with metallicity, can be used to obtain useful information on the different stellar populations present in the local volume.

Figure 3.7 The relation between Z_{max} and the cylindrical velocity components (V_R, V_ϕ, V_Z) for the calibration stars in the local sample. Note the strong correlation between Z_{max} and the radial velocity component shown in the upper panel, V_R , as well as with the vertical velocity component shown in the lower panel, V_Z . The middle panel exhibits no strong correlation between Z_{max} and the rotational velocity component, V_ϕ , other than that expected from the presence of the thick-disk and halo populations. The blue dashed line is a reference line at zero for each component. Note, in the middle panel, the clear excess of stars with retrograde motions for $Z_{max} > 15$ kpc, which we associate with the outer-halo component.

3.5.2 How Many Components in the Stellar Halo?

If the halo of the Galaxy is spatially and kinematically complex, as argued by Carollo et al. (2007) and other previous authors, a natural question that arises is just how many components must be invoked to accommodate the available data. Note that here we are considering the definition of a “component” to mean a *bona-fide* stellar population, in the traditional sense, which is to say that the member stars share a common set of locations, kinematics, compositions (MDFs), and possibly ages (or distributions of ages), indicative of a likely common astrophysical origin. This definition would not extend to include the presence of *individual* substructures, such as debris streams (e.g., Yanny et al. 2003; Belokurov et al. 2006; Grillmair 2006; Bell et al. 2008; Grillmair et al. 2008; Klement et al. 2009; Schlaufman et al. 2009), and other overdensities such as the Virgo Overdensity (An et al. 2009, and references therein). Rather, our analysis seeks to model the kinematics of the halo using a minimum number of components, which themselves may or may not comprise the superposition of numerous individual substructures. The distinction is irrelevant for our approach.

Our most powerful tool for distinguishing various halo components is consideration of the rotational behavior of likely halo stars. A sub-sample of the local calibration stars, satisfying rather strict limits on metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, and orbital distances above the plane, $Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc, should be dominated by the halo components, with little or no thick-disk or MWTD contamination. We now consider such a sample for addressing this issue.

The question of how many components may comprise a complex halo can be subtle, since in principle individual components should be free to take on wide ranges of mean rotational velocity and dispersion, and it may or may not be possible to reliably separate them if there exists too large an overlap in their kinematic behaviors. Simple subjective guesses for the likely input parameters needed to carry out mixture-model analyses are not suitable for obtaining statistically sound answers to the question of the need (or not) for multiple components. Fortunately, alternatives exist. Kauffman & Rousseeuw (1990) describe the use of a clustering algorithm “Partitioning Around Medoids” (PAM), and its large-N extension “Clustering LARge Applications” (CLARA). These algorithms seek clusters of objects that have a high degree of similarity, while maximizing the degree of dissimilarity between different clusters. The original data set is initially partitioned into clusters around k so-called “representative objects,” referred to as the medoids, then an iterative scheme is applied to locate the medoids that best achieve the similarity/dissimilarity goal. The algorithm employed by PAM/CLARA is similar to the well-known *k-means* clustering algorithm, but it

is more robust to outliers, and enjoys the computational advantage that it obtains a unique partitioning of the data without the need for explicit multiple starting points for the proposed clusters.

The quality of the resulting partitions selected by PAM/CLARA can be assessed by inspection of the dimensionless parameter $s(i)$, which takes on values in the range $-1 \leq s(i) \leq +1$. This parameter measures the similarity of a given datum i to its closest representative object, relative to its next nearest representative object. If $s(i)$ is close to $+1$, we can reasonably conclude that the datum is properly assigned. If not, and $s(i)$ takes on values closer to 0 or -1 , we can conclude that either it is not clear to which representative object the datum should be assigned ($s(i) \sim 0$) or that it has been misassigned ($s(i) \sim -1$). Once a successful partition of the data has been made, we can inspect the following summary values: (1) $\bar{s}(i)$, the average of $s(i)$ within a given cluster, and (2) $\bar{s}(k)$, the average of $s(i)$ for the entire data set. This last number provides some guidance on what value of k is most appropriate for a given data batch, i.e., the number of clusters is chosen such that $\bar{s}(k)$ is a maximum⁴.

Table 3.1 summarizes the results of the partitioning exercise (using CLARA) for different input numbers of clusters, $1 \leq k \leq 3$. Column (1) lists the numbers of clusters. Column (2) lists the numbers of stars assigned to each cluster. Column (3) lists the coordinate (V_ϕ) for the representative object nearest the center of each proposed cluster. The inter-quartile range (IQR; see definition in Table 3.1) in V_ϕ covered by the proposed cluster is listed in column (4). The summary statistics $\bar{s}(i)$ and $\bar{s}(k)$ are listed in columns (5) and (6), respectively. Note that the results are ordered in Table 3.1 from high to low numbers of the proposed objects in each cluster.

As seen in Table 3.1, the first (non-trivial) split suggested by CLARA ($k = 2$) results in essentially equally populated clusters with positive (60 km s^{-1}) and negative (-142 km s^{-1}) coordinates, albeit with rather different IQRs. Each of the two clusters has moderately high values of $\bar{s}(i)$, and the average over both clusters, $\bar{s}(k)$, indicates a significant split. As one progresses to the case $k = 3$, CLARA splits the negative coordinate cluster into two pieces (at coordinates -23 km s^{-1} and -175 km s^{-1}), and moves the positive cluster to higher velocity (135 km s^{-1}). Note that the significance for two of the individual splits drops to below $\bar{s}(i) = 0.60$, as does the average $\bar{s}(k)$. This provides an indication that there is likely to be no need for three or more components in order to fit a reasonable mixture model to these data.

⁴The partitioning experiment described here only considers individual velocity components that have larger dispersions than could be accounted for by expected errors in the derived rotation velocities.

Table 3.1. Cluster Analysis Results: Partitioning Around Medoids

k	Objects	Coordinate (km s ⁻¹)	IQR (km s ⁻¹)	$\bar{s}(i)$	$\bar{s}(k)$	$\langle V_\phi \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	σ_{V_ϕ} (km s ⁻¹)	Fraction	p-value
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
1	710	-31	178	-71	142	1.00	0.002
2	363	60	40	0.65	0.61	-18	99	0.51	0.350
	347	-142	142	0.57	...	-128	159	0.49	...
3	310	-23	74	0.66	0.53	-55	94	0.66	0.321
	230	-175	132	0.50	...	-277	104	0.17	...
	170	135	77	0.43	...	75	95	0.17	...

Note. — The interquartile range (IQR) is a measure of the scale (dispersion) of the data. In the case of a normal distribution the IQR is related to the dispersion by $\sigma = \text{IQR}/1.349$

The partitions suggested by CLARA can be used to guide choices of input parameters for mixture-modeling of the proposed clusters. The R statistical software package (<http://www.r-project.org/>), and in particular its associated package R-Mix (<http://www.math.mcmaster.ca/peter/mix/mix.html>), provide convenient tools for simple analyses of mixtures.

Here we take the coordinates of the proposed medoids as input starting points for $\langle V_\phi \rangle$, and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = \text{IQR}/1.349$ as estimates of the input starting points for the dispersions of the (assumed Gaussian) individual components. R-Mix quickly converges, and provides the final estimates of the means, dispersions, and fractions listed in columns (7)-(9) of Table 3.1, respectively. The final column of Table 3.1 lists the so-called p-value, which represents the probability of obtaining a value of reduced χ^2 for the fit as large (or larger) by chance. The results of the fits are shown in Figure 3.8. It is clear, even from casual inspection, that the case of a single cluster ($k = 1$) is a poor description of the data. This impression is confirmed from the p-value of the chi-square statistic for this fit (0.002), which strongly rejects the null hypothesis of a single cluster.

As can be seen, the $k = 2$ component fit appears much improved, and indeed the p-value cannot reject the null hypothesis that two components are sufficient to describe these data. The p-value for the $k = 3$ case is also unable to reject the null hypotheses, but we emphasize that the quality of the initial partitions from CLARA strongly suggest that $k = 2$ is an appropriate choice for the number of components. A likelihood ratio test, which compares the statistical improvement of the fit obtained from $k = 3$ components over that with $k = 2$ components, indicates only minimal improvement is obtained from the four additional degrees of freedom (the two additional means and dispersions, and the two additional mixture fractions). In other words, the value of the maximum likelihood is not increased sufficiently to justify the need for an additional component in the fit. The conclusion of this exercise is that, while larger numbers of halo components beyond two can be *accommodated* by the available kinematical information, they are not *required*, nor do they provide superior fits to the data.

Figure 3.8 R-Mix results for the low-metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$) sub-sample of local calibration stars at large distances from the plane, $Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc, using as input guesses the medoids and dispersions obtained with the clustering analysis (shown in Table 3.1). The top panel represents the fit for the case $k = 1$ (one component), while the second and third panels show the fit for two and three components, respectively. The blue lines in each panel denote the proposed mixture model for the distribution of observed rotational velocities, while the red lines are the individual Gaussian distributions included in the model. As discussed in the text, the one-component fit is strongly rejected, while both the two- and three-component fits provide adequate descriptions of the data.

3.5.3 The Maximum Likelihood Technique

For more flexibility in our further analyses of mixture models, and to specify the kinematic parameters of the various components in the local volume, it is convenient to implement a maximum likelihood approach. This has been carried out, making use of the routine AMOEBA (Press et al. 1992) for performing searches for the maximum in the likelihood function, as described below.

Maximum Likelihood (ML) analysis is a well-known general method for statistical estimation. The basic theory of this technique assumes that the data can be described by a probability density function, $f(X; \alpha)$, where X is a variable, and α represents the parameter (or vector of parameters) characterizing the known form of f . The aim of the method is then to estimate α . If X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n are the individual data, and assuming that they are independent and drawn from f , then the likelihood function can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 L(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n) &= f(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n | \alpha) \\
 &= f(X_1 | \alpha) f(X_2 | \alpha) \dots f(X_n | \alpha) \\
 (3.2) \qquad &= \prod_{1 \leq i \leq n} f(X_i | \alpha)
 \end{aligned}$$

In its classical form, this equation gives the likelihood of obtaining the data, given α (Wall & Jenkins 2003).

The basic parameters we consider in this analysis, V_ϕ and Z_{max} , are used to define a likelihood function such that all the main structural components in the solar neighborhood (with the exception of the thin disk, which contains very few stars in our sample) are included in α .

It has been argued that the thick-disk component may include stars with substantially lower abundance than its peak value (around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.6$). Several authors have claimed a low-metallicity tail for the thick disk (the MWTD) extending to stars as metal deficient as $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$, or even lower (Norris, Bessell, & Pickles 1985; Morrison, Flynn, & Freeman 1990; Beers & Sommer-Larson 1995; Layden 1995; Martin & Morrison 1998; Chiba, Yoshii, & Beers 1999; Katz et al. 1999; Chiba & Beers 2000; Beers et al. 2002). The question of the limiting abundance of the MWTD has been considered several times in the past (Rodgers & Roberts 1993; Layden 1995; Beers & Sommer-Larsen 1995; Ryan & Lambert 1995; Twarog & Anthony-Twarog 1996; Chiba & Beers 2000), and in more recent work as well (Reddy & Lambert 2008). In particular, Chiba & Beers (2000) claimed that the MWTD contributes about

30% of the metal-poor stars in the abundance range $-1.7 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.0$ in the solar neighborhood. Note that, in the majority of these efforts, the kinematics of the MWTD were assumed to be similar (or identical) to those of the canonical thick disk. The small samples of stars available previously for investigation of this question limited the available options.

Ivezić et al. (2008) adopted a different approach, modeling the observed photometric metallicities and rotational velocities of main-sequence turnoff stars from SDSS DR6 (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2008) as a function of distance from the Galactic plane, for a narrow cone at the North Galactic Pole. The marginal distributions of metallicity and rotation velocities for these data were fit *independent of one another* to non-Gaussian functions for the disk (and single Gaussians in metallicity and rotation velocity for the halo), from which an adequate description of the global behavior of the disk+halo was obtained. We remind the reader that in our approach we seek to model the observed properties of the stars in our local sample by assuming that stars are associated with identifiable individual stellar populations, with differing kinematics and metallicity distributions, that comprise the disk and halo populations.

In the present paper we explore the possibility that the thick-disk system may comprise two separate stellar populations, with independent kinematics, that we associate with the canonical thick-disk and MWTD components. The Galactic halo is assumed to be a two-component structure, comprising the inner and outer halos, as discussed by Carollo et al. (2007). Thus, the general expression for the likelihood function takes the form:

$$(3.3) \quad \log f = \sum_{i=1}^n \log [F_{td} \cdot f_{td}^i + F_{mwtd} \cdot f_{mwtd}^i + F_{in} \cdot f_{in}^i + F_{out} \cdot f_{out}^i]$$

where F_{td} , F_{mwtd} , F_{in} , and F_{out} are the stellar fractions of the thick disk, MWTD, inner halo, and outer halo, respectively. On the left side of Eqn. 3.3, the function f depends on the mean velocity, dispersion, and stellar fraction of each component. On the right side of the equation, the functions f^i denote the (Gaussian) velocity distributions adopted to represent each component.

Thus, the likelihood function has eleven⁵ output parameters that must be determined (the fractions, and the mean rotation velocities and dispersions of each component). However, the problem can be greatly simplified by working in different ranges of metallicity, combined with different values of Z_{max} (or $|Z|$), where one component is dominant with respect to the others, and then fitting the distribution of the rotational

⁵The fractions must sum to 1.

velocity in each range of metallicity separately. Adopting this approach, we first consider the extremes of the MDF for the local sample ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ for the metal-poor sub-sample, and $-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$ for the metal-rich sub-sample). The first range is completely dominated by the two overlapping halo components, the inner and outer halo; we expect that many of the stars in this sub-sample belong to the outer halo, which has a peak in its MDF at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \simeq -2.2$ (Carollo et al. 2007). The second range contains stars belonging primarily to the thick-disk population, whose MDF has a peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.6$. The ML analysis proceeds by specifying several input parameters *a-priori*, then holding them fixed during subsequent analysis (e.g., by derivation of the global behavior of V_ϕ at the extremes of the metallicity ranges). A similar approach was adopted by Chiba & Beers (2000) and other previous work.

In subsection 3.5.4 we first derive the trends of $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ and σ_{V_ϕ} for the low-metallicity sub-sample (the thick disk and MWTD are assumed to not be present in this region of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$) as a function of Z_{max} . This analysis fixes the values of the mean rotational velocity and dispersion for the outer-halo population by consideration of the extrema of these trends. Once these values are specified, ML fits are obtained for the mean rotation and dispersion of the inner-halo population.

In subsection 3.5.5 we examine the trends of $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ and σ_{V_ϕ} for the high-metallicity sub-sample, as a function of $|Z|$, to derive the mean rotation velocity and dispersion for the thick-disk population. We also derive the gradient in the rotation velocity for the thick disk as a function of $|Z|$. The ML analysis is then extended to include the full range of metallicity for the local sample, in order to derive the values of the stellar fractions (F_{id} , F_{in} , F_{out}) as a function of Z_{max} .

In subsection 3.5.6 we consider stars in the intermediate-metallicity sub-sample ($-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$), split into three distinct metallicity intervals, to assess the requirement for a MWTD as an independent component. We then employ a mixture-model analysis to test for the presence of a MWTD component in each of these intervals as a function of $|Z|$. Finally, we explore the metallicity range of the MWTD component.

3.5.4 Extracting the Inner/Outer Halo Components in the Low-Metallicity Range

3.5.4.1 Characteristic Properties of the Outer-Halo Component

Here we examine the properties of the mean Galactocentric rotational velocity, $\langle V_\phi \rangle$, and its dispersion, σ_{V_ϕ} , as a function of the vertical distance, Z_{max} , for stars in the local sample falling into the low-metallicity range ($[Fe/H] < -2.0$). At high Z_{max} this sample is expected to be dominated by halo stars with large retrograde motions, suggesting membership in the outer-halo population.

Figure 3.9 shows the result of this exercise. Here, the values of $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ and σ_{V_ϕ} are evaluated by passing a box of 100 stars, with an overlap of 70 stars per bin, through the data. The blue curves represent the sub-sample of stars in the range of metallicity $-1.5 < [Fe/H] < -1.2$, shown for comparison purposes, while the red curves indicate stars in the low-metallicity sub-sample. In the upper panel, for $Z_{max} < 5$ kpc, the rotational velocities of the intermediate-metallicity stars exhibit a strong gradient, declining from a value of ~ 100 km s⁻¹ down to an average velocity of ~ 0 km s⁻¹. This behavior is likely due to the overlap of two stellar populations, the MWTD and the inner halo, which dominates the sample starting from $Z_{max} \sim 5$ kpc. Above this value of Z_{max} the average rotational velocity is ~ 0 km s⁻¹, or slightly prograde, over the range $5 \text{ kpc} < Z_{max} < 15 \text{ kpc}$, then trends toward retrograde values as Z_{max} increases.

Figure 3.9 Mean Galactocentric rotational velocity (upper panel), and its dispersion (lower panel), as a function of Z_{\max} , for intermediate-metallicity stars ($-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.2$; blue curves) and low-metallicity stars ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$; red curves). The values of these quantities are obtained by passing a box of 100 stars, with an overlap of 70 stars per bin, through the data. The horizontal dotted line in the top panel indicates a zero (non-rotating) velocity. The values of the dispersion are not corrected for observational errors.

The low-metallicity sub-sample exhibits an abrupt change of $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ in the range of Z_{max} between 5 and 10 kpc, which indicates a transition between the inner- and outer-halo populations. The $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ for this sub-sample then slowly trends to a constant value $\langle V_\phi \rangle \sim -100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at large Z_{max} , after undergoing a few oscillations that are likely due to correlations between contiguous overlapping bins.

For comparison with previous work we have also considered the rotational behavior of the low-metallicity sub-sample, as a function of $|Z|$, up to $|Z| = 2 \text{ kpc}$. In this metallicity range we expect that most of the stars are associated with the inner-halo component, with little contamination from the MWTD (which we show below ceases contributing significant numbers of stars below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.8$) or from outer-halo stars due to the proximity to the disk plane. We confirm the existence of a gradient in the mean rotational velocity over this range of $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -28 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$, as also reported in Chiba & Beers (2000) (see discussion in subsection 3.11.1).

The lower panel of Figure 3.9 shows the dispersion of the Galactocentric rotational velocity, as a function of Z_{max} , for the two sub-samples. Note that the velocity dispersions discussed here still include the effects of observational errors, and are thus somewhat higher than their “true” values. Below we make use of the “as-observed” dispersions for the low-metallicity sub-sample for ML modeling of the observed distribution of V_ϕ .⁶

The velocity dispersion exhibits a mean value around 100 km s^{-1} for $Z_{max} < 5 \text{ kpc}$ for both sub-samples (slightly lower for intermediate-metallicity stars, and slightly higher for low-metallicity stars). At larger values of Z_{max} the dispersion increases for both sub-samples, with intermediate-metallicity stars trending to $\sigma_{V_\phi} \sim 125 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and low-metallicity stars trending to $\sigma_{V_\phi} \sim 190 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ for $Z_{max} > 20 \text{ kpc}$.

Figure 3.9 clearly indicates that above Z_{max} between 10 and 20 kpc, the low-metallicity sub-sample is dominated by a highly retrograde halo component with a large dispersion (outer halo), while the slightly prograde and lower dispersion component (inner halo) is dominant for $Z_{max} < 10 \text{ kpc}$. For the purpose of the ML analysis described in the following subsection the input values of the mean rotational velocity and dispersion for the outer-halo component are evaluated by choosing stars from the low-metallicity sub-sample with $Z_{max} > 15 \text{ kpc}$ (where contamination from the inner-halo population should be minimal). For the outer-halo component this analysis leads to a value for $\langle V_\phi \rangle = -80 \pm 13 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, slightly more retrograde than that obtained by

⁶Below we correct, as appropriate, derived velocity dispersions for the effects of measurement errors following the formalism of Jones & Walker (1988). In order to remove the effects of observational errors, the term $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i^2$, where ξ_i is the error on measurement, is subtracted from the observed dispersion.

Carollo et al. (2007) ($\sim -70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) from the DR5 sample of local calibration stars. For the dispersion we obtain $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 180 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (uncorrected for observational errors).

3.5.4.2 Maximum Likelihood Results

We adopt a likelihood function for V_ϕ for the low-metallicity sub-sample, based on a mixture of two Gaussian distributions representing the two halo components, with a normalization forcing their sum to unity ($F_{in} + F_{out} = 1$). The input parameters for the likelihood function are the values of $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ and σ_{V_ϕ} for the outer halo, as obtained in the previous section; the output parameters are the mean rotational velocity and its dispersion for the inner halo and the stellar fractions for the inner- and outer-halo components. The fit is then performed selecting different intervals of the vertical distance, Z_{max} .

As a first application, we have performed a fit for the low-metallicity sub-sample of stars, selected with $1 \text{ kpc} < Z_{max} < 10 \text{ kpc}$, and $Z_{max} > 10 \text{ kpc}$, respectively.⁷ While a contribution from a MWTD population may still be present, the lower limit of Z_{max} for the sub-sample close to the Galactic plane has been chosen to reduce its possible impact.

Figure 3.10 shows the result of this exercise. The histograms in each panel are the distribution of the observed V_ϕ in the two selected ranges of Z_{max} , while the green (inner halo) and red (outer halo) curves represent the results of the ML analysis for these two components; the blue curves are the mixture models obtained by their sum. Visual inspection suggests that the fits well-represent the observed distribution of the data for both cuts on Z_{max} . It is clear that the inner-halo component dominates the sub-sample of stars at $1 \text{ kpc} < Z_{max} < 10 \text{ kpc}$, while the net-retrograde, high-dispersion outer-halo population dominates for $Z_{max} > 10 \text{ kpc}$.

⁷It should be noted that this sample differs from that used in subsection 3.5.2 above, which was employed to assess the appropriate number of halo components.

Figure 3.10 Rotational properties for the low-metallicity sub-sample ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$) of stars in the local calibration-star sample, divided into stars with Z_{max} above or below 10 kpc from the Galactic plane. The histograms in the left-hand panels illustrate the observed distribution of V_{ϕ} , while the green (inner halo), and the red (outer halo) curves represent the results of the ML analysis. The blue curves are the proposed mixture model for the distribution of the rotational velocities for this sub-sample. The right-hand panels are the Double Root Residual (DRRs) for these fits (see text for description). The dot-dashed lines at ± 2 indicate an approximate 95% significance level.

Prior experience suggests that visual inspection of multiple-component fits are often insufficient for interpreting results of mixture-model analyses. Thus, we have also evaluated the so-called Double Root Residuals (DRRs) for these fits. The DRR plot is a variation of a hanging histogram, which is just a (non-normalized) difference plot between binned data and a proposed fitting function. One limitation of the hanging histogram is that it gives equal weight to residuals from bins near the extrema of a distribution (which are usually poorly populated) as to residuals near the middle of a distribution (which are usually well-populated, and hence subject to greater \sqrt{N}/N variations). A square-root transformation applied to the residuals provides a desirable variance stabilization. The DRR plot is a refinement to the canonical root-residual plot (Velleman & Hoaglin 1981), which avoids some difficulties with small data sets. The set of DRRs is obtained using:

$$(3.4) \quad DRR = \sqrt{2+4(N_{obs})} - \sqrt{1+4(N_{fit})} \quad \text{if } N_{obs} \geq 1$$

$$(3.5) \quad = 1 - \sqrt{1+4(N_{fit})} \quad \text{if } N_{obs} = 0$$

In the above, N_{obs} and N_{fit} are the number of observed and predicted stars in each bin, respectively.

There are several advantages of a DRR plot over a simple difference plot for illustrating the residuals. First, it graphically emphasizes *where* in a distribution lack of fit between data and model exists – the square-root transformation puts the residuals throughout the fit on an equal footing. Secondly, if the model is close to an adequate fit to the data, then the DRRs are roughly equivalent to normal deviates. Thus, a DRR with numerical value $> \pm 2$ is significant at the 95% (2σ) level, whereas DRRs less than this value indicate a reasonable agreement between data and model in a given bin. As can be appreciated from inspection of the right-hand panels in Figure 3.10, the DRRs for the inner/outer halo fits obtained from the ML analysis are acceptable for most bins, with the exception of bins near the high positive and high negative velocity regions for the $1 \text{ kpc} < Z_{max} < 10 \text{ kpc}$ cut. Indeed, the p-value of the reduced χ^2 for this cut strongly rejects the null hypothesis of a good fit ($p = 0.0003$). This suggests that complexity beyond the simple description of an inner-halo population we have adopted may remain to be explored.

By contrast, the DRRs for the $Z_{max} > 10 \text{ kpc}$ cut, and the p-value of the reduced χ^2 for the global fit ($p = 0.950$), both indicate that the proposed fit is acceptable. In this first application the utility of the DRRs becomes clear. Visual inspection of the fit shown in the upper-left panel of Figure 3.10 might have suggested that the proposed

mixture model was adequate (although the chi-square analysis rejected this hypothesis), while the DRRs clearly revealed the location in the distribution where the lack of fit was most obvious. In addition, the possible deviations from the proposed model fit in the lower-left panel of Figure 3.10 might have suggested lack of fit, but the DRRs indicated that the deviations are in fact not significant (as confirmed by the chi-square analysis). It is quite difficult for the eye to separate out the effects of root-N variations from real deviations for populations of different sizes. Indeed, it is the smaller size of the population for the fit in the lower-left panel, as well as the smaller individual bin populations, which account for the fact that the proposed model cannot be rejected, while it *is* rejected for the larger population shown in the upper-left panel.

To evaluate the mean rotational velocity, its dispersion, and the fractions of stars for the inner-halo components, a second set of Z_{max} cuts was examined. In this case we fit sub-samples of stars selected with different upper limits on Z_{max} (cumulative Z_{max}), and keeping the lower limit set at 1 kpc. The complete set of the derived inner-halo parameters and their 1σ errors are summarized in Table 3.2.

Estimates of the errors on the output parameters were obtained following a well-known procedure, based on the assumption that the maximum of the likelihood, L_{max} , is the best estimator for the parameters of the model, and that the logarithm of the likelihood ratio, $-2 \ln(\frac{L'}{L_{max}})$, is asymptotically distributed like the χ^2 distribution (e.g., Lupton 1993).

Table 3.2. Maximum Likelihood Results for the Low-Metallicity Sub-sample – Inner Halo Parameters

Z_{max}	$\langle V_{\phi, in} \rangle$	$\sigma_{V_{\phi, in}}$	F_{in}
(kpc)	(km s ⁻¹)	(km s ⁻¹)	
1–5	11 ± 4	113 ± 3	1.00 ± 0.01
1–10	7 ± 4	110 ± 3	0.93 ± 0.01
1–15	10 ± 4	106 ± 3	0.83 ± 0.02
1–20	13 ± 4	105 ± 4	0.78 ± 0.02
1–25	20 ± 4	100 ± 3	0.70 ± 0.02
1–30	23 ± 4	97 ± 3	0.66 ± 0.02

Note. — The input parameters for the outer halo have been fixed at $(\langle V_{\phi, out} \rangle, \sigma_{V_{\phi, out}}) = (-80, 180)$ km s⁻¹. The listed dispersions are not corrected for observational errors. The normalization $F_{in} + F_{out} = 1$ is assumed.

3.5.5 Extracting the Thick-Disk Component and the Fractions of Each Galactic Component

3.5.5.1 Characteristic Properties of the Thick-Disk Component

To extract information on the canonical thick-disk component we select a sub-sample of stars in the metallicity range $-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$, and derive its mean rotational velocity and dispersion as a function of vertical distance, $|Z|$, up to 4 kpc from the Galactic plane. It should be kept in mind that there may remain some contamination from MWTD stars even in this high-metallicity range, which might have an influence on the observed behavior.

Figure 3.11 shows the result of this exercise. As seen in the upper panel of this figure, for $|Z| < 1$ kpc, the mean rotational velocity is $\sim 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; as has been previously noted by several authors, it decreases at larger heights above the plane. A least-squares fit to the data yields $\Delta\langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta|Z| = -36 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$. Inspection of the lower panel of Figure 3.11 shows that, for $|Z| > 2$ kpc, σ_{V_ϕ} increases from the canonical value of around 40-50 km s^{-1} to on the order of 90 km s^{-1} . In the same panel we note the presence of some oscillations that are larger than the errors on the dispersion for each bin of $|Z|$. We suspect that this jagged structure of σ_{V_ϕ} could be due to the presence of substructures, which will be investigated in a future paper. The fiducial parameters we adopt for the thick disk are obtained by selecting the sample at $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, in the high-metallicity range mentioned above. This selection is intended to avoid contamination by thin-disk stars (including those with possibly mis-estimated metallicities).

We obtain a mean velocity and dispersion of $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 57 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (uncorrected for the observational errors, which are typically on the order of 5-6 km s^{-1} for large sub-samples, and 10-15 km s^{-1} for smaller sub-samples), respectively.

Figure 3.11 Mean rotational velocity (upper panel) and dispersion (lower panel), as a function of the vertical distance $|Z|$, for the high-metallicity sub-sample ($-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$) of stars in the local calibration-star sample. The values of these quantities are obtained by passing a box of 100 stars, with an overlap of 70 stars per bin, through the data. The values of the dispersions are not corrected for observational errors.

3.5.5.2 Maximum Likelihood Results

We now evaluate the stellar fractions of the thick-disk, inner-halo, and outer-halo components with the ML analysis, as a function of Z_{max} , including stars over the full metallicity range of our local sample. The analysis was performed by selecting sub-samples of stars located in *strips* of Z_{max} (differential Z_{max}). Recall that previously, for the low-metallicity sub-sample, cuts were selected for different values of the upper limit on Z_{max} (cumulative Z_{max}). The differential distribution is better able to respond to changes in the dominance of the overlapping structures, and thus is suitable for examination of the trend of the stellar fractions as a function of Z_{max} .

The mean rotational velocities and dispersions for each component are fixed to the values obtained above (dispersions uncorrected for the observational errors): $(\langle V_{\phi,td} \rangle, \sigma_{V_{\phi,td}}) = (182, 57) \text{ km s}^{-1}$; $(\langle V_{\phi,in} \rangle, \sigma_{V_{\phi,in}}) = (7, 110) \text{ km s}^{-1}$; $(\langle V_{\phi,out} \rangle, \sigma_{V_{\phi,out}}) = (-80, 180) \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Note that for the inner-halo parameters we have adopted the values listed in Table 3.2 for $1 < Z_{max} < 10 \text{ kpc}$. Values for these three components are taken as input parameters for the ML analysis, while the output parameters are the stellar fractions, F_{td} , F_{in} , and F_{out} , respectively. Note that it is not strictly necessary that we fix the input parameters of the various components; we do this in order to obtain robust estimates of their fractions, which would change if the inputs were allowed to vary.

The likelihood function comprises three components, $F_{td}f_{td}$, $F_{in}f_{in}$ and $F_{out}f_{out}$; as before, the f s are assumed to be Gaussian distributions representing the corresponding V_{ϕ} components. The likelihood function is normalized to $F_{td} + F_{in} + F_{out} = 1$. The results of the analysis are shown in Figure 3.12. It is clear from inspection of the left-hand panels of Figure 3.12 that, for $Z_{max} < 5 \text{ kpc}$, only two components contribute significantly – the thick disk and the inner halo. At $5 < Z_{max} < 10 \text{ kpc}$, only the inner-halo component contributes (the green line representing this component exactly overlays the blue mixture-model line). At $10 < Z_{max} < 15 \text{ kpc}$ the outer halo begins to contribute, although the inner halo is still dominant. At $15 < Z_{max} < 20 \text{ kpc}$, the inner halo and outer halo make comparable contributions. Finally, when $Z_{max} > 20 \text{ kpc}$, the outer-halo component is completely dominant, with very little contribution from the inner-halo component.

The right-hand panels of Figure 3.12 are the DRRs of the corresponding fits. The individual bin residuals for the subsets of the data above 15 kpc are consistent with adequate fits (as are the p-values of their reduced χ^2 determined for the global fits), but those for the cuts below 15 kpc exhibit significant deviations that may be of interest. We consider these in turn. We originally assumed that the extreme negative residual seen for $Z_{max} < 5 \text{ kpc}$ at highly prograde V_{ϕ} arose primarily from the absence of a

thin-disk component in our model. However, additional experiments were performed over the distance range $1 < Z_{max} < 5$ kpc, to explicitly avoid substantial thin-disk contamination; the lack of fit remained. We also considered a possible difference in the thick-disk fiducial parameters when evaluated using Z_{max} instead of $|Z|$. The estimated values obtained in the range $1 < Z_{max} < 2$ kpc are $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 190 \pm 2$ km s⁻¹ and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 46 \pm 1$ km s⁻¹ (not corrected for observational errors). When the ML analysis is performed with these thick-disk parameters, the lack of fit is slightly reduced, but the residuals in the velocity range $0 < V_\phi < 150$ km s⁻¹ increase. In this velocity range the lack of fit may indicate the presence of a MWTD component. To explore this possibility, a further experiment has been performed, adding a fourth component in the model to fit the sub-sample of stars in the upper panel of Figure 3.12, using the R-Mix modeling approach. We find that a four-component model provides a better fit (p-value = 0.11).⁸

With no restrictions on metallicity, there is considerable latitude allowed for the kinematic parameters derived for each component. This is, unfortunately, rather difficult to overcome on the basis of the simple mixture-model analysis we have employed. More detailed modeling, taking metallicity into account, is described below.

⁸With derived velocity dispersions $\sigma_{V_{\phi,I}} = 97 \pm 4$ km s⁻¹, $\sigma_{V_{\phi,II}} = 59 \pm 19$ km s⁻¹, $\sigma_{V_{\phi,III}} = 37 \pm 19$ km s⁻¹, and $\sigma_{V_{\phi,IV}} = 31 \pm 8$ km s⁻¹, and fractions for each component of $F_I = 0.26$, $F_{II} = 0.20$, $F_{III} = 0.30$ and $F_{IV} = 0.24$, respectively.

Figure 3.12 Rotational properties for the full metallicity range of stars in the local calibration-star sample. The histograms represent the observed distribution of V_{ϕ} , while the purple (thick disk), green (inner halo), and red (outer halo) curves represent the results of the ML analysis. The blue curves are the proposed mixture model for the distribution of the rotational velocities for this sample. Each panel corresponds to different cuts selected in intervals of Z_{\max} , as indicated. The right-hand panels are the Double Root Residuals (DRRs) for these fits (see text for description). The dot-dashed lines at ± 2 indicate an approximate 95% significance level.

This experiment shows that, close to the Galactic plane, the structure of the Galaxy is complex, and a fourth component is required to obtain a better fit. However, for the purpose of obtaining the stellar fractions of the inner- and outer-halo components as a function of the vertical distance Z_{max} , which is our primary objective in this section, we have chosen to employ the simpler three-component model, even though the fit is not optimal over all distance cuts. Issues related to the MWTD are discussed in the following sections.

Figure 3.13 shows the derived fractions of the three components in our basic model, the canonical thick disk, the inner halo, and the outer halo, as a function of Z_{max} , as derived from the ML analysis. The thick disk is denoted by a black dot, and is only present, as expected, in the first bin of vertical distance ($0 < Z_{max} < 5$ kpc). In this range the fraction of the thick-disk and inner-halo (green dots) components are roughly equal. Above $Z_{max} = 5$ kpc, only the inner-halo and outer-halo (red dots) components are present. The inner-halo stellar fraction decreases with increasing Z_{max} , while the outer-halo stellar fraction increases. The *inversion point* in the dominance of the inner/outer halo occurs in the range of Z_{max} between 15 and 20 kpc.

Table 3.3 reports the values of the stellar fractions for the three components, and their errors, evaluated as before.

Figure 3.13 Derived stellar fractions, as a function of Z_{max} , for the thick disk (black dots), inner-halo (green dots), and outer-halo (red dots) components. These fractions are evaluated with the ML analysis applied to the full metallicity sample, with the input kinematic parameters for each component held fixed.

Table 3.3. Stellar Fractions for the Thick Disk, Inner Halo, and Outer Halo

Z_{max} (kpc)	F_{td}	F_{in}	F_{out}
< 5	0.55 ± 0.03	0.45 ± 0.02	0.00 ± 0.02
5–10	0.00 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.02	0.00 ± 0.02
10–15	0.00 ± 0.04	0.80 ± 0.03	0.20 ± 0.02
15–20	0.00 ± 0.05	0.55 ± 0.04	0.45 ± 0.03
> 20	0.00 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.02

Note. — The input parameters for all three components have been fixed at the following values: $(\langle V_{\phi,td} \rangle, \sigma_{V_{\phi,td}}) = (182, 57)$ km s⁻¹; $(\langle V_{\phi,in} \rangle, \sigma_{V_{\phi,in}}) = (7, 110)$ km s⁻¹; $(\langle V_{\phi,out} \rangle, \sigma_{V_{\phi,out}}) = (-80, 180)$ km s⁻¹, respectively. The normalization $F_{td} + F_{in} + F_{out} = 1$ is assumed.

3.5.6 How Many Components in the Stellar Disk ?

We now consider the nature of the disk populations, and in particular explore the question of whether an independent MWTD must be present in order to account for the rotational properties of the stars in our local sample close to the Galactic plane. The approach used here is similar to that employed for modeling of the Galactic halo components. We seek to model the kinematics of the thick-disk system using a minimum number of components, assuming as before that the presence (or not) of individual substructures in each component is not relevant for our approach. We also assume that Schwarzschild velocity ellipsoids apply, and that the ellipsoids are aligned to the cylindrical coordinate system we employ.

In an initial set of experiments, we used the ML method to explore stars in an intermediate-metallicity range ($-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$) over different intervals in vertical distance from the plane, $|Z|$, but the results were inconclusive. The overlaps in the rotational behavior of the various components present over such a wide metallicity range made it difficult to isolate the kinematic properties of the individual components. Instead, we hope to simplify the problem by dividing our local sample of stars into three primary metallicity regions, which are intended to include as few populations as possible. These regions are (i) $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, (ii) $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, and (iii) $-1.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$. For the purpose of this discussion, we consider the contribution from a given component to be significant if its fraction, as assigned by the mixture-modeling analysis, is $> 10\%$.

We proceed by carrying out objective initial partitions for each metallicity region in two sets of intervals on distance from the plane, $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, and $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc. The lower limit of the first interval is set to 1 kpc to avoid contamination from stars of the thin-disk population, which, although they might not be expected to be present at metallicities $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$, may have had their metallicities slightly misestimated by the current SSPP, and entered the sample unintentionally. As previously, we used CLARA to obtain splits of the V_ϕ parameter for cases of $k = 1$, $k = 2$, and $k = 3$ clusters. The initial estimates for $\langle V_\phi \rangle$, and its dispersion, σ_{V_ϕ} , were then used as inputs for the R-Mix routine, which produced final estimates of the best-fit mixture models for each metallicity region and distance interval. Note that for this set of experiments all parameters are allowed to be “free”; we do not hold any of their properties fixed during the modeling procedure.

The results of the above experiment are listed in Table 3.4 and shown in Figures 3.14 and 3.15. Table 3.4 is divided into two sections corresponding to the intervals on vertical distance; within each section the results for the one-, two-, and three-cluster

splits are considered separately. Column (1) of this table lists the metallicity region while column (2) lists the numbers of stars in the cut. Columns (3)-(5) list the resulting $\langle V_\phi \rangle$, its dispersion, σ_{V_ϕ} , and the fractions obtained from the R-Mix analysis for component I, respectively. Columns (6)-(8) list the same quantities, where applicable, for component II. Columns (9)-(11) list the same quantities, where applicable, for component III. The final column lists the p-value for the chi-square of the residuals to the listed fit.

Table 3.4. R-Mix Results for Multiple-Component Fits to the Local Sample

[Fe/H]	N_{Stars}	$\langle V_{\phi,I} \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\sigma_{V_{\phi,I}}$ (km s ⁻¹)	F_I	$\langle V_{\phi,II} \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\sigma_{V_{\phi,II}}$ (km s ⁻¹)	F_{II}	$\langle V_{\phi,III} \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\sigma_{V_{\phi,III}}$ (km s ⁻¹)	F_{III}	p-value
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
Close to the Galactic Plane ($1 < Z < 2$ kpc)											
<i>Single Component</i>											
-2.0 to -1.5	1851	-10	103	1.00	< 0.001
-1.5 to -1.0	2277	46	104	1.00	< 0.001
-1.0 to -0.6	2217	146	64	1.00	< 0.001
<i>Two Components</i>											
-2.0 to -1.5	1851	-104	136	0.13	4	89	0.86	< 0.01
-1.5 to -1.0	2277	1	96	0.67	135	44	0.33	< 0.001
-1.0 to -0.6	2217	64	77	0.19	165	42	0.81	< 0.001
<i>Three Components</i>											
-2.0 to -1.5	1851	-95	152	0.11	-24	83	0.71	93	48	0.19	0.272
-1.5 to -1.0	2277	-193	142	0.01	-3	88	0.63	135	45	0.36	0.175
-1.0 to -0.6	2217	54	79	0.15	146	40	0.58	198	25	0.27	0.137
Farther from the Galactic Plane ($2 < Z < 4$ kpc)											
<i>Single Component</i>											
-2.0 to -1.5	2115	-30	117	1.00	< 0.001
-1.5 to -1.0	2710	14	104	1.00	< 0.001
-1.0 to -0.6	1963	108	81	1.00	< 0.001
<i>Two Components</i>											
-2.0 to -1.5	2115	-162	156	0.14	-9	93	0.86	0.037
-1.5 to -1.0	2710	-7	98	0.85	133	45	0.15	0.007
-1.0 to -0.6	1963	32	88	0.29	139	52	0.71	0.058
<i>Three Components</i>											
-2.0 to -1.5	2115	-311	200	0.02	-168	95	0.14	0	88	0.84	0.857
-1.5 to -1.0	2710	-121	134	0.03	-8	91	0.80	134	48	0.17	0.816
-1.0 to -0.6	1963	38	88	0.33	133	45	0.60	220	11	0.07	0.096

Note. — In the labels: I = Comp. I, II = Comp. II, and III = Comp. III

3.5.6.1 Close to the Galactic Plane ($1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc)

We first consider the behavior for the distance interval close to the Galactic plane.

The p-values for the one-cluster and two-cluster splits clearly indicate that there is no metallicity region over which acceptable mixture models exist. Acceptable fits are only obtained for the three-cluster splits, as indicated by the listed p-values. This is also reflected in the appearance of the components shown in Figure 3.14, and their associated DRRs. Note that in the case of metallicity region *iii* (the higher metallicity range shown in the lower panel of Figure 3.14), the DRRs do suggest some lack of fit in the region near 220 km s^{-1} , which might suggest contamination from thin-disk stars. However, recall that our distance interval was set to avoid such a contamination. We return to this point below.

Examination of the mean rotational velocities and dispersions for each of the metallicity regions for the three-cluster split is informative. Notice that for metallicity region *i* (the lowest metallicity considered), the three components are all considered significant (fractions $> 10\%$) contributors, and that their means and dispersions might be plausibly assigned to (I) the outer halo, (II) the inner halo, and (III) the MWTD. There is no component with the properties of the canonical thick disk present in this metallicity region, as expected. Inspection of the upper panel of Figure 3.14 is also revealing. The “flat-topped” (more properly, platykurtic) appearance of the distribution of V_ϕ seen here is a classic signature of a mixture of populations. Furthermore, the long tail in V_ϕ extending to large negative velocities requires an additional component in order to obtain an acceptable fit.

For metallicity region *ii* (intermediate-metallicity stars), there are only two significant contributors, components II and III. Examination of their means and dispersions suggest their identification with the inner-halo and MWTD components, respectively. The appearance of the middle panel of Figure 3.14 supports this interpretation as well. Note that the dominance of components II and III is so great that one might have expected that a two-cluster split would have been acceptable. However, some contamination from likely outer-halo stars at high negative velocities pushes the formal chi-square analysis into the region where the two-cluster hypothesis can be rejected. The derived means and dispersions of the dominant components in either the two-cluster or three-cluster splits are similar, in any case. The component we identify with the inner halo accounts for roughly 60% of the stars, while that identified with the MWTD accounts for roughly 40% of the stars in this metallicity region.

For metallicity region *iii* (the highest metallicity considered), all three components are significant contributors. Inspection of the means and dispersions suggests identification of the individual components with (I) the inner halo, (II) the MWTD, and (III) the canonical thick disk. It is of interest that the component we identify with the MWTD is the dominant contributor in this metallicity region, accounting for roughly 60% of the stars, while the component we identify with the inner halo only contributes 15%, the remaining 25% of the stars being accounted for by the canonical thick disk.

The possible lack of fit at high rotation velocities, revealed by the DRRs, is not likely to be simply the reduced number of stars at 1 kpc from the Galactic plane. As shown below, this component appears even more strongly present farther from the plane.

For all three metallicity regions we conclude that an independent MWTD component, with $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ in the range 100-150 km s⁻¹, and σ_{V_ϕ} in the range 40-50 km s⁻¹ (\sim 35-45 km s⁻¹, when corrected for observational errors), is required in order to account for the rotational behavior of the stars in our local sample located relatively close to the Galactic plane.

3.5.6.2 Additional Splits of the Nearby Sample on $|Z|$ and R

At the suggestion of the referee, we have carried out additional checks on the nature of the stellar populations close to the disk plane, and on the robustness of our results. We first split the local sample of stars with $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc into two pieces: subsample A corresponding to stars above the Galactic plane ($1 < Z < 2$ kpc), and subsample B corresponding to stars below the plane ($-2 < Z < -1$ kpc). The CLARA analysis with one-, two-, and three-cluster splits, for all three metallicity regions, was

Figure 3.14 R-Mix results for three sub-samples of local calibration stars covering the range of metallicity $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$ (upper panel), $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$ (middle panel), and $-1.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$ (lower panel), located close to the Galactic plane ($1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc). The input guesses are the medoids obtained with the CLARA clustering analysis. The histograms represent the observed distribution of V_ϕ , the blue lines in each panel denote the proposed mixture model for the distribution of observed rotational velocities, and the red lines are the individual Gaussian distributions included in the model. The right-hand panels are the Double Root Residuals (DRRs) for these fits (see text for description). The dot-dashed lines at ± 2 indicate an approximate 95% significance level. The apparent lack of fit for high velocity stars shown in the lower panel DRR plot is discussed in the text.

carried out within each sub-sample, followed by an R-mix mixture-model analysis using the starting points derived from CLARA. It is worth noting that, due to the much higher sampling frequency of SDSS for stars in the North Galactic Hemisphere, the total numbers of stars in each of these splits was typically 80% in sub-sample A, and 20% in sub-sample B.

The results of this exercise are as follows. For sub-sample A (the 5749 stars above the plane), in all metallicity regions, one- and two-cluster splits were strongly rejected (as before), while three-cluster splits produced acceptable fits. As found for the full-sample analysis, the intermediate-metallicity component in the three-cluster split provided evidence for only two significant contributors that we identify as the inner halo and the MWTD (a highly retrograde component is represented by a fractional contribution of 0.5%, compared with a fractional contribution of 1% in the full-sample analysis).

For sub-sample B (the 1669 stars below the plane), in all metallicity regions, a one-cluster split was strongly rejected. Two-cluster splits were rejected for metallicity regions *i* and *iii*, but an acceptable fit was found for the intermediate-metallicity stars of region *ii*. The derived parameters for this split are consistent with the association of an inner-halo component ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = -6 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 104 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and a MWTD component ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = 150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 45 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). Once again, as found for the full-sample analysis, the intermediate-metallicity region in the three-cluster split provided evidence for only two significant contributors, identified as the inner halo and MWTD (a highly retrograde component is represented by a fractional contribution of 0.8%). The three-cluster split for the higher-metallicity region, while acceptable, had only two significant contributors, associated with the inner halo and MWTD (a highly retrograde component contributed a 7% fraction). We conclude that, in spite of the rather large difference in the numbers of stars contained in the two sub-samples, individual analysis of these do not differ significantly from the analysis of the entire sample in this distance cut.

Similar to the above, we then split the local sample of stars with $1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$ into two pieces: sub-sample C corresponding to stars located in the inner solar cylinder ($7 < R < 8.5 \text{ kpc}$), and sub-sample D corresponding to stars located in the outer solar cylinder ($8.5 < R < 10.0 \text{ kpc}$). The CLARA analysis with one-, two-, and three-cluster split was carried out within each sub-sample, and for all metallicity regions, followed by an R-mix mixture-model analysis using the starting points derived from CLARA. In the case of the splits on R, similar numbers of stars were included in each sub-sample (C: 3287 stars; D: 4129 stars).

The results of this exercise are as follows. For sub-sample C, in all metallicity

regions, one-cluster splits were strongly rejected (as before). Two-cluster splits were rejected for metallicity regions *i* and *ii*, while an acceptable two-cluster split was obtained for the higher-metallicity stars (metallicity region *iii*). The derived parameters for this split are roughly consistent with association of an inner-halo component ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = 61 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 82 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and a MWTD component ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = 154 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 43 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). Three-cluster splits were found to be acceptable for metallicity regions *i* and *iii*, but were marginally rejected ($p = 0.04$) in the case of the intermediate-metallicity stars of region *ii*.

For sub-sample D, in all metallicity regions, 1-cluster splits were strongly rejected (as before). Two-cluster splits were rejected for metallicity regions *ii* and *iii*, while an acceptable 2-cluster split was obtained for the lower-metallicity stars in metallicity region *i*. The derived parameters for this split are consistent with the association with an outer-halo component ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = -97 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 166 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and an inner-halo component ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = -5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 87 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). Three-cluster splits were found to be acceptable in all three metallicity regions.

We conclude that the results obtained from these additional splits are fully consistent, within the expected variation induced by the different sub-sample sizes, with the previous results obtained of the full local samples in this distance interval.

3.5.6.3 Farther from the Galactic Plane ($2 < |Z| < 4 \text{ kpc}$)

In this distance interval we expect that the contribution from the outer-halo component will increase in metallicity region *i*, while in this same region the contribution of the MWTD should be minimal. For metallicity region *ii* we expect that the MWTD, although present, should be of less importance than the contribution from the inner-halo component. For metallicity region *iii* we might expect that, as in the case of the distance interval close to the Galactic plane, the MWTD should dominate over the inner-halo component. As described below, all of these expectations are indeed met.

Inspection of Table 3.4 indicates that, as before, the p -values for the one-cluster and, to a somewhat lesser extent, the two-cluster splits, indicate that there is no metallicity region over which acceptable mixture-model fits exist. The p -value for the two-cluster split for metallicity region *iii* is marginal ($p = 0.058$), indicating that a two-cluster split is almost an acceptable fit. If one were to accept this split as reasonable, the mean velocities and dispersions suggest identification of component I with the inner halo, and component II with the MWTD. Statistically acceptable fits are only obtained for the three-cluster splits, as indicated by the listed p -values. This is also reflected in the appearance of the components shown in Figure 3.15, and their associated DRRs

(with the exception of the lower panel for metallicity region *iii*, which suggests an even greater lack of fit for high rotation velocities than for the distance interval close to the plane).

We now examine the three-cluster splits in more detail.

For metallicity region *i* only components II and III are significant contributors. As can be seen in Table 3.4, the R-Mix procedure splits off a highly retrograde component, which may well be spurious, and in any case is only a minor (2%) contributor.

For metallicity region *ii* we identify component I with the outer halo, component II with the inner halo, and component III with the MWTD. Note, however, that component I again makes only a minor contribution, although its inclusion is apparently necessary to account for the asymmetric lower tail of the rotational velocity distribution.

For metallicity region *iii* we identify component I with the inner halo, and component II with the MWTD. Component III (which is clearly required, as seen from examination of the DRRs in the lower panel of Figure 3.15) makes only a minor (7%) contribution. This high-velocity feature is of interest, since it is stronger than the similar feature identified in the DRRs of this metallicity region in the distance interval closer to the plane. Further investigation of the nature of the stars in this region is clearly necessary, and is already underway. Stars with “thin-disk-like” metallicities and roughly solar (rather than thick-disk-like) $[\alpha\text{-element}/\text{Fe}]$ ratios located several kpc above the Galactic plane have been previously reported by Lee & Beers (2009), who speculated that such stars may have been originally formed in the thin disk, but were perturbed to large distances from the plane by past minor mergers. We defer a full discussion to a future paper.

Figure 3.15 The same as Figure 3.14, but for stars located farther from the Galactic plane ($2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc). The apparent lack of fit for high velocity stars shown in the lower panel DRR plot is discussed in the text.

We conclude that an independent MWTD component must exist in the region farther from the Galactic plane as well, in order to accommodate the observed rotational behavior of our local sample of stars. It is interesting to note how dominant the component we associate with the MWTD is (60%), relative to the component we identify with the inner halo (33%), for the metal-rich metallicity region. These roles quickly reverse in the intermediate-metallicity region, with the component associated with the inner halo accounting for 80% of the stars in this sample, and the component identified with the MWTD only 17%.

3.5.6.4 The Metallicity Range of the MWTD

Having established that a kinematically independent MWTD is indeed required in order to understand the rotational behavior of our local sample of stars, we now use a similar approach to the above to determine over what metallicity interval the MWTD is present. Ideally, we would like to have information on the shape of the MDF for this component, but our present data (due to the selection biases involved) is not suitable for such an analysis. We can, however, determine the upper and lower limits of its MDF. We accomplish this by considering metallicity regions *i* and *iii* (the lower- and higher-metallicity regions, respectively) for the distance interval close to the Galactic plane, where the MWTD component is more dominant and less overlapped with the inner-halo component than is the case for the interval farther from the plane.

For metallicity region *i* we repeat the $k = 2$ and $k = 3$ cluster-split experiments, lowering the upper limit on metallicity from $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, in steps of 0.1 dex, until a three-cluster split is no longer required, and a two-cluster split is adequate. That is, we seek the limiting metallicity where only the inner- and outer-halo components make significant ($> 10\%$) contributions. We find that this occurs for the limit $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$. Similarly, for metallicity region *iii*, we repeat the $k = 2$ and $k = 3$ cluster-split experiments, but this time raising the lower limit on metallicity from $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -1.0$, in steps of 0.1 dex, until a three-cluster split is no longer required, and a two-cluster split is adequate. A successful two-cluster split would then only require the presence of an inner-halo and a canonical thick-disk component. We find that a two-cluster split is adequate for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -0.8$, although there is weak evidence for the presence of the MWTD even for $-0.7 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$.

We conclude from this exercise that the MWTD is a significant contributor to the numbers of stars in the local volume over the metallicity range $-1.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.8$, and possibly up to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.7$.

3.6 Velocity Ellipsoids

We now derive estimates of the velocity ellipsoids for the thick disk, inner halo, and outer halo. A similar derivation has been attempted for the MWTD, as discussed at the end of this section. Note that all values of the velocity dispersions reported in this section are corrected for observational errors.

As already shown in Figure 3.6, the mean velocity in the (cylindrical coordinate) R and Z directions does not change with metallicity, remaining close to zero over all ranges of [Fe/H] considered. The behavior of the velocity dispersions is quite different, revealing a strong dependence on metallicity, as shown in Figure 3.16. In this figure the observed velocity dispersions for the V_R and V_Z components are plotted versus [Fe/H], with each bin representing an interval in metallicity of 0.1 dex. The observed trends are certainly related to the differing contributions of the various components in space and metallicity. In both panels the change in the behavior of the velocity dispersion versus metallicity (change in slope, and the increasing values) is particularly clear at $-1.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.5$, $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. The first metallicity interval is dominated by the thick-disk population, with a mean dispersion of $\sigma_{V_R} \sim 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_Z} \sim 40 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In the second metallicity range the sample is dominated by the inner-halo population, with some overlap from the MWTD. Finally, the most metal-deficient stars, which are dominated by members of the outer-halo population, exhibit much higher dispersions. The dependence (or not) of the shape of the halo velocity ellipsoid with metallicity was a matter of considerable discussion in past work (e.g., Norris 1994; Carney et al. 1996; Chiba & Beers 2000). It was understandably difficult to resolve, due to the small numbers of stars in these previous samples. It is now clear that both the radial (σ_{V_R}) and vertical (σ_{V_Z}) velocity dispersions increase at lower abundances. Similar results have been reported by Bond et al. (2009).

For the thick disk, using the same metallicity ranges ($-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$) and distance ranges ($1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$) as chosen above for determination of the V_ϕ component, we obtain $\langle V_R \rangle = 2.5 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\langle V_Z \rangle = 0.4 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\sigma_{V_R} = 53 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_Z} = 35 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, for the radial and vertical velocity components, respectively.

Figure 3.16 Velocity dispersions (corrected for observational errors) for the V_R (upper panel) and V_Z (lower panel) components, as a function of metallicity. The plot employs stars covering the full $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ of the local calibration-star sample. The bins represent a range of 0.1 dex in metallicity, and are non-overlapping.

To evaluate these quantities for the outer halo, we have explored a finer grid of metallicity for stars in the low-metallicity range ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$), as shown in Figure 3.17. In each panel, the points represent the values of the dispersions for a metallicity below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{max}}$, the maximum metallicity for stars in each sub-sample. As in Figure 3.16, the dispersions are corrected for the observational errors.

As shown in the upper panel of Figure 3.17, the dispersion of the V_R component is constant (or slightly increasing) in the range of metallicity $-2.4 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{max}} < -2.0$, reaching a value of $\sigma_{V_R} \sim 180 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at the lowest metallicity. Similar behavior can be noticed for the velocity dispersion in the vertical direction. A constant value of about $\sigma_{V_Z} \sim 120 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is obtained for $-2.4 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{max}} < -2.0$, falling slightly for the more metal-poor stars (albeit with large error bars). We adopt the mean velocities and dispersions for the outer halo corresponding to the metallicity upper limit $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{max}} = -2.2$ (i.e., $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.2$), where contamination from the inner halo should be minimal. These are $\langle V_R \rangle = -8.6 \pm 6.1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\langle V_Z \rangle = 1.9 \pm 4.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\sigma_{V_R} = 159 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_Z} = 116 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, for the radial and vertical components, respectively.

Figure 3.17 Velocity dispersions (corrected for observational errors) for the V_R (upper panel) and V_Z (lower panel) components, as a function of metallicity, for metal-poor stars in the local sample. Each bin represents a sub-sample of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{max}}$.

Determination of the velocity ellipsoid for the inner-halo population proved more challenging. A series of experiments in the range of metallicity $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, where contamination from the outer halo should be minimized, were carried out to obtain this information from a mixture-model analysis. However, the symmetry of the distribution for both the V_R and V_Z components precluded obtaining accurate estimates. Recall that, due to the existence of clear correlations between Z_{max} and other kinematic parameters, we cannot use Z_{max} in order to reduce the contamination of the inner halo by other components that are present in this metallicity interval (the outer halo and MWTD). When a two-component model is adopted, with the outer-halo parameters fixed, the R-Mix procedure provides estimates, for the radial component, of $\langle V_R \rangle = 3 \pm 17 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\sigma_{V_R} = 143 \pm 14 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (p-value ~ 0.07 ; i.e., marginally adequate). The same experiment for the vertical velocity component does not provide an adequate fit.

Frustrated by the mixture-model approach, we chose to obtain at least an estimated velocity ellipsoid for the inner halo by simply adopting the mean velocities and dispersions of the sub-sample of stars in this same metallicity range, with the knowledge that contamination from other components may still be present. This results in estimates of $\langle V_R \rangle = 3.0 \pm 2.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\langle V_Z \rangle = 3.4 \pm 1.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\sigma_{V_R} = 150 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_Z} = 85 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, for the means and dispersions of the radial and vertical velocity components, respectively. Note that these estimates agree, within the errors, with the $\langle V_R \rangle$ and σ_{V_R} estimated using the mixture-model analysis above.

Finally, we have attempted to estimate the remaining components of the velocity ellipsoid for the MWTD. Based on the results obtained in subsection 5.6.1, we have selected a sub-sample of stars with $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$ and distance interval $1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$, in which the dominant components are the inner halo and the MWTD (Table 3.4). When the R-Mix mixture-modeling analysis is employed with the stellar fractions of the two components fixed at the values reported in Table 3.4, a two-component model provides very good fits, with values $\langle V_R \rangle = -13 \pm 5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\langle V_Z \rangle = -14 \pm 5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\sigma_{V_R} = 64 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_Z} = 48 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. When corrected for the observational errors, the dispersions are $\sigma_{V_R} = 59 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_Z} = 44 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, respectively. One-component models are strongly rejected, with p-values < 0.001 . The two-component fit reveals a slight asymmetry in both of the velocity distributions. This asymmetry may be an indication that the orbits of stars in the MWTD component are non-circular and/or non-coplanar with those of stars in the thin disk. Figure 3.18 shows the fits obtained and the associated DRRs. Table 3.5 lists our final determinations of the velocity ellipsoids for the thick disk, MWTD, inner halo, and outer halo.

Table 3.5. Velocity Ellipsoids

Component	$\langle V_R \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\langle V_\phi \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\langle V_Z \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	σ_{V_R} (km s ⁻¹)	σ_{V_ϕ} (km s ⁻¹)	σ_{V_Z} (km s ⁻¹)
Thick Disk	3 ± 2	182 ± 2	0 ± 1	53 ± 2	51 ± 1	35 ± 1
MWTD	-13 ± 5	125 ± 4	-14 ± 5	59 ± 3	40 ± 3	44 ± 3
Inner Halo	3 ± 2	7 ± 4	3 ± 1	150 ± 2	95 ± 2	85 ± 1
Outer Halo	-9 ± 6	-80 ± 13	2 ± 4	159 ± 4	165 ± 9	116 ± 3

Note. — The reported values of V_ϕ and σ_{V_ϕ} for the MWTD are put in the center of the ranges estimated for this component reported in the text. The derived velocity dispersions of the velocity ellipsoids are corrected for the effects of observational errors, typically on the order of 5-6 km s⁻¹ for large sub-samples, and 10-15 km s⁻¹ for smaller sub-samples. Note that the errors listed in this table and throughout the text refer to random errors only, and do not take into account the existence of systematic errors, primarily related to uncertainties in the photometric distances, which are expected to be at least on the order of 10% (and in some cases as large as 15-20%).

It should be noted that, in addition to errors in our determination of the parameters of the velocity ellipsoids that arise from observational errors (affecting primarily the derived dispersions, which we attempt to correct for), there remain systematic errors that result from the propagation of errors in the distance estimates and proper-motion measurements. Monte Carlo experiments indicate that such errors are typically on the order of 5 km s⁻¹. These are not reported as separate components of the errors listed in Table 3.5.

Table 3.6. Velocity Ellipsoids: Tilt and Correlation

[Fe/H]	Tilt Angle	$C[V_R, V_Z]$
Close to the Galactic Plane ($1 < Z < 2$ kpc)		
-0.8 to -0.6	$7^\circ.1 \pm 1^\circ.5$	0.096 ± 0.020
-1.5 to -0.8	$10^\circ.3 \pm 0^\circ.4$	0.224 ± 0.009
< -1.5	$8^\circ.6 \pm 0^\circ.5$	0.151 ± 0.008
Farther from the Galactic Plane ($2 < Z < 4$ kpc)		
-0.8 to -0.6	$5^\circ.2 \pm 1^\circ.2$	0.106 ± 0.024
-1.5 to -0.8	$15^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.3$	0.367 ± 0.007
< -1.5	$13^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.4$	0.248 ± 0.008

An additional and much more difficult to quantify error comes from our use of the mixture-modeling approach itself. Finite mixture models, by definition, force the observed distribution of kinematic quantities to be described by the adopted number of components, and normalize the derived model to the sum of these components. If a component is *unrecognized*, and not included in the model, the recognized components are forced to take up its missing “signal”, and to adjust their derived parameters accordingly. For instance, if we were not to include the MWTD component, the parameters of the thick disk, inner halo, and outer halo would be altered in an attempt to accommodate the observed data. The same would apply, to an extent, if a superfluous component is included. These problems can be mitigated by statistical tests of the ability of the derived model to fit the observed distribution, but they cannot be entirely eliminated. This is particularly the case when one or more of the components are strongly overlapping in the kinematic quantities being modeled. The best defense against “mixture-model errors” of this sort is the examination of different samples of stars, ideally selected in different ways or over different ranges of distance, such that they sample the underlying components in ways that break possible degeneracies. In future analyses we plan to consider the kinematic properties of F-turnoff stars, G dwarfs, and subdwarf M stars from SDSS/SEGUE, which should provide tests of the necessity (or not) of the presence of our adopted components in the mixture-model analysis.

Figure 3.18 R-Mix results for the V_R (upper panel) and V_Z (lower panel) distributions. The selected range of metallicity is $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, and the stars are located close to the Galactic plane ($1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc). The histograms represent the observed distribution of V_R and V_Z in each panel, respectively. The blue lines in each panel denote the proposed mixture model, while the orange and green lines are the individual Gaussians included in the model, representing the MWTD and the inner halo, respectively. The right-hand panels are the Double Root Residuals (DRRs) for these fits (see text for description). The dot-dashed lines at ± 2 indicate an approximate 95% significance level.

3.7 On the Thick-Disk Scale Length and Scale Height

With the velocity-ellipsoid parameters for the canonical thick disk in hand, we can estimate its scale length and scale height by assuming that it is in equilibrium and well-mixed. Chiba & Beers (2000) estimated the scale length of the thick disk from its stellar kinematics, using their Eqn. 1, which assumes that the scale height of the thick disk is constant and that the ratio of σ_{V_R} to σ_{V_Z} is independent of radius. With their adopted values for the velocity dispersions and mean rotational velocity, Chiba & Beers derive a scale length of 4.5 kpc for the thick disk.

In this paper we do not need to make the above assumptions – we have a sufficient number of stars occupying a large enough region of space to measure the gradients in σ_{V_R} and σ_{V_Z} directly. We assume that the thick disk has an exponential density distribution in R and Z , with scale length h_R and scale height h_Z , respectively. The cross term, $\sigma_{V_{R,Z}}$, of the velocity dispersion is observed to be small for the thick disk. It takes a value of $\sigma_{V_{R,Z}} = 0.096 \pm 0.020$ at $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, and $-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$ (Section 9), so we can write the radial and Z -components of the Jeans Equation as

$$\frac{\partial \ln \sigma_{V_R}^2}{\partial R} - \frac{1}{h_R} + \frac{1}{R} \left\{ 1 - \frac{\sigma_{V_\phi}^2}{\sigma_{V_R}^2} + \frac{V_c^2 - \langle V_\phi \rangle^2}{\sigma_{V_R}^2} \right\} = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln \sigma_{V_Z}^2}{\partial Z} - \frac{1}{h_Z} + \frac{K_Z}{\sigma_{V_Z}^2} = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

where V_c and K_Z are the circular velocity and vertical acceleration. We measure the radial gradient of σ_{V_R} and the Z -gradient of σ_{V_Z} from our sample, and use the Kuijken & Gilmore (1991) estimate of $K_Z = 2\pi G \times 71 M_\odot \text{ pc}^{-2}$ at $|Z| = 1.1$ kpc. We adopt the following parameters for the velocity dispersion and mean motion of the canonical thick disk at the solar radius, and at a Z -height of 1.1 kpc: $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (53 \pm 2, 51 \pm 1, 35 \pm 1) \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

Over the interval $6 < R < 12$ kpc and $1 < |Z| < 3$ kpc, respectively, the variations in σ_{V_R} and σ_{V_Z} closely follow a linear behavior, with $\partial \sigma_{V_R} / \partial R = -5.8 \pm 1.3 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$ and $\partial \sigma_{V_Z} / \partial |Z| = 6.8 \pm 1.7 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$, respectively. With these parameters, the scale length for the thick disk is $h_R = 2.20 \pm 0.35$ kpc, and the scale height is $h_Z = 0.51 \pm 0.04$ kpc, where the errors represent the statistical uncertainties only.

The small value of h_R relative to the Chiba & Beers value comes about almost entirely because our mean motion for the thick disk ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) is significantly smaller than their value of 200 km s^{-1} . However, we note that several other authors also find a small value of h_R from independent arguments based on star counts, e.g., Reylé & Robin (2001).

Our value for the scale height of the thick disk is at the lower end of the range of previously reported estimates, so we must look critically at the input data from which h_Z was derived. The parameters which are used in estimating h_Z are K_Z , σ_{v_z} and its gradient, all evaluated at $|Z| = 1.1$ kpc. The value of K_Z at $|Z| = 1.1$ kpc comes from the Kuijken & Gilmore (1991) sample of K dwarfs, and is consistent with the known density of disk objects. It is also in excellent agreement with the K_Z value independently determined by Holmberg & Flynn (2000). For determining σ_{v_z} and its gradient, we chose stars from a narrow range of metallicity, $-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$. Although the values of σ_{v_z} and its gradient are well determined by our data, it is possible that our thick-disk sample at $|Z| = 1.1$ kpc is contaminated by thin-disk stars, which would reduce the apparent value of σ_{v_z} and lead to an underestimate of h_Z . Contamination by inner-halo stars could also lead to an incorrect estimate of $\partial\sigma_{v_z}/\partial|Z|$. However, the positive gradient of σ_{v_z} makes only a relatively minor contribution to the derived value of h_Z . For example, if the thick disk σ_{v_z} were in fact isothermal, the value of h_Z would increase from 0.51 to only 0.64 kpc.

We note that our kinematic estimate of the scale height of the thick disk is obtained at $|Z| = 1.1$ kpc, while the (usually larger, $h_Z \sim 1$ kpc) estimates come from star counts at $|Z| \sim 2$ to 4 kpc (eg Gilmore & Reid 1983). Although the thick disk is often represented as vertically exponential, and indeed appears to be exponential at larger $|Z|$, in fact it is unlikely to be strictly exponential. In the general version of the vertical Jeans Equation the $1/h_Z$ term in Eqn 7 is replaced by $\partial \ln \nu / \partial Z$, where $\nu(Z)$ is the vertical density distribution. If we adopt the form of $K_Z(Z)$ from Holmberg & Flynn (2000), and we assume that the thick disk is vertically isothermal with a velocity dispersion $\sigma_{v_z} = 35 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, then the Jeans Equation can be integrated numerically to derive $\nu(Z)$. Near the Galactic plane, $\nu(Z)$ changes slowly with $|Z|$ and becomes steeper as Z increases. At $|Z| = 1.1$ kpc, the ‘‘local scale height’’ $[-1/(\partial \ln \nu / \partial Z)]$ agrees almost exactly with our value of 0.64 kpc, as it must. On the other hand, one could define an effective scale height of the thick disk as the height above the Galactic plane at which $\nu(Z)$ has decreased by a factor e from its value at $Z = 0$. This height is 0.99 ± 0.04 kpc, but it is not directly comparable with the star-count scale heights at larger $|Z|$.

For the MWTD we have only the kinematic parameters given in Table 3.5, but these are sufficient to place some useful constraints on the radial structure of this component. As we have no information on the radial gradient of the velocity dispersion for this component, we assume that it follows the often-adopted relation $\sigma_{v_R}^2 \propto \exp(-R/h_\sigma)$, where h_σ is a length scale.

Then it follows from the radial component of the Jeans Equation that

$$\frac{1}{h_\sigma} + \frac{1}{h_R} = 1.04 \text{ kpc}^{-1} \quad (3.8)$$

If the two scale lengths are comparable, as they would be for a disk of uniform scale height and constant anisotropy, then the radial scale length of the MWTD is again short, ~ 2 kpc.

Regarding the scale height for the MWTD, we find at $|Z| = 1.1$ kpc (and adopting the velocity dispersion reported in Table 3.5, $\sigma_{V_z} = 44 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) a value of $h_z = 1.36 \pm 0.13$ kpc.

3.8 Density Profiles for the Stellar Halo Components

Assuming that the Galaxy is in dynamical steady state, the Jeans Equation for a spherically symmetric stellar system, in spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) , can be written as (Binney & Tremaine 1988):

$$\frac{d(\rho \langle V_r^2 \rangle)}{dr} + \frac{\rho}{r} [2 \langle V_r^2 \rangle - (\langle V_\theta^2 \rangle + \langle V_\phi^2 \rangle)] = -\rho \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \quad (3.9)$$

where $\langle V_i^2 \rangle$ ($i = r, \theta, \phi$) is related to the velocity dispersion σ_i^2 as:

$$\sigma_i^2 = \langle V_i^2 \rangle - \langle V_i \rangle^2. \quad (3.10)$$

Based on the well-supported assumption for both the inner and outer halos, $\langle V_r \rangle = 0$, and $\langle V_\theta \rangle = 0$, the above equation can be written as:

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d(\rho \sigma_{V_r}^2)}{dr} + \frac{2}{\rho} \sigma_{V_r}^2 \left[1 - \frac{\sigma_{V_\theta}^2 + \sigma_{V_\phi}^2}{2\sigma_{V_r}^2} - \frac{\langle V_\phi \rangle^2}{2\sigma_{V_r}^2} \right] = -\frac{d\Phi}{dr} \quad (3.11)$$

where σ_{V_r} , σ_{V_θ} , σ_{V_ϕ} , are the velocity dispersions in the directions of (r, θ, ϕ) , respectively (in the spherical system V_ϕ and V_θ are taken positive in the direction of Galactic rotation and in the direction away from the North Galactic Pole, respectively).

The anisotropy parameter, β , which describes the degree of anisotropy of the velocity distributions, is defined as $\beta = 1 - (\sigma_{V_t} / \sigma_{V_r})^2$, where σ_{V_r} and σ_{V_t} are the radial and tangential velocity dispersions, respectively. The latter is given by $\sigma_{V_t}^2 = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{V_\phi}^2 + \sigma_{V_\theta}^2)$. The values of the anisotropy parameter obtained with our dataset are $\beta_{in} = 0.6$ for the inner halo and $\beta_{out} = 0.2$ for the outer halo. The anisotropy parameters for the inner halo indicate that its velocity ellipsoid is radially elongated, while the outer halo exhibits a less radially-elongated shape for its velocity ellipsoid.

Assuming that the potential of the Galactic halo is approximately spherical and logarithmic, $\Phi(r) = V_c^2 \ln r$, which corresponds to a flat rotation curve of the Galaxy in the solar neighborhood, and assuming also $V_c(r) = V_c = 220 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, Eqn. 3.11 can be written as:

$$V_c^2 = -\sigma_{V_r}^2 \left(\frac{d \ln \rho}{d \ln r} + \frac{d \ln \sigma_{V_r}^2}{d \ln r} + 2\beta - \frac{\langle V_\phi \rangle^2}{\sigma_{V_r}^2} \right) \quad (3.12)$$

The density of stars in the Galactic halo components can be approximated by a power-law relation $\rho(r) \propto r^n$ (where n is negative, due to the finite extent of the Galaxy). Making this substitution, the previous equation becomes:

$$V_c^2 = -\sigma_{V_r}^2 \left(n + \frac{d \ln \sigma_{V_r}^2}{d \ln r} + 2\beta - \frac{\langle V_\phi \rangle^2}{\sigma_{V_r}^2} \right) \quad (3.13)$$

Note that the term $\langle V_\phi \rangle^2 / \sigma_{V_r}^2$ is negligible for the inner halo ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = 7 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), while it is *not negligible* for the outer halo ($\langle V_\phi \rangle = -80 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). The values obtained for this term are, for the inner halo, $\langle V_\phi \rangle^2 / \sigma_{V_r}^2 = 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$, and for the outer halo, $\langle V_\phi \rangle^2 / \sigma_{V_r}^2 = 0.25$.

In the solar neighborhood ($R = R$) we can use the velocity ellipsoids obtained in the cylindrical reference system (σ_{V_R} , σ_{V_ϕ} , σ_{V_Z}) to derive the parameter n from the previous equation for the two halo components. Adopting the values of the velocity ellipsoid reported in Table 3.5, we find the following power law for the two components:

$$\rho_{in} \sim r^{-3.17 \pm 0.20} \quad \rho_{out} \sim r^{-1.79 \pm 0.29}$$

The above estimate includes the term $d \ln(\sigma_{V_r}^2) / d \ln r$ in Eqn. 3.13, which takes into account the variation of σ_{V_r} as a function of the radius r . In the solar neighborhood it becomes $d \ln(\sigma_{V_r}^2) / d \ln r \sim d \ln(\sigma_{V_R}^2) / d \ln R$. This term has been evaluated by examining σ_{V_r} in 1 kpc intervals, in the range $6 < R < 12$ kpc, using the low-metallicity subsample ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2$). The minimum and maximum values of the dispersion in the above ranges are $\sigma_{V_R} = 156 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\sigma_{V_R} = 172 \pm 8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, respectively. By taking the logarithm and fitting the corresponding curve, we obtain $d \ln \sigma_{V_R}^2 / d \ln r = -0.26$.

Note that if the above term is neglected in Eqn. 3.13 we obtain:

$$\rho_{in} \sim r^{-3.43 \pm 0.20} \quad \rho_{out} \sim r^{-2.05 \pm 0.29}$$

Thus, this term has a considerable effect, and needs to be included. Regardless, our analysis points to an outer-halo population with a much shallower spatial density profile than that of the inner-halo population.

3.9 Evidence for Tilts in the Derived Velocity Ellipsoids

The orientation of the velocity ellipsoids is of interest for understanding the equilibrium and assembly of the various Galactic components, and has recently been studied by Siebert et al. (2008), Bienayme et al. (2009), and Smith, Evans, & An (2009), as well as by Bond et al. (2009). We have examined the (R, Z) kinematics of our local sample in order to estimate the tilts of the velocity ellipsoids as a function of the height above the Galactic plane and metallicity.

We note that it is not appropriate to use the maximum vertical height of the orbit, Z_{max} , as a parameter here, because selecting on Z_{max} is equivalent to a selection in the velocity components V_R and V_Z . This makes it difficult to separate the tilt for the inner and outer halos.

Figure 3.19 shows the velocity distribution in the (V_R, V_Z) plane as a function of the vertical distance, $|Z|$, and metallicity. Close to the Galactic plane (top panels), at $0 < |Z| < 1$ kpc, and at metallicity $-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$, the sub-sample contains mostly thick-disk stars, and the inclination of the velocity ellipsoid is small. At higher $|Z|$ values, the inclination slightly increases, possibly due to contamination from the MWTD and the metal-rich part of the inner halo. At intermediate metallicity (middle panels), $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.8$, the ellipsoid shows a strong inclination, increasing with $|Z|$. We note that this intermediate sample comprises two overlapping components, the MWTD and the inner halo, with contamination from the canonical thick disk and the outer halo. The thick disk and MWTD cannot be easily separated in the V_R and V_Z component, as already discussed in Section 6. The low-metallicity sample (bottom panel), $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, which contains mostly halo stars, again exhibits a strong inclination increasing with $|Z|$.

The tilt of the velocity ellipsoid in cylindrical coordinates can be described by the tilt angle and the correlation coefficient, given by:

$$\tan 2\alpha = \frac{2\sigma_{V_R Z}^2}{(\sigma_{V_R}^2 - \sigma_{V_Z}^2)} \quad (3.14)$$

$$C[V_R, V_Z] = \frac{\sigma_{V_R Z}^2}{(\sigma_{V_R}^2 \sigma_{V_Z}^2)^{1/2}} \quad (3.15)$$

where $\sigma_{V_R Z}$ is the covariance. The values obtained for the tilt angle and the correlation coefficient, in various ranges of the vertical distance and metallicity, are listed in Table 3.6. The errors on α and C are evaluated through a Monte Carlo simulation (10000 realizations for each star), using the velocity errors for individual stars and correcting

for the effect of the errors on the diagonal σ terms. We find that the tilt angle is statistically different from zero for all the selected samples, and the principal axes of the velocity ellipsoids point towards a location slightly above the Galactic center. For metal-rich stars close to the Galactic plane we obtain $\alpha = 7^\circ.1 \pm 1^\circ.5$, which is consistent with the inclination found by Siebert et al. 2008 ($7^\circ.3 \pm 1^\circ.8$) for a sample of stars at $|Z| < 1$ kpc. At intermediate metallicity and $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, the inclination is $\alpha = 10^\circ.3 \pm 0^\circ.4$; it increases to $15^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.3$ farther from the Galactic plane. These intermediate-metallicity samples are dominated by the MWTD and inner halo. Finally, at low metallicity, the sample comes mainly from the overlapping inner-/outer-halo populations, and the inclination of the velocity ellipsoid is $\alpha = 8^\circ.6 \pm 0^\circ.5$ and $13^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.4$ at $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, and $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc, respectively.

Figure 3.19 Observed tilt of the velocity ellipsoids in the (V_R, V_Z) plane for the metal-rich sub-sample with $-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$ (top panels), the intermediate-metallicity sub-sample with $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.8$ (middle panels), and the low-metallicity sub-sample with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$ (lower panels). The left column shows these sub-samples close the Galactic plane, while the right column shows these sub-samples selected at higher $|Z|$. In each panel, the black dots are the distribution of the V_R and V_Z velocities, the black dashed lines indicates the principal axes of the (cylindrical coordinate) velocity ellipsoids in the meridional plane, and the red-dashed lines denote the derived inclinations of the ellipsoids.

Having demonstrated that the velocity ellipsoid for the inner halo is pointing close to the Galactic center, we re-evaluated its velocity ellipsoid in spherical coordinates, in order to evaluate whether the inner halo is kinematically close to isotropic in (θ, ϕ) . If it were so, then the inner-halo kinematics would be consistent with a system for which the distribution function depends on energy and the *total* angular momentum, which would in turn be an interesting clue to its assembly. The sample was selected in the range of metallicity of $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.6$ and $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc, where the dominant component is the inner halo, albeit with contamination from the MWTD and the outer halo. A similar estimate for the outer halo is more uncertain, due to the difficulty in separating the two halo components, as mentioned above. However, we have attempted to select mostly outer-halo stars using the metallicity interval $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.4$ and $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc, being aware that the sample remains contaminated by the inner halo. For the inner halo, we find $(\sigma_{V_r}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_\theta}) = (160 \pm 3, 102 \pm 2, 83 \pm 2)$ km s⁻¹ and for the outer halo $(\sigma_{V_r}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_\theta}) = (178 \pm 9, 149 \pm 7, 127 \pm 6)$ km s⁻¹ respectively. We conclude that both halo components are significantly anisotropic in (θ, ϕ) .

3.10 The MDF of the Full Sample as a Function of Height Above the Galactic Plane

There is a sufficient number of stars in the DR7 calibration-star sample to construct “as-observed” MDFs for the entire sample (regardless of whether the star has an available proper motion, or is located within the cylinder we have defined above for the local sample of stars), in order to look for confirmation of the expected changes as a function of height above the Galactic plane. The number of stars employed is 30956.

We examine the MDFs for different intervals in $|Z|$, with cuts chosen to ensure there remain adequate numbers of stars in each interval.

Figure 3.20 shows the results of this exercise. Examination of the left-hand column of panels in this figure shows how the MDF changes from the upper panel, in which there are obvious contributions from the thick-disk, MWTD, and inner-halo components in the cuts close to plane, to the lower panel, with an MDF dominated primarily by inner-halo stars. In the right-hand column of panels, with distances from the plane greater than 5 kpc, the transition from inner-halo dominance to a much greater contribution from outer-halo stars is obvious. This demonstration is, by design, independent of any errors that might arise from derivation of the kinematic parameters, and provides confirmation of the difference in the chemical properties of the inner- and outer-halo

populations originally suggested by Carollo et al. (2007).

Although it might appear possible to attempt mixture-model analysis to obtain MDFs for each of the individual components, we recall that biases in the selection of the stars in the calibration-star sample would confound such an attempt. Other samples of SDSS stars, which are more suitable for such an analysis, are being studied for this purpose, and will be reported on in due course.

Figure 3.20 Observed metallicity distribution functions (MDFs) for the full sample of SDSS-SEGUE DR7 calibration stars as a function of vertical distance from the Galactic plane. The black histograms represent the MDFs obtained at different cuts of $|Z|$, while the red arrows denote the locations of the metallicity peaks of the MDF for the thick disk (~ -0.6), the MWTD (~ -1.3), the inner halo (~ -1.6), and the outer halo (~ -2.2), respectively.

3.11 Summary and Discussion

We have analyzed the SDSS/SEGUE sample of 32360 unique calibration stars from DR7, amplifying the previous analysis carried out by Carollo et al. (2007) on a smaller sample of similar stars from DR5. A Maximum Likelihood analysis of a local sub-sample of 16920 calibration stars has been developed in order to extract kinematic information for the major Galactic components (thick disk, inner halo, and outer halo), as well as for the elusive metal-weak thick disk (MWTD). We have measured velocity ellipsoids for the thick disk, the MWTD, the inner halo, and the outer halo, demonstrated the need for a MWTD component that is kinematically and chemically independent of the canonical thick disk (and put limits on the metallicity range of the MWTD MDF), obtained estimates of the scale length and scale height of the thick disk and MWTD, and derived the inferred spatial density profiles of the inner/outer halo components by use of the Jeans Equation. We have also presented evidence for tilts in the velocity ellipsoids for stars in our sample as a function of height above the plane, for several ranges in metallicity. Changes in the *in-situ* observed MDF for the full calibration-star sample, as a function of height above the Galactic plane, are consistent with those expected from kinematic analysis of the local sample. Our results are summarized and compared with previous related analyses below, followed by a discussion on their implication for the formation of the Milky Way in the context of other recent results.

3.11.1 Summary of Results and Comparison with Previous Work

We began by comparing the changes in the nature of the calibration-star sample that have occurred in going from the SDSS DR5 to the DR7 data releases. Aside from the 60% increase in the total sample size, the addition of numerous low-latitude observations from SEGUE, and recent improvements in the SSPP (in particular for the determination of metallicities for metal-rich stars) have enabled much clearer distinctions between the kinematic behavior of the various Galactic components we consider in our analysis.

3.11.1.1 Distribution of Orbital Eccentricity

The distribution of observed orbital eccentricity for our local sample of stars contains interesting information on the presence of various Galactic components as a function of height above the Galactic plane and over a number of cuts in metallicity. We found that, in the metallicity range $-1.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$, the canonical thick disk dominates close to the Galactic plane ($1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc), as well as at $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc. At

intermediate metallicity, $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, the distribution exhibits an interesting feature extending to $e \sim 0.5$, suggesting a likely MWTD population close to the Galactic plane. At larger distances the distribution appears more consistent with the inner-halo population. In the metallicity range $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$ the distribution assumes the form $f(e) \sim e$, which is associated entirely with the inner-halo population, and consistent with a well-mixed steady-state system of test particles for which the distribution function depends only on energy. In contrast to this behavior, we noted that the distribution of orbital eccentricity for the most metal-poor stars in our local sample ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$) deviates significantly from linearity. Such a distribution reflects the contribution from an outer-halo population with a smaller fraction of stars on high-eccentricity orbits.

3.11.1.2 Identification of Halo Components

We next explored which quantities can best be used to constrain the mixtures of components present in the local calibration-star sample, concluding that V_ϕ and Z_{max} are superior to available alternatives.⁹ The subtle, but important, question of how many components are required to account for the observed kinematics of halo stars in the local sample was then considered. On the basis of an objective clustering approach, applied to the low-metallicity sub-sample of local stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, we demonstrated that (a) a single-population halo is incompatible with the observed kinematics, that (b) a dual-component halo, comprising populations we associate with the inner and outer halo, is sufficient to accommodate the observed kinematics, and that (c) although additional components (of unspecified physical meaning) can be added, they are not required (and in any case, provide no statistically significant improvement in the kinematic fits). We concluded that a dual-halo model is preferred on the grounds of its simplicity. Previous claims for the existence of a complex (often, dual) halo have been made over the past few decades, but these were based on rather small samples of tracer stars or clusters, such that the statistical significance of the dual signature was difficult to assess (e.g., Norris 1994; Carney et al. 1996). We believe the existence of an inner/outer halo structure is now clearly confirmed.

⁹After the majority of our analysis was completed, we also investigated using the meridional velocity, defined as $V_M = (V_R^2 + V_Z^2)^{1/2}$, as a possible variable for separation of the inner- and outer-halo components. This experiment proved interesting (i.e., a retrograde V_ϕ was found for stars with high V_M). This variable is worthwhile to investigate further, since it does not require adoption of a gravitational potential, as is the case for Z_{max} .

3.11.1.3 Maximum Likelihood Analysis of Halo-Component Kinematics

We developed a flexible Maximum Likelihood (ML) approach for further analysis of the kinematics of Galactic components. We then used a low-metallicity sub-sample of local stars in order to obtain estimates of the mean rotational velocity and dispersion of the outer-halo population, obtaining values of $\langle V_\phi \rangle = -80 \pm 13 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, slightly more retrograde than that obtained by Carollo et al. (2007) ($\sim -70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) from the DR5 sample of local calibration stars. For the dispersion, we obtained $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 180 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ ($\sigma_{V_\phi} = 165 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ when corrected for observational errors), a substantially larger value than reported by previous authors who considered only a single-component halo. The ML approach was then used in order to estimate the rotation and dispersion of the inner-halo component, based on an examination of cuts on Z_{max} for the low-metallicity sub-sample. We obtained values for stars with $1 < Z_{max} < 10 \text{ kpc}$ (where the inner-halo component dominates) of $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 7 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, i.e., an essentially non-rotating inner halo, and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 110 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ ($\sigma_{V_\phi} = 95 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ when corrected for observational errors). These values do not change substantially when considering cuts on Z_{max} up to 30 kpc from the plane, although the derived fraction of inner-halo stars decreases with distance while the fraction of outer-halo stars increases with distance.

We note that while candidate outer-halo stars with large Z_{max} exhibit a large retrograde mean rotation *in the solar neighborhood*, these stars would have a smaller value of *in-situ* rotational velocity at greater Galactocentric distances. This is because an orbit with large Z_{max} tends to have large R_{apo} , and thus smaller $|V_\phi|$, at large Galactocentric distance, due the conservation of angular momentum. The azimuthal velocity at R_{apo} , $V_{\phi,apo}$ can be simply evaluated as $V_{\phi,apo} = V_\phi \cdot (R/R_{apo})$. Using the sub-sample with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2$ and $Z_{max} > 10 \text{ kpc}$, we obtain $\langle V_{\phi,apo} \rangle = -14 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as the most likely *in-situ* mean rotation of outer-halo stars, given that stars are most probably observed when they are near their apocentric distances. It is worth exploring this small amount of *in-situ* retrograde rotation in numerical simulations of galaxy formation and/or kinematic observations of extra-galactic halos, in order to compare with the present results for the Milky Way. We also note that the expected *in-situ* velocity dispersion of an outer-halo population also must decrease with distance, as can be verified by inspection of the Jeans Equation. Indeed, observations of distant samples of stars, which are expected to be dominated by members of the outer-halo population, have been shown by a number of authors to meet this expectation, at least for the radial-velocity component (e.g, Sommer-Larsen et al. 1997; Xue et al. 2008; Brown et al. 2009). It should be kept in mind that Sommer-Larsen et al. (1997) have also pointed out that the *nature* of the orbits of the more distant stars must change from lo-

cally radially anisotropic to tangentially anisotropic (with a transition point at around 20 kpc), in order to be consistent with a flat rotation curve. This latter point will prove challenging to verify observationally *in-situ* until high-quality proper motions for more distant stars can be obtained, e.g., with the Gaia mission.

In the analysis of Chiba & Beers (2000), which only considered a single halo component, a slightly more prograde inner halo was obtained (based on stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$), $\langle V_\phi \rangle \sim 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, along with a similar dispersion, $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 106 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The existence of a gradient in the mean rotational velocity for the inner-halo component, as claimed previously by Chiba & Beers (2000), is confirmed. We obtained a value of $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -28 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$, for stars located within 2 kpc of the Galactic plane. This gradient is substantially lower than the value reported by Chiba & Beers ($\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -52 \pm 6 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$). Note that the gradient reported by Chiba & Beers is based on a sample of stars primarily located within 1 kpc of the plane; beyond 1 kpc, their three bins are consistent with zero net rotation. Thus, the apparent difference in the gradient of the inner-halo population obtained with our present sample of local calibration stars may be related to the substantially larger number of stars included with $1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$, lowering the derived gradient. In any case, such a gradient may represent the signature of a dissipatively-formed flattened inner halo. Clearly, in many respects our inner-halo population is essentially kinematically identical to “the halo” population studied by Chiba & Beers (2000), and many others.

3.11.1.4 Maximum Likelihood Analysis of Thick-Disk-Component Kinematics

The mean rotational velocity and dispersion of the thick disk were then considered, based on inspection of a metal-rich ($-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$) sub-sample of stars close to the Galactic plane. We obtained values of $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 57 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ ($\sigma_{V_\phi} = 51 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ when corrected for observational errors) for stars in the range $1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$, where the thick disk is expected to dominate, and contamination from thin-disk stars should be negligible. The gradient in asymmetric drift of the thick-disk component as a function of height above the plane, noted by previous authors, is very clear in our data as well; we derived $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -36 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$, in excellent agreement with the rotational velocity gradients for disk stars obtained by Chiba & Beers (2000), Girard et al. (2006), Sheffield et al. (2007), and Ivezić et al. (2008). The dispersion of this population also increases with distance, although it is not clear how much this might be influenced by overlap with metal-rich stars from the inner-halo component. Several authors have argued that this gradient in the asymmetric drift of the thick disk is consistent with heating of an early disk by satellite merger(s)

(Quinn, Hernquist, & Fullagar 1993; Miros et al. 1995; Robin et al. 1996; Walker, Miros, & Hernquist 1996; Velázquez & White 1999; Aguerri, Balcells, & Peletier 2001; Chen et al. 2001; Hayashi & Chiba 2006).

3.11.1.5 Fractions of Galactic Components From the ML Analyses

The ML approach was then applied to the full range of metallicities in our sample of local calibration stars, in order to determine the fractional contribution of the three primary components in our model as a function of Z_{max} (fixing as inputs the values of mean rotational velocities and dispersions derived previously for each component). This exercise indicated that, within 5 kpc from the plane, the thick-disk and inner-halo components contribute roughly equally. Beyond 5 kpc the thick-disk component is absent, as expected. The inner-halo population dominates between 5 and 10 kpc. Beyond 10 kpc the outer halo increases in importance, is present in equal proportion to the inner halo between 15 and 20 kpc, and dominates beyond 20 kpc. The inversion point in the dominance of the inner/outer halo is located in the range $Z_{max} = 15\text{-}20$ kpc.

3.11.1.6 Tests for an Independent MWTD Component

We then used our extensive local dataset to examine the question of whether an independent MWTD component is required in order to account for the rotational properties of stars close to the Galactic plane. We selected sub-samples of stars in three metallicity regions, (i) $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, (ii) $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, and (iii) $-1.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$, and two intervals of distance from the plane, $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, and $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc. The clustering analysis approach was applied to each sub-sample, and used to demonstrate that, in the region closer to the Galactic plane, an independent MWTD component with $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 100\text{-}150$ km s⁻¹ and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 40\text{-}50$ km s⁻¹ (35-45, km s⁻¹, when corrected for the observational errors), is required in order to account for the rotational behavior of the stars in our local sample. Similarly, an independent MWTD component must also exist in the interval farther from the Galactic plane, in order to accommodate the observed rotational behavior of the local sample of stars in that region of $|Z|$. It is interesting to note that the contribution of the MWTD component dominates over that of the inner-halo component for stars in the most metal-rich metallicity interval considered, not only close to the Galactic plane, but in the more distant interval as well. A population of rapidly rotating stars was identified in the metal-rich sub-sample, in both the nearby and more distant interval, which is deserving of further study.

Although superposition of the inner-halo and thick-disk MDFs and selection biases in the sample of local calibration stars preclude a determination of the MDF for the

MWTD based on these data, we were able to demonstrate that the metallicity range covered by the MWTD is $-1.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.8$ ($\langle [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \rangle \sim -1.3$), and possibly up to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.7$.

The net rotational lag for the stars we identify with the MWTD ($\langle V_{lag} \rangle \sim 95 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) is quite different with respect to the canonical thick-disk lag ($\sim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$: Chiba & Beers 2000; 51 km s^{-1} : Soubiran, Bienayme, & Siebert 2003; $\sim 38 \text{ km s}^{-1}$: this paper). The results obtained with the mixture-modeling analysis suggest that, if the MWTD is considered an independent stellar component of the Galaxy, its most likely mean rotational velocity and dispersion are $\langle V_\phi \rangle \sim 100\text{-}150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ ($\langle V_{lag} \rangle \sim 70\text{-}120 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), and $\sigma_{V_\phi} \sim 40\text{-}50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ ($\sigma_{V_\phi} = 35\text{-}45 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ when corrected for observational errors). It may be of interest that the value for the MWTD lag obtained from our analysis is in good agreement with that derived for the putative population of satellite debris found by Gilmore, Wyse, & Norris (2002), who obtained a lag in the mean azimuthal streaming motion of $\sim 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ behind the Sun. Note that the reported Gilmore et al. dispersion, on the order of 70 km s^{-1} , is slightly higher than ours, but this might be readily explained by contamination from inner-halo stars. These authors argued that such parameters might well be associated with stellar debris from a past merger event.

Of even greater interest is the possible connection between the MWTD stellar component and the Monoceros stream. Indeed, as reported by Yanny et al. (2003), the systemic Galactocentric rotational velocity of the stream is $\sim 110 \pm 25 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, which is in very good agreement with the mean value of V_ϕ derived for the MWTD component ($\sim 125 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). In addition, the estimated mean value of the Monoceros stream metallicity is $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.3$ (Wilhelm et al. 2005), in agreement with the mean value of metallicity of the MWTD reported above.¹⁰ The similarity in rotational velocity and metallicity between the MWTD and the Monoceros stream requires further investigation, and will be carried out in the near future. Our analysis also indicated that the kinematic properties of the MWTD may change with height above the plane, as was already demonstrated for the thick-disk component, but superposition with inner-halo stars confounded a definitive determination. In any event, the preponderance of evidence suggests that the MWTD population may indeed be a kinematically and chemically distinct population from the canonical thick-disk population. We plan to address this issue in more detail in future investigations, through the use of stellar samples that are more suitable for analysis of the complexity of the thick-disk structure.

¹⁰Note, however, that the mean photometric metallicity estimate of the Monoceros stream reported by Ivezić et al. (2008) is somewhat higher, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.95$.

3.11.1.7 Velocity Ellipsoids

We next derived estimates of the velocity ellipsoids for the thick disk, inner halo, and outer halo; an approximate ellipsoid for the MWTD was also derived.

In the case of the thick-disk and outer-halo components, we examined the same sub-samples of stars used for determination of the rotational properties of these components. The inner-halo velocity ellipsoid component in the rotational direction was obtained from the ML analysis by holding the values of the rotational velocities and dispersions fixed for the thick-disk and outer-halo components. In the radial and vertical directions (where the strong overlap with multiple additional components complicates a mixture-model analysis), the velocities and dispersions were obtained adopting the mean velocity and dispersion of a sub-sample of stars in a more restricted range of metallicity ($-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$), where the inner halo is expected to be dominant.

Our derived ellipsoid for the rapidly rotating canonical thick disk is $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (53 \pm 2, 51 \pm 1, 35 \pm 1) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, after correction of the derived dispersions for measurement errors. These values closely match the thick-disk velocity ellipsoid obtained by Chiba & Beers (2000). For the outer halo, which exhibits a large net retrograde rotation, we obtained $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (159 \pm 4, 165 \pm 9, 116 \pm 3) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, corrected for measurement errors. These values are consistent with a more tangentially anisotropic velocity ellipsoid, which was previously advocated by Sommer-Larsen et al. (1997), from an analysis of radial velocities of distant horizontal-branch stars.

The inner halo is essentially non-rotating, with a derived mean value of $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 7 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and a velocity ellipsoid $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (150 \pm 2, 95 \pm 2, 85 \pm 1) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, corrected for measurement errors. Although our zero mean rotational velocity differs from that reported by Chiba & Beers (2000), $\langle V_\phi \rangle \sim 30\text{-}50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, our velocity ellipsoid values are consistent, within the reported errors, with the Chiba & Beers determinations of a radially anisotropic ellipsoid, $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (141 \pm 11, 106 \pm 9, 94 \pm 8) \text{ km s}^{-1}$. This agreement obtains even though the Chiba & Beers analysis adopted a one-component halo, from which we conclude that their sample (and others) did not include significant numbers of outer-halo stars.

Our results can also be compared with the recent analysis of SDSS subdwarfs by Smith et al. (2009). These authors obtained full space motions for a local sample of some 1800 subdwarfs selected on the basis of a reduced proper motion diagram, and used the same spectroscopic determinations of stellar atmospheric parameters as the present work. Note that for the purpose of their analysis they considered the halo as a single entity. They concur with our determination that the inner halo exhibits essentially no net rotation (they obtained $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 1 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), but reported a slightly

different derived velocity ellipsoid. Their values $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (137 \pm 2, 81 \pm 1, 89 \pm 1) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, agree with our determination for the vertical component of the inner halo ellipsoid, but are 15-20 km s^{-1} lower than our determinations for the radial and azimuthal components. Similarly, the values for the (single-component) halo velocity ellipsoid obtained by Bond et al. (2009), from an analysis of the space motions for some 100000 main-sequence stars from SDSS/SEGUE with available spectroscopy, $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (135 \pm 5, 85 \pm 5, 85 \pm 5) \text{ km s}^{-1}$, although in agreement with the Smith et al. ellipsoid, also differ from our results for the radial and azimuthal components.

We suspect that the resolution of these differences may be the presence of a significant MWTD component. The lower velocity dispersion of such a component, if unrecognized, may have an impact on the derived halo velocity ellipsoids. In this regard, it may be of significance that Smith et al. noted that their observed distribution of V_ϕ exhibited a significant asymmetry; their attempted decomposition of the distribution with a two-component model yielded estimates for the dispersions of 47 and 99 km s^{-1} , values reminiscent of what we would associate with the MWTD and inner-halo populations, respectively (although the mean rotational velocity they obtained for the component with a MWTD-like dispersion was only 17 km s^{-1}). They also pointed out that the asymmetry of their V_ϕ distribution increased for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -1.5$, consistent with this interpretation.

We have attempted to estimate the other two components (the radial and vertical components) of the velocity ellipsoid for the MWTD. Application of a mixture-model analysis, for the range of metallicity $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$ and distance interval $1 < |Z| < 2 \text{ kpc}$, indicates slightly negative velocities in the radial and vertical directions, $\langle V_R \rangle = -13 \pm 5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\langle V_Z \rangle = -14 \pm 5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, respectively. When combined with the previously estimated value for the rotational velocity dispersion of the MWTD, the velocity ellipsoid for the MWTD is $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z}) = (59 \pm 5, 40 \pm 3, 44 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1})$. Note that, for the rotational direction, we have adopted a value for the dispersion midway between the extremes obtained from the mixture-model analysis of different metallicity regions and distance intervals. The velocity asymmetries in the radial and vertical directions could indicate that stars in the MWTD component may not be on circular orbits nor have orbits that are co-planar with the orbits of stars associated with the thin-disk component. This could be another sign that the MWTD might be associated with stars from the Monoceros stream, as mentioned above.

We also demonstrated that all three components of the velocity dispersions increase with decreasing metallicity, in a manner suggesting discontinuous transitions from the thick disk to the MWTD, and from the inner to the outer halo. This is a fundamental

new result (also reported by Bond et al. 2009), which can be used to place constraints on possible formation scenarios for the stellar components of the Milky Way by comparison with new-generation numerical simulations.

3.11.1.8 Thick-Disk System Scale Lengths and Heights

Our extensive data set for the disk systems has also been used to obtain kinematic estimates of the thick-disk scale length and scale height. In our form of the Jeans Equation, separated into radial and vertical components, we have included the gradients in σ_{V_R} and σ_{V_Z} , which are directly measured from the data. We found that the vertical acceleration, K_Z , obtained by Kuijken & Gilmore (1991) is in optimal agreement with the value independently determined by Holmberg & Flynn (2000). Adopting the dispersion for the thick disk reported in Table 3.5, a mean rotational velocity, $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and K_Z at 1.1 kpc, we found a scale length, $h_R = 2.20 \pm 0.35 \text{ kpc}$, and a scale height, $h_Z = 0.51 \pm 0.04 \text{ kpc}$. The smaller value of our scale length with respect to that of Chiba & Beers (2000) (4.5 kpc) results from our mean rotational velocity of the thick disk, which is significantly smaller than theirs. However, our estimate of h_R is in agreement with that of others, based on star counts (Reyle & Robin 2001).

A large range of thick-disk scale heights has been reported in the literature – from 0.6 kpc to 1 kpc (Gilmore & Wyse 1985; Kuijken & Gilmore 1989; Robin et al. 1996; Norris 1996; Ng et al. 1997; Buser et al. 1999; Chen et al. 2001; Kerber et al. 2001; Ojha 2001; Reyle & Robin 2001; Du et al. 2003; Larsen & Humphreys 2003; Du et al. 2006), and from 1.1 kpc to 1.6 kpc (Gilmore & Reid 1983; Robin & Creze 1986; Spagna et al. 1996; Buser et al. 1998). Our kinematic evaluation of h_Z falls at the lower end of these estimates. A possible explanation might be the derived velocity dispersion in the vertical direction for the thick disk (35 km s^{-1}), which could be reduced by the presence of thin-disk stars in the selected sub-sample. The gradient of σ_{V_Z} does not contribute significantly in the Jeans Equation; even when an isothermal thick disk is considered ($\partial\sigma_{V_Z}/\partial|Z| = 0$), we obtain $h_Z = 0.64 \text{ kpc}$. Note that our estimate of the scale height is made at $|Z| = 1.1 \text{ kpc}$, while the “usually larger” estimates come from star counts at $|Z| \sim 2$ to 4 kpc (see references above). In these works, the thick disk appears as vertically exponential at larger $|Z|$, but in fact, it is unlikely to be strictly exponential. If we consider the general version of the Jeans Equation, and perform a numerical integration under the assumption that the thick disk is vertically isothermal, with a velocity dispersion of $\sigma_{V_Z} = 35 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, we find that at $|Z| = 1.1 \text{ kpc}$, the “local scale height” is in perfect agreement with our value of 0.64 kpc. On the other hand, if we define an effective scale height of the thick disk as the height above the Galactic

plane at which the density decreases by a factor e from its value at $|Z| = 0$, we find that this height is 0.99 ± 0.04 kpc, which is not directly comparable with the star count scale heights at larger $|Z|$.

In the case of the MWTD, we have only the kinematic parameters listed in Table 3.5 (i.e., no directly measured gradients could be obtained), which can be used to derive important constraints on the radial structure of this component. Indeed, using the radial component of the Jeans Equation, and assuming that $\sigma_{V_R}^2 \propto \exp(-R/h_\sigma)$, where h_σ is a scale length, we find that the MWTD scale length is again short, ~ 2 kpc. This result comes from the assumption that the MWTD presents a uniform scale height and constant anisotropy. The scale height has been derived adopting the same value of the vertical acceleration reported above, and under the same assumptions. We obtained $h_Z = 1.36 \pm 0.13$ kpc, in agreement with the larger values of the scale height estimation of the canonical thick disk.

3.11.1.9 Inferred Density Profiles of the Inner- and Outer-Halo Components

The kinematics for our local sample of calibration stars were used to infer density profiles for the inner-halo and outer-halo components. We obtained $\rho_{in} \sim r^{-3.17 \pm 0.20}$ for the inner halo, consistent with the derived density profile of “the halo” found by many previous authors (e.g., Harris 1976; Zinn 1985; Hartwick 1987; Carney, Latham, & Laird 1990; Preston et al. 1991; Chiba & Beers 2000). In contrast, the density profile obtained for the outer halo, $\rho_{out} \sim r^{-1.79 \pm 0.29}$, is substantially shallower than that of the inner halo, as expected from the higher values of the velocity dispersions for this component. It is thus of interest to note that Ivezić et al. (2000), based on a sample of RR Lyraes located between 10 and 50 kpc from the Galactic center selected from SDSS commissioning data, obtained a slope of -2.7 ± 0.2 . From the QUEST RR Lyrae Data (which cover basically the same distance range as the Ivezić et al. sample), Vivas & Zinn (2006) obtained values for the derived slope between -2.5 ± 0.1 and -3.1 ± 0.1 , depending on the adopted level of flattening and local density. Our low value of the slope for the outer-halo component is reminiscent to that obtained by Miceli et al. (2008) for Oosterhoff Type II RR Lyraes (-2.88 ± 0.11 ; the value for Oosterhoff Type I class is even smaller, -2.26 ± 0.07). Note that both of these values assumed a spherical halo, and included stars only up to about 30 kpc away. When a flattened halo is considered, the Miceli et al. slope changes from -2.43 ± 0.06 (all RR Lyrae types, spherical halo) to -3.15 ± 0.07 . Sesar et al. (2009) report a dramatic “steepening” of the halo density profile beyond 30 kpc, based on an analysis of RR Lyraes and main-sequence stars from the SDSS equatorial stripe, in the sense

that the numbers of stars at large Galactocentric distances is much lower than would be expected from extrapolation of the (single halo component) density profile they adopt to describe the density profile within 30 kpc. Alternatively, this result could be interpreted as arising from the changeover from inner-halo to outer-halo dominance in the star counts, with the outer-halo contributing substantially fewer stars beyond 30 kpc (we roughly estimate that the local relative normalization of outer-halo to inner-halo spatial density laws is about 10%). Thus, although differences in the precise values of the slopes obtained from different data sets and different analysis approaches remain, it appears that the inner/outer halo model very naturally accounts for observed changes in the density profile of halo tracers with distance reported by a number of previous groups.

3.11.1.10 Derived Tilts of the Velocity Ellipsoids

The kinematic parameters derived for stars in our local sample have been used to examine tilts of the velocity ellipsoids, as a function of height above the Galactic plane, over several intervals in metallicity.

Misalignment of the velocity ellipsoids with the adopted cylindrical coordinate system has been found for all the selected sub-samples. At high metallicity the tilt angle is $7^\circ.1 \pm 1^\circ.5$, when $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, and $5^\circ.5 \pm 1^\circ.2$ at $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc. A similar value was reported by Siebert et al. (2008) for a sample of RAVE-survey stars at $|Z| < 1$ kpc ($7^\circ.3 \pm 1^\circ.8$). At intermediate metallicity the tilt angle is $10^\circ.3 \pm 0^\circ.4$, and $15^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.3$, while for low-metallicity stars we found $8^\circ.6 \pm 0^\circ.5$, and $13^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.4$, at $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc and $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc, respectively. The velocity ellipsoids point close to the Galactic center, as can be inferred from Figure 3.19. Bond et al. (2009) also report similar tilts of the velocity ellipsoid for low-metallicity stars. The existence of these tilts indicates that motions of stars in our local sample are aligned with respect to a spherical, rather than cylindrical, coordinate system.

We considered the possibility that the inner halo and/or outer halo might exhibit kinematics close to isotropic in (θ, ϕ) , which would be consistent with a system for which the distribution function depends on the energy and the total angular momentum. For a sample of stars with $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.6$, and located at $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc, where the dominant component is expected to be the inner halo, we find $(\sigma_{V_r}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_\theta}) = (160 \pm 3, 102 \pm 2, 83 \pm 2)$ km s⁻¹. These values are somewhat higher than those recently obtained by Smith et al. 2009 (142, 81, 77) km s⁻¹, and Bond et al. (2009) (141, 85, 75) km s⁻¹. In the case of the outer halo, a similar estimate is more uncertain, due to the difficulty in separating the two halo components in V_ϕ and V_Z . Nevertheless, an

attempt was made, employing the interval of metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.4$ and $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc, which should emphasize outer-halo stars. We obtained $(\sigma_{V_r}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_\theta}) = (178 \pm 9, 149 \pm 7, 127 \pm 6)$. The conclusion of this exercise is that both the inner and outer halo are significantly anisotropic in (θ, ϕ) .

3.11.1.11 Variation of the Observed Metallicity Distribution Function with Distance from the Galactic Plane

Finally, we examined the “as-observed” MDF using the full sample of calibration stars, to look for confirmation of the expected changes as a function of the height above the plane (Fig. 20). We constructed MDFs at different intervals of $|Z|$, close to the Galactic plane ($0 < |Z| < 5$ kpc), and farther from the Galactic plane ($5 < |Z| < 9$ kpc, and $|Z| > 9$ kpc). In the first case, the MDF exhibits a transition from a thick-disk and MWTD-dominated population to an inner-halo dominated population, while in the second case, there is clear evidence for a transition from inner-halo to outer-halo dominance.

3.11.1.12 Comparison with the Results of Bond et al. (2009)

The recent analysis conducted by Bond et al. (2009) considered the kinematics of a larger sample of SDSS stars than the present investigation, based on both photometric and spectroscopic metallicity estimates. Although the analysis techniques and the adopted models differ somewhat from those used herein, the basic conclusions of these two studies are very similar. We point out that the Bond et al. approach was not able to effectively split an assumed single-halo population into inner- and outer-halo components, since the metallicities of outer-halo stars are lower than can be usefully assigned abundances from photometric techniques. Nevertheless, one can see the presence of stars with retrograde velocities in the lower-right panel of Figure 6 of Bond et al. (stars selected with $|Z|$ in the range 5-7 kpc) as an “excess” population relative to their assumed single-halo population (note that in Bond et al., the rotational velocities are assigned an opposite sign than in the present work; we are referring to stars in their figure with $V_\phi > 250 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). Similarly, again from inspection of the same panel in their Figure 6, essentially all of their data points with positive (meaning retrograde) rotational velocities fall *under* their single-Gaussian fit, while those with negative (meaning prograde) velocities in the range $-150 < V_\phi < 0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ fall *above* their single-Gaussian fit. This apparent lack of fit is almost certainly due to the lack of an inner/outer split in their model of the halo population. Nevertheless, due to the relatively small number of outer halo stars at the distance limit of their sample (7 kpc), the derived kinematics of their “halo population” are quite similar to our inner-halo

population.

The results of these two studies for the thick-disk populations, although approached in a different way, are also compatible. In the Bond et al. approach, the disk stars in their sample were modeled with a non-Gaussian distribution for the rotational velocities, incorporating a component with a fixed lag in velocity relative to what we would consider the canonical thick disk. We would identify this lower rotational velocity component with the MWTD of our analysis. It is interesting that they found that this model was able to accommodate the observed behavior of their sample smoothly with increasing height above the Galactic plane. Clearly, there remains more to be learned from future analysis of these data.

3.11.2 Discussion

The structural and kinematic parameters obtained in this paper provide valuable information for understanding the formation of the stellar halos and thick disks of the Milky Way. We have confirmed that the inner- and the outer-halo components exhibit different kinematic properties and inferred spatial distributions, and (from the previous analysis of the DR5 sample of calibration stars by Carollo et al. 2007, and confirmed by our *in-situ* analysis of the full calibration-star sample) that their metallicity distribution functions differ significantly as well. We have also confirmed the presence of a significant vertical gradient in $\langle V_\phi \rangle$ as a function of $|Z|$ at low abundances, which suggests that the inner-halo component was most likely formed by dissipational processes.

A number of recent theoretical and observational efforts provide supporting evidence for the existence of an inner/outer halo dichotomy in the Milky Way, and in other similar galaxies. We consider these in turn.

3.11.2.1 The Halos: Evidence from Theoretical Modeling

De Lucia & Helmi (2008) have adapted a high-resolution simulation of a Milky Way-like halo, combined with a semi-analytic approach, to explore the formation of the Galaxy. They found *no evidence* for a “continuous” metallicity gradient for halo stars, but rather, evidence for a strong concentration of higher-metallicity halo stars toward the Galactic center, and the presence of lower-metallicity stars at distances beyond 20 kpc from the Galactic center. The results of this simulation bear a strong resemblance to the properties of the dominant inner halo we find within 10-15 kpc from Sun, as well as with its rather steep inferred density profile, and an outer halo that dominates beyond 15-20 kpc, with a much shallower inferred density profile.

In a recent paper, Zolotov et al. (2009) have investigated the formation of the stellar halos in simulated disk galaxies, using high-resolution SPH + N-Body simulations. They found that the inner regions ($r < 20$ kpc) contain both accreted and *in-situ* stellar populations (the latter includes stars formed in the main halo). Contrasting with this, the outer regions of the simulated halos were assembled through pure accretion and the disruption of satellites.

Other recent supporting evidence is found in a simulation by Salvadori et al (2009). These authors studied the age and metallicity distribution function of metal-poor stars in the Milky Way halo, as a function of Galactocentric radius, from a study combining N-body simulations and semi-analytical methods. They found that the stellar distributions, within 50 kpc from the center of their simulated galaxy, follow a power-law in radius, r^n , where $n \sim -3.2$ for stars with $-2 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1$, and $n \sim -2.2$ for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -2$. In this context, the relative contribution of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -2$ strongly increases with r (16% within $7 < r < 20$ kpc, up to $> 40\%$ for $r > 20$ kpc). Note that our spatial-density power laws for the inner and outer halo are in reasonable agreement, within the errors, with the values found by Salvadori et al (2009).

Cooper et al. (2009) have also conducted simulations of the formation of stellar halos within the Λ CDM paradigm, offering a number of improvements over previous efforts. Their results, which cover a range of possible halo formation histories, produce predicted metallicity shifts at various radii, several of which are reminiscent of what we have found in our own analysis of the Milky Way's halo system. It is notable that, in all cases, the lowest metallicity stars in their simulations are accreted (or stripped) from the very sort of ultra-faint dwarf galaxies that Carollo et al. (2007) suggested may be related to the origin of the outer-halo population.

3.11.2.2 The Halos: Evidence from Observations of Other Galaxies

For at least a decade, the mystery of the relatively "metal-rich" halo of M 31 has presented a challenge to our understanding of its formation history. Photometric and spectroscopic observations by Kalirai et al. (2006b), and more recently by Koch et al. (2008a), have demonstrated that a metal-poor halo of M 31 does indeed exist, but is located beyond 40 kpc from its center (substantially different than observed for the Milky Way, where the outer halo becomes dominant beyond 20 kpc). Their description of a dual-halo model for the Andromeda Galaxy parallels what we observe for the Milky Way, albeit on different length scales.

Recent observations of the Milky Way analogue NGC 891 have provided additional information on the structure and the stellar populations for this relatively mas-

sive spiral galaxy in the NGC 1023 group (Ibata, Mouhcine, & Rejkuba 2009; Rejkuba, Houhcine, & Ibata 2009). Analysis of their data revealed the presence of a thick-disk structure with vertical scale height $h_Z = 1.4$ kpc, and scale length $h_R = 4.8$ kpc, somewhat larger than values that have been inferred for the Milky Way. The MDF of the thick-disk structure exhibits a peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.9$ (as compared to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.6$ for the canonical thick disk of the Milky Way) that does not change significantly in the vertical and radial directions. When they considered the MDF for stars in regions resembling the solar cylinder we have examined in the present paper (distance along the major axis ~ 8 kpc, vertical distance intervals of ~ 3 -4 kpc and 5-7 kpc), they detected a substantial population of intermediate-metallicity stars, with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.0$. By way of contrast, at these same vertical distances the MDF of the Milky Way is dominated by the inner halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$; Ivezić et al. 2008; this paper). The intermediate-metallicity population in the solar cylinder of NGC 891 might be associated with a component similar to the Milky Way’s MWTD, but are present at larger distances from the plane in this galaxy than in the Milky Way. The difference between the vertical extension in the MDF of the disk populations, between NGC 891 and the Milky Way, may simply reflect different (stochastic) formation histories for the two galaxies.

The stellar halo of NGC 891 exhibits a shallow metallicity gradient, with average metallicity decreasing from $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.15$ to -1.27 from the inner regions to the outskirts. A similar trend was also found in the inner halo of M 31 (20 kpc from the nucleus; Durrell, Harris, & Pritchett 2001), and in the halo of NGC 5128, which is the nearest giant elliptical galaxy (Rejkuba et al. 2005). In subsequent work, metal-poor halos were detected for these galaxies, at distances larger than $12r_{\text{eff}}$ from the center (Chapman et al. 2006; Kalirai et al. 2006a). However, in NGC 891, at the same radius, a metal-poor halo has not (yet) been detected. In this regard we note that in the right-hand panel of Figure 18 in Rejkuba et al. (2009) there is a clear transition of the MDF, from intermediate ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.0$) metallicity to a lower ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.5$) metallicity, which suggests the presence of a metal-poor population like that in the inner halo of the Milky Way. We suspect that when additional photometry at larger distances is carried out for NGC 891 its MDF will reveal metal-poor halo population(s) similar to those of the Milky Way.

Recent spectroscopic studies of the metallicities and other elemental abundances in the ultra-faint dSph galaxies (Kirby et al. 2008; Koch et al. 2008b; Norris et al. 2008; Frebel et al. 2009) have clearly demonstrated that the frequently cited result (e.g., Helmi et al 2006) that “the progenitors of nearby dSph’s appear to have been different from the building blocks of the Milky Way,” while true for the more luminous mem-

bers of the dSph population, does not necessarily pertain to its fainter systems. While we refer the reader to the reviews of Koch (2009) and Tolstoy, Hill, & Tosi (2009) for more thorough discussions, we note here two relevant points. First, it has been shown that the metallicities of stars in even the more luminous dSphs (e.g., Sculptor; Battaglia et al. 2008) are spatially stratified, with the more metal-poor objects being found preferentially in their outer regions. These metal-poor stars are clearly the most likely to be stripped from their parents during tidal interactions, with the halo(s) of the Milky Way as the obvious recipients. Secondly, the works cited above establish that extremely metal-poor stars ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3.0$) exist in the ultra-faint systems, and for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.6$, one finds $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] \sim 0.3\text{--}0.5$, similar to Galactic halo values. It is not difficult to imagine a substantial population of low-luminosity dwarfs, most of which have already been completely dissolved, accounting for the entire population of stars in the presently observed outer-halo component of the Milky Way. We look forward to further guidance for this idea to be obtained by additional high-resolution spectroscopic observations of stars in the low-luminosity dwarfs, as well as detailed elemental abundance determinations for stars with kinematics that suggest membership in the outer-halo population (e.g., Ishigaki et al. 2009; Roederer 2009; Zhang et al. 2009; Roederer et al., in preparation).

3.11.2.3 The Thick Disk: Evidence from Theoretical Modeling

Simulations that attempt to account for the formation of the thick-disk component have suggested that the asymmetric drift we find for this structure can be naturally accommodated. According to the simulations of Abadi et al. (2003), it may also be consistent with the expected behavior if the thick disk is comprised solely of debris from merging satellites. The formation of a MWTD component may be the result of a stochastic event, such as assimilation of the debris from a moderately metal-poor, low-mass satellite.

Modern cosmogonies predict the formation of the thick disk by predominantly dissipationless processes. In this context, thick-disk stars were vertically heated from a pre-existent thin disk during a significant minor merger or perturbation by a cold dark matter sub-halo (Kazantzidis et al. 2009), or directly deposited at large scale heights as tidally stripped debris during the accretion of smaller satellite galaxies (e.g., Statler 1988; Abadi et al. 2003; Yoachim & Dalcanton 2008). Villalobos & Helmi (2008) have investigated in detail the heating process by a minor merger. They found that the trend of the ratio $\sigma_{V_z}/\sigma_{V_R}$ with radius in the final disks is a good discriminant of the initial inclination of the merging satellite. For the Milky Way, the observed $\sigma_{V_z}/\sigma_{V_R}$

is ~ 0.6 (Chiba & Beers 2000; this paper), which suggest that the thick disk of the Galaxy could have been produced by a merger of intermediate inclination. The values found for the MWTD velocity ellipsoid provide a ratio $\sigma_{V_Z}/\sigma_{V_R} \sim 0.7$, which could be explained through a merger of different inclination.

Hayashi & Chiba (2006) have shown that disk thickening, quantified by the change of its scale height (or the square of its vertical velocity dispersion), strongly depends on the individual mass of an interacting sub-halo. In this scenario of hierarchical formation, the MWTD could be formed through the early merger (at least with respect to the merger responsible for the formation of the canonical thick disk) of a satellite with a less massive, younger pre-existing disk. Note, however, that the existence of stars with disk kinematics and older than the last major merger event is difficult to accommodate in the Λ CDM scenario (Abadi et al. 2003). The results of the simulations of Abadi et al. suggest that the tidal debris from satellites can contribute not only to the Galactic halo, but also to the disk system. The contribution to the halo or to the disk depends on the orbit of the merging satellite, and on the degree to which dynamical friction circularized the orbits before disruption (Statler 1988). An accreted satellite that contributes significantly to the thick disk must be disrupted on an orbital plane very close to that of the disk, and be massive enough to survive the disruption until its orbit is circularized within the disk. In this scenario, the predicted location of the disrupted satellites responsible for the formation of the thick disk and MWTD is within the thick-disk system itself. We have noted in subsection 3.11.1 that some properties of the Monoceros stream (rotational velocity and metallicity) are in good agreement with those of the MWTD. *The Monoceros stream could be part of the disrupted satellite that was also responsible for the formation of the thick-disk system.*

3.11.2.4 The Metal-Weak Thick Disk: Additional Evidence Needed from Observations

We have attempted to constrain the properties of the MWTD as an independent kinematic component from the canonical thick disk. It was found that its velocity lag is $\sim 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ lower than the canonical thick disk; its velocity ellipsoid appears similar to that of the thick disk (although its vertical velocity dispersion, and hence its inferred scale height, appear somewhat larger). These values are, of course, still uncertain due to the significant kinematic and spatial overlap of the MWTD with the thick-disk and inner-halo components. Additional study (informed by more-detailed abundance analyses of likely MWTD stars) must be given to this problem before its final resolution can be obtained. Other sub-samples of stars from SDSS/SEGUE, beyond the calibra-

tion stars discussed in our study, as well as stars from other surveys such as RAVE, will help shed light on the nature of the Galactic components we have described. It is evident that the final observational picture has yet to be drawn; nuances continue to be revealed as our database of information expands. Witness the “highly flattened” inner-halo component suggested by Morrison et al. (2009) that comprises stars with intermediate low metallicities, and is confined to a region close to the Galactic plane, but (in contrast to the MWTD) is not supported by rotation.

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4

Carbon-Enhanced Metal-Poor Stars in the Inner and Outer Halo Components of the Milky Way

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Abstract

The carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars in the inner- and outer-halo components of the Milky Way are explored, based on accurate determinations of the carbon-to-iron abundance ratios and kinematic quantities for over 30000 calibration stars from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) and its first extension, (SDSS-II). The carbon abundance estimates are based on fits to the CH G-band at 4305 Å; the kinematic and orbital parameters have been evaluated for a subsample of the calibration stars (with distances $d < 10$ kpc from the Sun), employing previously developed methods. We find that 1%, 6%, and 18% of stars in the metallicity intervals $-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.5$, $-2.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.5$, respectively, exhibit carbon-to-iron abundance ratios ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$, or “carbonicity”) in excess of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] = +0.7$, our adopted definition for CEMP stars. We examine the carbonicity distribution function (CarDF) as a function of distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$, and demonstrate that its nature changes dramatically with increasing distance. For $|Z| < 5$ kpc, relatively few CEMP stars are identified (over all metallicities). For distances $|Z| > 5$ kpc, the CarDF exhibits a strong tail towards high values, up to $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > +3.0$. For low metallicity stars located above

$|Z| = 5$ kpc we confirm a significant increase in the fraction of CEMP stars with declining metallicity, as indicated by previous work. In the low metallicity regime, for both $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.4$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$, we find a clear increase in the CEMP star fraction with $|Z|$, approaching $\sim 15\%$ in the most distant bins. We have sought to understand whether these behaviors are metallicity driven, due to differences in the mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ of the inner- and outer-halo components, or population driven, due to differences in the fractions of CEMP stars associated with each population at a given metallicity. To accomplish this, we have obtained a statistical separation of the inner- and outer-halo components in velocity space using the Extreme Deconvolution technique, which provides membership probabilities for each star. At low metallicity ($-2.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$), where the dominant component is the outer halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{peak,out}} = -2.2$), there is evidence for a significant contrast in the CEMP star fraction between the inner- and outer-halo components, such that $F_{\text{CEMP}_{\text{out}}} \sim 2 \times F_{\text{CEMP}_{\text{in}}}$. This may continue to even lower metallicities, but the sample is too small to be certain. These results are considered in the context of the formation of the halo system of the Milky Way, and the likely progenitors of the inner- and outer-halo populations.

4.1 Introduction

The Milky Way provides astronomers with a unique opportunity to explore the formation and evolution of large spiral galaxies, as well as the nature of their stellar populations and recognized structures. The key to this understanding comes from the availability, for large numbers of individual stars, of the powerful combination of six-dimensional phase-space information (location and velocity) and chemical abundances. Metal-poor stars, in particular, shed light on the early stages of galaxy formation and chemical evolution, as they represent the fossil record of the first generations of stars that formed shortly after the Big Bang.

Although theory suggests that the bulge of the Galaxy may harbor numerous ancient (though not necessarily the most metal-poor) stars (e.g., Tumlinson 2010), the vast majority of presently recognized metal-poor stars are found in the halo components of the Galaxy. According to Carollo et al. (2007; C07) and Carollo et al. (2010; C10), the inner and outer halos possess different peak metallicities (inner: $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$; outer: $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.2$), as well as different spatial distributions, with the inner halo exhibiting a flatter density profile than the nearly spherical outer halo. Their analysis of the kinematics of a local sample of calibration stars from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (York et al. 2000) indicated that the transition from dominance by the inner

halo to outer halo occurs in the range 15-20 kpc from the Sun. A similar transition range has been inferred from analysis of the “vertical” photometric stripes (de Jong et al. 2010), obtained during the SEGUE sub-survey of the SDSS (Yanny et al. 2009).

C07 and C10 also demonstrated that the inner-halo population is essentially non-rotating, with $V_\phi = 7 \pm 4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, while the outer-halo population exhibits a significant retrograde signature, with $V_\phi = -80 \pm 13 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (where V_ϕ is the Galactocentric rotational velocity). The velocity ellipsoids of these populations differ as well. The derived velocity ellipsoids, $(\sigma_{v_R}, \sigma_{v_\phi}, \sigma_{v_z}) = (\text{inner: } 150 \pm 2, 95 \pm 2, 85 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}; \text{ outer: } 159 \pm 4, 165 \pm 9, 116 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1})$, evaluated in a Galactocentric cylindrical reference frame.

The observed differences in the nature of the spatial distributions and kinematics of the stellar populations associated with the inner- and outer-halo components suggests that, in the context of modern hierarchical cosmogonies, their progenitor mini-halos and subsequent merging and accretion scenarios differed as well. If the inner halo formed from a limited number of moderately massive mini-halos (see, e.g., Bullock & Johnston 2005; Schlafman et al. 2009, 2011), while the outer halo resulted from the accretion of less massive ones (C07; Frebel et al. 2010; Norris et al. 2010a,b,c), one might expect to find chemical signatures associated with the presently observed stellar populations that reflect these differences. Previous studies have provided hints that this may indeed be the case. For example, studies of the [Mg/Fe] abundance ratios of stars thought to be associated with the inner halo appear different (generally 0.1 dex higher) than those associated with the outer halo (Roederer 2009). This same study also demonstrated that stars associated with the inner halo exhibit considerably lower star-to-star abundance scatter for both the iron-peak element ratio [Ni/Fe] and the neutron-capture element ratio [Ba/Fe] than found for stars of the outer halo. Chemically peculiar stars, such as the α -element-enhanced very metal-poor star BS 16934-002 (Aoki et al. 2007a; [Fe/H] = -2.7), the low [Mg/Fe] (-0.1), high [Ca/Fe] (+1.1) extremely metal-poor star SDSS J234723.6+010833.4 (Lai et al. 2009; [Fe/H] = -3.2), and the low [Si/Fe] (-1.0), low [Ca/Fe] (-0.6) extremely metal-poor star identified by Cohen et al. (2007; [Fe/H] \sim -4.0) all have inferred distances (and metallicities) that suggest membership in the outer-halo population. All three of the recognized ultra metal-poor stars ([Fe/H] \leq -4.0, HE 0557-4840; Norris et al. 2007) or hyper metal-poor stars ([Fe/H] \leq -5.0, HE 0107-5240; Christlieb et al. 2002, and HE 1327-2326; Frebel et al. 2005) are similarly thought to be members of the outer-halo population. These results may all be related to the star formation histories in the progenitor populations, their accretion histories, or both.

In the present paper we focus on another possibly useful indicator of chemical

differences in the nature of the inner- and outer-halo components, the carbon-to-iron ratio, $[C/Fe]$, which we refer to as the “carbonicity.” In particular, we make use of the SDSS/SEGUE calibration-star sample from SDSS DR7 (Abazajian et al. 2009) in order to search for possible contrasts between the frequency and degree of carbon enhancement for the carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars from this sample that can be kinematically associated with these two halo components.

CEMP stars were originally defined as the subset of very metal-poor stars ($[Fe/H] \leq -2$) that exhibit elevated carbon relative to iron, $[C/Fe] > +1.0$ (Beers & Christlieb 2005)¹. In the last two decades it has been recognized, primarily from spectroscopic follow-up of metal-poor candidates selected from objective-prism surveys (e.g., Beers et al. 1985, 1992; Christlieb 2003), that roughly 20% of stars with $[Fe/H] < -2.0$ exhibit enhanced carbonicity, up to several orders of magnitude larger than the solar ratio (Lucatello et al. 2006). Some recent studies (e.g., Cohen et al. 2005; Frebel et al. 2006), have claimed that this fraction is somewhat lower (14% and 9%, respectively, for $[Fe/H] < -2.0$). The Frebel et al. (2006) study is of particular interest, as the authors argued that the relative fraction of CEMP stars appears to increase substantially with distance above the Galactic plane, suggesting a possible connection with changes in the underlying stellar populations. In any case, the fraction of CEMP stars rises to 30% for $[Fe/H] < -3.0$, 40% for $[Fe/H] < -3.5$, and 100% for $[Fe/H] < -4.0$ (Beers & Christlieb 2005; Frebel et al. 2005; Norris et al. 2007); definitive explanations for the origin of this increase have yet to be offered. Regardless of the ultimate reason, these results indicate that significant amounts of carbon were produced in the early stages of chemical evolution in the Universe.

There exist a number of classes of CEMP stars, some of which have been associated with proposed progenitor objects. CEMP-s stars (those with s-process element enhancement), for example, are the most commonly observed type to date. High-resolution spectroscopic studies have revealed that around 80% of CEMP stars exhibit s-process-element enhancement (Aoki et al. 2007b). The favored mechanism invoked to account for these stars is mass transfer of carbon-enhanced material from the envelope of an asymptotic giant-branch (AGB) star to its binary companion; it is this surviving companion that is now observed as a CEMP-s star (e.g., Herwig 2005; Sneden et al. 2008). The class of CEMP-no stars (which exhibit no strong neutron-capture-element enhancements) is particularly prevalent among the most metal-poor stars. Possible progenitors for this class include massive, rapidly rotating, mega metal-poor ($[Fe/H] < -6.0$) stars, which models suggest have greatly enhanced abundances of

¹Other authors have used slightly different criteria, e.g., $[C/Fe] > +0.7$ (Aoki et al. 2007b), in order to account for the effects of dilution of carbon during giant-branch evolution.

CNO due to distinctive internal burning and mixing episodes, followed by strong mass loss (Hirschi et al. 2006; Meynet et al. 2006, 2010). Another mechanism is pollution of the interstellar medium by so-called faint supernovae associated with the first generations of stars, which experience extensive mixing and fallback during their explosions (Umeda & Nomoto 2003, 2005; Tominaga et al. 2007). This model well reproduces the observed abundance pattern of the CEMP-no star BD+44°493, the ninth-magnitude $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.7$ star (with $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] = +1.3$, $[\text{N}/\text{Fe}] = +0.3$, $[\text{O}/\text{Fe}] = +1.6$) discussed by Ito et al. (2009). The recently reported extremely metal-poor Damped Lyman- α (DLA) by Cooke et al. (2010; $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -3.0$) exhibits enhanced carbonicity ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] = +1.5$) and other elemental abundance signatures that Kobayashi et al. (2011) also associate with production by faint supernovae.

The present paper is outlined as follows. Section 4.2 describes the techniques used to estimate carbonicity ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$) from the low-resolution SDSS spectra, compares our estimates with a sample of very low metallicity stars with available high-resolution spectroscopic determinations, and obtains first-pass estimates of the fractions of CEMP stars for various cuts on $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Section 4.3 summarizes the calibration-star sample from SDSS DR7 we examine here, and presents the “as-observed” distributions of metallicity and carbonicity for this sample as functions of height above the Galactic plane. Section 4.4 explores the global fraction of CEMP stars of this sample in the low metallicity regime, describes our adopted technique for derivation of stellar population membership probabilities for the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration stars, and obtains estimates of the fractions of CEMP stars associated with the inner- and outer-halo populations. Finally, Section 4.5 summarizes the main results and considers their implications for the formation and evolution of the Galactic halo populations.

4.2 [C/Fe] Ratios for the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 Calibration-Star Sample

4.2.1 Estimation of Carbon Abundance Ratios

Carbon abundance ratios are estimated from the CH G-band at $\sim 4300 \text{ \AA}$ by matching the observed SDSS spectra near this feature with an extensive grid of synthetic spectra. In order to construct the grid we employed the NEWODF models of Castelli & Kurucz (2003). Synthetic spectra were generated using the `turbospectrum` synthesis code (Alvarez & Plez 1998), which employs line broadening according to the prescription of Barklem & O’Mara (1998) and Barklem & Aspelund-Johansson (2005). The molecular

Figure 4.1 Example of carbon abundance estimation procedure. Upper panel: Input optical spectrum (black line) superposed with a synthetic spectrum (red line) with $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] = 0$ (the starting value). The legend at the top of this panel lists the input values determined by the SSPP for T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. Middle panels: Best fits to the CH G-band obtained from the three different search ranges considered (left: $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] < 0$; center: $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$ covering the full grid range; right: $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > 0$). The red line in each case is the best fit, while the green line is the ratio of the best fit to the input spectrum. The legend above each of these panels provides the best estimate of $[\text{C}/\text{H}]$, along with a correlation coefficient between the fitted spectrum and the input spectrum (CC), and the reduced χ^2 of the fit (Chi2). Note in the left-hand panel that no value of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] < 0$ provides an acceptable fit. Lower panel: Final adopted fit, represented by the superposed red line. The legend above this panel lists the resulting derived $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$.

species CH and CN are provided by B. Plez (private communication; Plez & Cohen 2005). The other linelists used are the same as in Sivarani et al. (2006). For the purpose of this exercise we adopted the solar abundances of Asplund et al. (2005).

The synthetic spectra cover wavelengths between 3600Å and 4600Å, with original resolution of $\Delta\lambda = 0.005\text{Å}$, smoothed to the SDSS resolving power ($R = 2000$) and re-binned to linear 1 Å pixels. The stellar parameters of the grid cover the ranges $3500 \leq T_{\text{eff}} \leq 9750$ K (steps of 250 K), $0.0 \leq \log g \leq 5.0$ (steps of 0.5 dex) and $-2.5 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq 0.0$ (steps of 0.5 dex). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.5$, models with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.5$ were adopted. The carbon grid goes from $[\text{C}/\text{H}] = [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] - 0.5$ to $[\text{C}/\text{H}] = +0.5$ (the upper limit is in agreement with AGB models). For example, at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.5$, the grid covers the range from $[\text{C}/\text{H}] = -3.0$ to $+0.5$, which corresponds to the range of carbonicity $-0.5 < [\text{C}/\text{Fe}] < +3.0$.

Once constructed, we linearly interpolate within this grid, which is sufficient for the size of the steps in the parameters. We have checked this by taking a worse case scenario, generating test synthetic spectra at low temperatures ($T_{\text{eff}} = 3500$ K) and over the above ranges of gravity, metallicity, and carbon abundance. The linearly interpolated grid was able to recover the input parameters to within a few tenths of dex, which is consistent with our expected errors in the method. Estimation of carbon abundance was accomplished using chi-square minimization of the deviations between the observed and synthetic spectra in the wavelength region between 4285 Å and 4320 Å, as carried out by the IDL routine AMOEBA (a down-hill Simplex search procedure). The initial value for $[\text{C}/\text{H}]$ for the global grid search was set to the same value as the input stellar $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] = 0.0$), derived as described below. During the search, the carbon abundances are allowed to vary; all other stellar parameters are kept constant. In order to provide some protection from falling into local minima, separate searches were performed with lower and higher ranges of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$ considered. In almost all cases these converged to the same minima as found for the global search. When not, we took the value that resulted in the best fit in the region of the CH G-band, as judged from a correlation coefficient for the resulting match. Figure 4.1 provides an example of the spectral fitting process for determination of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$ for a warm CEMP star in our sample². The upper panel shows the input optical spectrum superposed with a synthetic spectrum with $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] = 0$. The middle panel shows the best fits to the CH G-band obtained from the three different ranges of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$ considered. The lower panel shows

²Note that the figure, which relates to the derivation of the best-fit value of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$, contains a middle (center) panel which is identical to the middle (right) panel. This is not an oversight. It is merely due to the fact that starting the chi-square minimization process covering the full grid (center) and requiring $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > 0$ both converged to the same values.

the final adopted fit.

Estimates of the errors in the final determinations of $[C/Fe]$ were obtained based on a limited set of noise-injection experiments for stars over a range of temperatures and S/N ratios. These experiments indicated that, for stars with a minimum S/N = 15/1 in the region of the G-band, $[C/Fe]$ could be measured over the T_{eff} range of our sample with a maximum error of 0.5 dex, decreasing to 0.05 dex for the highest S/N spectra (S/N > 50/1). We assigned final errors to the estimate of $[C/Fe]$ using a linear function in S/N between these extremes. Spectra not achieving the minimum S/N level (or which suffered from anomalies such as pixel dropouts) were considered non-detections. In addition, in order to claim a detection we required that the equivalent width of the CH G-band obtain a minimum value of 1.2 Å, a value again chosen based on inspection of the noise-injection experiments.³ In cases where this condition was not met, we consider the measured $[C/Fe]$ an upper limit.

We can obtain a check on our determinations of atmospheric parameters and $[C/Fe]$, for at least a subset of our stars, based on available high-resolution follow-up spectra. There are three sources for our comparisons, Aoki et al. (2008), Behara et al. (2010), and W. Aoki et al. (in preparation). Since these high-resolution programs were mostly interested in very and extremely metal-poor stars, our comparison sample is dominated by stars with $[Fe/H] < -2.5$. Table 4.1 lists the derived atmospheric parameters and carbon abundance ratios for the stars in common (the label HiRES indicates the high-resolution results, while the label SSPP refers to our analysis of the low-resolution SDSS spectra).

Figure 4.2 shows the comparison of the derived parameter estimates. Neglecting the one star for which the SDSS spectrum yielded only an upper limit (SDSS J081754.9+264103.8), there are 22 unique objects (note that the star SDSS J091243.7+021623.7 was observed by both Behara et al. 2010 and Aoki et al.; we average the two sets of results for the following discussion). Robust estimates of the zero-point offsets and rms scatter indicate good agreement for temperature ($\langle \Delta T_{\text{eff}} \rangle = -46$ K; $\sigma(T_{\text{eff}}) = 160$ K) and metallicity ($\langle \Delta [Fe/H] \rangle = -0.08$ dex; $\sigma([Fe/H]) = 0.21$ dex), while surface gravity exhibits a small zero-point offset but a fairly large scatter ($\langle \Delta(\log g) \rangle = 0.01$ dex; $\sigma(\log g) = 0.96$ dex). Difficulty in estimation of $\log g$ is not surprising, given that molecular carbon bands (in particular for later type stars) can easily confound gravity sensitive features in a low-resolution spectrum.

³The G-band equivalent width measured in this study covers a slightly wider wavelength region than that defined by Beers et al. (1999): 26 Å (this paper) vs. 15 Å (Beers et al. 1999), but it is centered on the same wavelength (4305 Å). It also makes use of a global fit to the continuum, rather than the fixed sidebands employed previously. Thus, although the equivalent widths are similar, they are not identical.

Figure 4.2 Left panels: Comparison of derived estimates of atmospheric parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$), and carbonicity, $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$, as derived from the low-resolution spectra (SSPP) and the high-resolution follow-up spectra (HiRES). A one-to-one line is shown for each. Right panels: Histograms of the differences between the SSPP and HiRES determinations.

Table 4.1. Comparison with high-resolution spectroscopy: Atmospheric parameters and carbon abundances

IAU Name	PLATE-MJD-FIBER	REF	T_{eff}		$\log g$		[Fe/H]		[C/Fe]	
			HiRES	SSPP	HiRES	SSPP	HiRES	SSPP	HiRES	SSPP
SDSS J000219.9+292851.8	2803-54368-459	A11	6350	6184	4.00	3.24	-3.07	-2.97	+2.74	+2.73
SDSS J003602.2-104336.3	0654-52146-011	A08	6595	6475	3.58	4.59	-2.49	-2.49	+2.50	+2.21
SDSS J012617.9+060724.8	2314-53713-090	A11	6850	6841	4.00	4.73	-3.05	-2.80	+3.02	+2.67
SDSS J025956.4+005713.3	1513-53741-338	A11	4750	4537	1.50	4.31	-2.45	-3.75	-0.18	+0.00
SDSS J030839.3+050534.9	2335-53730-314	A11	6150	5938	4.00	3.36	-1.99	-2.41	+2.26	+2.31
SDSS J035111.3+102643.2	2679-54368-543	A11	5650	5542	4.00	3.14	-2.87	-2.89	+1.44	+1.61
SDSS J071105.4+670128.2	2337-53740-564	A11	5250	5252	2.80	2.70	-2.91	-2.91	+1.98	+2.16
SDSS J072352.2+363757.2	2941-54507-222	A11	5000	5105	1.80	2.33	-3.49	-3.48	+1.96	+1.39
SDSS J074104.2+670801.8	2939-54515-414	A11	5000	5171	2.10	2.35	-3.03	-2.92	+0.80	+0.84
SDSS J081754.9+264103.8	1266-52709-432	A08	6213	6075	3.28	3.58	-2.88	-3.03	+1.19	< +1.54
SDSS J091243.7+021623.7	0471-51924-613	A11	6300	6138	4.00	3.40	-2.53	-2.76	+2.20	+2.33
SDSS J091243.7+021623.7	0471-51924-613	B10	6500	6138	4.50	3.40	-2.50	-2.76	+2.17	+2.33
SDSS J092401.9+405928.7	0938-52708-608	A08	6264	6201	3.67	4.53	-2.65	-2.81	+2.58	+2.56
SDSS J103649.9+121219.8	1600-53090-378	B10	6000	5873	4.00	3.12	-3.20	-3.31	+1.47	+1.94
SDSS J124123.9-083725.5	2689-54149-292	A11	4900	5108	1.80	2.45	-2.91	-2.90	+0.48	+0.65
SDSS J124204.4-033618.1	2897-54585-210	A11	4950	5112	2.00	2.56	-2.88	-3.02	+0.55	+0.77
SDSS J134913.5-022942.8	0913-52433-073	B10	6200	6132	4.00	4.46	-3.00	-3.04	+2.82	+2.49
SDSS J161226.2+042146.6	2178-54629-546	A11	5450	5365	4.00	2.42	-2.72	-3.19	+0.59	+0.98
SDSS J161313.5+530909.7	2176-54243-614	A11	5150	5338	1.60	2.67	-3.50	-2.89	+2.07	+1.64
SDSS J164610.2+282422.2	1690-53475-323	A11	6350	6125	4.00	3.45	-2.63	-2.78	+2.80	+2.53
SDSS J170339.6+283649.9	2808-54524-510	A11	4900	5120	4.80	3.58	-3.30	-3.32	+0.37	+0.43
SDSS J170733.9+585059.7	0353-51703-195	A08	6656	6567	3.19	3.47	-2.44	-2.68	+2.27	+2.43
SDSS J173417.9+431606.5	2799-54368-138	A11	5250	5172	2.80	2.15	-2.43	-3.18	+1.70	+2.43
SDSS J204728.8+001553.8	0982-52466-480	A08	6489	6324	3.76	3.77	-2.22	-2.28	+1.93	+1.98

Note. — A08: Aoki et al. (2008); B10: Behara et al. (2010); A11: W. Aoki et al. (in preparation). Note that the star SDSS J091243.7+021623.7 was reported on by both B10 and A11.

The agreement in estimates of the carbonicity is quite good ($\langle \Delta[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] \rangle = 0.03$ dex; $\sigma([\text{C}/\text{Fe}]) = 0.32$ dex), since we expect even the high-resolution determinations to be accurate to no better than about 0.10-0.15 dex.

4.2.2 Detections, Upper Limits, and First-Pass Frequencies of CEMP Stars

In this work there are 31187 unique stars for which estimates of [C/Fe] were carried out (other objects were either repeats, in which case they were averaged, had insufficient spectral S/N ratios, were clear cases of QSOs, cool white dwarfs, or very late-type stars, or had some spectral defect in the region of the G-band which prevented mea-

surements being obtained – all such stars are dropped from the subsequent analysis). This sample can be divided into two categories: stars that have a measured [C/Fe] (with the G-band detected; $N^D = 25647$), and stars for which only an upper limit on [C/Fe] has been obtained (G-band undetected; $N^L = 5540$). We call the associated two sets of stars subsample D and subsample L, respectively. Figure 4.3 shows [C/Fe] as a function of metallicity for the two categories, subsample D (top panel) and subsample L (bottom panel). The “ridge lines” in both of these plots are due to grid effects in the chi-square fitting procedure. It is worth noting that most of the stars with measured [C/Fe] (subsample D) exhibit carbonicity below [C/Fe] = +0.7, which appears to be a natural dividing threshold between carbon-normal stars and carbon-rich stars. Note that this limit was also established by Aoki et al. (2007b), by including in their analysis expected evolutionary effects on the definition of CEMP. We adopt this value of [C/Fe] to define the carbon-rich stars in our sample. There is an evident correlation between [C/Fe] and [Fe/H] seen in this figure, in particular for stars with [Fe/H] < -1.0. The relative number of stars with carbon excess increases as the metallicity decreases, as has been seen previously by numerous studies.

Adopting the definition of carbon-rich stars as above, we distinguish two subcategories within subsamples D and L: stars with [C/Fe] \leq +0.7 (C-norm), and stars with [C/Fe] > +0.7 (C-rich). In the case of subsample L, the carbon status for a star can be assessed with certainty only when [C/Fe] \leq +0.7, and remains unknown for stars having [C/Fe] > +0.7. Indeed, suppose that the limit assigned to a given star is [C/Fe]_{lim} = +1.5. Then, all values below [C/Fe]_{lim} can still be accepted for that star, including carbonicity well below [C/Fe] = +0.7. When the upper limit is below [C/Fe] = +0.7, however, the carbon status of the star can be assessed as C-norm. Not surprisingly, there is a strong temperature effect in the assessment of the carbon status for stars in our sample. For example, stars with higher T_{eff} (above $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 6250$ K) would require quite high [C/Fe] for the G-band to be detected; stars without a detected G-band are included in the L subsample. Thus, the fractions of CEMP stars we derive in this paper are lower limits to the true fractions. In a future paper we plan to obtain an explicit correction function to account for the “missing” stars due to this temperature effect.

Figure 4.3 Carbonicity, $[C/Fe]$, as a function of the metallicity, $[Fe/H]$, for subsample D (top panel) and subsample L (bottom panel). The dashed red line represents the solar carbon abundance ratio $[C/Fe] = 0.0$, while the solid red line denotes the adopted limit that divides C-norm stars from C-rich stars, $[C/Fe] = +0.7$. The “ridge lines” in both of these plots are due to grid effects in the chi-square fitting procedure.

Table 4.2. Numbers of Stars with Detected and Undetected G-Bands and Fractions of Carbon-Rich Stars

Metallicity	N_{C-norm}^D	N_{C-rich}^D	N_{C-norm}^L	N_{C-un}^L	F_{C-rich} %
$-1.5 < [Fe/H] \leq -1.0$	9113	149	335	3	1.6
$-2.0 < [Fe/H] \leq -1.5$	4376	377	2651	226	5.1
$-2.5 < [Fe/H] \leq -2.0$	506	173	1387	458	8.4
$-4.0 < [Fe/H] \leq -2.5$	13	46	201	201	18.0

Note. — *C-un* indicates stars with unknown carbon status (see text).

Taking into account the above definitions, the fraction of C-rich stars can be formulated as:

$$F_{C-rich} = \frac{N_{C-rich}^D}{N_{C-rich}^D + N_{C-norm}^D + N_{C-norm}^L} \quad (4.1)$$

where N_{C-norm}^D and N_{C-rich}^D are stars belonging to subsample D and having $[C/Fe] \leq +0.7$ and $[C/Fe] > +0.7$, respectively, while N_{C-norm}^L are stars in subsample L and having $[C/Fe] \leq +0.7$. Stars with unknown carbon status are not included in the above definition.

Table 4.2 reports the number of stars belonging to the various categories for different ranges of metallicity, as well as the total fractions of C-rich stars.

4.3 Selection of the Sample for Decomposition

We begin with the 31187 unique DR7 calibration stars for which estimates of $[C/Fe]$ exist, and with distances slightly revised from those presented in C07 and C10, as described below. Details concerning the nature of the calibration-star sample can be found in C10; here we recall a few facts concerning these stars that are of importance for the present analysis.

Spectra of the SDSS/SEGUE calibration stars were obtained to perform spectrophotometric corrections and to calibrate and remove the night-sky emission and absorption features (telluric absorption) from SDSS spectra. The spectrophotometric calibration stars cover the apparent magnitude range $15.5 < g_0 < 17.0$, and satisfy the color ranges $0.6 < (u-g)_0 < 1.2$; $0.0 < (g-r)_0 < 0.6$.⁴ The telluric calibration stars cover the same color ranges as the spectrophotometric calibration stars, but at fainter apparent magnitudes, in the range $17.0 < g_0 < 18.5$.

Estimates of the atmospheric parameters were obtained from the SEGUE Stellar Parameter Pipeline (SSPP; see Lee et al 2008a,b; Allende Prieto et al. 2008; Smolinski et al. 2011). Typical internal errors for stars in the temperature range that applies to the majority of the calibration stars are $\sigma(T_{\text{eff}}) \sim 125$ K, $\sigma(\log g) \sim 0.25$ dex, and $\sigma[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim 0.20$ dex. The external errors in these determinations are of similar size.

In C10, a correction was applied for the metallicity determinations of the SSPP, which we adopt here as well:

$$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C = -0.186 + 0.765 * [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A - 0.068 * [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A^2 \quad (4.2)$$

where $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A$ is the adopted metallicity from the SSPP, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C$ is the corrected metallicity. This polynomial has little effect on stars with metallicity greater than about $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.5$, but lowers the estimated metallicities for stars below this abundance by 0.1 to 0.2 dex. C10 describes the radial velocity estimates (with a precision of 5-20 km s^{-1} , depending on the S/N ratio of the spectrum, and with a negligible zero point offset), as well as photometric distance estimates, obtained by using the SSPP surface gravity estimate for luminosity classification, then following the procedures of Beers et al. (2000).

In a recently submitted paper, Schönrich et al. (2010) have criticized the Beers et al. (2000) method of distance determination, and the results of the C07 and C10 that relied on it. They claimed that the counter-rotating halo found in C07 and C10 is a result of biases in distance estimates for main-sequence dwarfs, and furthermore that the distance derivation is influenced by sorting a subset of the stars into incorrect positions in the color-magnitude diagram of an old, metal-poor population. In a rebuttal paper (Beers et al., in preparation), we demonstrate that their claims concerning dwarf distances are incorrect (due to their adoption of the wrong main-sequence absolute magnitude relationship from Ivezić et al. 2008). We have applied the procedure suggested in the rebuttal paper to reassign intermediate-gravity stars that were originally

⁴The subscript 0 in the magnitudes and colors indicates that they are corrected for the effects of interstellar absorption and reddening, based on the dust maps of Schlegel, Finkbeiner, & Davis (1998).

classified as main-sequence turnoff stars into dwarf or subgiant/giant luminosity classifications in cases where their derived T_{eff} were substantially lower than expected for the turnoff. Revised distances for these stars have been adopted as well. A reassessment of the kinematics indicates that the retrograde signal for the subsample at very low metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$) remains. The interested reader can find more details in Beers et al. (in preparation).

C10 applied a series of cuts to their sample, designed to better enable measurement of the kinematic and orbital properties of the various stellar populations considered. This produced a subsample of stars in the local volume (distance from the Sun $d < 4$ kpc and with $7 < R < 10$ kpc, where R is the Galactocentric distance projected onto the plane), which they referred to as the “Local Sample” ($N \sim 17000$). These restrictions were made in order to mitigate against the increase in the errors in the derived transverse velocities, which scale with distance from the Sun, and to improve the applicability of the simple models for the adopted form of the Galactic potential. For our present analysis we do not need to redetermine the velocity parameters of the underlying stellar populations, so we can relax these cuts somewhat. As described below, in order to increase the numbers of stars in our sample with measured $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$, we have relaxed the constraint on the distance from the Sun, to $d < 10$ kpc, and removed the constraint on the projected distance R . With these relaxed cuts the total number of stars climbs to 30874. We refer to this new sample as the “Extended Sample.”

The upper panel of Figure 4.4 shows the as-observed metallicity distribution function (MDF) for the DR7 calibration stars belonging to the Extended Sample (black histogram), as well as for stars in the Local Sample, as described above (red histogram). The MDFs of the two samples are clearly very similar, and comprise stars with metallicities that sample all of the primary stellar components of the Galaxy (with the exception of the bulge). The lower panel of Figure 4.4 is the distribution of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$ (estimated as described above), which we refer to as the Carbonicity Distribution Function (CarDF) for the Extended Sample (black histogram), and for the Local Sample (red histogram)⁵. The inset in the panel shows a rescaling appropriate for the high $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$ tail of this distribution. As in the case of the MDFs, the shape of the two CarDFs are similar, with a strong peak at 0.2-0.3, and two tails, one at low carbonicity ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] < 0$), and one that extends to high values, $+0.5 < [\text{C}/\text{Fe}] < +3.0$. The total number of stars with high carbonicity is significantly different in the two samples. Indeed, for the Extended Sample we find 728 stars with $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > +0.7$, while for the Local Sample the number is reduced to 318.

⁵We employ the term “carbonicity distribution function” to emphasize that we are describing the ratio of carbon to iron, rather than the carbon abundance distribution itself.

Figure 4.4 Upper panel: Metallicity Distribution Function (MDF), as-observed, for the Extended Sample of SDSS/SEGUE calibration stars (black histogram), and for the Local Sample (red histogram). Lower panel: Carbonicity Distribution Function (CarDF), as-observed, for the Extended Sample of calibration stars (black histogram), and for the Local Sample (red histogram). Note that the Extended Sample contains significant numbers of dwarfs, main-sequence turnoff stars and giants (77%, 13%, and 10%, respectively), while the local sample primarily comprises dwarfs (88%) and main-sequence turnoff stars (9%), due to the larger volume explored by the subgiants and giants. The inset shows a rescaled view of the high carbonicity tail.

4.3.1 As-Observed MDF and CarDF of the Extended Sample as a Function of the Height Above the Galactic Plane

We now examine the MDFs and the CarDFs of the Extended Sample of calibration stars for different intervals in $|Z|$, with cuts chosen to ensure there remain adequate numbers of stars in each interval. The first (left-hand) column and the third column of Figure 4.5 show the MDFs, while the second column and the fourth (right-hand) column are the CarDFs. In the first and third columns, the red arrows indicate the peak metallicities of the various stellar populations considered by C10. In the second and fourth column, the blue arrows show the location of the solar carbon-to-iron ratio ($[C/Fe] = 0.0$), and the location of the natural threshold that divides carbon-normal from carbon-rich stars ($[C/Fe] = +0.7$), as identified above.

Examination of the first column of panels in Figure 4.5 shows how the MDF changes from the upper left panel, in which there are obvious contributions from the thick-disk, the metal-weak thick disk (MWTD), and inner-halo components in the cuts close to the Galactic plane, to the lower left panel, with an MDF dominated primarily by inner-halo stars. In the third column of panels, with distances from the plane greater than 5 kpc, the transition from inner-halo dominance to a much greater contribution from outer-halo stars is clear. This demonstration is, by design, independent of any errors that might arise from derivation of the kinematic parameters, and provides confirmation of the difference in the chemical properties of the inner- and outer-halo populations originally suggested by C07. The second and fourth columns show the results of the same exercise for the CarDFs. Close to the Galactic plane (second column; up to $|Z| = 3$ kpc), where the thick disk and MWTD are the dominant components, the CarDF is strongly peaked at values between $[C/Fe] = 0.0$ and $[C/Fe] = +0.3$. The CarDFs of the thick disk and MWTD will be explored in a future paper. Here we simply note that in the regions close to the plane, where these components dominate the sample, there are not large numbers of stars populating regions of high carbonicity. At larger distances from the Galactic plane, where the inner halo begins to be the dominant component, there appears a tail in the carbonicity distribution towards higher values, $[C/Fe] > +0.5$. In the fourth column of panels, where the distance from the Galactic plane is $|Z| > 5$ kpc, and where we expect to see the beginning of the transition from inner-halo dominance to outer-halo dominance, the tails towards high $[C/Fe]$ values become even more evident. The CarDF exhibits a strong peak at $\sim +0.3$ and a long tail towards high values of carbonicity, up to $[C/Fe] = +3.0$. The nature of the CarDF is likely to be influenced by the change of the MDF as a function of the distance from the Galactic plane, due the well-known trend of increasing $[C/Fe]$ with declining $[Fe/H]$.

Figure 4.5 First and third columns: As-observed metallicity distribution functions (MDFs) for the Extended Sample of SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration stars as a function of vertical distance from the Galactic plane. The histograms represent the MDFs obtained at different cuts of $|Z|$. The red arrows denote the locations of the metallicity peaks of the MDF for the thick disk (-0.6), the MWTD (~ -1.3), the inner halo (-1.6), and the outer halo (-2.2), respectively, assigned by C10. Second and fourth columns: As-observed carbonicity distribution functions (CarDFs) for the Extended Sample of SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration stars as a function of vertical distance from the Galactic plane. The blue arrows shows the location of the solar value of carbon-to-iron ratio ($[C/Fe] = 0.0$), and the natural threshold that divides carbon-normal from carbon-rich stars ($[C/Fe] = +0.7$). The histograms represent the CarDFs obtained at different cuts of $|Z|$.

However, as discussed below, there is evidence that the observed changes may reflect real changes in the chemistry of the inner- and outer-halo populations, even at a given (low) metallicity.

By adopting the threshold of $[C/Fe] > +0.7$, the fraction of SDSS/SEGUE calibration stars with high carbonicity in the subsample at $|Z| > 9$ is 20%, (which, as argued above, is a lower limit), in line with previous estimates for stars with $[Fe/H] < -2.0$.

4.4 Extreme Deconvolution and Membership Probabilities

C07 and C10 have shown that, in the relatively nearby volume explored by the SDSS/SEGUE calibration-star sample, the two stellar components of the Galactic halo are strongly overlapped in their spatial distribution, velocity ellipsoids, and MDFs. Thus, to explore possible differences in the frequencies of carbon-enhanced-metal-poor stars, it is essential to assign inner- and outer-halo membership probabilities to each star in the sample that is likely to belong to the halo system. We describe how this is accomplished in the sections below.

4.4.1 Basic Parameters

In the solar neighborhood, the set of parameters that best identify the presence of the main structures are the distance from the Galactic plane, the rotational velocity of a star in a cylindrical frame with respect to the Galactic center, and the stellar metallicity (see C10). For consideration of the disk system of the Galaxy, the distance from the Galactic plane is best represented by $|Z|$ (the present distance of a star above or below the Galactic plane), while for the halo components, a more suitable distance is Z_{max} (the maximum distance of a stellar orbit above or below the Galactic plane), which depends on the adopted gravitational potential. The choice of Z_{max} for the Galactic halo is necessary because of the much larger spatial extent of its two primary components, relative to that of the disk components.

Before seeking a deconvolution, we need to check for possible correlations between all the basic parameters we wish to employ. In C10 we have shown that Z_{max} has a significant correlation with V_R and V_Z , but not with V_ϕ , other than that expected from the presence of the thick-disk population at high positive rotation velocity and the halo at lower rotational velocity. A very similar behavior is confirmed for the Extended Sample as well (Figure 4.6). We conclude that the Galactocentric rotational velocity,

V_ϕ , and the vertical distance, Z_{max} , when combined with metallicity, can be used to obtain useful information on the different stellar populations present in the Extended Sample.

The primary chemical parameter of the present analysis is the carbonicity, $[C/Fe]$, so it is important to check for its possible correlations with the basic parameters defined above. The result of this exercise is shown in Figure 4.7. Here, the upper panel shows the Galactocentric rotational velocity as a function of metallicity for the Extended Sample. The gray dots represent the stars in the sample with $[C/Fe] < +0.7$, while the red dots denote the stars with enhanced carbonicity, $[C/Fe] > +0.7$. It is worth noting that the stars with $[C/Fe] > +0.7$ are *almost all* located in the halo components of the Galaxy, with few exceptions. The middle panel of Figure 4.7 shows the Galactocentric rotational velocity as a function of $[C/Fe]$. This plot shows no evidence of correlation between V_ϕ and $[C/Fe]$. Finally, the lower panel of Figure 4.7 represents $[Fe/H]$ as a function of $[C/Fe]$. Here, there is clear evidence of a correlation between $[Fe/H]$ and $[C/Fe]$: the carbonicity increases as the metallicity decreases. A similar trend was already noticed in past works, such as Beers et al. (1992), where the authors found that $\sim 10\%$ of stars with $[Fe/H] \leq -2.0$ exhibited strong CH G-bands, as confirmed by other work since. We have evaluated the as-observed fractions of carbon-rich stars in our Extended Sample over several bins in metallicity. With the adopted definition of carbon-rich stars ($[C/Fe] > +0.7$), and following Eqn. 4.1, we find that 1%, 6%, and 18% of stars in the intervals $-1.5 < [Fe/H] < -0.5$, $-2.5 < [Fe/H] < -1.5$, and $[Fe/H] < -2.5$, are carbon-rich, respectively.

It is not surprising that most of the stars with $[C/Fe] > +0.7$ are found in the halo components of the Milky way, because they are very metal poor. We also notice that, in the very metal-poor regime ($[Fe/H] < -2.0$), the observed over-abundance of carbon increases as the metallicity decreases, which may be due to shifts in the stellar populations from inner to outer halo. The outer halo has a peak of metallicity at $[Fe/H] \sim -2.2$ (C07; C10); the large fraction of CEMP stars at low metallicity may be related to the much larger fraction of such stars associated with the outer-halo component. This issue is investigated more thoroughly below.

Figure 4.6 The relationship between Z_{\max} and the cylindrical velocity components (V_R, V_ϕ, V_Z) for the SDSS/SEGUE calibration stars in the Extended Sample. The strong correlation between Z_{\max} and the radial velocity component shown in the upper panel, V_R , as well as with the vertical velocity component shown in the lower panel, V_Z , is confirmed for the Extended Sample. The middle panel exhibits no strong correlation between Z_{\max} and the rotational velocity component, V_ϕ , other than that expected from the presence of the thick-disk and halo populations. The dashed line is a reference line at zero velocity for each component. Note, in the middle panel, the clear excess of stars with retrograde motions for $Z_{\max} > 10$ -15 kpc, which we associate with the outer-halo component.

Figure 4.7 Global behavior of the basic parameters, V_ϕ , $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, and $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$, for the Extended Sample of SDSS/SEGUE calibration stars with detected CH G-bands. Upper panel: Galactocentric rotational velocity as a function of the metallicity. Middle panel: Galactocentric rotational velocity as a function of $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$. Lower panel: Metallicity vs. carbonicity. In all panels, the gray dots represent stars with low carbonicity, $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] < +0.7$, while the red dots denote the stars with high carbonicity, $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > +0.7$.

4.4.2 CEMP Fractions in the Low Metallicity Regime: Global Behavior

The top panel of Figure 4.8 shows the fraction of CEMP stars in the Extended Sample, as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, in the metal-poor regime ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.4$), and at vertical distance $Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc (chosen to avoid thick-disk contamination). Here, each bin in metallicity corresponds to an interval of $\Delta[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.2$ dex, with the exception of the last bin, where stars are selected in the range $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.6$. The fractions of CEMP stars in each bin are obtained by selecting objects with $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > +0.7$, and application of Eqn. 4.1. Errors on the CEMP fraction are evaluated through the jackknife approach. This technique is similar to bootstrapping, but instead of sampling with replacement, it recomputes the statistical estimate leaving out one observation at a time from the sample (Wall & Jenkins 2003). The dash-dotted line is a second order polynomial fit to the data.

The increase of the fraction of CEMP stars with declining metallicity seen in the top panel of Figure 4.8 pertains to the global behavior of the data in the metal-poor regime. If metallicity alone is the driver of the carbon-enhancement phenomenon, one might wonder if the strong increase in the fraction of CEMP stars at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ could be due to the increasing importance of the outer-halo component, which has a peak of metallicity at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.2$ and a long tail extending to much lower metallicity.

The bottom panel of Figure 4.8 shows the fraction of CEMP stars in the Extended Sample as a function of distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$, for stars satisfying $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.4$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$, respectively. The CEMP star fractions in each bin are obtained by applying the same criteria and definitions for the top panel, and indicate a clear dependence of the CEMP star fraction on distance from the Galactic plane. At these low metallicities, significant contamination of the sample from thick-disk or MWTD stars is not expected; the observed fractions must pertain to the halo system alone. The observed increase of the CEMP star fractions with $|Z|$ would be difficult to understand if the halo system represents a single population. In such a case, one might expect the CEMP star fractions to be roughly constant, as a function of $|Z|$, for any given cut in metallicity. From inspection of this panel, this is clearly not what the data show.

A similar trend of increasing CEMP star fraction with height above the Galactic plane was previously suggested by Frebel et al. (2006), based on a much smaller sample of stars from the Hamburg/ESO survey (Wisotzki et al. 2000; Christlieb 2003). Our expanded data set now clearly indicates the existence of a strong spatial variation of CEMP star frequency *within the halo system*, and suggests that the observed carbon

Figure 4.8 Top panel: Global trend of the CEMP fraction as a function of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, for the metal-poor stars of the Extended Sample with $Z_{\max} > 5 \text{ kpc}$. Each bin of metallicity has width $\Delta[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.2 \text{ dex}$, with the exception of the lowest-metallicity bin, which includes all stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.6$. The error bars are evaluated with the jackknife method. Bottom panel: Global trend of the CEMP star fraction as a function of distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$, for the low metallicity stars of the Extended Sample. The stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.4$ are shown as filled circles, while those with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$ are shown as purple stars. Each bin has a width of $\Delta|Z| = 1 \text{ kpc}$, with the exceptions of the last bins, which are 2 kpc in width; errors are derived using the jackknife approach.

enhancement is unlikely to be purely driven by metallicity alone. Rather, it points to a real difference in CEMP star fractions associated with the inner- and outer-halo populations, and opens the possibility for different carbon production mechanisms and/or different chemical evolutionary histories within their progenitors. We return to this question below, after considering a method to probabilistically classify individual stars as likely inner- or outer-halo members.

4.4.3 The Extreme Deconvolution Technique

Inference of the distribution function of an observable given only a finite, noisy set of measurements of that distribution is a problem of significant interest in many areas of science, and in astronomy in particular. The observed distribution of a parameter is just the starting point, but what is desired is knowledge of the distribution that we would have in the case of very small uncertainties of the data and with all of the dimensions of the parameter measured; in other words, the closest representation of the underlying distribution. Usually, the data never have these two properties, and it is then challenging to find the underlying distribution without taking into account the uncertainty of the data (Bovy, Hogg, & Roweis 2009; hereafter BHR09). The Extreme Deconvolution (XD) technique of BHR09 confronts all of these issues and provides an accurate description of the underlying distribution of a d -dimensional quantity by taking into account the potentially large and heterogeneous observational uncertainties, as well as missing dimensions.

BHR09 have generalized the well known mixtures-of-Gaussians density-estimation method to the case of noisy, heterogeneous, and incomplete data. In this method, the underlying distribution of a quantity \mathbf{v} is modeled as a sum of K Gaussian distributions

$$(4.3) \quad p(\mathbf{v}) = \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j N(\mathbf{v} | \mathbf{m}_j, \mathbf{V}_j),$$

where the function $N(\mathbf{v} | \mathbf{m}_j, \mathbf{V}_j)$ is the d -dimensional Gaussian distribution with mean \mathbf{m} and variance tensor \mathbf{V} and α_j are the amplitudes, normalized to sum to unity (all of these parameters are grouped together as θ in what follows). The data \mathbf{w}_i are assumed to be noisy samples from this distribution

$$(4.4) \quad \mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{v}_i + \text{noise},$$

where the noise is drawn from a normal distribution with zero mean and known covariance matrix \mathbf{S}_i . Here and in what follows, we ignore the projection matrices \mathbf{R}_i of BHR09, since the data we will apply this technique to are complete.

The likelihood of the model for each data point is given by the model convolved with the uncertainty distribution of that data point. Since a Gaussian distribution convolved with another Gaussian distribution is again a Gaussian, the likelihood for each data point is a sum of Gaussian distributions

$$(4.5) \quad p(\mathbf{w}_i|\theta) = \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j N(\mathbf{w}_i|\mathbf{m}_j, \mathbf{T}_{ij})$$

where

$$(4.6) \quad \mathbf{T}_{ij} = \mathbf{V}_j + \mathbf{S}_i.$$

The objective function is the total likelihood, obtained by simply multiplying the individual likelihoods together for the various data points

$$(4.7) \quad \ln \mathcal{L} = \sum_i \ln p(\mathbf{w}_i|\theta) = \sum_i \ln \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j N(\mathbf{w}_i|\mathbf{m}_j, \mathbf{T}_{ij}).$$

The optimization of this objective function provides the maximum likelihood estimate of the distribution, or its parameters. BHR09 develop a fast and robust algorithm to optimize the likelihood, based on an adaptation of the expectation-maximization algorithm⁶ (Dempster et al. 1977).

The XD technique provides the best-fit values of the amplitude, mean, and standard deviation of each Gaussian component, as well as the so called *posterior probability* that the observed data point \mathbf{w}_i is drawn from the component j . The posterior probability is given by

$$(4.8) \quad p_{ij} = \frac{\alpha_j N(\mathbf{w}_i|\mathbf{m}_j, \mathbf{T}_{ij})}{\sum_k \alpha_k N(\mathbf{w}_i|\mathbf{m}_k, \mathbf{T}_{ik})},$$

(see BHR09 for the derivation of this formula). The posterior probability is a powerful statistical tool to perform probabilistic assignments of stars to a Gaussian component in the model distribution. In Galactic studies, the Gaussian component could represent a primary structural component such as a disk or halo, a moving group, or a spatial or velocity overdensity.

In many respects the XD technique described above is similar to the maximum likelihood technique adopted in C10, but is more general, because it takes into account the uncertainties of the measurements and provides the membership probabilities.

⁶Code implementing this algorithm is available at <http://code.google.com/p/extreme-deconvolution/>.

Figure 4.9 Rotational properties of the Extended Sample of SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration stars with metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc. Upper panel: The black histogram represents the observed distribution of V_{ϕ} , while the green (inner halo), and red (outer halo) curves show the results of the Extreme Deconvolution analysis. Middle panel: The observed velocity distribution function (black histogram), and the inner and outer halo weighted velocity distribution functions (frequencies), denoted by the green and the red histograms, respectively. In this panel, all the distributions are normalized and take into account the membership probability of each star. Lower panel: The posterior probability for the inner- and outer-halo components as a function of the rotational velocity, V_{ϕ} .

4.4.4 Application to the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 Calibration Stars

The basic parameters for application of the XD approach for the analysis at hand are the Galactocentric rotational velocity, V_ϕ , the maximum vertical distance, Z_{max} , and the metallicity, $[Fe/H]$. We employ the XD technique to determine the underlying distribution of the rotational velocity of halo stars and to determine the posterior membership probabilities for each star. In practice, the entries for the XD algorithm are the Galactocentric rotational velocity and its uncertainty for each star, $V_{\phi,i}$ and $\varepsilon_{V_{\phi,i}}$, respectively. These two parameters, together with all the other kinematic and orbital quantities, are derived by using the same procedures employed by C07 and C10 (but with revised distances for the reassigned main-sequence turnoff stars, as mentioned previously).

Our plan is to make use of a sample in which the constraint on the distance from the Sun, d , and on the projected Galactic distance, R , are relaxed (in order to take advantage of the larger numbers of CEMP stars in the Extended Sample). As a consequence, the data set becomes noisier than the Local Sample, because uncertainties on the transverse velocities increase with the distance d . In the terminology of the XD approach, the analysis of the Extended Sample falls into the case where all the observables are known, but some of the derived parameters have large uncertainties.

The Galactic halo is assumed to be a two-component structure, comprising the inner and the outer halo, as discussed in C07 and C10. Thus, the general expression for the likelihood takes the form:

$$(4.9) \quad \ln \mathcal{L} = \sum_i \ln[\alpha_{in} \cdot N_{in}^i + \alpha_{out} \cdot N_{out}^i],$$

where α_{in} and α_{out} are the amplitude of the inner halo and outer halo, respectively. The velocity distributions are assumed to be Gaussian, thus

$$(4.10) \quad N_{in/out}^i = N(V_{\phi,i} | V_{\phi,in/out}, \sigma_{\phi,in/out}^2 + \varepsilon_{V_{\phi,i}}^2),$$

The membership probabilities then take the form:

$$(4.11) \quad p_{i,in} = \frac{\alpha_{in} N_{in}^i}{\alpha_{in} N_{in}^i + \alpha_{out} N_{out}^i}$$

and

$$(4.12) \quad p_{i,out} = \frac{\alpha_{out} N_{out}^i}{\alpha_{in} N_{in}^i + \alpha_{out} N_{out}^i}$$

for the i th star.

4.4.4.1 Extreme Deconvolution Results for the Extended Sample

In this section the *posterior probabilities* derived through the application of the XD are obtained for the Extended Sample ($d < 10$ kpc, no constraints on R), selected in the range of metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, and with vertical distance $Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc. The results are shown in Figure 4.9. In this figure, the upper panel shows the observed velocity distribution function (black histogram), while the green and red curves represent the resulting Gaussian velocity distributions for the inner- and outer-halo components. The middle panel shows the derived velocity distribution for the two components, obtained by weighting each star with its membership probability, and normalized such that the total area corresponds to unity. The black histogram is the observed distribution as in the top panel, but normalized to unity as well. In the lower panel, the posterior probability as a function of the rotational velocity, V_ϕ , is shown. This probability has been obtained using Eqns. 4.10 and 4.11. For each star in the sample, the XD technique assigns two probability values, the first associated to the inner halo, and the second related to the outer halo. Since in our model a star is required to belong to one or the other component (there are no orphans allowed), and the summed inner- and outer-halo posterior probabilities are forced to unity at each point, the two curves simply complement one another.

The values obtained for the mean rotational velocity and its dispersion are, for the inner halo, $V_\phi = 56 \pm 11$ km s⁻¹, and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 93 \pm 35$ km s⁻¹; for the outer halo, $V_\phi = -141 \pm 31$ km s⁻¹, and $\sigma_{V_\phi} = 138 \pm 58$ km s⁻¹. The errors on the velocity and its dispersion have been evaluated by employing the jackknife method. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test of the null hypothesis that the velocity distributions of stars belonging to the inner- and outer-halo components could be drawn from the same parent population is rejected at a high level of statistical significance ($p < 0.001$).

4.4.5 Contrast of CEMP Stellar Fractions in the Two Halo Components

We now consider the distribution of carbonicity ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$) for the Extended Sample with metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and at $Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc. These selections ensure the presence of essentially all halo stars in the sample, with little or no contamination expected from the thick disk or MWTD⁷.

The top panel of Figure 4.10 shows the CarDF for the Extended Sample. There

⁷Note that the number of stars shown in Figure 4.10 differs from the numbers shown in Figure 4.9, as Figure 4.10 includes only stars with detected G-band features.

are two clear peaks that emerge, one at $[C/Fe] \sim +0.3$, and the second around $[C/Fe] \sim +1.8$, along with a tail extending towards higher values of carbonicity. The bottom panel of Figure 4.10 shows the weighted CarDFs for the inner- and outer-halo components. The underlying distribution of each population has been obtained by weighting the values of the CarDF with the membership probabilities of each star. As usual, the green distribution denotes the inner halo, while the red distribution represents the outer halo. A K-S test of the null hypothesis that the CarDF of stars belonging to the inner- and outer-halo components could be drawn from the same parent population is rejected at high statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). The KS test clearly suggests that the carbon distribution functions of the inner- and outer-halo components are distinct.

The contrast of the CEMP star fractions in the inner- and outer-halo components can be investigated by applying the XD analysis to subsamples of stars in restricted ranges of metallicity. The stars employed are those belonging to the Extended Sample, selected in the low metallicity range ($[Fe/H] < -1.4$) and with $Z_{max} > 5$ kpc.

A first attempt was made by selecting stars in intervals of metallicity such that $\Delta[Fe/H] = 0.2$ dex, and applying the XD technique to the rotational velocity distribution of each subsample. This experiment was not successful, due to the low number of stars in each bin. A much better result has been obtained by choosing a larger interval on metallicity, $\Delta[Fe/H] = 0.5$ dex.

Figure 4.11 shows the global trend of the CEMP star fraction (subsection 4.4.2), as a function of metallicity (black dot-dashed curve), overplotted with the derived inner- and outer-halo CEMP star fractions. The blue filled stars represent the predicted values of the CEMP star fractions for each bin of metallicity, i.e. $-2.0 < [Fe/H] < -1.5$, $-2.5 < [Fe/H] < -2.0$, and $-3.0 < [Fe/H] < -2.5$ (hereafter bin1, bin2, and bin3). The predicted values are derived using the global trend of CEMP star fractions vs. $[Fe/H]$ (second order polynomial; Fig. 4.8), and the posterior probability for each star in the subsamples associated with each bin of metallicity, such that:

$$F_{CEMP_{pred}}^k = \frac{1}{\sum_i (p_{ij})} \cdot \sum_i (p_{ij} f^k) \quad (4.13)$$

where p_{ij} is the posterior probability, derived by applying the XD analysis to the subsample of stars selected in bin1, bin2, and bin3, respectively. The parameter f^k represents the CEMP star fractions obtained in each bin of metallicity from application of the second order polynomial (j and k denote the halo component and the bin of metallicity, respectively).

Figure 4.10 The carbonicity distribution functions (CarDF) for the Extended Sample with $[Fe/H] < -2.0$ and $Z_{max} > 5$ kpc. Top panel: CarDF for the entire sample. Bottom panel: Weighted CarDF for the inner- and outer-halo components, shown by the green and red histograms, respectively.

Figure 4.11 Global trend of the CEMP star fraction as a function of the metallicity, and for the metal-poor stars of the Extended Sample with $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc. The blue dash-dotted curve denotes the second order polynomial fit representing the global trend. The blue filled circles denote the predicted values of the CEMP fractions in each bin of metallicity, having a width of $\Delta[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.5$ dex. The green and red filled circles show the location of the observed CEMP star fractions for the inner halo and outer halo, respectively. The error bars are evaluated with the *jackknife* method.

Note that the expression in Eqn. 4.13 provides an estimate of the CEMP fraction that is driven by the global trend of F_{CEMP} as a function of the metallicity (Fig. 4.8, top panel). Eqn. 4.13 makes use of the full shape of the posterior probability, and thus, a considerable overlap between the kinematic distributions of the two components is still present. Therefore, we are not expecting to find a significant difference in the predicted values for the two components in each bin of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$.

The predicted value of CEMP star fractions in bin1 is $F_{CEMP_{pred,in,1}} = (5.8 \pm 0.03)\%$, $F_{CEMP_{pred,out,1}} = (5.9 \pm 0.03)\%$, for the inner halo and outer halo, respectively. The same calculations for bin2 provide $F_{CEMP_{pred,in,2}} = (11.9 \pm 0.1)\%$ and $F_{CEMP_{pred,out,2}} = (12.0 \pm 0.1)\%$. For the third bin we find $F_{CEMP_{pred,in,3}} = (22.9 \pm 0.6)\%$ and $F_{CEMP_{pred,out,3}} = (22.7 \pm 0.6)\%$. The error on each fraction is evaluated by employing the jackknife method.

Not surprisingly, the above predicted values of the CEMP star fractions in the inner and outer halo are very similar in all bins of metallicity. The presence of a contrast in the CEMP star fraction for the two components can be better investigated by reducing the overlap in the kinematic distributions. This can be done by employing the *hard-cut-in-probability* method. For each halo component, the lower limit of the membership probability is chosen to be $p_{lim} = 0.7$. This limit is set reasonably high to reduce the contamination between the halo components. We have selected two subsamples of stars such that, $p_{i,inner} > p_{lim}$, and $p_{i,outer} > p_{lim}$ (i denotes the star), and for each subsample, the CEMP star fraction is evaluated following Eqn. 4.1.

The result of this exercise is shown in Figure 4.11. Here, the green (inner) and the red (outer) filled circles denote the values of the CEMP star fractions obtained by employing the hard-cut-in-probability method. The *observed* CEMP star fractions in bin1 are, $F_{CEMP_{obs,in,1}} = (5.2 \pm 0.6)\%$ and $F_{CEMP_{obs,out,1}} = (7.7 \pm 1.0)\%$, for the inner and outer halo, respectively. In the case of bin2, we find $F_{CEMP_{obs,in,2}} = (9.4 \pm 0.8)\%$ and $F_{CEMP_{obs,out,2}} = (20.3 \pm 2.3)\%$. Finally, in the third bin, the observed fractions are, $F_{CEMP_{obs,in,3}} = (20.5 \pm 2.4)\%$ and $F_{CEMP_{obs,out,3}} = (30.4 \pm 4.8)\%$.

In the highest metallicity bin, $-2.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, the CEMP star fractions for the two halo components are close to the expected value ($\sim 6\%$), with overlapping error bars. Note that the inner halo is the dominant component in this range of metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{peak,in} = -1.6$), and we were not expecting to find a high contrast in the CEMP star fractions. At lower metallicity, $-2.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, where the dominant component is the outer halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{peak,out} = -2.2$), there is evidence of a significant contrast in CEMP fractions between the inner- and outer-halo components, such that $F_{CEMP_{obs,out,2}} \sim 2 \times F_{CEMP_{obs,in,2}}$. This contrast is confirmed also in the lowest bin of metallicity, $-3.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.5$, even though it is less remarkable, $F_{CEMP_{obs,out,3}} \sim 1.5 \times F_{CEMP_{obs,in,3}}$, and has a much larger error bar.

It is important to note that most of the stars in the lowest metallicity bin belong to the category for which only an upper limit of $[C/Fe]$ has been provided (classified as "L", see subsection 4.2.2). A significant number of stars in the lowest metallicity bin have high T_{eff} ($\sim 65\%$ above ~ 6250 K), and thus only quite high values of $[C/Fe]$ are expected to be detected. Thus, it is our expectation that the quoted frequencies for CEMP star fractions, at least at low metallicity, represent lower limits. Moreover, the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration-star sample has a limited number of stars with $[Fe/H] < -2.5$. The extremely metal-poor regime will be further investigated in a future paper using the much larger sample of such stars in the SDSS/SEGUE DR8 release (Aihara et al. 2011).

4.5 Summary and Discussion

We have analyzed the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration stars in order to explore the global properties of the carbonicity distribution function ($[C/Fe]$; CarDF) of the halo components of the Milky Way, and the possible contrast of CEMP star fractions between the inner halo and the outer halo. Carbon abundance estimates have been obtained for 31187 stars, based on fits of the CH G-band at 4305 \AA , with a mean error on $[C/Fe]$ of the order of 0.2 dex. Kinematic and orbital parameters were derived employing the methodologies described in C10. A deconvolution of the inner- and outer-halo components, along with derivation of the membership probabilities for each star, has been obtained by applying the Extreme Deconvolution (XD) analysis to the Extended Sample of calibration stars, selected in the low metallicity range ($[Fe/H] < -1.4$) and with $Z_{\text{max}} > 5$ kpc. Contrasts of the CEMP star fractions have been obtained by employing the hard-cut-in-probability method to subsamples of stars selected in several bins of metallicity.

4.5.1 Summary of Main Results

Our main results are the following:

- The as-observed distribution of $[C/Fe]$, which we refer to as the Carbonicity Distribution Function (CarDF), has been derived at various intervals on distance above or below the Galactic plane. At $|Z| > 5$ kpc, where we expect to see the beginning of the transition from inner-halo dominance to outer-halo dominance among halo stars, the CarDF exhibits a strong peak at $\sim +0.3$ and a long tail towards high values of carbonicity, up to $[C/Fe] = +3.0$. The fraction of CEMP

stars (defined here to mean $[C/Fe] > +0.7$) for the subsample at $|Z| > 9$ kpc (where the dominant component is the outer halo) is 20%, in agreement with previous estimates for stars at similarly low metallicities, $[Fe/H] < -2.0$.

- *Almost all* the CEMP stars are located in the halo components of the Milky Way.
- We observe a significant increase of the fraction of CEMP stars with declining metallicity. Following Eqn. 4.1, we find that 1%, 6%, and 18% of stars in the intervals $-1.5 < [Fe/H] < -0.5$, $-2.5 < [Fe/H] < -1.5$, and $[Fe/H] < -2.5$, are carbon-rich, respectively.
- In the low metallicity regime, $[Fe/H] < -1.4$, and at vertical distances $Z_{max} > 5$ kpc, a continued increase of the fraction of CEMP stars with declining metallicity is found (Fig. 4.8, top panel). A second-order polynomial provides a good fit to the CEMP star fraction.
- In the low metallicity regime, for both $[Fe/H] < -1.4$ and $[Fe/H] < -1.8$, we find a clear increase in the CEMP star fraction with distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$ (Fig. 4.8, bottom panel). At these low metallicities, contamination from the thick-disk and MWTD populations is unlikely; this is an observed property of the halo system.
- The Extreme Deconvolution technique of BHR09 has been applied to subsamples of stars selected in three bins of metallicity, $-2.0 < [Fe/H] < -1.5$, $-2.5 < [Fe/H] < -2.0$, and $-3.0 < [Fe/H] < -2.5$, and with $Z_{max} > 5$ kpc. We have successfully decomposed the inner and outer halo in all three bins, and obtained the inner- and outer-halo membership probabilities for each star.
- At low metallicity, $-2.5 < [Fe/H] < -2.0$, where the dominant component is the outer halo ($[Fe/H]_{peak,out} = -2.2$), there is evidence for a significant contrast in the CEMP star fraction between the inner and the outer halo, such that $F_{CEMP_{obs,out,2}} \sim 2 \times F_{CEMP_{obs,in,2}}$. The contrast is confirmed also in the lowest metallicity bin, $-3.0 < [Fe/H] < -2.5$, even though it is less remarkable, $F_{CEMP_{obs,out,3}} \sim 1.5 \times F_{CEMP_{obs,in,3}}$, and has a larger error bar.

4.5.2 Implications for Galaxy Formation

A possible scenario for the formation of the inner- and the outer-halo components has been described in C07. The fact that the outer-halo component of the Milky Way exhibits a net retrograde rotation (and a different distribution of overall orbital properties), clearly indicates that the formation of the outer halo is distinct from that of the inner halo and the disk components. In C07, it was suggested that the outer-halo component formed, not through a dissipative, angular-momentum conserving contraction, but rather through dissipationless chaotic merging of smaller subsystem within a pre-existing dark matter halo. These subsystems would be expected to be of much lower mass, and subject to tidal disruption in the outer part of a dark matter halo, before they fall farther into the inner part. As candidate (surviving) counterparts for such subsystems, one might consider the low luminosity dwarf spheroidal galaxies surrounding the Milky Way. In the case of the inner halo, C07 argued that the low-mass sub-Galactic fragments formed at an early stage rapidly merge into several more massive clumps, which themselves eventually dissipatively merge (owing of the presence of gas that had yet to form stars). The essentially radial merger of the few resulting massive clumps gives rise to the dominance of the high-eccentricity orbits for stars that we assign to membership in the inner halo. Star formation within these massive clumps (both pre- and post-merger) would drive the mean metallicity to higher abundances. This would be followed by a stage of adiabatic compression (flattening) of the inner halo component owing to the growth of a massive disk, along with the continue accretion of the gas onto the Galaxy. This general picture is supported, at least qualitatively, by the most recent numerical simulations of the formation and evolution of large disk galaxies (e.g., Font et al. 2011).

The observed large fraction of CEMP stars in both halo components indicates that significant amounts of carbon were produced in the early stages of chemical evolution in the Universe. The observed contrast of CEMP star fractions in the inner- and outer halo strengthen the picture that the halo components had different origins, and supports a scenario in which the outer-halo component has been assembled by the accretion of small subsystems. In this regard, it is interesting that the MDF of the inner halo (peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$) is in the metallicity regime associated with the CEMP-s stars, which are primarily found with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.5$, while the MDF of the outer halo (peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.2$), might be associated with the metallicity regime of the CEMP-no stars, which are primarily found with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.5$ (Aoki et al. 2007b).

The fact that, in the metal-poor regime, the outer halo exhibits a fraction of CEMP stars that is larger than the inner halo ($\text{CEMP}_{outer} \sim 2 \cdot \text{CEMP}_{inner}$), suggests that mul-

multiple sources of carbon, besides the nucleosynthesis of AGB stars in binary systems, were present in the pristine environment of the outer-halo progenitors (lower mass sub-halos). These sources could be the fast massive rotators and/or the faint supernovae mentioned in the Introduction. Karlsson (2006) also explored the possibility that primordial gas was pre-enriched in heavy metals by less massive SNe ($13 < M/M_{\odot} < 30$), whose ejecta underwent substantial mixing and fallback, while the C (and N, O) originated from massive rotating stars with $M \geq 40 M_{\odot}$. If the CEMP stars in the outer halo are predominantly CEMP-no stars (which has yet to be established), it might suggest that non-AGB-related carbon production took place in the primordial mini-halos. The predominance of CEMP-s stars in the inner halo, if found, would suggest that the dominant source of carbon was the nucleosynthesis in AGB stars in a binary system. This would place important constraints on the primordial IMF of the sub-systems responsible for the formation of the two halo components.

Recent efforts to model, from the population synthesis standpoint, the fractions of observed CEMP stars in the halo have struggled to reproduce results as high as 15-20% for metallicities $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ (e.g., Izzard et al. 2009; Pols et al. 2010). However, note that these predictions are based solely on carbon production by AGB stars. While such calculations may prove meaningful for the inner-halo population, they may not be telling the full story for carbon production associated with the progenitors of the outer-halo population. Indeed, the observed increase of the CEMP star fraction with $|Z|$ we have found would be difficult to understand if the halo system represents a single population. In any event, the lower CEMP fraction in the inner halo may relieve some of the tension with current model predictions.

The fact that the CEMP star fraction exhibits a clear increase with $|Z|$ could suggest that the relative numbers of CEMP stars in a stellar population is not driven by metallicity alone. The proposed coupling of the cosmic microwave background to the initial mass function (CMB-IMF hypothesis; Larson 1998, 2005; Tumlinson 2007) is one mechanism for imposing a temporal dependence on the IMF. This effect, coupled with chemical evolution models, predicts that the CEMP fraction would be expected to increase as the metallicity decreases, but with similar metallicity regimes forming carbon according to the expected yields of the predominant mass range available at that time. In the hierarchical context of galaxy formation, star forming regions are spatially segregated, and their chemical evolution can proceed at different rates, with stars at the same metallicity forming at different times. Depending on the source(s) of carbon, this trend could predict a spatial variation of the CEMP fraction at the same metallicity, increasing in older populations and decreasing in younger ones.

The larger fraction of CEMP stars associated with the outer-halo component could

be due to the nature of the progenitor low-mass mini-halos (mass, density, etc.) in which they formed. A natural place to look for them are the ultra-faint dwarf spheroidal galaxies surrounding the Milky Way discovered in the course of the SDSS (Willman et al. 2005; Belokurov et al. 2006a,b; Zucker et al. 2006, and many others since). Early hints of the possible association of CEMP stars with the ultra faint galaxies came from the recognition that a (serendipitously) spectroscopically targeted star from SDSS in the direction of the Canes Venatici ultra-faint dwarf, SDSS J132755.56+333521.7, is a carbon-rich giant with a radial velocity and inferred distance commensurate with this very metal-poor satellite galaxy (Zucker et al. 2006). The existence of CEMP stars in ultra-faint dwarf spheroidal galaxies has now been definitively established (Norris et al. 2010a,b; Lai et al., in preparation). Norris et al. 2010b reported the discovery of an extremely carbon-rich red giant, Segue 1-7, in the Segue 1 system. This star exhibits a metallicity $[Fe/H] = -3.5$, carbonicity $[C/Fe] = +2.3$, and a low barium abundance ($[Ba/Fe] < -1.0$), which place it in the CEMP-no category. This discovery is consistent with the idea that the CEMP-no stars may indeed be associated with the ultra-faint dwarf spheroidal galaxies; further such investigations should prove of great interest.

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5

Summary and Conclusions

5.1 Brief Synopsis of the Main Thesis Results

The main results of this work, presented in the three papers that make up the bulk of this thesis, can be summarized as follows:

- *Two Stellar Components in the Milky Way Halo*

Based on an analysis of a large sample of calibration stars from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) DR5, it has been shown that the Galactic halo comprises (at least) two broadly overlapping structural components, an inner and an outer halo. These components exhibit different spatial density profiles, stellar orbits, and stellar metallicities. It was found that the inner-halo component dominates the population of halo stars found at distances up to 10-15 kpc from the Galactic center, while the outer-halo component dominates in the region beyond 15-20 kpc. The inner halo was shown to comprise a population of stars exhibiting a flattened spatial density distribution, with an inferred axial ratio on the order of ~ 0.6 . Inner-halo stars possess generally high orbital eccentricities, and exhibit a small (or zero) net prograde rotation around the center of the Galaxy. The metallicity distribution function (MDF) of the inner halo peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$, with tails extending to higher and lower metallicities. The outer halo, in contrast, comprises stars that exhibit a much more spherical spatial distribution, with an axial ratio ~ 0.9 to 1.0. Outer-halo stars cover a wide range of orbital eccentricities, including many with lower eccentricity orbits than found for most stars associated with the inner halo, and exhibit a clear retrograde net rotation

(between -40 and -70 km s $^{-1}$) about the center of the Galaxy. The MDF of the outer halo peaks at lower metallicity than that of the inner halo, around $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$, and includes a larger fraction of low-metallicity stars than does the MDF of the inner-halo population.

- ***The Stellar Halos and Thick Disks of the Milky Way***

The structure and kinematics of the recognized stellar components of the Milky Way are explored, based on well-determined atmospheric parameters and kinematic quantities for 32360 “calibration stars” from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) and its first extension, (SDSS-II), which included the sub-survey SEGUE: Sloan Extension for Galactic Understanding and Exploration. Full space motions for a sub-sample of 16920 stars, exploring a local volume within 4 kpc of the Sun, are used to derive velocity ellipsoids for the inner- and outer-halo components of the Galaxy, as well as for the canonical thick-disk and proposed metal-weak thick-disk populations. This new sample of calibration stars represents an increase of 60% relative to the numbers used in a previous analysis. The question of whether the data require the presence of at least a two-component halo in order to account for the rotational behavior of likely halo stars in the local volume, and whether more than two components are needed, is examined. Also, the question of whether the proposed metal-weak thick disk is kinematically and chemically distinct from the canonical thick disk is addressed, leading to the result that the Galactocentric rotational velocity inferred for the metal-weak thick disk, as well as its mean metallicity, appear quite similar to the values derived previously for the Monoceros stream, suggesting a possible association between these structures. The fractions of each component required to understand the nature of the observed kinematic behavior of the stellar populations of the Galaxy as a function of distance from the plane is evaluated. Scale lengths and scale heights for the thick-disk and metal-weak thick-disk components are determined. Spatial density profiles for the inner- and outer-halo populations are inferred from a Jeans Theorem analysis. The full set of calibration stars (including those outside the local volume) is used to test for the expected changes in the observed stellar metallicity distribution function with distance above the Galactic plane *in-situ*, due to the changing contributions from the underlying stellar populations.

It has been found that: (a) A single-population halo is incompatible with the observed kinematics of local stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, while a dual (inner/outer) halo model is necessary to describe the observations. (b) The net rotation of the

outer halo is slightly more retrograde than previously reported, $\langle V_\phi \rangle = -80 \pm 13$ km s⁻¹. (c) The net rotation of the inner halo is consistent with zero (at the two-sigma level), $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 7 \pm 4$ km s⁻¹. (d) There exists a gradient in the mean rotational velocity of likely inner-halo stars, $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -28 \pm 9$ km s⁻¹ kpc⁻¹, for stars located within 2 kpc of the Galactic plane. (e) The dispersions in the rotational-velocity component for both the inner- and outer-halo populations increase with distance from the plane. This may apply to the MWTD as well. (f) The net rotation of the canonical thick-disk population, for stars close to the plane, is $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 182 \pm 2$ km s⁻¹. (g) The asymmetric drift of the thick disk varies with distance from the plane, as shown by previous work, $\Delta \langle V_\phi \rangle / \Delta |Z| = -36 \pm 1$ km s⁻¹ kpc⁻¹. (h) The thick-disk and MWTD systems only contribute to our sample within 5 kpc of the plane, the inner-halo population dominates between 5 and 10 kpc, and the outer-halo population dominates beyond 20 kpc. The inversion point in the dominance of the inner/outer halo is located in the distance range 15-20 kpc. (i) A MWTD, kinematically independent of the canonical thick disk (with net rotation $\langle V_\phi \rangle = 100$ -150 km s⁻¹), is required to account for the rotational properties of low-metallicity stars close to the Galactic plane. (j) The metallicity range for stars that are likely members of the MWTD is -1.8 [Fe/H] -0.8 , possibly up to [Fe/H] ~ -0.7 . (k) The derived velocity ellipsoids, $(\sigma_{V_R}, \sigma_{V_\phi}, \sigma_{V_Z})$, for the four components we have considered are as follows – Thick Disk = $(53 \pm 2, 51 \pm 1, 35 \pm 1)$ km s⁻¹, MWTD = $(59 \pm 3, 40 \pm 3, 44 \pm 3)$ km s⁻¹, Inner Halo = $(150 \pm 2, 95 \pm 2, 85 \pm 1)$ km s⁻¹, and Outer Halo = $(159 \pm 4, 165 \pm 9, 116 \pm 3)$ km s⁻¹. (l) The kinematically derived scale length and scale height for the thick disk are $h_R = 2.20 \pm 0.35$ kpc and $h_Z = 0.51 \pm 0.04$ kpc, respectively. The radial scale length for the MWTD is on the order of $h_R \sim 2$ kpc, while the scale height is 1.36 ± 0.13 kpc. (m) The slopes of the inferred power-law spatial-density profiles for the inner- and outer-halo populations are -3.17 ± 0.20 and -1.79 ± 0.29 , respectively. (n) The tilt angle, α , between the long axis of the Schwarzschild velocity ellipsoid and the sun-center line is, in Galactocentric cylindrical coordinates, for stars of relatively high metallicity ($-0.8 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.6$), $\alpha = 7^\circ.1 \pm 1^\circ.5$ for $1 < |Z| < 2$ kpc, and $\alpha = 5^\circ.2 \pm 1^\circ.2$ for $2 < |Z| < 4$ kpc, consistent with one another. For stars of intermediate metallicity ($-1.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.8$), the tilt is $\alpha = 10^\circ.3 \pm 0^\circ.4$ close to the plane, and $\alpha = 15^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.3$ farther from the plane, which differ significantly from one another. For stars of lower metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$), the tilt is $\alpha = 8^\circ.6 \pm 0^\circ.5$ close to the plane, and $\alpha = 13^\circ.1 \pm 0^\circ.4$ farther from the plane, again significantly different. (o) The “as-observed” metallicity distribution function

of stars in our sample exhibits clear changes with distance from the Galactic plane, exhibiting the anticipated shift from dominance by thick-disk and MWTD populations, with peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.6$ and -1.3 , respectively, to dominance by the inner-halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$) and outer-halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$) populations.

- ***Carbon-Enhanced Metal-Poor Stars in the Inner and Outer Halo Components of the Milky Way***

The carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars in the inner- and outer-halo components of the Milky Way are explored, based on accurate determinations of carbon abundance ratios and kinematic quantities for over 30000 calibration stars from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) and its first extension, (SDSS-II). The carbon abundance estimates are based on fits of the CH G-band at 4300 \AA . The kinematic and orbital parameters have been evaluated for a subsample of the calibration stars (with distances $d < 10 \text{ kpc}$ from the Sun), employing previously developed methods. The “as-observed” carbonicity distribution function ($[\text{C}/\text{Fe}]$; CarDF) as a function of distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$, is examined, and found that its nature changes dramatically with increasing distance. For $|Z| < 5 \text{ kpc}$, few CEMP stars are identified. For distances $|Z| > 5 \text{ kpc}$, the CarDF exhibits a strong tail towards high values, up to $[\text{C}/\text{Fe}] > +3.0$. For stars located above $|Z| = 5 \text{ kpc}$, and with metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.4$, we confirm a significant increase in the fraction of CEMP stars with declining metallicity, as indicated by previous works. Among the lowest metallicity stars, with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.8$, the fraction of CEMP stars increases from a few percent to roughly 10% up to $|Z| = 5 \text{ kpc}$, and continues to increase, up to 20%, for stars located between 5 and 10 kpc from the plane. Whether these behaviors are metallicity driven, due to differences in the mean metallicity of the inner- and outer-halo components, or population driven, due to differences in the fractions of CEMP stars associated with each population at a given metallicity, has been sought. This was accomplished by obtaining a statistical separation of the inner- and outer-halo components in velocity space using the Extreme Deconvolution technique, which provides membership probabilities for each star. At low metallicity ($-2.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$), where the dominant component is the outer halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{peak,out}} = -2.2$), there is evidence for a significant contrast in the CEMP star fraction between the inner- and outer-halo components, such that $F_{\text{CEMP,out}} \sim 2 \times F_{\text{CEMP,in}}$. This may continue to even lower metallicities, but the sample is too small to be certain.

5.2 The Challenge of Distance Determination

In Galactic studies (structure, kinematics, density profiles, etc.), knowledge of the six dimensional phase space parameters (positions and velocities) is a fundamental requirement. Derivation of sufficiently accurate distances is an important step in carrying out kinematic analyses that make use of full space motions, as these must be combined with radial velocities and proper motions in order to assemble the local velocity components of a given stellar sample. Two main methods to derive accurate stellar distances have been applied during the last three decades: trigonometric parallax (direct geometric measure of the distance) and the photometric parallax (an indirect method).

The accuracy of ground-based telescopic measurements of the parallax angle is limited to about 0.01 arcseconds, and thus to stars no more than 100 pc distant. This is because the Earth's atmosphere limits the sharpness of a star's image. Space-based telescopes are not limited by this effect, and can accurately measure distances to objects well beyond the limits of ground-based observations.

The Hipparcos (HIGH Precision PARallax COLlecting Satellite) mission was planned as the first automated attempt to measure stellar positions, distances, and motions from space – where instruments are free of the atmospheric blurring that plagues ground-based astrometry. Nevertheless, it uses the same principles as ground-based parallax measurements. The Hipparcos mission's main objective was to measure accurate stellar distances for its 118,000 carefully selected principal targets, whose brightnesses reach down to magnitude 12.5. The project aimed to measure parallaxes for these targets with a precision of 2 milliarcseconds. As it turned out, Hipparcos exceeded expectations, achieving accuracies at the 1 milliarcsecond level for all its principal targets; in addition, high-precision photometric measurements of these stars apparent brightnesses were obtained. The Hipparcos Catalogue, a high-precision catalogue of more than 100,000 stars, was published in 1997. The lower precision Tycho Catalogue of more than a million stars (measured with the same satellite) was published at the same time, while the enhanced Tycho-2 Catalogue of 2.5 million stars was published in 2000. The Hipparcos results have had a huge impact on a very broad range of astronomical research, such as the provision of an accurate reference frame, constraints on stellar structure and stellar evolution, and on Galactic kinematics and dynamics. A detailed review of the Hipparcos scientific literature between 1997-2007 can be found in Perryman (2007). In spite of the formidable accuracy in distance determination, the Hipparcos data could not reveal the distinct kinematic signature of the outer halo, due to its limiting magnitude $V < 12$, and the small number of known very metal-poor stars

at the time the input catalog was assembled.

Due in part to the outstanding scientific results of the Hipparcos mission, a second astrometric mission has been planned by the ESA (European Space Agency), as a cornerstone mission in the near future. Gaia (Global Astrometric Interferometer for Astrophysics)¹ will be launched in 2012, and will provide unprecedented positional and radial velocity measurements with the accuracy needed to produce a stereoscopic and kinematic census of about one billion stars in our Galaxy and throughout the Local Group. This amounts to about 1 per cent of the *entire* Galactic stellar population. Combined with astrophysical information for each star, provided by on-board multi-color photometry, these data will have the precision necessary to quantify the early formation, and subsequent dynamical, chemical, and star formation evolution of the Milky Way. The main aims of Gaia are to: (1) Measure the positions of ~ 1 billion stars both in the Galaxy and other members of the Local Group, with an accuracy as good as $\sim 20 \mu\text{as}$, (2) Perform spectral and photometric measurements of all objects targetted for positions, (3) Derive space velocities of the Galaxy's constituent stars using the stellar distances and motions, and (4) Create a three-dimensional structural map of the Galaxy. The limiting magnitude of the Gaia satellite is $V = 20$. At this magnitude, Gaia will measure the parallax to an accuracy of $\sim 220 \mu\text{as}$ for $\sim 200 \cdot 10^6$ stars. Therefore, with the outcome of this mission, it will be certainly possible to obtain an extremely accurate determination of the outer-halo parameters.

The indirect method of photometric parallax measurements has provided satisfactory results in the last decade, with the advent of large optical sky surveys such as SDSS. The majority of the luminous Galactic stellar content ($> 90\%$) resides in the form of main-sequence stars. A direct measurement of their spatial distribution requires accurate estimates of stellar distances to faint flux levels ($V \sim 15-18$) for the 1–10 kpc distance range. The large area covered by the SDSS, with accurate photometric measurements (~ 0.02 mag) and faint flux limits ($r < 22$), allows one to explore the stellar distribution in the Galaxy. This approach have been recently used by different authors (Ivezić et al. 2008; Juric et al. 2008). In particular, Juric et al. (2008) used a photometric parallax relation appropriate for main-sequence stars and directly mapped the Galactic stellar number density. The distance range covered was 100 pc to 20 kpc (6500 deg^2), with an accuracy of 18% for a star with $r = 20$.

The methods used to derive the distances in this thesis are based on photometric parallax measurements as well (Beers et al. 2000), and have been extensively discussed

¹As the project evolved, the single interferometer concept was replaced by a new payload design. The mission name remained, however, even though it no longer reflects the methods used to perform the science operations.

in Chapter 2 (Carollo et al. 2007), Chapter 3 (Carollo et al. 2010), and Appendix A. However, the accuracy achieved by using the Beers et al. (2000) method is $\leq 20\%$, far from the accuracy that Gaia will obtain. Nevertheless, the separation of the Galactic halo into two components with different spatial distributions, kinematics, and orbital properties is clear and robust. The presence of a retrograde signature and an associated high velocity dispersion for the outer halo have been identified in both Carollo et al. (2007) and Carollo et al. (2010) with high accuracy. These signals have been confirmed by employing the revised distances reported in Appendix A.

5.3 Concluding Remarks

5.3.1 Implications for Galaxy Formation

An early model for the formation of the Galaxy, based on the rapid (a few hundred million years) monolithic collapse of a gaseous proto-Galaxy (Eggen, Lynden-Bell, & Sandage 1962), has yielded to the more recent idea that the halo of the Galaxy was assembled, over the span of several billion years, from smaller proto-Galactic clumps (Searle & Zinn 1978).

The hierarchical assembly model has received close attention in recent years, in part because it fits well with the prevailing theory for the formation and evolution of structure in the Universe, based on the early collapse of ‘mini-halos’ of cold dark matter (CDM) (White & Rees 1978; Moore et al. 2006). Modern numerical simulations for the assembly of large spirals based on CDM cosmogonies predict that the stars in the halos of galaxies like the Milky Way might be comprised of the shredded stellar debris of numerous dwarf-like galaxies that have been torn apart by tidal interactions with their parent galaxy (Bullock & Johnston 2005; Abadi et al. 2006; Moore et al. 2006; Brook et al. 2007). Recent quantitative analysis of the amount of structure visible in the halo of the Galaxy from SDSS imaging provides compelling additional evidence (Bell et al. 2008). Others have argued that some combination of a monolithic collapse and a hierarchical assembly model may be necessary to fully explain the observed data (Majewski 1993; Zinn 1993; Chiba & Beers 2000).

Within the context of the CDM model, the formation of the inner halo may be understood in the following manner. Low-mass sub-Galactic fragments are formed at an early stage. These fragments rapidly merge into several (in many simulations, two – Bekki & Chiba 2001; Abadi et al. 2006) more-massive clumps, which themselves eventually dissipatively merge (due to the presence of gas that has yet to form stars). The essentially radial merger of the few resulting massive clumps gives rise to the

dominance of high-eccentricity orbits for stars that are assigned membership in the inner halo. Star formation within these massive clumps (both pre- and post-merger) would drive the mean metallicity to higher abundances. This is followed by a stage of adiabatic compression (flattening) of the inner halo component owing to the growth of a massive disk, along with the continued accretion of gas onto the Galaxy (Bekki & Chiba 2001; Chiba & Beers 2001).

The fact that the outer-halo component of the Milky Way exhibits a net retrograde rotation (and a different distribution of overall orbital properties), as found in this thesis, clearly indicates that the formation of the outer halo is distinct from that of both the inner-halo and disk components. We suggest, as others have before, that the outer-halo component formed, not through a dissipative, angular-momentum-conserving contraction, but rather through dissipationless chaotic merging of smaller subsystems within a pre-existing dark-matter halo. These subsystems would be expected to be of much lower mass, and subject to tidal disruption in the outer part of a dark-matter halo, before they fall farther into the inner part. As candidate (surviving) counterparts for such subsystems, one might consider the low-luminosity dwarf spheroidal galaxies surrounding the Galaxy, in particular the most extreme cases recently identified from the SDSS (Belokurov et al. 2006, 2007). Subsystems of lower mass, and by inference, even lower metallicity, may indeed be destroyed so effectively that none (or very few) have survived to the present day. If so, the outer-halo population may have been assembled from relatively more metal-poor stars, following the luminosity-metallicity relationship for Local Group dwarf galaxies (Dekel et al. 2003). The net retrograde rotation of the outer halo may be understood in the context of the higher efficiency of phase mixing for the orbits of stars that are stripped from subsystems on prograde, rather than retrograde orbits (Quinn & Goodman 1986; Norris & Ryan 1989), or may simply be due to non-uniform accretion directions as set by local large scale structure.

5.3.2 The Halos: Additional Observational Evidence

It is important to recall here that multiple evidence for the presence of a dual stellar halo have been pointed out by several authors in past works, primarily from analysis of the spatial profiles (or inferred spatial profiles) of halo objects (Hartwick, 1987; Zinn, 1993; Preston et al., 1991; Kinman et al., 1994). In addition, tentative claims for a net retrograde motion of halo objects by previous authors supports the existence of a likely dual-component halo (Majewski 1992; Carney et al. 1996; Wilhelm et al. 1996; Kinman et al. 2007; Lee 2007).

More evidence has been provided by recent studies, which are discussed in some

detail in Appendix A, to which I refer the reader. Here I briefly summarize the main points.

1. The Metallicity Distribution Function of the C10 Sample with Revised Distances and Variation with Distance from the Plane

The previous analysis of C07 and C10 both concluded that the MDF of the stars in the SDSS calibration-star sample was inconsistent, for regions beyond the possible influence of the disk system, with being drawn from a location-invariant parent population, as would be demanded by the single-halo hypothesis. In Appendix A it has been verified that this claim remains valid, even after reassignment of a subset of the C10 TO stars into alternative luminosity classifications.

2. Distribution of Galactocentric Radial Velocities for BHB Stars from SDSS DR8 and Variation with Metallicity

The SDSS spectroscopic samples comprise a number of alternative tracers that can be used to explore the nature of the Milky Way's halo. Among the most powerful are the blue horizontal-branch stars, which are intrinsically bright and numerous, and have well-calibrated photometric distances. By using the sample of Xue et al. (2011) from the SDSS DR8 data release ($N > 4000$ stars), it has been shown that the Galactocentric radial velocities for two subsamples of the 4512 BHB stars in the range $5 < r < 40$ kpc (which includes roughly 90% of the full sample reported by Xue et al. 2011), exhibit a different Galactocentric radial velocity distribution, when split on metallicity above and below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$. Indeed, the sample at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ exhibits a dispersion of $100 \pm 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Gaussian fit), while the lower metallicity stars require a Gaussian with dispersion of $116 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The difference in the Galactocentric radial velocity distributions, combined with the presence of a flat velocity peak in the low-metallicity distribution, suggests that a mixture of populations may well be present, which of course would support the dual-halo interpretation.

3. The SDSS DR7 BHB Sample Analyzed by Deason et al. (2010)

Deason et al. (2010) have examined a sample of BHB stars selected from SDSS DR7, using a combination of color cuts and cuts on the $\log g$ and T_{eff} from the SSPP (SEGUE Stellar Parameter Pipeline). They found this sample of halo stars exhibits a dichotomy between a prograde, comparatively metal-rich component ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2$) and a retrograde, comparatively metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2$) component. Single-halo interpretations are clearly not supported by their analysis.

4. **Spatial Variations in Metallicity and Density Profiles for Modeled Halo Components from de Jong et al. (2010)**

During the course of the SEGUE sub-survey conducted during SDSS-II (Yanny et al. 2009), ten “vertical” (in Galactic coordinates) photometric scans of width 2.5° , crossing the Galactic plane at fixed longitudes, were imaged in the *ugriz* passbands. By using this data-set, de Jong et al. (2010) employed a CMD fitting approach based on templates of old stellar populations with differing metallicities to obtain a sparse three-dimensional map of the stellar mass distribution at $|Z| > 1$ kpc. The maps of de Jong et al. (2010) provide clear *in situ* evidence for a shift in the mean metallicity of the Milky Way’s stellar halo: within $r < 15$ kpc their derived stellar halo exhibited a mean metallicity of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$, changing to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.2$ at larger Galactocentric distances. In addition, inspection of the spatial density profiles of their template populations (their Fig. 7) suggested rather different spatial behaviors for their “inner-halo like” template population and that of their “outer-halo like” template population. Their derived inner-halo population density profile falls off rapidly with distance from the Galactic center to $r \sim 15 - 20$ kpc; beyond this region a substantially lower density outer-halo profile with only a slowly varying profile was found. Clearly, these findings provide compelling support of the kinematics-based inferences of C07 and C10, as confirmed by our above reanalysis, as well as by the newly considered BHB samples.

5. **Rejection of Single Power-Law Descriptions of the Milky Way’s Halo based on Deep SDSS Imaging from Sesar et al. (2010)**

The region known as Stripe 82 (an area of $\sim 250 \text{ deg}^2$ along the Celestial Equator) has been multiply scanned in the *ugriz* filters over the course of SDSS and its extensions, in particular during the Supernova Survey conducted as part of SDSS-II (Frieman et al. 2008).

Sesar et al. (2010) have argued persuasively that single power-law profiles are incapable of describing the spatial variation of the halo system. These authors presented evidence, based on both RR Lyrae stars and main-sequence stars, that the halo stellar number density profile significantly steepens beyond a Galactocentric distance of $r \sim 30$ kpc. It is worth noting that a “steepening” density profile might also be envisaged as describing the behavior of a profile that suffers a large drop in stellar density at a given distance, and goes over to a more slowly varying profile with distance, as seen in the de Jong et al. (2010) analysis.

6. From the CFHT Legacy Survey

Sesar, Ivezić & Jurić (2011) used deep Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope Legacy Survey (CFHTLS) data for 170 deg² to study the distribution of near-turnoff main sequence stars in the Galactic halo along four lines of sight, to heliocentric distances of ~ 35 kpc. They find that the halo stellar number density profile becomes steeper at Galactocentric distances greater than $r \sim 30$ kpc, and emphasize that single power-law models are strongly disfavored by the data.

5.3.3 Evidence of Chemical Distinctions between the Inner- and Outer-Halo Components

In the last three years, multiple evidence that the two halo components may have distinct chemical signatures have started to emerge.

First, as was shown originally by Carollo et al. (2007), their metallicity distribution functions are significantly different, with a peaks of metallicity at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$ for the inner halo, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.2$ for the outer halo.

This recognition has stimulated several groups to obtain high-resolution spectroscopy of Galactic halo stars. Examples are Roederer (2009) and Zhang et al. (2009). In the first study, the author shows that the $[\text{Mg}/\text{Fe}]$ abundance ratios of stars thought to be associated with the inner halo appear different (generally 0.1 dex higher) than those associated with the outer halo. This same study also demonstrated that stars associated with the inner halo exhibit considerably lower star-to-star abundance scatter for both the iron-peak element ratio $[\text{Ni}/\text{Fe}]$ and the neutron-capture element ratio $[\text{Ba}/\text{Fe}]$ than found for stars of the outer halo. Zhang et al. (2009) obtained elemental abundance for a sample of 26 metal-poor stars ($-3.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$), selected to be likely members of the outer halo through their kinematic and orbital parameters. They found that the α -element (Mg, Si, Ca, Ti) to iron ratios are overabundant relative to the solar values, and increase with decreasing metallicity, They argue that the slope of $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ vs. $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ is caused by the presence of outer-halo stars. In addition, they found that $[\text{Zn}/\text{Fe}]$ is low in the very low metallicity range, which is different from the trend of Zn abundances found by previous studies.

Nissen & Schuster (2010) have determined precise abundance ratios for 94 dwarf stars in the solar neighborhood with $-1.6 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -0.4$, and having halo kinematics. They show that halo stars fall into two populations, clearly separated in $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$. The high- α stars exhibit prograde Galactic orbits, while the low- α stars are predominantly (two-thirds) in retrograde orbits. This results suggest that the high- α population is connected to a dissipative component of the Galaxy that experienced rapid chemical

evolution, whereas the low- α stars were accreted from dwarf galaxies that had a lower star formation rate.

In this thesis, Chapter 4 has shown that, at low metallicity ($-2.5 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$), where the dominant component is the outer halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_{\text{peak, out}} = -2.2$), there is evidence for a significant contrast in the CEMP star fraction between the inner- and outer-halo components, such that $F_{\text{CEMP}_{\text{out}}} \sim 2 \times F_{\text{CEMP}_{\text{in}}}$. This may continue to even lower metallicities, but the sample is too small to be certain. In addition, there is an indication that the CEMP stars in the inner halo could be predominantly CEMP-s stars, while the ones associated with the outer halo could be mainly CEMP-no stars.

The remarkable results of these studies suggest that future efforts in pursuing high-resolution spectroscopy for a large sample of stars should be given high priority.

5.3.4 The Halos: Evidence from Observations of Other Galaxies

For at least a decade, the mystery of the relatively “metal-rich” halo of M 31 has presented a challenge to our understanding of its formation history. Photometric and spectroscopic observations by Kalirai et al. (2006), and more recently by Koch et al. (2008a), have demonstrated that a metal-poor halo of M 31 does indeed exist, but is located beyond 40 kpc from its center (substantially different than observed for the Milky Way, where the outer halo becomes dominant beyond 20 kpc). Their description of a dual-halo model for the Andromeda Galaxy parallels what we observe for the Milky Way, albeit on different length scales.

Recent observations of the Milky Way analogue NGC 891 have provided additional information on the structure and the stellar populations for this relatively massive spiral galaxy in the NGC 1023 group (Ibata, Mouhcine, & Rejkuba 2009; Rejkuba, Mouhcine, & Ibata 2009). Analysis of their data revealed the presence of a thick-disk structure with vertical scale height $h_z = 1.4$ kpc, and scale length $h_R = 4.8$ kpc, somewhat larger than values that have been inferred for the Milky Way. The MDF of the thick-disk structure exhibits a peak at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.9$ (as compared to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.6$ for the canonical thick disk of the Milky Way) that does not change significantly in the vertical and radial directions. When they considered the MDF for stars in regions resembling the solar cylinder we have examined in this thesis (distance along the major axis ~ 8 kpc, vertical distance intervals of ~ 3 -4 kpc and 5-7 kpc), they detected a substantial population of intermediate-metallicity stars, with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.0$. By way of contrast, at these same vertical distances the MDF of the Milky Way is dominated by the inner halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$; Ivezić et al. 2008). The intermediate-metallicity population in the solar cylinder of NGC 891 might be associated with a component

similar to the Milky Way's MWTD, but is present at larger distances from the plane in this galaxy than in the Milky Way. The difference between the vertical extension and MDF of the disk populations between NGC 891 and the Milky Way may simply reflect different (stochastic) formation histories for the two galaxies.

The stellar halo of NGC 891 exhibits a shallow metallicity gradient, with average metallicity decreasing from $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.15$ to -1.27 from the inner regions to the outskirts. A similar trend was also found in the inner halo of M 31 (20 kpc from the nucleus; Durrell, Harris, & Pritchet 2001), and in the halo of NGC 5128, which is the nearest giant elliptical galaxy (Rejkuba et al. 2005). In subsequent work, metal-poor halos were detected for these galaxies, at distances larger than $12r_{\text{eff}}$ from the center (Chapman et al. 2006; Kalirai et al. 2006). However, in NGC 891, at the same radius, a metal-poor halo has not (yet) been detected. In this regard we note that in the right-hand panel of Figure 18 in Rejkuba et al. (2009) there is a clear transition of the MDF, from intermediate ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.0$) metallicity to a lower ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.5$) metallicity, which suggests the presence of a metal-poor population like that in the inner halo of the Milky Way. We suspect that when additional photometry at larger distances is carried out for NGC 891 its MDF will reveal metal-poor halo population(s) similar to those of the Milky Way.

Recent spectroscopic studies of the metallicities and other elemental abundances in the ultra-faint dSph galaxies (Kirby et al. 2008; Koch et al. 2008b; Norris et al. 2008; Frebel et al. 2009) have clearly demonstrated that the frequently cited result (e.g., Helmi et al 2006) that "the progenitors of nearby dSphs appear to have been different from the building blocks of the Milky Way", based on the MDF of the more luminous members of the dSph population, is not longer necessarily a true statement. In recent studies, chemical similarities between stars members of the dSphs and halo stars, started to emerge (Frebel et al. 2010). This might suggest that the sub-systems that formed the halo components of the Milky Way were not fundamentally different from the progenitors of the present-day dwarfs. While we refer the reader to the reviews of Koch (2009) and Tolstoy, Hill, & Tosi (2009) for more thorough discussions, we note here two relevant points. First, it has been shown that the metallicities of stars in even the more luminous dSphs (e.g., Sculptor; Battaglia et al. 2008) are spatially stratified, with the more metal-poor objects being found preferentially in their outer regions. These metal-poor stars are clearly the most likely to be stripped from their parents during tidal interactions, with the halo(s) of the Milky Way as the obvious recipients. Secondly, the works cited above establish that extremely metal-poor stars ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3.0$) exist in the ultra-faint systems, and for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.6$, one finds $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] \sim 0.3-0.5$, similar to Galactic halo values. It is not difficult to imagine a substantial

population of low-luminosity dwarfs, most of which have already been completely dissolved, accounting for the entire population of stars in the presently observed outer-halo component of the Milky Way. Further guidance for this idea will be obtained by additional high-resolution spectroscopic observations of stars in the low-luminosity dwarfs, as well as detailed elemental abundance determinations for stars with kinematics that suggest membership in the outer-halo population (e.g., Ishigaki et al. 2009; Roederer 2009; Zhang et al. 2009; Roederer et al. 2010).

5.3.5 The Halos from Theoretical Modeling

De Lucia & Helmi (2008) have adapted a high-resolution simulation of a Milky Way-like halo, combined with a semi-analytic approach, to explore the formation of the Galaxy. They found *no evidence* for a "continuous" metallicity gradient for halo stars, but rather, evidence for a strong concentration of higher-metallicity halo stars toward the Galactic center, and the presence of lower-metallicity stars at distances beyond 20 kpc from the Galactic center. The results of this simulation bear a strong resemblance to the properties of the dominant inner halo we find within 10-15 kpc from Sun, as well as with its rather steep inferred density profile, and an outer halo that dominates beyond 15-20 kpc, with a much shallower inferred density profile.

In a recent paper, Zolotov et al. (2009) have investigated the formation of the stellar halos in simulated disk galaxies, using high-resolution SPH + N-Body simulations. They found that the inner regions ($r < 20$ kpc) contain both accreted and *in-situ* stellar populations (the latter includes stars formed in the main halo). Contrasting with this, the outer regions of the simulated halos were assembled through pure accretion and the disruption of satellites.

Other recent supporting evidence is found in a simulation by Salvadori et al (2009). These authors studied the age and metallicity distribution function of metal-poor stars in the Milky Way halo, as a function of Galactocentric radius, using a combination of N-body simulations and semi-analytical methods. They found that the stellar distributions, within 50 kpc from the center of their simulated galaxy, follow a power-law in radius, r^n , where $n \sim -3.2$ for stars with $-2 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1$, and $n \sim -2.2$ for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -2$. In this context, the relative contribution of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -2$ strongly increases with r (16% within $7 < r < 20$ kpc, up to $> 40\%$ for $r > 20$ kpc). Note that our spatial-density power laws for the inner and outer halo are in reasonable agreement, within the errors, with the values found by Salvadori et al (2009).

Cooper et al. (2009) have also conducted simulations of the formation of stellar halos within the Λ CDM paradigm, offering a number of improvements over previous

efforts. Their results, which cover a range of possible halo formation histories, produce predicted metallicity shifts at various radii, several of which are reminiscent of what we have found in our own analysis of the Milky Way's halo system. It is notable that, in all cases, the lowest metallicity stars in their simulations are accreted (or stripped) from the very sort of ultra-faint dwarf galaxies that Carollo et al. (2007) suggested may be related to the origin of the outer-halo population.

In a very recent paper, Font et al. (2011), explored the formation of stellar halos around disk galaxies, by using cosmological hydrodynamical simulations (Galaxies-Intergalactic Medium Interaction Calculation; GIMIC). They have simulated an unprecedentedly large sample of ~ 400 disk galaxies, taking into account accurate treatments of metal dependent radiative cooling, star formation, supernova feedback, and chemodynamics. The main remarkable result of this simulation is that a *dual halo* in disk-like galaxies is a *general property of the stellar spheroids of Milky Way-mass disc galaxies*. Indeed, they found that a single power-law distribution of mass density and surface brightness cannot match the profiles over all radii. Beyond $r \sim 30$ kpc, the power-law index of -3.5 provides an excellent fit, but the same power-law underpredicts the mass density/surface brightness at smaller radii. In addition, they obtained a significant metallicity shift in the simulated galaxy populations; $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ drops by 0.6 to 0.9 dex from the inner ($r < 30$ kpc) to the outer ($r \sim 30\text{--}100$ kpc) regions. The change in slope of the mass density profile at $r \simeq 30$ kpc is apparently driven by the large contribution from in situ star formation in the inner regions, and accreted stars at larger radii. The same mechanism is responsible for the large-scale metallicity shift.

5.3.6 The Thick Disks from Theoretical Modeling

Simulations that attempt to account for the formation of the thick-disk component have suggested that the asymmetric drift we find for this structure can be naturally accommodated. According to the simulations of Abadi et al. (2003), it may also be consistent with the expected behavior if the thick disk is comprised solely of debris from merging satellites. The formation of a MWTD component may be the result of a stochastic event, such as assimilation of the debris from a moderately metal-poor, low-mass satellite.

Modern cosmogonies predict the formation of the thick disk by predominantly dissipationless processes. In this context, thick-disk stars were vertically heated from a pre-existent thin disk during a significant minor merger or perturbation by a cold dark matter sub-halo (Kazantzidis et al. 2009), or directly deposited at large scale heights as tidally stripped debris during the accretion of smaller satellite galaxies (e.g., Statler

1988; Abadi et al. 2003; Yoachim & Dalcanton 2008). Villalobos & Helmi (2008) have investigated in detail the heating process by a minor merger. They found that the trend of the ratio $\sigma_{V_z}/\sigma_{V_R}$ with radius in the final disks is a good discriminant of the initial inclination of the merging satellite. For the Milky Way, the observed $\sigma_{V_z}/\sigma_{V_R}$ is ~ 0.6 (Chiba & Beers 2000; Carollo et al. 2010), which suggests that the thick disk of the Galaxy could have been produced by a merger of intermediate inclination. The values found for the MWTD velocity ellipsoid provide a ratio $\sigma_{V_z}/\sigma_{V_R} \sim 0.7$, which could be explained through a merger of different inclination.

Hayashi & Chiba (2006) have shown that disk thickening, quantified by the change of its scale height (or the square of its vertical velocity dispersion), strongly depends on the individual mass of an interacting sub-halo. In this scenario of hierarchical formation, the MWTD could be formed through the early merger (at least with respect to the merger responsible for the formation of the canonical thick disk) of a satellite with a less massive, younger pre-existing disk. Note, however, that the existence of stars with disk kinematics and older than the last major merger event is difficult to accommodate in the Λ CDM scenario (Abadi et al. 2003). The results of the simulations of Abadi et al. suggest that the tidal debris from satellites can contribute not only to the Galactic halo, but also to the disk system. The contribution to the halo or to the disk depends on the orbit of the merging satellite, and on the degree to which dynamical friction circularized the orbits before disruption (Statler 1988). An accreted satellite that contributes significantly to the thick disk must be disrupted on an orbital plane very close to that of the disk, and be massive enough to survive the disruption until its orbit is circularized within the disk. In this scenario, the predicted location of the disrupted satellites responsible for the formation of the thick disk and MWTD is within the thick-disk system itself. We have noted in this work that some properties of the Monoceros stream (rotational velocity and metallicity) are in good agreement with those of the MWTD. *The Monoceros stream could be part of the disrupted satellite that was also responsible for the formation of the thick-disk system.*

5.3.7 Future Work

The work presented in this thesis has provided important hints to both observational and theoretical studies of Galactic structure and galaxy formation. The presence of a second stellar halo component has been established. The kinematics, orbital parameters, and spatial distributions of the inner- and outer-halo components have been explored in great detail. In addition, evidence for different chemical signatures in the two halo components is beginning to emerge from analysis of the carbon-enhanced

metal-poor (CEMP) stars. The thick-disk system (thick disk and metal-weak thick disk) has been considered as a two-component structure, and the kinematic and orbital parameters, as well as metallicity distributions, of the individual components have been evaluated.

The main steps that should be accomplished in the next 2-3 years are, (a) confirmation of a distinct chemical signature, in term of CEMP-s and CEMP-no stars, in the inner and outer halo, through the analysis of high-resolution spectroscopy of stars selected to be members of one or another component; (b) explore additional evidence of chemical distinction between the inner and outer halo, through the analysis of the α -elements in stars selected to be member of the two components; (c) a possible confirmation that the metal-weak thick disk is a separate and independent component with respect the thick disk (CEMP frequency and distribution, α -elements); (d) keep exploring the existing- and newly-discovered dwarf satellite galaxies of the Milky Way to better establish their link to the outer-halo component.

The research topics indicated above may be accomplished by using existing databases such as the SDSS/SEGUE calibration stars (and other sub-samples), the metal-poor stars from SDSS DR8, as well as the Hamburg/ESO Survey (HES) stars of Christlieb and collaborators (Christlieb 2003), and the HK survey datasets of Beers et al. (1985, 1992), and subsequent follow-up. In addition, RAVE (Zwitter et al. 2008) can be employed for studies related to the thick-disk system. The new large scale survey Sky Mapper (Keller et al. 2007), which will start no later than this year, will provide an enormous amount of data (southern hemisphere) that can be immediately employed to find more metal-poor stars, and new dwarf satellite galaxies of the Milky Way (Stromlo Milky Way Satellites (SMS)² Survey; Jerjen 2010).

²http://msowww.anu.edu.au/~jerjen/SMS_Survey.html

Below I address how the research topics listed above can be accomplished.

1. **Membership Selection of Inner/Outer Halo and TD/MWTD Stars**

Knowledge of the full space motions (U,V,W), orbital parameters, and metallicity can be used to assign a membership probability (inner/outer halo; TD/MWTD) to each star. When a radial velocity for a star is not available (a spectrum has not been obtained, and the full space motion cannot be retrieved), membership likelihood can be assigned using the reduced proper motion diagram, which is very powerful in separating the different populations in the Galaxy, when used in combination with the color of a star (Carollo et al. 2006). This technique is particularly suitable for the selection of likely outer-halo stars, and to identify the most metal-poor stars in the Galaxy, which are members of this Galactic component (Carollo et al. 2007, 2010).

Another useful technique is the Extreme Deconvolution approach (Bovy et al. 2009), already applied in Chapter 4 to assign a membership probability to inner- and outer-halo stars. The same techniques can be employed to separate stars member of the thick disk and MWTD.

Once the stars are accurately assigned to the inner- or outer-halo component, high-resolution spectroscopic observations of these stars will provide detailed information on their chemical composition (α -elements, enhancement of Barium, and other-neutron capture elements), and possibly reveal additional evidence of chemical distinctions between the two halo components. Similar observations will be of interest also for the member stars of the thick disk and MWTD.

High-resolution spectroscopic follow-up will provide crucial information to address some issues that need further investigation; several are listed below.

2. **$[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ Distribution in the Thick-Disk and Halo Systems**

Two fundamental questions need to be answered, (1) If the inner- and outer-halo populations have distinct astrophysical origins (such as might arise from star formation taking place in more massive or less massive dwarf galaxies), could their $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ distribution be significantly different?³ and (2) Can we confirm that the MWTD is a distinct population from the canonical thick disk by an analysis of their $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ distributions?

³Note that such investigations started to be considered in a recent paper (Nissen & Shuster 2010).

3. **Metallicity (Iron Abundance) Distribution Function**

Various theoretical models have been employed to predict the halo MDF. However, the observed MDF fails to match the predicted MDFs, in particular there is an observed lack of stars at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3.5$. It is thus mandatory to obtain larger, statistically complete and unbiased samples of the most metal-poor stars. This can be successfully accomplished by the use of large telescopes, in combination with their instruments capable of obtaining spectra with $R > 15000$.

4. **Origins of Carbon-Enhanced Metal-Poor Stars**

Two fundamental questions need to be answered, (1) Are the carbon-enhanced metal-poor (CEMP) stars in the outer halo prevalently CEMP-no (exhibit low abundance of s-process elements such as Ba), while those in the inner halo mostly belong to the CEMP-s (enhancement of s-process elements) category, (as suggested in Chapter 4)?

5. **Neutron-Capture Elements in Metal-Poor Stars**

While abundance studies for neutron-capture elements have been conducted for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -3.5$, the sample size for lower metallicity is still very small. The $[\text{Sr}/\text{Ba}]$ abundance ratios in the lowest metallicity range seems to be similar to the solar value, but the reason is unknown. It is thus urgent to determine the Sr and Ba abundances for more stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3.0$. Note that such an investigation has also been suggested in a recent paper (Frebel & Norris 2011).

6. **Search for CEMP-no Stars in Ultra-Faint Dwarf Spheroidals**

As suggested in Chapter 4 of this thesis, most of CEMP stars in the outer-halo component could be associated to the CEMP-no category. Therefore, high-resolution spectroscopic observations of the member stars of the ultra-faint dwarf spheroidals devoted to measure neutron-capture elements (e.g., Ba), would be of extreme importance.

7. **The Metal-Weak Thick Disk: Additional Evidence Needed from Observations**

In Chapter 3, we attempted to constrain the properties of the MWTD as an independent kinematic component from the canonical thick disk. It was found that its velocity lag is $\sim 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ lower than the canonical thick disk; its velocity ellipsoid appears similar to that of the thick disk (although its vertical velocity dispersion, and hence its inferred scale height, appear somewhat larger). These

values are, of course, still uncertain due to the significant kinematic and spatial overlap of the MWTD with the thick-disk and inner-halo components. Additional study (informed by more-detailed abundance analyses of likely MWTD stars) must be given to this problem before its final resolution can be obtained.

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Appendix A

The Case for the Dual Halo of the Milky Way

Beers, T.C., Carollo, D., Ivezić Z., An, D., Chiba, M., Norris, E.J., Bailer-Jones, C. A., Freeman, K.C., Lee Y.S., Munn, J.A., Re Fiorentin, P., Rockosi, C.M., Sivarani, T., Wilhelm, R., Yanny B., York, D.G., submitted to the *Astrophysical Journal*

Abstract

Based on an analysis of the local kinematics of SDSS DR7 calibration stars, Carollo et al. have resolved the stellar population of the Milky Way halo into at least two components. This result has recently been criticized by Schönrich et al., who claim that the retrograde signature associated with the outer halo is due to the adoption of faulty distances. We refute this claim, and demonstrate that the Schönrich et al. photometric distances are themselves flawed because *they adopted an incorrect main-sequence absolute magnitude relationship from the work of Ivezić et al.* When compared to the recommended relation from Ivezić et al., which is tied to a Milky Way globular cluster distance scale and accounts for age and metallicity effects, the incorrect relation adopted by Schönrich et al. yields, on average, 18% shorter distances (independent of metallicity) for stars near the main-sequence turnoff (TO). When the correct relationship is used, the distances assigned by Carollo et al. and Ivezić et al. for low-metallicity dwarfs agree to within 6-10%, depending on the color range considered. We have also compared the Carollo et al. distances with the distances derived from the calibrated isochrones of An et al., and find a similar level of agreement for low-metallicity dwarfs. Schönrich et al. also point out that stars of intermediate gravity

($3.5 \leq \log g < 4.0$, based on spectroscopic determinations) are likely misclassified, at least for colors significantly redder than the TO region, with which we concur. We implement a new procedure to reassign luminosity classifications for the TO stars that require it. New derivations of the rotational behavior for the Carollo et al. stars that are most likely associated with the outer halo demonstrate that, when either a sample of exclusively dwarf stars or the full sample of dwarf, TO, and subgiant/giant stars is used, the retrograde signature and high velocity dispersion of the outer-halo population remains, with values similar to those previously derived. An additional test of the reality of the retrograde signature is provided, based exclusively on the observed proper motions of low-metallicity stars. Further evidence for a complex halo comes from inspection of the metallicity distribution function of the Carollo et al. sample as a function of distance from the Galactic plane. We summarize additional lines of evidence for a dual halo, based on different stellar samples from the SDSS and other surveys. We conclude that the overwhelming body of evidence rejects the single-halo interpretation beyond reasonable doubt.

A.1 Introduction

The nature of the stellar halo of the Milky Way has been debated for many decades. Among the questions that have been asked: Is the halo a monolithic structure, well-described by a simple Gaussian velocity ellipsoid? If so, is it in zero net rotation, and does that rotational character apply to all of its constituent stars? Do the stars in the halo comprise a single stellar population, with similar ages and drawn from a common metallicity distribution function (MDF)? Can the spatial distribution of the halo stars be adequately described by a single density law (power-law or otherwise)? Due to the difficulty of teasing out the properties of such a low density component (as compared, e.g., to the bulge and disk systems) the basic data required to address these and other questions has only recently begun to arrive. Not surprisingly, multiple interpretations have emerged.

Massive new datasets from, e.g., SkyMapper (Keller et al. 2007), Gaia (Perryman et al. 2001), and eventually, LSST (Ivezić et al. 2008a), will provide definitive answers to the above questions, and of course, raise new ones. However, it is critical to address these issues with presently available data, so that the most meaningful probes of future datasets can be developed.

The two largest spectroscopic datasets available today for examination of the stellar populations of the Milky Way are the RAdial Velocity Experiment (RAVE; Steinmetz

et al. 2006; Zwitter et al. 2008) and the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al. 2000), in particular the subsurvey Sloan Extension for Galactic Understanding and Exploration (SEGUE; Yanny et al. 2009). The SEGUE-2 subsurvey (Rockosi et al., in preparation) has recently been publicly released as part of SDSS DR8 (Aihara et al. 2011), and will add to this bounty of information. For now, we concentrate on the information available from the previous public release from SDSS, DR7 (Abazajian et al. 2009), and in particular address the criticisms raised by Schönrich et al. (2010; S10) of the previous work of Carollo et al. (2007; C07) and Carollo et al. (2010; C10).

C07 performed a kinematic analysis (within a local volume) for a large sample of calibration stars from SDSS DR5 (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2007), and argued for the existence of at least a two-component halo. In their view the Galactic halo comprises two broadly overlapping structural components, an inner and an outer halo. These components exhibit different spatial density profiles, stellar orbits, and stellar metallicities. It was found that the inner-halo component dominates the population of halo stars found at distances up to 10-15 kpc from the Galactic center, while the outer-halo component dominates in the region beyond 15-20 kpc. The inner halo was shown to comprise a population of stars exhibiting a flattened spatial density distribution, with an inferred axial ratio on the order of ~ 0.6 . According to C07, inner-halo stars possess generally high orbital eccentricities, and exhibit a small (or zero) net prograde rotation around the center of the Galaxy. The MDF of the inner halo peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$, with tails extending to higher and lower metallicities. By comparison, the outer halo comprises stars that exhibit a more spherical spatial density distribution, with an axial ratio ~ 0.9 . Outer-halo stars possess a wide range of orbital eccentricities, exhibit a clear retrograde net rotation, and are drawn from an MDF that peaks at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$, a factor of four lower than that of the inner-halo population.

C10 used an expanded sample of calibration stars available from SDSS DR7, which included the SEGUE sample, to refine and extend the results of C07. They derived velocity ellipsoids for the inner- and outer-halo components of the Galaxy, as well as for the canonical thick-disk and the proposed metal-weak thick-disk populations. C10 also considered the fractions of each component required to understand the nature of the observed kinematic behavior of the stellar populations of the Galaxy as a function of distance from the Galactic plane. Spatial density profiles for the inner- and outer-halo populations were inferred from a Jeans Theorem analysis. The full set of calibration stars (including those outside the local volume) was used to test for the expected changes in the observed stellar MDF with distance above the Galactic plane *in situ*, due to the changing contributions from the underlying stellar populations.

Derivation of sufficiently accurate distances is a crucial required step in carrying

out kinematic analyses that make use of full space motions, as these involve distances, combined with radial velocities and proper motions, in order to assemble the local velocity components of a sample. It is these distances that have been called into question by S10. In the present paper, we show that many of their objections arise from *their incorrect adoption* of a main-sequence absolute magnitude relationship from Ivezić et al. (2008b; I08) that *does not apply* for metal-poor halo stars near the main-sequence turnoff (TO), and which leads to assignments of stellar distances that strongly disagree (a shorter scale by 10-18%) with those derived using the correct relationship recommended by I08. A legitimate criticism by S10 relates to the luminosity classifications for stars of intermediate gravity (as assigned spectroscopically) used by C07 and C10, which we demonstrate below is easily corrected. We then consider a new kinematic analysis of likely outer-halo stars from C10, and demonstrate that their original claim that the halo of the Milky Way requires at least a two-component model (with the outer-halo component in net retrograde rotation and possessing a large velocity dispersion) remains intact.

This paper is outlined as follows. In Section A.2 we summarize the procedures used by C07 and C10 to derive absolute magnitudes and distance estimates for their stars, which were based on those described by Beers et al. (2000). A technique for the reassignment of (some) luminosity classifications for TO stars in the original C10 sample is then developed and applied. In Section A.3 we compare with absolute magnitudes and distances derived by the approaches of I08 and An et al. 2011 (in preparation; A11) for stars spectroscopically classified as likely dwarfs based on their derived surface gravities, as well as with those claimed by S10. We demonstrate concordance between the distances for low-metallicity dwarf stars obtained by C10, I08, and A11, and the apparent discordance of all three of these techniques with the results of S10. In Section A.4 we reanalyze the kinematics of likely outer-halo stars from the C10 dwarf sample, as well as from the full sample, including stars of dwarf, TO, and subgiant/giant luminosity classifications, and compare to the results obtained from adoption of the I08, A11, and S10 distances. Additional tests for the presence of a kinematically and/or chemically distinct outer halo in the C10 sample are discussed in Section A.5. Section A.6 presents a summary of further evidence in favor of a dual halo model for the Milky Way, based on other data sets from SDSS and elsewhere. Our conclusions are given in Section A.7.

A.2 Procedures Used for Absolute Magnitude and Distance Estimates

A.2.1 As Employed by C07 and C10

The analyses of C07 and C10 made use of distance estimates for various luminosity classes as assigned by the software pipeline employed by SDSS/SEGUE to estimate stellar atmospheric parameters based on low-resolution ($R \sim 2000$) spectroscopy and *ugriz* photometry. The SEGUE Stellar Parameter Pipeline (SSPP) assigns distances for stars under the following assumed luminosity classes – D: dwarf, TO: main-sequence turnoff, SG/G: subgiant and giant, FHB: Field Horizontal-Branch, and AGB: Asymptotic Giant Branch.¹ Details of the development, calibration, and validation of the SSPP can be found in Lee et al. (2008a,b), Allende Prieto et al. (2008), and Smolinski et al. (2011), to which we refer the interested reader.

The SSPP obtains estimates of stellar effective temperatures, T_{eff} , with errors of determination on the order of 150 K. The surface gravity estimates returned by the SSPP are accurate, for stars other than the coolest giants, to on the order of 0.25 dex. Metallicity estimates for stars in the temperature range $4500 \text{ K} < T_{\text{eff}} < 7000 \text{ K}$ are accurate to on the order of 0.2 dex.

The SSPP distance estimates for various luminosity classes are based on a set of absolute magnitude relationships (using absorption and reddening-corrected Johnson V magnitudes and $B - V$ colors) calibrated to Galactic globular and open clusters, as described by Beers et al. (2000; their Table 2). As demonstrated in Beers et al., photometric distances estimated for their sample are in good agreement with distances derived from accurate Hipparcos parallaxes. Even when confined to TO stars alone (with well-examined assignment of stars into the TO class provided from previous work), the photometric distances using the Beers et al. formulae are consistent with Hipparcos distances.

The samples used by C07 and C10 were selected from the calibration stars of SDSS/SEGUE, which cover an apparent magnitude range of $15.5 < g_0 < 18.5$. In those analyses, confinement to a local sample with distances less than 4 kpc from the Sun corresponds to a g -band absolute magnitude fainter than $M_g = 2.5$, i.e., the local sample is dominated by D and TO stars. This is in contrast to the sample considered by Beers et al. (2000), which is dominated by SG/G stars.

¹The FHB and AGB classes do not pertain to the sample of calibration stars used by C07 and C10, and so are not discussed further here.

Since the Beers et al. (2000) approach makes use of a non-SDSS photometric system, it is also necessary to employ a color transformation from the SDSS system. Zhao & Newberg (2006) derived a transformation obtained by making matches of SDSS stars with available Johnson magnitudes and colors from the HK survey of Beers and colleagues (Beers et al. 1985, 1992), as well as additional photometry of the HK sample stars obtained over the past decade (see, e.g., Beers et al. 2007, and references therein). They obtained:

$$V = g - 0.561(g - r) - 0.004$$

$$B - V = 0.916(g - r) + 0.187$$

Stars from the HK survey were used in order to specifically include stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, which pertain to most halo stars, although the results did not differ drastically from those of Fukugita et al. (1996) that were based primarily on higher abundance stars. The color range of the matching stars sets the region of applicability of the above transformation, which is $-0.5 < g - r < 1.0$. The choice of distance estimates based on a non-SDSS photometric system was one of necessity at the time the SSPP was put into operation, as there were no suitably calibrated fiducials based on SDSS photometry of Galactic clusters available, and the isochrones that had been developed were rather primitive. These limitations no longer apply, and future versions of the SSPP will employ alternative distance estimates based on improvements that have become available in the past year.

It should be noted that the SSPP, by design, does not identify a preferred distance estimate, leaving the choice of the appropriate luminosity classification to the user's discretion. This choice is due, in part, to the fact that the estimation of surface gravity by the SSPP has evolved with time, and may continue to do so in the future. Hence, as many users will rely, at least at some level, on $\log g$ estimates for making distance estimates based on luminosity classifications from available spectroscopic information, no "approved" distance estimate is supplied by the SSPP.

For the purpose of the analyses carried out by C07 and C10, the following spectroscopically assigned surface gravity intervals from the SSPP were used in the assignment of luminosity classifications:

- D: $\log g \geq 4.0$
- TO: $3.5 \leq \log g < 4.0$
- SG/G: $\log g < 3.5$

Estimates of $\log g$ carry errors, and one has to be concerned about the possible effects on any resulting analyses based on their adoption. For the present, this is best assessed by consideration of inferences based on samples of individual luminosity classes relative to the sample as a whole, which we discuss below.

Note that the above prescription for assignment of luminosity class does not take into account the “known” evolutionary stage of a given star, as might be inferred from the location of a star in a color-magnitude diagram expected to pertain to objects of a given age and metallicity. This uncertainty is of particular concern for stars assigned to the TO class, since an alternative assignment to the D or SG/G class could result in potentially large discrepancies in the adopted distance. This “defect” (actually a choice, given that such knowledge is at best only partially constrained with present data, and in any case relies on assumptions regarding the underlying stellar population one adopts) is one of the criticisms of the C07 and C10 work levied by S10. However, it can be readily addressed, as described below.

As part of their analysis, I08 compared absolute magnitude estimates obtained by the Beers et al. (2000) procedures with those used in their own analysis (which only applied to dwarfs). Pointing at the bottom left panel of their Fig. 21, which examined the main-sequence comparisons of Galactic clusters between the two studies, I08 concluded that “... the median offset of implied M_r evaluated in small bins of $u-g$ and $g-r$ color is -0.07 mag, with an rms of 0.06 mag”. This satisfying level of agreement provided additional reason to have faith in the distances for the majority of stars in the C10 sample upon which their kinematic analysis was based. This agreement remains intact, as shown below.

A.2.2 A Refined Prescription for Luminosity Class Assignments

As pointed out above, refinements in luminosity class assignment require assumptions about the ages and age distributions of the population(s) to which they will be applied. For the present discussion, which turns on the nature of the stars associated by C07 and C10 with the inner- and outer-halo populations, it is reasonable to adopt a uniformly old age, with the unavoidable caveat that not all stars of these populations may strictly adhere to this assumption.

We proceed as follows.

First, a set of theoretical $\log g$ vs. T_{eff} diagrams is obtained, based on the Y² isochrones (Demarque et al. 2004), for a population with age set to 12 Gyrs, metallicities in the range $-3.0 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq 0.0$, and with $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ set to 0.0 for solar metallicity, $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.3$ for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.0$, and using a linear scaling between $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0$ and

Table A.1. Luminosity Class Refinements for Main-Sequence Turnoff Stars

Former Class	T_{eff} Range	Gravity Interval	New Class
TO	$\geq T_{\text{crit}}$	$3.75 \leq \log g < 4.00$	TO
TO	$\geq T_{\text{crit}}$	$3.50 \leq \log g < 3.75$	TO
TO	$< T_{\text{crit}}$	$3.75 \leq \log g < 4.00$	D
TO	$< T_{\text{crit}}$	$3.50 \leq \log g < 3.75$	SG/G

$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.0$. We then obtain the effective temperatures at the position of the main-sequence turnoff for each model, T_{MSTO} , and assign a “critical temperature”, T_{crit} , to be 250 K cooler than T_{MSTO} . The offset of 250 K was chosen since, in the region of the MSTO, this roughly corresponds to the two-sigma accuracy of the estimated temperature from the SSPP, and provides a reasonable location for the base of the subgiant branch for isochrones of old, low-metallicity populations. Our purpose is to define a criterion such that a reassignment of luminosity classes can be considered for stars of intermediate gravity ($3.5 \leq \log g < 4.0$) that are cooler than T_{crit} .

A second-order polynomial is fit to the positions of the T_{MSTO} values for each model:

$$T_{\text{MSTO}} = 5572 - 519.3[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] - 44.3[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]^2 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The critical temperature is then simply set to $T_{\text{crit}} = T_{\text{MSTO}} - 250$. This process is illustrated in Fig. A.1. The critical temperature is used in order to separate intermediate-gravity stars classified as TO by C07 and C10 into either bona-fide TO stars (those with $T_{\text{eff}} \geq T_{\text{crit}}$) or into the D or SG/G classes (those with $T_{\text{eff}} < T_{\text{crit}}$) according to their surface gravity estimates, as summarized in Table A.1. Note that stars with original luminosity classifications D and SG/G are not changed by this procedure.

The luminosity class reassignment procedure described above affects a total of 4514 of the original 16920 accepted stars in the C10 sample (26%). The upper left panel of Fig. A.2 shows the CMD for the original assignments of C10, while the upper right panel is that obtained after the revised assignments have been applied to this same sample. The gray dots are stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, while the red dots are stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$.² As can be appreciated from comparison of these two panels, stars that formerly fell into regions of the CMD that might be considered astrophysically unlikely for an old, metal-poor population have primarily moved into either the D or SG regions. The lower panels of Fig. A.2 contrast the absolute magnitudes of the revised and original C10 classifications (lower left) and the corresponding derived distances (lower right).

²We have made use of the corrected metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C$, as described by C10, here and throughout the rest of this paper, for the quoted metallicities.

Figure A.1 Theoretical surface gravity ($\log g$) vs. T_{eff} diagram based on the Y^2 isochrones (Demarque et al. 2004), under the assumption of a uniform age of 12 Gyrs. From left to right in the figure, the isochrones cover the range of metallicities $-3.0 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < 0.0$, in steps of 0.5 dex. The $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ ratios are set to 0.0 for solar metallicity, $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.3$ for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -1.0$, and are linearly scaling between $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.0$. The red dots mark the position of the MSTO, while the blue dots correspond to temperatures 250 K cooler than the MSTO, referred to as T_{crit} . The vertical dashed lines connect the multi-valued positions on the isochrones at a given T_{eff} . Stars with estimated gravities in the range $3.5 \leq \log g < 4.0$, which were classified as TO by C07 and C10, are reassigned to either D or SG/G classes if their metallicities and T_{eff} place them to the right side of these divisions, or remain classified as TO if their metallicities and T_{eff} place them to the left of these divisions. See text for additional details.

Inspection of the upper left panel of Fig. A.2 clearly shows the presence of the “spurious” TO stars in the original C10 sample, most easily seen among the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ stars as the plume extending from roughly $M_r = 3.7$ to $M_r = 4.7$, over the color range $0.25 < g-i < 0.6$. Comparison with the upper right panel of this figure shows that most of these stars (51%) are reassigned to D status, with only some 10% being reassigned to SG/G status (the remaining stars, 39%, retain their original luminosity classification of TO). At low metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, the fraction of reassigned TO stars to D status is 85%, while those reassigned to SG/G status comprise 14%, and only a small fraction retain their TO classification. At higher metallicities, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, 44% of the TO stars are reassigned to D status, and only a small fraction are reassigned to SG/G status. The remaining stars, 56%, retain their original luminosity classification of TO.

The lower left panel of Fig. A.2 shows the difference in the assigned M_r absolute magnitudes that arises when one compares the revised C10 estimates with those of C10. For the TO stars that were reclassified as D stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, the revised C10 determinations are fainter by a median offset of 0.08 mags (rms 0.36 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset of the revised C10 absolute magnitudes is 0.30 mags (rms 0.24 mags) fainter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$. For the TO stars that were reclassified as SG/G stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, the revised C10 determinations are brighter by a median offset of 0.48 mags (rms 0.31 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset of revised C10 absolute magnitudes is 0.44 mags (rms 0.22 mags) brighter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$.

For the TO stars that were reclassified as D stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, the revised C10 determinations are fainter by a median offset of 0.97 mags (rms 0.43 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset of revised C10 absolute magnitudes is 0.60 mags (rms 0.25 mags) fainter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$. For the TO stars that were reclassified as SG/G stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, the revised C10 determinations are brighter by a median offset of 1.07 mags (rms 0.42 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset of revised C10 absolute magnitudes is 0.63 mags (rms 0.24 mags) brighter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$.

The lower right panel of Fig. A.2 shows the fractional difference in the derived distances between the revised C10 and C10 scales. For TO stars that were reclassified as D stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the C10 distances is 26% (rms 9%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset increases to about 19% (rms 6%). Both are in the direction that the revised C10 scale is shorter than the original C10 scale for the reclassified TO \rightarrow D stars. For TO stars that were reclassified as SG/G stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$

Figure A.2 *Upper left*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for the C10 sample, using the original luminosity classifications. *Upper right*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for the C10 sample, using the revised luminosity classifications, as described in the text. The stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ are shown as gray dots, while those with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ are shown as red dots. *Lower left*: Difference between the M_r absolute magnitudes for the revised luminosity classifications and the original C10 classifications, as a function of $g-i$. *Lower right*: Fractional change in derived distances for the revised luminosity classifications vs. the original C10 classifications, as a function of $g-i$.

and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the C10 distances is 33% (rms 16%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset decreases to about 25% (rms 11%). Both are in the direction that the revised C10 scale is longer than the original C10 scale for the reclassified TO \rightarrow SG/G stars.

For TO stars that were reclassified as D stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the C10 distances is 36% (rms 14%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset decreases to about 24% (rms 9%). Both are in the direction that the revised C10 scale is shorter than the original C10 scale for the reclassified TO \rightarrow D stars. For TO stars that were reclassified as SG/G stars, and with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the C10 distances is 65% (rms 26%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset decreases to about 34% (rms 14%). Both are in the direction that the revised C10 scale is longer than the original C10 scale for the reclassified TO \rightarrow SG/G stars.

It is worth considering that our reclassification procedure *assumes* that many of the stars with spectroscopically assigned surface gravities in the range $3.75 \leq \log g < 4.0$ (those significantly cooler than an inferred old-population main-sequence turnoff) are indeed metal-poor dwarfs with slightly misestimated $\log g$. This is certainly a conservative assumption, and errs on the side of decreasing distances for actual TO or SG/G stars to the much smaller values that would be derived if they are in fact main-sequence dwarfs. These fine adjustments require further study and verification by high-resolution spectroscopic follow-up of a sample of such stars, at a variety of metallicities and temperatures.

Note that for construction of Figures 2-8, and for the distance-scale comparisons we carry out below, it is useful to consider samples that explore the same local volumes. For simplicity, and for consistency with C07 and C10, we have selected stars with revised C10 distance estimates that satisfy $7 < R < 10$ kpc and $d < 4$ kpc as our basis sample.

A.2.3 Comparison Between Revised C10 and S10

The essence of the S10 complaint is that the distance scale utilized by C07 and C10 is too “long”, i.e., that we have artificially inflated the estimates of stellar distances through the combination of (1) the use of misclassified TO stars (which they suggest could be D stars instead), and in particular, (2) the use of an absolute magnitude scale for the D stars that assigns luminosities to main-sequence stars which displaces them to larger-than-appropriate distances. We have shown above that the first issue is easily

Figure A.3 *Upper left*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for the revised C10 luminosity classifications and with spectroscopically assigned D classifications. *Upper right*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated from equation A1 of I08, as adopted by S10. The stars with $[Fe/H] > -2.0$ are shown as gray dots, while those with $[Fe/H] < -2.0$ are shown as red dots. *Lower left*: Difference between the M_r absolute magnitudes for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications for the revised C10 and S10 calculations, as a function of $g-i$. *Lower right*: Fractional change in derived distances from the revised C10 sample as compared to those adopted by S10, as a function of $g-i$.

corrected for, and that in any case it only applies to some 14% of the total calibration stars from C10, roughly 2300 stars. Of these, 4% of the full sample (680 stars) possess the very low metallicities (below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$) that strongly influence the derived properties of a proposed outer-halo population. Thus, even if there might be some impact, it is substantially diluted by the relatively small numbers of stars for which this concern exists. In any case, we have applied the correction procedures described above, carried out the luminosity classification changes for the cooler TO stars, and in the analysis below, refer to the modified sample as the revised C10 sample. The second issue turns on whether or not one should put faith in our adopted main-sequence absolute magnitude scale, which we address in detail below.

Fig. A.3 shows the result of the comparison of the revised C10 determinations with those of S10. The upper left panel of this figure shows the CMD for stars with spectroscopic assignments of D ($\log g \geq 4.0$), with absolute magnitudes from the revised C10 sample. The upper right panel shows the corresponding CMD obtained using the absolute magnitudes from S10 (Eqn. A.3 below). Note that in the evaluation of both relationships, the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C$ from C10 was employed, although similar results are obtained when the adopted metallicities from the SSPP ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A$) are used. The stars are color-coded to indicate metallicities above and below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$.

The lower left panel of Fig. A.3 shows the difference in the assigned M_r absolute magnitudes that arises when one compares the revised C10 estimates with those of S10 for stars spectroscopically classified as D stars ($\log g \geq 4.0$). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, the revised C10 determinations are brighter by a median offset of 0.38 mags (rms 0.19 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset of revised C10 absolute magnitudes is 0.45 mags (rms 0.20 mags) brighter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$. The offsets are even larger for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. For the redder stars with $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 determinations compared with S10 is 0.45 mags (rms 0.16 mags) brighter; for bluer stars with $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset is 0.52 mags (rms 0.18 mags) brighter.

The lower right panel of this figure shows the fractional difference in the derived distances between the revised C10 and S10 scales. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the S10 distances is 19% (rms 10%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset increases to about 23% (rms 11%). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the S10 distances is 23% (rms 10%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset is 27% (rms 11%). All distance differences are in the sense that the revised C10 scale is (as expected) longer than the S10 scale.

A.3 Absolute Magnitudes and Distances Based on Alternative Schemes

Since much of the discord between the conclusions reached by C10 and S10 arise from their adopted absolute magnitudes and distances, we now consider two additional approaches for obtaining estimates of these quantities. It is worth keeping in mind that these comparisons are only valid for stars that are confidently assigned D status, for which we enforce the requirement that they have spectroscopic gravity estimates assigned by the SSPP of $\log g \geq 4.0$.

A.3.1 The Empirical Calibration of I08

We first consider the relationship adopted by I08, as summarized by their equation A7, used in conjunction with the metallicity correction in their equations A2/A3. When combined into a single equation, one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_r(g-i, [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]) = & -0.56 + 14.32x - 12.97x^2 \\
 & + 6.127x^3 - 1.267x^4 + 0.0967x^5 \\
 & - 1.11 [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] - 0.18 [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.2}$$

where $x = (g-i)$. This was the recommended final photometric parallax relationship from I08, where it is claimed to be valid (for main-sequence stars) over a wide color range ($0.2 < g-i < 4.0$).

S10 did not make use of the above equation, but rather, adopted an absolute magnitude relationship taken from a previous stage of the I08 analysis, given there as equation A1, and applied a metallicity correction from A2/A3 to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_r(g-i, [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]) = & 1.65 + 6.29x - 2.30x^2 \\
 & - 1.11 [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] - 0.18 [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.3}$$

where $x = (g-i)$.

S10 argued that their adopted absolute magnitude determinations agreed better with their preferred set of isochrones (the BaSTI isochrones: Pietrinferni et al. 2004, 2006), but in fact I08 did not expect this relationship (which is from an early step in their development of the appropriate absolute magnitude prediction) to perform well for bluer stars near the main-sequence turnoff. This is a crucial limitation, as the calibration-star

Figure A.4 *Upper left*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated from equation A1 of I08, as adopted by S10. *Upper right*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated from equation A7 of I08, as adopted by I08. The stars with $[Fe/H] > -2.0$ are shown as gray dots, while those with $[Fe/H] < -2.0$ are shown as red dots. *Lower left*: Difference between the M_r absolute magnitudes for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications for the S10 and I08 calculations, as a function of $g-i$. *Lower right*: Fractional change in derived distances from those adopted by S10 as compared to those adopted by I08, as a function of $g-i$.

sample considered by C07 and C10 includes a considerable number of bluer objects – 19% of the C10 sample, for example, have $g-i < 0.4$. The fraction becomes even larger at low metallicity – 31% for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, and 46% for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. This relationship also does not take into account corrections for differing ages of the underlying stellar populations that were applied by I08 in seeking a more generally useful photometric parallax method. The combination of these two effects accounts for much of the discrepancy cited by S10 in the absolute magnitudes (hence distances) used by the C07 and C10 studies.

The upper left panel of Fig. A.4 shows the CMD for stars with spectroscopic assignments of D ($\log g \geq 4.0$), with absolute magnitudes assigned by the relationship adopted by S10 (Eqn. A.3 above). The upper right panel shows the corresponding CMD obtained using the absolute magnitudes from Eqn. A.2 above, which is the recommended relationship from I08. Note that in the evaluation of both relationships above, the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C$ from C10 was employed, although similar results are obtained when either the photometric metallicity estimates from I08 or the adopted metallicity from the SSPP ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A$) are used. The stars are color-coded to indicate metallicities above and below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$. Note, however, that since both procedures adopted the same metallicity correction scheme, there are *no differences* in their behavior over different intervals of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$.

The lower left panel of Fig. A.4 shows the difference in the assigned M_r absolute magnitudes that arises when one compares the adopted S10 and I08 relationships. For stars with $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset is 0.23 mags, with the S10 assignments being fainter. The difference for bluer stars with $g-i < 0.4$ range from ~ 0.23 mags fainter at the red end of this interval to roughly 1.0 mags fainter at the blue end (median difference of 0.48 mags).

The lower right panel of this figure shows the fractional difference in the derived distances between S10 and I08. For redder stars with $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the difference amounts to no more than about 15% at the blue end of this range (median offset of 10%), but for the bluer stars with $g-i < 0.4$ the difference increases from $\sim 15\%$ up to roughly 40%, with a median offset of 20%. All distance differences are in the sense that the S10 scale is shorter than the I08 scale.

Figure A.5 *Upper left*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated from equation A1 of I08, as adopted by S10. *Upper right*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated using the calibrated isochrone fitting procedures of A11. The stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ are shown as gray dots, while those with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ are shown as red dots. *Lower left*: Difference between the M_r absolute magnitudes for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications for the S10 and A11 calculations, as a function of $g-i$. *Lower right*: Fractional change in derived distances from those adopted by S10 as compared to those adopted by A11, as a function of $g-i$.

Figure A.6 *Upper left*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with revised C10 luminosity classifications and with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, as a function of $g-i$. *Upper right*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated from equation A7 of I08, as adopted by I08. The stars with $[Fe/H] > -2.0$ are shown as gray dots, while those with $[Fe/H] < -2.0$ are shown as red dots. *Lower left*: Difference between the M_r absolute magnitudes for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications for the A11 and I08 calculations, as a function of $g-i$. *Lower right*: Fractional change in the revised distances from C10 as compared to those adopted by I08, as a function of $g-i$.

A.3.2 The Calibrated Isochrone Approach

Distances to individual stars can also be estimated using a set of stellar isochrones, once they have been properly calibrated against the observed colors and magnitudes of stars with known distances and ages. For the present exercise, we follow the prescription in An et al. (2009b) to derive distances to individual stars employing stellar isochrones with empirical corrections on the colors (An et al. 2009a). This calibration was based on photometry from An et al. (2008) for a number of open and globular clusters, including M67 ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.0$) and M92 ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.4$), which provides metallicity-dependent color corrections in *ugriz* over the metallicity range under consideration. A full description of the isochrone calibration can be found in A11.

After correcting the photometry for dust extinction, we performed model fits over the full parameter space (with metallicity range $-3.0 \leq [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq +0.4$). We included *griz* photometry and the key SSPP atmospheric parameters ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, $\log g$, T_{eff}) in the model fits, and found a best-fitting model by searching for a minimum χ^2 of the fit. Note that, for consistency with the other approaches, the corrected metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C$ was employed. We assumed minimum errors in the photometry of 0.01 mags for *gri* and 0.02 mags for *z*, and took conservative errors of 0.3 dex for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, 160 K for T_{eff} , and 0.4 dex for $\log g$, as characteristic errors in each of these parameters (including possible systematic scale differences between the SSPP and the models). The lower limit of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ in the models is -3.0 , so we assumed $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.0$ for any stars with metallicity less than this value. This choice has a negligible impact on distance estimation, since the isochrones are insensitive to a change in the atmospheric abundances for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3.0$. An age of 12 Gyr is assumed for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.0$, while 4 Gyr is taken for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -0.3$, with a linearly interpolated value for metallicities between the two boundaries. Solutions for distances were dropped from further consideration in cases where either the fitting process did not converge, or if the final reduced χ^2 of a converged fit exceeded 1.2.

Unlike the original approach described by An et al. (2009b), the calibrated isochrones actually reach into the main-sequence turnoff region, thus distance estimates are available for both TO and SG stars, in addition to D stars, albeit with lower accuracy in the distance estimates. For the purpose of our present comparisons we only accepted stars with spectroscopic assignments of surface gravity $\log g \geq 4.0$. An inter-comparison of results from various color indices indicates that the internal error in the distance modulus is ~ 0.1 mag; an additional ~ 0.1 mag error is expected from the errors in age, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$, and adopted $E(B-V)$. This suggests that the associated distance-modulus error is $\sim 0.1 - 0.2$ mags for individual stars. As was the case for the I08

approach, the effects of binarity are more difficult to quantify, and are not included in this error estimate (see An et al. 2007).

The upper left panel of Fig. A.5 shows the CMD obtained using the absolute magnitudes from equation A1 of I08 as adopted by S10. The upper right panel shows the CMD for stars with spectroscopic assignments as D ($\log g \geq 4.0$), with absolute magnitudes assigned by the calibrated isochrone procedure of A11. Note that in the evaluation of both relationships above, the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_C$ used by C10 was employed, although similar results are obtained when either the photometric metallicity estimates or the adopted metallicity from the SSPP ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]_A$) were used. The stars are color-coded to indicate metallicities above and below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$. As is clear from inspection of the upper right panel, the A11 procedure assigns roughly half of the spectroscopic D stars into SG/G classifications, with correspondingly brighter absolute magnitudes near $M_r \sim 3$.

The lower left panel of Fig. A.5 shows the difference in the assigned M_r absolute magnitudes that arises when one compares the adopted S10 and A11 relationships for stars spectroscopically classified as D stars. For the purpose of this exercise we focus on the stars to which the A11 procedure assigns dwarf status, with absolute magnitudes $M_r > 4.0$. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, the S10 determinations are fainter than those of A11 by a median offset of 0.10 mags (rms 0.09 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while they are fainter by up to 0.7 mags (median offset of 0.31 mags, rms 0.15 mags) for the bluer stars with $g-i < 0.4$. The offsets are significantly larger for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. For the redder stars with $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the S10 determinations compared with A11 is 0.24 mags (rms 0.06 mags) fainter; for bluer stars with $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset is 0.41 mags (rms 0.15 mags) fainter.

The lower right panel of this figure shows the fractional difference in the derived distances between S10 and A11 scales. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the S10 distances with respect to the A11 distances is only about 4% (rms 4%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset increases to about 13% (rms 6%). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the S10 distances with respect to the A11 distances increases to 10% (rms 3%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset increases to about 17% (rms 6%). All distance differences are in the sense that the S10 scale is shorter than the A11 scale.

Figure A.7 *Upper left*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with revised C10 luminosity classifications and with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, as a function of $g-i$. *Upper right*: $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated from equation A7 of I08, as adopted by I08. The stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ are shown as gray dots, while those with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ are shown as red dots. *Lower left*: Difference between the M_r absolute magnitudes for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications for the revised C10 and A11 calculations, as a function of $g-i$. *Lower right*: Fractional change in the revised distances from C10 as compared to those adopted by A11, as a function of $g-i$.

Figure A.8 *Upper left:* $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated using the calibrated isochrone fitting procedures of A11. *Upper right:* $M_r, g-i$ CMD for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, with absolute magnitudes calculated from equation A7 of I08, as adopted by I08. The stars with $[Fe/H] > -2.0$ are shown as gray dots, while those with $[Fe/H] < -2.0$ are shown as red dots. *Lower left:* Difference between the M_r absolute magnitudes for stars with spectroscopically assigned D classifications for the A11 and I08 calculations, as a function of $g-i$. *Lower right:* Fractional change in derived distances from those adopted by A11 as compared to those adopted by I08, as a function of $g-i$.

A.3.3 Comparison with the C10 Dwarfs

We now compare the C10 sample, with revised TO classifications, with the calculations of I08 (Fig. A.6) and with those of A11 (Fig. A.7). As can be appreciated by inspection of these figures, the absolute magnitude scale for the revised C10 sample agrees well with those from both I08 and A11 (in the latter case, one can only consider the stars considered dwarfs by the A11 procedure; see below).

The lower left panel of Fig. A.6 shows the difference in the assigned M_r absolute magnitudes that arises when one compares the revised C10 estimates with those of I08 for stars spectroscopically classified as D stars. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, the revised C10 determinations are brighter by a median offset of 0.21 mags (rms 0.16 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset of revised C10 absolute magnitudes is 0.14 mags (rms 0.27 mags) brighter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$. The offsets are of similar size for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. For the redder stars with $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 determinations compared with I08 is 0.23 mags (rms 0.15 mags) brighter; for bluer stars, the median offset is 0.13 mags (rms 0.14 mags) brighter.

The lower right panel of this figure shows the fractional difference in the derived distances between the revised C10 and I08 scales. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the I08 distances is 10% (rms 9%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset is about 6% (rms 7%). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the I08 distances is 11% (rms 8%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset is 6% (rms 6%). All distance differences are in the sense that the revised C10 scale is longer than the I08 scale.

Turning to Fig. A.7, if we focus on the stars that are assigned dwarf status by the A11 procedure (we accomplish this by only comparing stars with derived $M_r > 4.0$), the agreement between the revised C10 estimates of absolute magnitude and distance is only slightly worse, with respect to A11, than with respect to I08.

The lower left panel of Fig. A.7 shows the difference in the assigned M_r absolute magnitudes that arises when one compares the revised C10 estimates with those of A11, for stars spectroscopically classified as D. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, the revised C10 determinations are brighter by a median offset of 0.31 mags (rms 0.18 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset of revised C10 absolute magnitudes is 0.17 mags (rms 0.15 mags) brighter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$. The offsets are smaller for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. For the redder stars with $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 determinations compared with I08 is 0.21 mags (rms

0.14 mags) brighter; for bluer stars with $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset is 0.15 mags (rms 0.12 mags) brighter.

The lower right panel of this figure shows the fractional difference in the derived distances between the revised C10 and A11 scales. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the A11 distances is 15% (rms 10%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset decreases to about 8% (rms 8%). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the revised C10 distances with respect to the I08 distances is 10% (rms 7%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset is 7% (rms 6%). All distance differences are in the sense that the revised C10 scale is longer than the A11 scale.

A.3.4 Comparison Between A11 and I08

For completeness, Fig. A.8 shows the comparison between the isochrone fitting procedure of A11 and the calculations of I08.

The lower left panel of Fig. A.8 shows the difference in the assigned M_r absolute magnitudes between the A11 and I08 estimates, for stars spectroscopically classified as D (and with $M_r > 4.0$, in order to only compare the stars considered as dwarfs by the A11 procedure). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$, the A11 determinations are fainter by a median offset of 0.10 mags (rms 0.08 mags) for $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, while the median offset is 0.12 mags (rms 0.08 mags) fainter for bluer stars in the range $g-i < 0.4$. The offsets are smaller for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. For the redder stars with $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the A11 determinations compared with I08 is 0.06 mags (rms 0.06 mags) brighter; for bluer stars with $g-i < 0.4$, the median offset is 0.10 mags (rms 0.08 mags) fainter.

The lower right panel of this figure shows the fractional difference in the derived distances between the A11 and I08 calculations. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the A11 distances with respect to the I08 distances is 5% (rms 4%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset is also about 5% (rms 4%). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ and $0.4 < g-i < 0.8$, the median offset of the A11 distances with respect to the I08 distances is 3% (rms 3%). In the bluer range, $g-i < 0.4$, the offset is similar, about 4% (rms 4%). The distance differences are in the sense that, for the redder stars, the A11 scale is longer than that of I08, while for the bluer stars, the A11 scale is shorter than that of I08.

If we restrict our attention to the stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, the ones that matter the most for inferences concerning an outer-halo population, we conclude from the

above analysis that the I08 and A11 distance scales are compatible with one another (maximum offsets of around 5%), while the revised C10 distance scale differs (in the sense of being longer) than both the I08 and A11 scales by no more than about 10% (better for stars near the main-sequence turnoff, around 6-7%). By contrast, the S10 scale differs (in the sense of being shorter) with respect to the I08 scale by between 10% and 18% (independent of metallicity; worse for stars near the main-sequence turnoff), and similarly, between 10% and 17% (worse for stars near the main-sequence turnoff) with respect to the A11 scale. Although it is presently unknown which of these distance scales is closer to “ground truth”, the greater disagreement of the S10 scale (in particular close to the main-sequence turnoff), not only with respect to the revised C10 scale, but also with respect to those of I08 and A11, suggests that it is the S10 scale that should be considered suspect, rather than the revised C10 scale.

A.4 A Reanalysis of Kinematics for Likely Outer-Halo Stars

We now reconsider a limited kinematic analysis for a local sample of the SDSS DR7 calibration stars following the procedures described by C10, making use of the four different sets of distance assignments discussed above for calculation of the full space motions. In order to provide a fair comparison, we apply the same local volume constraints ($7 < R < 10$ kpc and $d < 4$ kpc) to the various samples, but use the values of R and d that would be obtained for each of the different distance scales. This has the obvious result that different numbers of stars will enter into each sample. Recall that we have already specified the basis sample to include stars with revised C10 distance estimates that satisfy $7 < R < 10$ kpc and $d < 4$ kpc. In order to maximize the contribution from proposed outer-halo stars, we choose to only include stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \leq -2.0$. Our purpose is to test the robustness of the retrograde signature that was criticized by S10, which is most evident at low metallicity.

Fig. A.9 shows histograms of V_ϕ for the stars spectroscopically classified as type D in the revised C10 sample, for all ranges of Z_{max} (the maximum value of the distance above or below the Galactic plane reached by a given star during its orbit). The red lines shown in each panel are the two components of a model obtained by the R-Mix procedure (<http://www.math.mcmaster.ca/peter/mix/mix.html>) employed by C10, which the interested reader is referred to for additional details. As can be appreciated from inspection of this figure, all four of the distance calibrations we consider lead to distributions of V_ϕ that include asymmetric tails, which would not be

Table A.2. R-Mix Results for the Low-Metallicity Subsample: Kinematic Parameters

Sample	Number	$\langle V_{\phi,I} \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\sigma_{V_{\phi,I}}$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\langle V_{\phi,II} \rangle$ (km s ⁻¹)	$\sigma_{V_{\phi,II}}$ (km s ⁻¹)	<i>p-value</i> 1-Comp
Spectroscopically Identified Dwarfs						
[Fe/H] < -2.0 ; Z _{max} > 0 kpc						
Rev. C10	1298	-77 ± 57	117 ± 15	44 ± 11	79 ± 10	< 0.001
I08	635	-84 ± 66	94 ± 21	53 ± 20	72 ± 8	< 0.001
A11	360	-100 ± 28	124 ± 11	52 ± 12	70 ± 8	< 0.001
S10	694	-46 ± 47	85 ± 11	72 ± 14	64 ± 8	< 0.001
[Fe/H] < -2.0 ; Z _{max} > 5 kpc						
Rev. C10	469	-59 ± 20	147 ± 11	8 ± 10	78 ± 11	< 0.001
I08	184	-200 ± 40	83 ± 28	20 ± 8	84 ± 6	< 0.001
A11	173	-395 ± 15	35 ± 12	-24 ± 12	116 ± 9	< 0.001
S10	119	13 ± 7	92 ± 5	0.8
All Stars – D, TO, and SG/G						
[Fe/H] < -2.0 ; Z _{max} > 0 kpc						
Rev. C10	1471	-91 ± 23	124 ± 8	40 ± 9	80 ± 7	< 0.001
[Fe/H] < -2.0 ; Z _{max} > 5 kpc						
Rev. C10	577	-94 ± 23	153 ± 9	12 ± 10	83 ± 10	< 0.001

expected to arise for a single-component halo. Naturally, the suggested components and significance of the splits vary from sample to sample; Table A.2 summarizes these results. Column (1) lists the sample under consideration (recall that the samples differ only in their adopted distances as described above). Columns (2) and (3) list the inferred means and dispersions (and their errors) of an assumed Gaussian population for the first component of a two-component fit to the observed distribution of V_ϕ , based on the R-Mix procedure. Columns (4) and (5) list the same quantities for the second component (where required). Column (6) is the p-value of the fits to a one-component model.

The first section of Table A.2 concerns the parameters of the R-Mix fits, for D stars only, associated with Fig. A.9. Note that the number of dwarfs listed in the revised C10 sample is more than twice that in the other samples; this is the result of the inclusion of the reclassified TO \rightarrow D described above (including a subset of the stars with $3.75 \leq \log g < 4.00$). In the other samples, only the stars with $\log g \geq 4.0$ are included. From inspection of the table, the suggested splits from R-Mix all include a retrograde and a prograde component, and are highly statistically significant (in the sense that a one-component fit is strongly rejected). This even includes the S10 sample, although one can see that the formal derived velocity for the first component is less retrograde than found for the other samples.

Fig. A.10 shows the result of a similar analysis for the four different sets of distance calibrations, but restricted to only include stars with derived estimates of $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc. The samples of spectroscopically classified D stars on orbits that reach beyond 5 kpc from the disk plane is much smaller than considered for all ranges of Z_{\max} , but the fraction of likely outer-halo stars included by this cut on Z_{\max} should be increased.

Inspection of Fig. A.10 reveals some interesting differences. While the revised C10 sample (which is considerably larger than the other samples) shown in the upper left panel exhibits a clear asymmetric tail extending to negative V_ϕ , the tails of the I08 and A11 samples are weaker than previously, but located at larger negative values of V_ϕ . We judge this to be primarily the result of the smaller numbers of stars included. Of particular interest is the lower right panel, which shows the result for the S10 sample. As can be seen, if one were to accept the S10 absolute magnitude scale and corresponding distances, one would indeed be driven to interpret at least this cut on the data as well-represented by a single component, which was the essence of the argument presented by S10.

The second section of Table A.2 concerns the parameters of the R-Mix fits, for D stars only, associated with Fig. A.10. From inspection of the table, the suggested splits from R-Mix include a retrograde and a prograde component for the revised C10

Figure A.9 *Upper left*: Histogram of V_ϕ for stars with revised C10 distances, with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, and all values of Z_{\max} . The red solid lines are the suggested components from the R-Mix procedure, while the blue solid line is the final mixture model. *Upper right*: Similar, for D stars with I08 distances. *Lower left*: Similar, for D stars with A11 distances. *Lower right*: Similar, for D stars with S10 distances.

Figure A.10 *Upper left*: Histogram of V_ϕ for stars with revised C10 distances, with spectroscopically assigned D classifications, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, and $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc. The red solid lines are the suggested components from the R-Mix procedure, while the blue solid line is the final mixture model. *Upper right*: Similar, for D stars with I08 distances. *Lower left*: Similar, for D stars with A11 distances. *Lower right*: Similar, for D stars with S10 distances.

sample, the I08 sample, and the A11 sample, all of which are highly statistically significant, but *not* for the S10 sample, which only allows for a marginally prograde one-component fit. It is revealing that the inferred prograde velocities for the second components have dropped considerably from the case that considered all values of Z_{\max} . The split of the A11 sample to include a highly retrograde, low dispersion, component, is presumably driven by small number statistics.

Finally, we consider a similar set of analyses for the full revised C10 sample, including the D, TO, and SG/G classifications and their associated distances and derived space motions. Fig. A.11 shows the results of this exercise for both the full range of Z_{\max} (left panel) and the case where only stars with $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc are considered. Inspection reveals the clear presence of an asymmetric tail towards negative V_{ϕ} in both cases, which we associate with the outer-halo component, as also concluded by C07 and C10.

The last two sections of Table 2 apply to the samples shown in Fig. A.11. As can be seen from inspection of this table, the mean velocity of the retrograde component is rather similar to that obtained by C07 and C10, albeit with a slightly larger formal error. The dispersions of the components are also similar to those obtained previously. A one-component halo is strongly rejected in both cases.

In all of the above, it should be recalled that the final results given by C10 for the parameters of the various suggested populations were derived with a custom maximum-likelihood procedure, not from the R-Mix procedure described above. Hence, small differences are expected in the final derived values.

A.5 Additional Tests for the Presence of a Kinematically and/or Chemically Distinct Outer Halo

The limited kinematic analysis carried out above is already strong evidence for the need of more than a single-component halo for the Milky Way, and provides insight as to why a dual halo interpretation halo was not supported by S10, when using their adopted absolute magnitude scale. Nevertheless, additional tests of a complex halo model that are not strongly influenced by the adopted distance scale (other than for sample selection) are useful to carry out. In this section we consider four such pieces of evidence – (1) The origin of the retrograde signature from the revised C10 D classifications as well as for the full set of D, TO, and SG/G classifications, (2) Changes in the

Figure A.11 *Left panel*: Histogram of V_ϕ for stars with revised C10 distances, with spectroscopically assigned D, TO, and SG/G classifications, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, and all values of Z_{\max} . The red solid lines are the suggested components from the R-Mix procedure, while the blue solid line is the final mixture model. *Right Panel*: Similar, but for stars with $Z_{\max} > 5$ kpc.

as-observed MDF of the revised C10 sample (including stars without measured proper motions and located outside the local samples considered in the kinematic analysis), (3) The observed distribution of Galactocentric radial velocities for the well-selected sample of Blue Horizontal-Branch (BHB) stars from SDSS DR8 discussed by Xue et al. (2011), and (4) Changes in the as-observed MDF of the BHB sample over different cuts in Galactocentric distance.

A.5.1 Additional Evidence (1):

The Origin of the Retrograde Signature

It is useful to ask if the single-halo hypothesis, e.g., a halo as described by the best-fit kinematic model from Bond et al. (2010) (and argued to be valid by S10) can be rejected even without making use of the analysis of full space motions. The gist of the difficulty with the single-halo hypothesis is the fact that the derived rotational velocity distribution is asymmetric for stars with low $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ (this asymmetry is already present for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, and becomes even stronger for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$).

The fraction of low-metallicity stars with high retrograde motions ($V_\phi < -200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) in the SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration-star sample is significantly larger than those with high prograde motions. For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$ (and exploring $Z_{max} > 0$ kpc) the fraction of stars with high retrograde motions is 9%, compared with 4% of stars with high prograde motions ($V_\phi > 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). For stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, the fractions are 13% highly retrograde compared with 5% highly prograde. For orbits reaching to larger distances from the Galactic plane, $Z_{max} > 5$ kpc, the asymmetry is even stronger (as expected), 16% compared with 5% for $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, and 20% compared with 6% at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$. This asymmetric behavior is present even when only dwarfs are considered (Fig. A.9, Fig. A.10), which alleviates concerns about potential systematic distance errors associated with the other stellar classifications.

Belief in the reality of the derived asymmetry in the rotation velocities leads naturally to several important questions. For example, “Are stars in the highly retrograde subsample different in any other measured property than the rest of sample?,” and “Why do they possess such large inferred retrograde velocities?”

Fig. A.12 demonstrates that the distributions of g apparent magnitudes and $g-i$ colors are very similar for the full sample and the retrograde subsample (the large red squares highlight the subsample of stars with highly retrograde motion, $V_\phi < -200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). Their distance distributions are also similar (median distances of D stars are both ~ 2.1 kpc; median distances of the D, TO, and SG/G stars are both ~ 2.5 kpc). Since these are the quantities which, by and large, drive the spectroscopic target selection, it is unlikely that spectroscopic selection effects are important in this context. The apparent structure in this figure (the discontinuity at $g = 17$) is simply the transition between the two categories of calibration stars in the sample. The spectrophotometric calibration stars cover the apparent magnitude range $15.5 < g < 17.0$, and satisfy the color ranges $0.6 < u-g < 1.2$; $0.0 < g-r < 0.6$. The telluric calibration stars cover the same color ranges as the spectrophotometric calibration stars, but at fainter apparent magnitudes, in the range $17.0 < g < 18.5$.

Figure A.12 *Upper left*: Apparent g -band magnitude vs. $g-i$ colors for the C10 stars with revised distances and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, exclusively for stars spectroscopically classified as D. The stars with highly retrograde motions, $V_\phi < -200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, are indicated by the red stars; the rest of the sample is indicated with blue dots. The apparent structure as a function of g magnitude in this diagram is due to the different selections used for the two classes of calibration stars. *Upper right*: Similar, but for the full set of C10 classifications, D, TO, and SG/G. *Lower left*: The proper motion distribution (vector components along the R.A. and Dec. directions) for the C10 stars with revised distances and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$, exclusively for stars spectroscopically classified as D. The stars with highly retrograde motions, $V_\phi < -200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, are indicated by the red stars; the rest of the sample is indicated with blue dots. *Lower right*: Similar, but for the full set of C10 classifications, D, TO, and SG/G.

Although lower latitude stars (mostly arising from the SEGUE survey) are present, the stars discussed here are observed at primarily high Galactic latitudes (the median value of $|b|$ is $\sim 60^\circ$ for all subsamples considered). Any presumed rotational signature has the greatest leverage at lower latitudes. Hence, the concern that errors in the adopted distance scale have “amplified” the derived rotational velocity component is relieved somewhat by the distribution of the sample stars on the sky themselves. Instead, the origin of the derived highly retrograde motions is primarily driven by their large (and asymmetric) measured proper motions (bottom panels of Fig. A.12). The measured proper motions for the retrograde subsample are much larger than the random ($\sim 3-5 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$) and systematic ($< 1 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$) proper motion errors. These proper motion errors were determined using a sample of $\sim 60,000$ quasars and are robust (see Section 2.3 of Bond et al. 2010). Of course, this quasar-based analysis cannot exclude catastrophic errors (i.e., much larger than expected from quasar behavior) in a small fraction of stars due to effects such as a bad early-epoch plate, nearby bright stars with diffraction spikes, large galaxies, etc. In order to minimize these concerns, we have verified that the sky distribution of the 95 D stars (and 144 D, TO, and SG/G stars) in the retrograde subsample, selected with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -1.5$ and $V_\phi < -200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, is similar to that for the full sample (i.e., the retrograde stars do not come from an isolated small region, and issues such as chromatic differential aberration are unlikely). In addition, we have visually inspected their SDSS images, and found that essentially all are clean detections of isolated blue stars. Based on this analysis, we conclude that there is no evidence that the large observed proper motions for the retrograde subsamples are due to unrecognized systematic errors.

In summary, the selection of stars by metallicity (a spectroscopic quantity), generates a subsample with a derived asymmetric rotational velocity distribution that is primarily due to the asymmetry of the measured proper motions themselves (obtained from from imaging data). Although one can always raise the issue of selection effects in the SDSS spectroscopic sample, any simple mechanism that would introduce the observed behavior seems unlikely, because spectroscopic targeting of the calibration-star sample is performed without direct knowledge of the proper motion measurements. Therefore, this interplay between the independent imaging and spectroscopic measurements is a strong argument that the asymmetric V_ϕ distribution for low-metallicity stars is real, and that it does not arise because of errors related to derived distances or other effects we are aware of.

A.5.2 Additional Evidence (2):

The Metallicity Distribution Function of the C10 Sample with Revised Distances and Variation with Distance from the Galactic Plane

The previous analyses of C07 and C10 both concluded that the MDF of the stars in the SDSS calibration-star sample was inconsistent (for regions beyond the possible influence of the disk system) with being drawn from a location-invariant parent population, as would be demanded by the single-halo hypothesis. Here we verify that this claim remains valid, even after reassignment of a subset of the C10 TO stars into alternative luminosity classifications. This is important to check because, as noted above, the majority of these reassignments were TO \rightarrow D, which clearly leads to a reduction in their typical distances.

Fig. A.13 shows the as-observed MDF for the C10 sample with revised distances, for cuts on distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$. This figure exhibits strikingly similar behavior to that seen in, e.g., Fig. 20 of C10. The SDSS/SEGUE DR7 calibration stars located within 5 kpc of the plane display MDFs that are influenced primarily by the presence of the thick-disk, the metal-weak thick disk, and the proposed inner-halo populations. In the ranges of distance greater than 5 kpc, one sees a clear transition from the MDF of the proposed inner-halo population, with peak metallicity near $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$, to an MDF dominated by progressively lower metallicity stars, with a peak near $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$, that are associated with the proposed outer-halo population.

From these first two additional pieces of evidence it is difficult, either kinematically or chemically, to justify the single-halo hypothesis unless other attributes (such as smooth gradients of unknown physical origin in the motions and metallicities of member stars in the SDSS/SEGUE calibration-star sample) are invoked.

Figure A.13 As-observed metallicity distribution functions for stars from C10 with revised distances, for various cuts in distance from the Galactic plane, $|Z|$. The vertical red arrows mark the positions of the primary stellar components modeled by C10, the thick disk ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.6$), the metal-weak thick disk ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.3$), the inner halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.6$), and the outer halo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.2$).

A.5.3 Additional Evidence (3):

The Distribution of Galactocentric Radial Velocities for BHB Stars from SDSS DR8 and Variation with Metallicity

The SDSS spectroscopic samples comprise a number of alternative tracers that can be used to explore the nature of the Milky Way’s halo system. Among the most powerful are the BHB stars, which are intrinsically bright and numerous, and have well-calibrated photometric distances. These have already been used by a number of previous authors, including Yanny et al. (2000), Sirko et al. (2004a,b), Xue et al. (2008, 2011), Bell et al. (2010), and Deason et al. (2010), to explore various aspects of the nature of the Milky Way’s stellar halo.

The Xue et al. (2011) sample from the SDSS DR8 data release is of particular value, because all of the constituent BHB stars have been classified based on carefully applied spectroscopic tests of the Balmer lines, in addition to the usual color cuts. It is a large ($N > 4000$ stars), well-controlled sample, with available metallicities, radial velocities, and distance estimates, that samples the inner and outer regions of the Galaxy at distances up to 80 kpc from the Galactic center.

For the purpose of our present analysis we use the distance estimates for the FHB stars reported by the SSPP, which in turn rely on the metallicity-dependent calibration of the horizontal branch adopted by Beers et al. (2000). We employ the metallicity estimate reported from the SSPP attributed to Wilhelm, Beers, & Gray (1999), which should be superior to alternative estimates for these warm stars, and is accurate to on the order of 0.25-0.3 dex. The reported radial velocities are expected to be accurate to better than 20 km s^{-1} , based on numerous previous tests.

The left-hand column of panels shown in Fig. A.14 compare the distributions of Galactocentric radial velocities for two subsamples of the BHB stars in the range $5 < r < 40$ kpc (which includes roughly 90% of the full sample reported by Xue et al. 2011), after removal of stars with $|Z| < 4$ kpc (to ensure elimination of thick-disk BHB stars). The top panel, which applies to BHB stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, shows the best-fit Gaussian (obtained from the R-Mix procedure), with a derived mean of $-15 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and a dispersion of $100 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. R-Mix cannot reject the single-component hypothesis for this subsample. As is immediately clear from inspection of the bottom panel, the distribution of Galactocentric radial velocities for the BHB stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ exhibits rather different behavior. We emphasize that this subsample is chosen from stars populating the same spatial distribution and having similar distances (the median distance of the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ subsample is 17.5 kpc; the median distance of

Figure A.14 *Left Panels*: Distribution of Galactocentric radial velocities for a sample of well-classified Blue Horizontal-Branch (BHB) stars, based on the sample from SDSS DR8 of Xue et al. (2011), including stars in the range of Galactocentric distance $5 < r < 40$ kpc, and with $|Z| > 4$ kpc. In the top panel, the blue line is the best-fit Gaussian for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$. In the bottom panel, for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, the red lines represent components of the best two-component fit suggested by R-Mix, and the blue line is the resulting mixture model. *Right Panels*: Similar, but for the case where BHB stars from plug-plates in the direction of the two most prominent wraps of the Sagittarius tidal stream have been removed. The metallicity estimates are based on those derived using the procedures described by Wilhelm, Beers, & Gray (1999), which are optimal for these warmer stars ($T_{\text{eff}} > 7000$ K).

the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ subsample is 18.8 kpc); only the metallicity cut differs. Although the R-Mix procedure strongly rejects the single-component hypothesis (with $p = 0.002$), the derived best-fit mean would be $-16 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, with a dispersion of $112 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In order to obtain an acceptable description of these data, R-Mix requires a two-component fit (with means of I: $-54 \pm 13 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, II: $108 \pm 18 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and dispersions of I: $92 \pm 6 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, II: $70 \pm 7 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, respectively).

The region of the Galaxy explored by the BHB stars considered here includes possible members of the Sagittarius tidal stream (see Ruhland et al. 2011), so we have carried out the same experiment as above, but with all BHB stars from plug-plates in the directions toward the two most prominent wraps of the Sgr stream removed from the analysis. The results are shown in the right-hand column of panels in Fig. A.14. Although the total numbers of BHB stars are reduced, little else changes. The median distance of the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ subsample is 16.8 kpc, while the median distance of the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ subsample is 18.4 kpc, similar to the previous case. The best-fit Gaussian for the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2.0$ subsample, obtained from the R-Mix procedure, has a mean of $-16 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and a dispersion of $99 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. R-Mix cannot reject the single-component hypothesis for this subsample. In the case of the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ subsample, the R-Mix procedure once again rejects the single-component hypothesis (with $p = 0.02$); the derived best-fit mean would be $-16 \pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, with a dispersion of $112 \pm 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. To obtain an acceptable description of these data, R-Mix requires a two-component fit (with means of I: $-52 \pm 13 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, II: $114 \pm 19 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and dispersions of I: $94 \pm 6 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, II: $69 \pm 8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, respectively).

In both cases (with or without the Sgr fields included) a two-sample K-S test rejects the hypothesis that the subsamples of stars split at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$ are drawn from the same parent population at high statistical significance ($p = 0.01$ for the first instance and $p = 0.03$ in the second instance). Similarly, a parametric F-test that the dispersions are the same rejects this hypothesis in both cases with $p < 0.001$. Clearly, the observed radial velocities and metallicities of the BHB stars are telling us that the halo is not a single population.

A.5.4 Additional Evidence (4):

The Metallicity Distribution Function of SDSS DR8 BHB Stars and Variation with Galactocentric Distance

We now reconsider evidence similar to that presented in C07, which reported an apparent variation of the nature of the MDF for horizontal-branch stars selected from SDSS DR5. Here we make use of the same sample discussed above, the BHB stars from Xue et al. (2011), which is substantially larger. As before, we have considered this sample for two instances – with and without inclusion of BHB stars from plug-plates in the directions of the Sgr tidal stream.

The left-hand column of panels in Fig. A.15 shows the distribution of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ in intervals of Galactocentric distance for the full sample, after removal of stars with $|Z| < 4$ kpc. The peak of the MDF in this panel is at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.7$, close to what we would associate with dominance by an inner-halo population. Comparing with the lower panels, the peak of the MDF shifts to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2$, close to that we would associate with an outer-halo population. The strength of the low-metallicity tail in the lower panels is also clearly greater than seen in the top panel. The fractions of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ increase from 31% for stars with $5 < r < 10$ kpc to between 46% and 49% for stars at larger Galactocentric distances. Indeed, a K-S test of the null hypothesis that the MDFs of stars shown in the lower panels for the individual cuts on Galactocentric distance r could be drawn from the same parent population as the stars shown in the top panel, against an alternative that the stars are drawn from more metal-poor parent MDFs, is rejected at high levels of statistical significance (one-sided probabilities of $p < 0.001$ for all three higher cuts on Galactocentric distance).

The right-hand column of panels in Fig. A.15 is similar, but with the BHB stars from plug-plates in the directions of the Sgr tidal stream removed. As can be verified by inspection, little changes. The fractions of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ increase from 30% for stars with $5 < r < 10$ kpc to between 44% and 48% for stars at larger Galactocentric distances. A K-S test of the null hypothesis that the MDFs of stars shown in the lower panels for the individual cuts on Galactocentric distance r could be drawn from the same parent population as the stars shown in the top panel, against an alternative that the stars are drawn from more metal-poor parent MDFs, is rejected at high levels of statistical significance (one-sided probabilities of $p < 0.001$ for all three higher cuts on Galactocentric distance), as in the previous case.

It is also interesting that the most dramatic shift in the appearance of the MDFs in both the left-hand and right-hand columns of panels shown in Fig. A.15 occurs between

Figure A.15 *Left Panels:* As-observed MDF for the Xue et al. (2011) BHB stars for various cuts on the distance from the Galactic center, r . Stars with $|Z| < 4$ kpc have been removed from the sample. *Right Panels:* Similar, but for the case where BHB stars from plug-plates in the direction of the two most prominent wraps of the Sagittarius tidal stream have been removed. In both cases, the nature of the MDF appears to shift from the top panels, which exhibit distributions that we associate with the inner-halo population, over to distributions in the lower three panels that are dominated by the outer-halo population. The metallicity estimates are based on those derived using the procedures described by Wilhelm, Beers, & Gray (1999), which are optimal for these warmer stars ($T_{\text{eff}} > 7000$ K). The dashed blue line provides a reference at $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$.

the top panels at $5 < r < 10$ kpc, and the next larger cuts in distance, at $10 < r < 20$ kpc, and hardly changes thereafter. Indeed, a K-S test of the third distance cuts compared with the second cuts, as well as for the fourth cuts compared with the third cuts, cannot reject the hypothesis that the samples are drawn from the same parent populations. Such a behavior might be easier to reconcile with a superposition of multiple populations, rather than by invoking a continuous change that might be expected if a strong gradient in metallicity were present in the halo of the Galaxy. In any event, this behavior is difficult to reconcile with a single-halo population possessing a spatially invariant MDF.

A.6 Further Evidence for the Dual Halo of the Milky Way

Quite independent of the above discussion of the C07 and C10 calibration-star samples and the DR8 BHB sample, a substantial amount of evidence in support of the dual-halo interpretation has already appeared in the literature. Below we summarize a few of the examples we consider the most persuasive.

A.6.1 From Inside the SDSS

A.6.1.1 The SDSS DR7 BHB Sample Analyzed by Deason et al. (2010)

Deason et al. (2010) have examined a sample of BHB stars selected from SDSS DR7, using a combination of color cuts and $\log g$ and T_{eff} intervals from the SSPP. Their sample overlaps substantially with that used by Xue et al. (2008) to obtain estimates of the mass and constraints on the mass profile of the Milky Way, which was based on SDSS DR6 (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2008). The Deason et al. sample is larger (by about a factor of two) than that used by Xue et al., not only due to the additional targets that were included in DR7, but also because their selection is not as restrictive.

Among other results, these authors have used a set of adopted distribution functions to model the observed Galactocentric radial velocities as a function of distance and metallicity. They found that this sample of halo stars exhibits a dichotomy between a prograde, comparatively metal-rich component ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -2$), and a retrograde, comparatively metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2$) component. Although these properties are quite similar to those advocated by C07 and C10, they concluded that the existence of a low-metallicity retrograde population may simply indicate that estimates of the rotation of the Local Standard of Rest (LSR), for which they adopt the IAU recommended

value of 220 km s^{-1} , may be underestimated by some 20 km s^{-1} . They also point out that their results contrast somewhat with those from C07 and C10, in that *both* their retrograde and prograde populations are found in the distant regions of the halo, and are not necessarily due to a shift in stellar populations with distance from the Galactic center, as envisioned by the Carollo et al. studies. While such details demand further investigation, it is clear that the Deason et al. results would not support a single-halo interpretation of the present data.

A.6.1.2 Spatial Variations in the Metallicity and Density Profiles for Modeled Halo Components from de Jong et al. (2010)

During the course of the SEGUE subsurvey conducted during SDSS-II (Yanny et al. 2009), ten “vertical” (in Galactic coordinates) photometric scans of width 2.5° , crossing the Galactic plane at fixed longitudes, were imaged in the *ugriz* passbands. The purpose of these scans was to extend previous SDSS imaging to include selected areas in the latitude range $-50^\circ < b < +50^\circ$, to obtain more detailed information on the transition from the halo system to the disk system of the Milky Way. In their analysis of these data, de Jong et al. (2010) employed a CMD fitting approach, based on templates of old stellar populations with differing metallicities, to obtain a sparse three-dimensional map of the stellar distribution at $|Z| > 1 \text{ kpc}$.

The maps of de Jong et al. (2010) provide clear *in situ* evidence for a shift in the mean metallicity of the Milky Way’s stellar halo – within $r < 15 \text{ kpc}$ their derived stellar halo exhibited a mean metallicity of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -1.6$, changing to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.2$ at larger Galactocentric distances. In addition, inspection of the spatial density profiles of their template populations (their Fig. 7) suggested rather different spatial behaviors for their “inner-halo like” template population and that of their “outer-halo like” template population. Their derived inner-halo density profile falls off rapidly with distance from the Galactic center to $r \sim 15 - 20 \text{ kpc}$; beyond this region a substantially lower density, slowly varying, outer-halo density profile was found. Note that the de Jong et al. analysis was restricted to distances $r < 30 \text{ kpc}$. When a single power-law was fit to this entire region they obtained an index of $n = -2.75 \pm 0.07$, in excellent agreement with the previous work of Bell et al. (2008) and Jurić et al. (2008).

Clearly, these findings provide compelling support for the kinematics-based inferences of C07 and C10, as confirmed by our own reanalysis above, as well as by the newly considered BHB samples.

A.6.1.3 Rejection of Single Power-Law Descriptions of the Milky Way’s Halo based on Deep SDSS Imaging from Watkins et al. (2009) and Sesar et al. (2010)

The region known as Stripe 82 (an area of ~ 250 deg² along the Celestial Equator) has been multiply scanned in the *ugriz* filters over the course of SDSS and its extensions, in particular during the Supernova Survey conducted as part of SDSS-II (Frieman et al. 2008).

Both Watkins et al. (2009) and Sesar et al. (2010) have argued persuasively that single power-law profiles are incapable of describing the spatial variation of the halo system. These authors presented evidence, based on both RR Lyrae stars and main-sequence stars, that the halo stellar number density profile significantly steepens beyond a Galactocentric distance of $r \sim 30$ kpc. It is worth noting that a “steepening” density profile might also be envisaged as describing the behavior of a profile that suffers a large drop in stellar number density at a given distance, and goes over to a more slowly varying profile with distance, as was seen in the de Jong et al. (2010) analysis.

A.6.2 From Outside the SDSS

Over the past several decades there have been numerous studies of the nature of the halo system that provide evidence indicating the halo of the Milky Way may not comprise a single population, based on analyses of the spatial number density profiles of halo tracer objects (such as globular clusters or field horizontal-branch stars), and of the kinematics of small subsamples of these. Here we briefly mention a subset of these, based on data obtained outside the SDSS.

Representative spatial analysis papers include Hartwick (1987), Sommer-Larsen & Zhen (1990; using density profiles inferred from local kinematics) Preston et al. (1991), Zinn (1993), Kinman et al. (1994), and Chiba & Beers (2000; using density profiles inferred from local kinematics), all of which reached similar conclusions. According to these studies, the halo is best described as flattened in the inner regions, but going over to a much more spherical distribution at larger radii. Similar work has been conducted with ever increasing sample sizes in recent years. Examples include analyses of RR Lyraes based on the data from the QUEST survey (Vivas & Zinn 2006), as well as from the LONEOS sample (Miceli et al. 2008). In this latter example, Miceli et al. argued for the presence of a dual halo in order to account for the apparently very different spatial profiles of Oosterhoff Type I and Oosterhoff Type II variables in their sample. Most recently, Sesar et al. (2011) used deep imaging data from the CFHT Legacy Survey to study the distribution of near-turnoff main sequence stars in

the Galactic halo along four lines of sight, to heliocentric distances of ~ 35 kpc. They found that the halo stellar number density profile becomes steeper at Galactocentric distances greater than $r \sim 30$ kpc, and emphasize that single power-law models are strongly disfavored by the data.

Representative kinematical analysis papers include Norris & Ryan (1989), Allen et al. (1991), Carney et al. (1996), Wilhelm et al. (1996), Borkova & Marsakov (2003), Kinman et al. (2007), and de Propris et al. (2010). Several of these papers (Norris & Ryan 1989; Allen et al. 1991; Carney et al. 1996) emphasized the clear presence of individual stars, in particular those with low metallicities, associated with large retrograde motions. Below $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.0$, the numbers of retrograde stars in both Allen et al. (1991) and Carney et al. (1996) are well in excess of the numbers expected for fair samples drawn from a single halo population with little or no net rotation. Indeed, both sets of authors commented on the need for a complex halo in order to accommodate their observations. Wilhelm et al. (1996), Borkova & Marsakov (2003), and Kinman et al. (2007) all reported significant net retrograde motions for subsamples drawn from their BHB and RR Lyrae star samples, respectively. Most recently, de Propris et al. (2010) have presented radial velocity data from BHB stars indicating that the velocity dispersion profile of the halo appears to increase towards large Galactocentric radii, while the stellar velocity distribution is non-Gaussian beyond 60 kpc. They concluded that the outer halo consists of a multitude of low luminosity overlapping tidal streams from recently accreted objects.

A.7 Summary and Conclusions

We have considered the criticisms of S10 in detail, and demonstrated that their claim that the retrograde signature of the outer-halo population is due to incorrect distance determinations or improper assignments of the stellar luminosity classes appears spurious. The original assertions of C07 and C10 are in fact confirmed by our analysis. The distance scale advocated by S10 was based on their adoption of the incorrect main-sequence absolute magnitude relationship from the work of I08. We have shown that, for redder stars, this scale is roughly 10% (in the median distance) shorter than the correct globular cluster-based scale suggested by I08, increasing to 18% shorter for bluer stars near the main-sequence turnoff, independent of metallicity. Comparison with a calibrated isochrone approach by A11 indicates that, for stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$ (which dominate the membership of the outer-halo population), the S10 scale is roughly 10% shorter for redder stars and 17% shorter for bluer stars near the main-

sequence turnoff. The distance scale for main-sequence dwarfs with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.0$, based on the revised C10 classifications (including reassigned TO \rightarrow D stars), agree with the determinations of both I08 and A11 at a level of 6-10%, which we consider more than adequate.

We have carried out an abbreviated kinematic analysis for the very low-metallicity stars that dominate the proposed outer-halo component, using the distance scales of the various studies considered above. Based on this analysis, we confirm the existence of a significant retrograde population (with a large velocity dispersion), which C07 and C10 associated with this structure. Furthermore, we have shown that the origin of the retrograde signature at low metallicity is traceable to the asymmetric distribution of the observed proper motions, not to the assignment of incorrect distances. The shift of the MDF for the C10 sample with distance from the Galactic plane, the distribution of Galactocentric radial velocities for BHB stars from SDSS DR8, as well as the variation of the BHB MDF with Galactocentric distance, in addition to other evidence from inside and outside the SDSS, are all consistent with a kinematically and/or chemically distinct superposition of inner- and outer-halo populations in the Milky Way, and not with a homogeneous single-halo population.

Over the span of the past quarter century, data from many independent surveys, based on very different selection criteria, distance estimation techniques, and analysis methodologies, have been pointing with ever increasing confidence to the conclusion that a single-halo description is no longer valid for the Milky Way. We have summarized the most relevant results here, although much additional evidence exists.

It is important to note that recent high-resolution, cosmologically-based simulations, in particular those of Zolotov et al. (2009, 2010) and Font et al. (2011), now include at least approximate prescriptions for the star formation and dissipative accretion processes, as well as other pertinent baryonic physics such as metal-dependent cooling and supernova feedback, greatly expanding their predictive power. This new generation of simulations indicates that a dual halo (with different stellar spatial density profiles and clear metallicity shifts between an inner- and outer-halo population) is *a generic expectation* for large spiral galaxies such as the Milky Way and M31. Additional analyses of the SDSS/SEGUE stars, beyond those in the calibration-star subset, should help to strengthen the observational case for (at least) a dual halo, and to refine estimates of the parameters that describe the individual components. Ultimately, geometric distances from Gaia for stars in the halo populations will eliminate any remaining questions concerning the impact of uncertain photometric parallaxes on these conclusions. However, our view is that presently available data already reject the single-halo interpretation beyond reasonable doubt.

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Appendix B

Extreme Enhancements of r-process Elements in the Cool Metal-Poor Main-Sequence Star SDSS J2357–0052

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Abstract

We report the discovery of a cool metal-poor, main-sequence star exhibiting large excesses of r-process elements. This star is one of two newly discovered cool subdwarfs (effective temperatures of 5000 K) with extremely low metallicity ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$) identified from follow-up high-resolution spectroscopy of metal-poor candidates from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey. SDSS J2357–0052 has $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.4$ and $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] = +1.9$, and exhibits a scaled solar r-process abundance pattern of heavy neutron-capture elements. This is the first example of an extremely metal-poor, main-sequence star showing large excesses of r-process elements; all previous examples of the large r-process-enhancement phenomena have been associated with metal-poor giants. The metallicity of this object is the lowest, and the excess of Eu ($[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}]$) is the highest, among the r-process-enhanced stars found so far. We consider possible scenarios to account for the detection of such a star, and discuss techniques to enable searches for similar stars in the future.

B.1 Introduction

Over the course of the past decade, a great deal of observational effort has been dedicated to studies of the chemical enrichment of the early universe through high-resolution spectroscopic measurements of the elemental abundances of metal-poor stars in the Galaxy. Of particular interest are the extremely metal-poor (EMP) stars, with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$ ¹, as such stars are expected to have recorded the nucleosynthesis products associated with the first generations of stars, perhaps even by individual supernovae, according to models such as the supernova-induced, low-mass star formation scenario (i.e. Audouze & Silk 1995; Shigeyama & Tsujimoto 1998).

A number of interesting abundance patterns have been noted to occur for individual EMP stars; the most remarkable example is perhaps the occurrence of the so-called r-process-enhanced stars (e.g. Sneden et al. 2009; Cayrel et al. 2001). Some EMP stars have been shown to exhibit over-abundances of the heavy neutron-capture elements, such as Eu with respect to Fe, by more than an order of magnitude, while the abundance patterns of their heavy elements agree well with that of a scaled solar r-process component (Sneden et al. 2008). Such stars may well represent the yields of an essentially pure r-process production event, the yields of which were apparently not fully mixed into the interstellar medium during early stages of the Galaxy’s evolution.

The astrophysical site(s) of the r-process is/are not yet established with confidence. However, an important clue may be the fact that all extremely r-process-enhanced stars (r-II stars; Beers & Christlieb 2005) identified to date have been found in a relatively narrow metallicity range ($-3 < [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2.5$). The upper metallicity bound for the presence of r-II stars is well constrained by measurements for a large sample of stars in this metallicity range ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.5$), and could be explained by the increase of the Fe abundance with a limited supply of Eu from individual supernovae².

By contrast, high-resolution spectroscopic measurements for the lower metallicity range, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$, are still few in number. Thus, to obtain stronger constraints on the nature of the r-process, and in particular to possibly narrow the mass range of supernovae that may be capable of producing the r-process elements, further investigations for neutron-capture elements in EMP stars are strongly desired.

Here we report elemental abundance measurements for two EMP stars discovered during the course of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York et al. 2000).

¹ $[A/B] = \log(N_A/N_B) - \log(N_A/N_B)_\odot$, and $\log \epsilon_A = \log(N_A/N_H) + 12$ for elements A and B.

²An exception is COS 82 in the dwarf spheroidal galaxy Ursa Minor, which exhibits $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.5$ and $[r/\text{Fe}] = +1.5$ (Aoki et al. 2007). However, such an object has not yet been found among the Milky Way field stars.

These stars are the first known examples of cool main-sequence stars (subdwarfs) with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$, one of which exhibits extremely large excesses of the r-process elements.

B.2 Observations and Analysis

B.2.1 Sample Selection and Observations

The two cool subdwarfs investigated in the present work were selected from a large sample of candidate EMP stars observed during the Sloan Extension for Galactic Exploration and Understanding (SEGUE; Yanny et al. 2009), based on atmospheric parameters obtained by the SEGUE Stellar Parameter Pipeline (SSPP; Lee et al. 2008). These stars were listed as EMP stars with strong CH bands and $\log g \sim 3.5$, and were expected to be examples of carbon-enhanced metal-poor stars.

High-resolution follow-up spectroscopy was conducted with the Subaru Telescope High Dispersion Spectrograph (HDS; Noguchi et al. 2002) in 2008 August and October. The “snapshot” high-resolution ($R=30,000$), moderate S/N (~ 30) observations revealed these two stars to have high surface gravities, based on the weak absorption lines of ionized species (e.g., Fe2) and the broad wings of their Mg1 b lines. The strong CH bands are explained by the high pressure in the subdwarf’s atmospheres, rather than due to a carbon excess. The metallicity of these two stars are significantly lower than previously known cool subdwarfs (e.g., Yong & Lambert 2003), except for the dwarf carbon star G77-61 (Plez & Cohen 2005). Moreover, very strong Ba2 absorption lines were found for SDSS J2357–0052, suggesting large excesses of the heavy neutron-capture elements.

In order to determine detailed chemical compositions of these stars, we obtained higher resolution ($R = 60,000$), higher S/N spectra, covering 3500–6800 Å, with Subaru/HDS in 2008-2009. Table 1 lists details of the observations. The observed spectra around the Eu2 3819 Å feature are shown in Figure B.1. For comparison purposes, we also obtained a spectrum with the same instrumental setup for the cool, very metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2$) subdwarf G 19–25, selected from Yong & Lambert (2003).

Figure B.1 Observed spectra around the Eu II 3819 Å line. The stellar name and derived $[Fe/H]$ are given in each panel.

Table B.1. Objects and Observing Log

Star ^a	Obs. date (UT)	Setup ^b	Exposure (min.)	Count (5000 Å)	HJD	V_{helio} (km s ⁻¹)
SDSS J2357-0052	Aug 21, 2008	Yd	15	430	2454700	-9.1 ± 0.3
$V_0 = 15.612$	Oct 4, 2008	Yd	15	480	2454744	-9.3 ± 0.1
$(V-K)_0 = 2.059$	Nov. 16, 2008	Bc	160	2890	2454786	-10.0 ± 0.1
$(g-r)_0 = 0.612$	June 30/July 2, 2009	Bc	180	2610	2455012/14	-10.2 ± 0.1
$E(B-V) = 0.030$	Sep 11, 2009	Yd	80	1620	2455086	-9.0 ± 0.1
	Sep 12, 2009	Bc	120	1690	2455087	-9.2 ± 0.1
SDSS J1703+2836	July 6, 2008	Yd	10	390	2454654	-178.2 ± 0.2
$V_0 = 15.342$	July 2, 2009	Bc	120	1650	2455015	-178.0 ± 0.1
$(V-K)_0 = 2.098$	Sep 11, 2009	Yd	120	1080	2455086	-178.1 ± 0.1
$(g-r)_0 = 0.593$	Sep 12, 2009	Bc	120	1970	2455087	-177.7 ± 0.1
$E(B-V) = 0.065$
G 19-25	Sep 10, 2009	Yd	10	7700	2455086	-32.4 ± 0.2
$V_0 = 11.64$	Sep 11, 2009	Bc	10	8000	2455087	-32.5 ± 0.1
$(V-K)_0 = 2.023$
$E(B-V) = 0.000$

^aThe full names are SDSS J235718.91-005247.8 and SDSS J170339.60+283649.9. The PLATE-MJD-FIBER names in the SDSS/SEGUE databases are 1489-52991-251 and 2808-54524-510, respectively.

^bThe HDS standard setups Yd and Bc cover 4100-6800 Å and 3550-5250 Å, respectively

B.2.2 Data Reduction and Measurements

Standard data reduction procedures were carried out with the IRAF echelle package³. The sky background was removed when the spectra are affected by the moon, as they were for several of the exposures.

Equivalent widths (W 's) for isolated absorption lines were measured by fitting Gaussian profiles as well as by direct integration of the absorption features. We found that the values obtained by direct integration are slightly higher for strong lines, probably due to inadequate fits of the assumed Gaussian profiles to the line wings. Hence, we adopted the values obtained by direct integration when the $\log(W/\lambda)$ value is larger than -4.7 , which corresponds to $W = 100 \text{ mÅ}$ at $\lambda = 5000 \text{ Å}$, while the results of Gaussian fitting are adopted for weaker lines. We used the line list compiled by Aoki et al. (2010, in preparation) for studies of extremely metal-poor stars in the Galactic halo.

Radial velocities were measured for our program stars using selected Fe lines in the

³IRAF is distributed by the National Optical Astronomy Observatories, which is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc. under cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation.

wavelength region 4050–5200 Å. Heliocentric radial velocities are listed in Table B.1 for individual spectra obtained in each run with the same setup. The radial velocities of SDSS J2357–0052 measured from the November 2008 and June/July 2009 spectra are about 1 km s⁻¹ different from measurements obtained during August/October 2008. This difference is significantly larger than the random errors of the measurements (Table B.1), which are estimated from $\sigma_v N^{-1/2}$, where σ_v is the standard deviation of the derived values for individual lines and N is the number of lines used. However, taking the systematic errors of the measurements into account, which could be as large as 0.5 km s⁻¹, further confirmations for the variation of radial velocity are required to derive any conclusion on the possible binarity of this object.

B.2.3 Atmospheric Parameters

The effective temperatures (T_{eff} 's) of our objects are determined from the $(V - K)_0$ colors and the temperature scale of Alonso, Arribas, & Martínez-Roger (1996), assuming $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.0$ for the SDSS objects. The V_0 magnitude is derived from the SDSS g_0 and $(g - r)_0$, using the transformations of Zhao & Newberg (2006). The K magnitude is adopted from the 2MASS catalogue (Skrutskie et al. 2006), using the reddening estimates by (Schlegel et al. 1998). The photometry data and derived effective temperatures are given in Table B.1 and B.2, respectively. The derived T_{eff} 's of the two SDSS stars are quite similar. In the table, we also give the estimate of T_{eff} obtained from $(g - r)_0$ and a temperature scale constructed based on the ATLAS model atmospheres⁴. These T_{eff} 's are higher by 100–150 K than those from $(V - K)_0$ derived above. We adopt the averages of the two determinations. Application of the recent effective temperature scale of Casagrande et al. (2010) yields temperature estimates about 100 K higher T_{eff} than Alonso et al.'s scale for the same value of $(V - K)_0$; this result agrees well with the values adopted in the present work. The T_{eff} of G 19–25 is adopted from Alonso, Arribas, & Martínez-Roger (1996a) determined by the Infrared Flux Method, which was also adopted by Yong & Lambert (2003).

The surface gravity ($\log g$) for the SDSS stars is estimated from the isochrones of Kim et al. (2002) for metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.5$) stars, adopting ages of 12 Gyr and assuming these stars are on the main sequence. The surface gravities ($\log g = 4.8$) are insensitive to the assumed metallicity and ages for such cool main-sequence stars. The $\log g$ of G 19–25 is estimated by demanding the Fe abundances derived from Fe1 and Fe2 agree. The metallicity adopted in the abundance analysis is $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.3$ and -1.9 for the SDSS stars and G 19–25, respectively, which are obtained by iterations of the

⁴wwwuser.oat.ts.astro.it/castelli/colors/sloan.html

analysis procedure described below.

Elemental abundances are measured by standard analyses for equivalent widths using ATLAS model atmospheres with no convective overshooting (Castelli & Kuruz 2003), with enhancements of the α -elements. We performed analyses for more than 60 FeI lines in the SDSS stars, whose equivalent widths range from 5 mÅ to 200 mÅ. Our analyses show that a decreasing trend of derived abundances with increasing equivalent widths emerges when the van der Waals broadening based on Unsöld (1955)'s treatment is enhanced, as was done in our previous studies (e.g. Aoki et al. 2002), even though no micro-turbulence is assumed. Hence, we adopt the Unsöld (1955)'s broadening with no modification in our analysis. We note that the iron abundance derived from weak lines ($\log(W/\lambda) < -5$), as well as the abundances for most of the neutron-capture elements (e.g., Y, La, Eu), also based on weak lines, are insensitive to the nature of the pressure broadening.

We confirmed that there remains no significant correlation between the derived Fe abundances from individual FeI lines and their excitation potential, supporting the estimates of their effective temperatures from broadband colors.

The absolute magnitude of subdwarfs with $T_{\text{eff}} = 5000$ K is $M_V = 7.4$, according to the isochrones of Kim et al. (2002). This indicates that the stellar mass is $0.52 M_{\odot}$, and the distances of SDSS J2357–0052 ($V = 15.6$) and SDSS J1703+2836 ($V = 15.3$) are 440 pc and 370 pc, respectively. Adopting these distances as well as radial velocities and proper motions (SDSS J2357–0052: $\mu_{\alpha} = 46$ and $\mu_{\delta} = -172$ mas yr $^{-1}$; SDSS J1703+2836: $\mu_{\alpha} = -27$ and $\mu_{\delta} = -129$ mas yr $^{-1}$, with errors of ~ 2.5 mas yr $^{-1}$; Munn et al. 2004), the kinematics of the SDSS stars are calculated using the procedures of Chiba & Beers (2000). SDSS J2357–0052 is tentatively assigned to the outer-halo component (Carollo et al. 2007, Carollo et al. 2010), based on its retrograde orbit ($V_{\phi} = -83 \pm 70$ km s $^{-1}$), its moderate eccentricity ($e = 0.47$), and its large Z_{max} value (the maximum distances of the orbits from the Galactic plane) of 8 kpc, coupled with its location in a Toomre energy diagram ($V = -306, (U^2 + W^2)^{1/2} = 191$ km s $^{-1}$); the kinematics of SDSS J1703+2836 are more consistent with the inner halo.

B.2.4 Abundance Measurements

The derived elemental abundances for our stars are listed in Table B.2. Although only one FeII line is clearly detected in the spectra of the SDSS stars, the derived iron abundance from the FeII line agrees with that from FeI lines within the measurement error. Moreover, the Ti abundances from the two ionization stages agree well in both objects. These results clearly exclude the possibility that these stars are cool giants with

$\log g \sim 2$, but support the above estimates of the gravities.

The spectrum synthesis technique is adopted to determine the carbon abundance from the CH molecular band at 4315 Å. Although the derived abundance ratios are slightly higher than solar, these values are typical for unevolved, extremely metal-poor stars (e.g., Spite et al. 2005), thus these stars are not carbon-enhanced objects.

Barium abundances are obtained by an analysis including hyperfine splitting and isotope shifts (McWilliam 1998), assuming the isotope ratios expected for the r-process-enhanced case (see below). The final result is derived from the three weaker lines in the red region, which are less sensitive to hyperfine splitting. Hyperfine splitting is also included in the analysis of Mn I lines.

The abundances of Eu, Er, and Yb are determined by the spectrum synthesis technique, carefully checking on the effects of blending from other absorption features, for Eu II 3819, 4129 and 4205 Å, Er II 3692 Å, and Yb II 3694 Å. Atomic line data for Eu, Er, and Yb are adopted from Lawler et al. (2001), Lawler et al. (2008), and Sneden et al. (2008, 2009), respectively, including the effect of hyperfine splitting for Eu and Yb. The upper limit on the Th abundance is determined by the spectrum synthesis technique for the Th II 4019 Å line.

Random errors in the abundance measurements are estimated to be $\sigma N^{-1/2}$, where σ is the standard deviation of derived abundances from individual lines and N is the number of lines used in the analysis. When only a few lines are available, the σ of Fe I is adopted in the estimates. The errors due to the uncertainty of the atmospheric parameters ($\delta T_{\text{eff}} = 150$ K, $\delta \log g = 0.3$, $\delta v_{\text{micro}} = 0.2$ km s⁻¹) are also estimated, and added in quadrature to the random errors. The metallicity of G 19–25 obtained by our analysis agrees, within the errors, with that derived by Yong & Lambert (2003), adopting the same T_{eff} .

B.3 Discussion

The two SDSS stars studied in the present work turned out to be the lowest metallicity cool subdwarfs yet known, with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$. Metal-poor subdwarfs have been extensively studied by Yong & Lambert (2003), yet their most metal-poor objects have $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -2.5$. The much larger and deeper SDSS/SEGUE surveys are clearly potentially interesting sources for the discovery of additional examples of extremely metal-poor, cool subdwarfs.

These two stars exhibit quite similar abundance ratios of their lighter elements ($Z \leq 28$). The over-abundances of the α -elements and under-abundances of Mn are similar

Figure B.2 The abundances ($\log \epsilon$ values) of neutron-capture elements in SDSS J2357-0052 (dots). The solid and dotted lines indicate the abundance patterns of the r- and s-process components in Solar System material (Arlandini et al. 1999), normalized at Ba ($Z = 56$)

to those found for other EMP stars. Other iron-peak elements trace the Fe abundances, while EMP giants usually show under-abundances of Cr as well as over-abundances of Co. However, discrepancies of Cr abundance ratios between EMP giants and main-sequence turn-off stars are known to occur (e.g., Lai et al. 2008), and our results are similar to those of turn-off stars. Lithium is not detected for either star, and the upper limits on its abundance are significantly lower than the Spite plateau value, as expected for cool stars with substantial convective envelopes.

A surprising result is that one of the first two subdwarfs with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -3$ studied by high-resolution spectroscopy exhibits large excesses of neutron-capture elements. Figure B.2 shows the abundances ($\log \epsilon$ values) of neutron-capture elements in SDSS J2357–0052. Comparisons with the abundance patterns of the r- and s-process components in solar-system material indicate that the origin of neutron-capture elements is clearly associated with the r-process. This result immediately confirms that large excesses of r-process elements are not a phenomena found only for red giants (see Sneden et al. 2008).

The $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}]$ abundance ratio of SDSS J2357–0052 ($[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] = +1.9$) is the highest among the stars that exhibit excesses of r-process elements at low metallicity (Fig. B.3). This is basically because of the low Fe abundance of this object ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.4$). Indeed, the Eu abundance of this object ($[\text{Eu}/\text{H}] = -1.4$) is similar to those previously found for other r-II stars, e.g., CS 31082-001: $[\text{Eu}/\text{H}] = -1.28$ (Hill et al. 2002); HE 1523–0901 : $[\text{Eu}/\text{H}] = -1.14$ (Frebel et al. 2007).

The large excesses of heavy neutron-capture elements in r-II stars are usually interpreted as a result of the pollution of interstellar matter by a supernova (or some other event) that yields amounts of r-process elements and subsequent low-mass star formation from the enriched material. The fact that only a small fraction of stars show such excesses (roughly 5% of stars with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] < -2$ according to Barklem et al. 2005) indicates that the event(s) associated with the production of r-process elements were rare, and did not produce significant amounts of Fe.

Since r-II stars have previously only been found in the metallicity range $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] > -3$ (Fig. 3), the respective sites of the r-process have been supposed to be supernovae of less massive progenitors (e.g. 8–10 M_{\odot} ; Wanajo & Ishimaru 2006). Our discovery of SDSS J2357–0052 indicates that the metallicity range in which highly r-process-enhanced stars appear extends to as low as $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.4$, and thus opens the possibility that a larger range of progenitor masses may have been involved.

The apparent upper bound of $[\text{Eu}/\text{H}]$ in r-II stars might indicate the existence of a limit of the enrichment by a supernova yielding r-process elements. The mass ratio of Eu/H corresponding to $[\text{Eu}/\text{H}] \sim -1.5$ is $M_{\text{Eu}}/M_{\text{H}} \sim 10^{-11}$. If the Eu mass produced by

Figure B.3 The Eu abundance ratios of Galactic halo and disk stars (upper panel). The large filled circle indicates our result for SDSS J2357-0052, while open circles are for very metal-poor stars taken from literature (Hill et al. 2002; Sneden et al. 2003; Honda et al. 2004; Ishimaru et al. 2004; Christlieb et al. 2004; Aoki et al. 2005; Barklem et al. 2005; Preston et al. 2006; François et al. 2007; Frebel et al. 2007; Hayek et al. 2009; Roederer et al. 2010). Results for less metal-poor stars shown by the small filled circles are taken from the SAGA database (Suda et al. 2008). The lower panel shows the distribution of r-II stars ($[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] > +1.0$, solid line) and r-II + r-I ($[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] > +0.5$) stars (dotted line), following the nomenclature of Beers & Christlieb (2005).

a single supernova is assumed to be $10^{-7}M_{\odot}$ (Wanajo & Ishimaru 2006), the amount of interstellar matter polluted by that could only be on the order of 10^4M_{\odot} . The Fe production by such stars is estimated to be $\sim 2 \times 10^{-3}M_{\odot}$ (Wanajo et al. 2009). If this is mixed into a metal-free cloud of 10^4M_{\odot} , the resulting metallicity is $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -4$. If the cloud mass is assumed to be smaller, taking account of the low explosion energy of a supernova by a less massive progenitor, the Fe abundance of SDSS J2357–0052, as well as those of neutron-capture elements, could be explained by the contribution of a single supernova.

Another scenario to explain the large excesses of r-process elements in SDSS J2357–0052 is that the object belongs to a binary system in which the massive companion has exploded, yielding the r-process elements. A possible binary system with a highly elliptical orbit is suggested for the r-process-enhanced star HE 2327-5642 ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.78$; $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] = +0.98$) by Mashonkina et al. (2010), based on a single radial velocity measurement showing significant departure ($\sim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) from 16 others (with errors on the order of 0.2-0.5 km s^{-1}). Since this observation (if not spurious) may have some relationship with the phenomena of large r-process excess, further investigations of radial velocity changes for r-II stars (including SDSS J2357–0052) are strongly desired.

It may be of interest that the first EMP r-II subdwarf appears to be associated with the outer halo. Given the possible distinct astrophysical origins between the inner- and outer-halo populations (e.g., masses of their progenitor sub-haloes, and/or star formation histories; Carollo et al. 2007, 2010), it would clearly be desirable to establish membership assignments for known r-II stars. This can be realized with sufficient accuracy if additional r-II subdwarfs are found. This could be accomplished by targeting candidates very and extremely metal-poor stars identified by SDSS/SEGUE with high proper motions (likely subdwarfs) and low T_{eff} .

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